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CONTACT DETAILS

ISHA International Secretariat
c/o Fachschaftsinitiative Geschichte
Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin
Institut für Geschichtswissenschaften
Friedrichstraße 191-193a
10099 Berlin

Website	https://ishainternational.wordpress.com/
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/isha.inter
E-mail	info@isha.international
Open-access archive	https://ishainternational.wordpress.com/archive/

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EDI TOR IAL

Rome, 15 May 2024

Dear ISHA members
Dear readers

Another year has passed, and the next issue of Carnival is ready for publication. It was my third term and fourth issue of Carnival as Editor-in-Chief. As I am writing this editorial, I am not only looking back on the preparations for this issue but on a whole trajectory. Year by year, we managed to reflect on the internal workings of the editorial board, improve our peer review process, update the submission guidelines and increase the transparency of our publication by including the journal information on the ISHA website. My deep dive into the archives of ISHA at the University Archive at the KU Leuven in Belgium resulted in tracking down more previous issues of Carnival and related publications and conference proceedings, which will soon be available online in digitised format. The updated and modern lay-out also visually marks a new phase in the life of Carnival.

Rome was not built in a day, and all the work done on Carnival can only be described as the fruits of the labour of a motivated and committed team of editors. My heartfelt gratitude therefore goes out to the editorial board for their hard work, for circulating the call for papers, their critical eye, providing constructive feedback to the authors, and for sharing the academic standards to make Carnival into a more professional and transparent publication. Likewise, I want to thank all the authors for submitting their research to Carnival and for continuously improving their articles together with the editorial board. I am most proud of the quality and range of topics and disciplines that is collected in this issue.

Thank you to all readers, and I wish all of you a most pleasant reading experience.

Much ISHA love

Charlotte Rottiers

Editor-in-Chief

EDITORIAL BOARD

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF

Charlotte Rottiers is a PhD Candidate at the Faculty of Architecture, KU Leuven. Her current research investigates the material representation of Belgian diplomacy (1831-1914). Her interests lie in architectural history, cultural and political representation and the formation of identity through art and architecture.

ORCID: [0000-0002-7798-0575](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7798-0575)

EDITORIAL BOARD

Bertalan Bordas is a PhD candidate at the University of Pécs Interdisciplinary Doctoral School, also serves as an Assistant Lecturer there and a part-time lecturer at Eötvös Loránd University. An ISHA member since 2021, his research focuses on International History, particularly Britain's role in Central Eastern Europe.

ORCID [0000-0002-5659-1757](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5659-1757)

Zorana Cvijanovic is a PhD Candidate in Medieval and Early Modern Intellectual History at Radboud University. Her research revolves around the reception of classical literature and figures in the Middle Ages, particularly the concept of virtuous pagans in Medieval Latin and Greek literature.

ORCID [0009-0005-1234-4251](https://orcid.org/0009-0005-1234-4251)

David Kraus is a PhD candidate at Phillips Universität Marburg, working on the papacy of Innocent IV and the crusade against the von Hohenstaufen.

ORCID [0009-0002-4790-7120](https://orcid.org/0009-0002-4790-7120)

Julia Boechat Machado is a PhD Candidate at Central European University. In 2023, she also worked in ISHA as Webmaster and a Member of the Council. She is interested in cultural history, especially in what concerns the Soviet Union, and researches topics in the History of the Book and the History of Publishing.

ORCID [0000-0001-9440-4257](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9440-4257)

Zora Piskačová is a PhD Candidate in Modern European History at University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill. Her research focuses on Central Europe with particular focus on interwar Poland and Czechoslovakia. Topically she works at the intersection of urban history, borderlands studies, and peace and conflict studies.

ORCID [0009-0004-8729-0166](https://orcid.org/0009-0004-8729-0166)

Barbara Testini is a PhD student in the conjoint programme in Historical Studies at the Universities of Florence and Siena. Her current research project deals with the representations of Africa emerging from the Italian press from the 1950s to present day. Her academic interests also involve issues of memory, representation, and dystopian feminist literature.

ORCID [0009-0007-9578-0036](https://orcid.org/0009-0007-9578-0036)

Victor Wagner has a BA in communication studies and a joint MA degree in European History (2022) from HU Berlin and UC Dublin. His research usually addresses questions of diplomacy, nationalism, European integration, communication or media systems. His MA thesis discussed the dynamics and power struggles during unofficial truces in World War I.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Chandini Jaswal is a second-year master's student of History at Panjab University, India. She secured the gold medal in her undergraduate history degree. Jaswal is a core team member at Karwaan Heritage, India and a communication member at The Museum of British Colonialism, UK-Kenya. Jaswal's research interest focuses on subcontinental history, particularly women's studies in pre-modern India through histories of art. She has presented her research at conferences such as the New York Conference on Asian Studies and the Indian Association for South Asian Studies. Furthermore, she is engaged in documenting oral histories of the 1947 Partition.

ORCID: [0000-0003-4333-6893](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4333-6893)

Brooklyn Hortenstine is an incoming Ph.D. student in the Department of History at Northwestern University in Evanston, Illinois, United States. She is interested in the history of People with Disabilities in 20th-century Europe, having extensively written and researched on topics such as eugenics, post-war justice, and the Independent Living Movement in the German-speaking world. She holds a bachelor's and a master's degree in history from Austin Peay State University in Clarksville, Tennessee, as well as a master's in Comparative History from Central European University in Vienna, Austria. Her master's thesis focused on the inclusion and exclusion of People with Disabilities in Germany from 1945 to 1989, prior to the formal passage of disability rights. Currently, she is researching the role of self-help groups in Nazi Germany. Her work is particularly focused on the role and establishment of the Reichsbund for the Physically Disabled.

ORCID: [0009-0008-9638-2598](https://orcid.org/0009-0008-9638-2598)

Beatrice Leeming is a graduate student at the University of Cambridge. Her BA was at Durham University, and her MPhil was in Cambridge. She has been interested in cultural memory, transnational and migrating memory, and their representation. In her PhD, she is exploring the memorialisation of Holocaust sites since the 1990s, and the negotiation of 'relevance' by the visitors and the visited. In her previous research, she has explored the representation of 'difficult memory' in film, in Romania and in Germany. She is generously funded by the Cambridge Trust, and will take up a fellowship at the Institute for Contemporary History in Munich this year.

ORCID: [0009-0002-9871-808X](https://orcid.org/0009-0002-9871-808X)

Omer Merzić is a historian and editor born in Sarajevo in 1997. He currently lives and works in Sarajevo and London. He received his MA from the Department of History at Goldsmiths, University of London, and graduated from the Faculty of Philosophy at the University of Sarajevo. Omer's academic career has been committed to uncovering lesser-known narratives and challenging conventional historical interpretations. He currently works as an editor in the publishing house Dobra knjiga in Sarajevo, where he applies his professional knowledge to the publication of historical works. Omer volunteered at prestigious institutions such as the National Archives at Kew in London and the Institute of History in Sarajevo, which further enhanced his understanding of historical research and preservation.

ORCID: [0000-0001-7518-2193](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7518-2193)

Tinatin Mirianashvili is currently pursuing her MA in the Medieval Studies Department at the Central European University in Vienna. She obtained her BA in Liberal Arts at the Agricultural University of Georgia. She has presented her research at the 20th Annual Conference of the European Association for the Study of Religions and the 8th International Conference "The Modernity of Antiquity," dedicated to the 30th anniversary of diplomatic relations between Georgia and Greece. She participated in the Brno Summer School of Auxiliary Historical Sciences and the Summer University of CEU: Magic and Witchcraft: Belief and Persecution in Global Perspective. During her BA, she mastered the languages Latin, Ancient Greek, and French, allowing her to study primary sources, while she furthered her knowledge in German and Arabic during her MA. Her current research project questions the role of ecclesiastical and academic authorities in the thirteenth-century academic condemnations at the University of Paris.

Davide Politi is a Master's Student in Medieval Studies at Central European University in Vienna and a PhD Candidate at Ludwig Maximilian University in Munich. Originally from Naples, he earned his BA in History from the Alma Mater Studiorum of Bologna. His research specialises in European history from the eleventh to the fourteenth centuries, with particular emphasis on narratology, intellectual history, medieval Latin literature, preaching and exempla, monastic orders, and history of magic.

ORCID Number: [0009-0000-2120-721X](https://orcid.org/0009-0000-2120-721X)

Klára Řiháková is a first-year, part-time MSc student of History at the School of History, Classics and Archaeology, University of Edinburgh. She obtained her BA degree in English literature and History at Northumbria University, Newcastle upon Tyne in 2022, having written a bachelor's dissertation highlighting the intertwined nature of student activism, political developments, mobility, scholarship schemes, and activists. Her main research interest lies in the transnational approach to the history of activism and social movements transgressing the Cold War boundaries.

ORCID: [0009-0002-0429-8396](https://orcid.org/0009-0002-0429-8396)

Moreno Stedile is currently pursuing his MA in Social History at the University of São Paulo. In 2020, he obtained his BA in History at the University of São Paulo. He is an active member of the research group "Ana Gertrudes, mulher da terra: social history of subaltern groups in the global south (Africa & Americas)," coordinated by Prof. Wissenbach (USP), as well as of the Early Modern Iberian History Study Group, coordinated by Prof. Megiani (USP). His research focused on travel literature in Eastern Africa in the Early Modern Period, acknowledging the negotiated dimension of that textual production and the agency and active interaction between African societies and the world in that period.

Tvrtko Srdoc is a second-year student in Medieval Studies at the CEU in Vienna. His previous education (BA) was in History and Philosophy at the University of Rijeka, Croatia. The focus of his interest lies mainly in intellectual history (chiefly history of philosophy) of the Middle Ages, particularly the philosophy and theology written in Latin from the ninth to the fourteenth centuries. His BA thesis "Cosmological Argument in Medieval Philosophy: St. Thomas Aquinas and Herman Dalmatin" is currently being published as an article in the *Croatica Christiana Periodica*. At the CEU, he is continuing his research into Thomas Aquinas and the thirteenth century scholastic philosophy, particularly focusing on the so-called free will debate of the late thirteenth and early fourteenth centuries. Alongside Thomas, another intriguing philosopher sparking his interest is Henry of Ghent and the subsequent "voluntarist" tradition.
ORCID: [0009-0001-3675-9559](https://orcid.org/0009-0001-3675-9559)

Jelena Vukojević is a PhD Candidate of the Department of classics at Faculty of Philosophy, University of Belgrade. She earned both her bachelor's and master's degrees in classics from the same faculty, with a specialized focus on the stylistic nuances of the Latin language spanning various genres and historical periods. Currently, she is engaged as a research assistant at the Department of classics, Belgrade. From January 2023 she is a secretary of the editorial board of *Lucida intervalla*, an international peer-reviewed journal for Classical studies. Her field of study is Latin language and (digital) epigraphy, and she has a keen interest in ancient languages, cultures, and the teaching thereof.
ORCID profile: [0000-0002-6454-2656](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6454-2656)

Defining Victimhood: The Exclusion of People with Disabilities in Post-War Justice in Germany

BROOKLYN HORTENSTINE

Incoming PhD Candidate, Northwestern University in Evanston, Illinois

Abstract

In 1984, in response to petitions to recognise victims of euthanasia and people who were sterilised under Nazi laws for the purposes of reparations, the German Federal Minister of Finance declared that the requests were being denied because they were not repealed by the Allies, “had role models in foreign states” and “violated neither natural law nor rule of law.” This statement sparked a debate that had only made small steps in improvement after many of the surviving victims died and was never fully settled. This paper examines the intricacies of German post-war justice for people with disabilities through policies of reparations for sterilisation victims and the families of euthanasia victims. Because the Western Allied powers deemed the sterilisation law a measure of public health, most of the victims of the 1933 sterilisation law never saw an apology or responsibility taken by the German government for their ailments. Additionally, families of people who were killed under ‘euthanasia’ were excluded with the simple explanation that it was impossible to give reparations to people who were dead, and they did not qualify for simply being related. While these issues were addressed in some ways, they were never treated with the same regard as victims in other categories. This research is based not only on German laws concerning the treatment and reparations of Holocaust victims but also on stories shared by both victims of sterilisation and the surviving families of those who were victims of euthanasia, pulled from German newspapers, mostly from the 1980s, as well as other publications and stories which were shared. Attention will be paid both to West and East Germany, though it should be noted that the paper will focus mostly on West Germany, as the East refused to compensate victims for most of its history. A very brief history of sterilisation policies in the Allied nations will also be in order to explain their conclusions, but it will by no means be the focus of this paper. While scholars have addressed the lack of compensation before, my paper will stress these measures as a long history of a lack of disability rights.

Keywords: Reparations – Post-war Germany – People with Disabilities – Sterilisation – Euthanasia

Introduction

In the aftermath of the Second World War, the international community set out to prosecute the crimes committed by Nazi Germany, a task that required definitions of the extent of the crimes, of victims and perpetrators. While these categories remain delicate and elusive at best among historians of the Holocaust, they were necessary to deliver justice to the victims of the Holocaust, despite the many flaws that became apparent over time. Historians have spent decades trying to redefine and sort out the intricacies of the Nuremberg Trials and other trials concerning crimes that were committed while the Nazis were in power.¹ However, despite the ongoing attention, certain groups of victims remained largely unacknowledged and were denied justice in post-war Germany. Victims of sterilisation, and the families of those killed through ‘euthanasia’ are some of the most excluded groups in this case, and global acceptance of the legalisation of coerced sterilisation kept the German government from making amends until most of the survivors in these categories had died. Ultimately, the case for sterilised victims and the children of euthanasia victims shows that Germany, along with the rest of the world, was unwilling to dismantle their ableist prejudices and rehabilitate medical ethics even in the wake of the Holocaust.² This article examines post-war justice first by discussing the definitions of genocide and crimes against humanity agreed upon by the Allied powers and their effect on the legality of the 1933 sterilisation law, before turning to international efforts to receive reparations from West Germany, the stance of East Germany in the compensation debate with international organisations, and finally requests made by citizens on the individual level on behalf of themselves or their families.

Background

To properly explain the ease at which global communities dismissed sterilisation in the Nazi case, an understanding of eugenics in the wider twentieth century is crucial. As wider historiography shows, the practice of controlling a population to prevent social decline was a defining factor of the twentieth century. Coined in 1883 by Francis Galton, the term “eugenics” is derived from the Greek word for “wellborn.” It sought to create a scientific method for ensuring the biological fitness of a society. Galton and his supporters believed that physical, mental, and even moral traits of human beings could be controlled genetically, and severely discounted the role of one’s

¹ For a concise history of post-war trials and debates by and large see Mary Fulbrook, *Reckonings: Legacies of Nazi Persecution and the Quest for Justice*, (New York: Oxford University Press, 2020). For a deeper focus on crimes committed in hospitals and against people with disabilities, see Michael S. Bryant, *Confronting the “Good Death:” Nazi Euthanasia on Trial, 1945-1953* (Boulder: University Press of Colorado, 2005).

² Ableism refers to prejudice held against people because of their disabilities.

environment and circumstances.³ While the concept of eugenics emerged at the end of the nineteenth century, it was not until the twentieth century that nations began to view eugenics as something to be implemented on a wide scale.

Eugenic practices can be divided into two broader categories: positive eugenics and negative eugenics. Positive eugenics refers to a particular emphasis on fostering the reproduction of the most ‘fit’ members of society.⁴ In its purest form, positive eugenics does not promote strategies that work against minority groups that might be considered ‘undesirable.’ Examples of positive eugenics include, but are not limited to, the use of *in vitro* fertilisation, artificial insemination, and the development of sperm banks.⁵ These procedures are most commonly associated with current discussions on fertility, but the ideas behind them began developing as early as the 1930s. Despite these concepts occupying the minds of scholars as a possibility, the lack of technology meant that in the twentieth century, the practices of positive eugenics alone remained an ideal rather than a reality to the world.⁶

By contrast, negative eugenics were policies put in place to control the reproduction of “those individuals who are so meagrely or defectively endowed by nature that their offspring are bound to be antisocial, or at least unable to care for themselves.”⁷ This definition did not explicitly include everyone with a disability, nor did it directly exclude others, but it made it clear that being “anti-social” and defying the norms set forth by society would be treated as a disability itself. In some ways, it even implies that living a lifestyle outside of what was deemed *normal* is a larger disability than the inability to care for oneself. Unlike positive eugenics, negative eugenics did not rely on science too complex for its time and thus became the dominant model that proved successful in eugenic pursuits. It relied on forced sterilisation via vasectomy or tubal ligation, processes that were established at the end of the nineteenth century.⁸

Eugenic policies were implemented in numerous countries throughout the twentieth century, and while it would be reductionist to say that Nazi Germany was inspired by one nation in particular, German and American collaboration in the movement is notable. For example, prominent eugenicist Charles Davenport, who was one of the leading proponents for compulsory sterilisation in the United States, collaborated heavily with German eugenicists at the time. In the

³ Mark B. Adams, ed., *The Wellborn Science: Eugenics in Germany, France, Brazil, and Russia*, Monographs on the History and Philosophy of Biology (New York: Oxford University Press, 1990), 3.

⁴ Maurizio Meloni, “Into the Wild: The Radical Ethos of Eugenics,” in *Political Biology: Science and Social Values in Human Heredity from Eugenics to Epigenetics* (London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, 2016), 64–92.

⁵ Meloni, 71.

⁶ Meloni, “Into the Wild,” 70–71.

⁷ Harry H. Laughlin, “The Relation of Eugenics to Other Sciences,” *The Eugenics Review* 11, no. 2 (1919): 53–64, quoted in Meloni, 71.

⁸ Meloni, 71.

1920s, the United States passed some of the most widespread sterilisation laws on state levels, which were upheld by the Supreme Court in 1927. American genetic societies were the leaders, scholarly and financially, for the global eugenics movement.⁹ Leading American funders like the Rockefeller and Carnegie Institutes were known to fund German eugenicists with the equivalent of millions of dollars.¹⁰ Additionally, membership in the International Federation of Eugenic Organizations (IFEEO) allowed German scholars access to research, articles, and legislation on the practices of eugenics worldwide.¹¹ Through their exchange of information, German eugenicists no doubt became familiar with America's system of documenting familial illnesses through the establishment of the Eugenics Record Office as well as the difficulties faced by their American colleagues when implementing eugenic practices on both state and federal levels.¹²

In 1933, Hitler passed the Law for the Prevention of Genetically Diseased Offspring, commonly referred to as the Nazi sterilisation law or simply the 1933 sterilisation law. The new legislation legalised nationwide sterilisation performed by surgeons if “following the experience of medical science, it may be expected with great probability that their offspring may suffer severe physical or mental hereditary impairment.”¹³ Disabilities that fell under this category included schizophrenia, “feeble-mindedness,” Huntington's disease, epilepsy, “insanity,” hereditary blindness, and hereditary deafness. People who could propose sterilisation included the patient themselves, a legal guardian, a doctor, a psychiatrist, or a director of a health or living institution, but the final decision rested with hereditary health courts who would review the case and vote for or against the procedure.¹⁴

The addition of hereditary health courts and the strict implementation on a national level suggest a level of American influence, but the insistence that Nazi-Germany simply adopted American laws is greatly exaggerated. The Nazis may have drawn off American failures in eugenics and curated their list of disabilities from Laughlin's “Model Sterilisation Law,” but the law itself was drawn mainly from the sterilisation law drafted by a committee of the Prussian Health Board in 1932.¹⁵ Regardless of its level of direct and traceable influence, American and German

⁹ Edwin Black, *War against the Weak: Eugenics and America's Campaign to Create a Master Race* (New York: Four Walls Eight Windows, 2003), 272–77.

¹⁰ Black, 284. In 1923 alone, the Rockefeller Foundation funded German scientists with \$410,000, amounting to about 4 million in the twenty-first century.

¹¹ Black, 280–83. Membership to the society was organisational. A multitude of German Kaiser Wilhelm Institutes were active in the IFEEO, most notably the Kaiser Wilhelm Institute for Psychiatry, the Institute for Anthropology, Human Hereditary, and Eugenics, and the Institute for Brain Research.

¹² Egbert Klautke, “The Germans Are Beating Us at Our Own Game: American Eugenics and the German Sterilization Law of 1933,” *History of the Human Sciences* 29, no. 3 (July 2016): 25–43, <https://doi.org/10.1177/0952695116631230>.

¹³ Klautke, 32.

¹⁴ Klautke, 32.

¹⁵ Klautke, 31.

eugenicists largely continued to support one another despite slowly changing attitudes regarding sterilisation. Both nations used the support of the other to justify their practices.¹⁶ American Joseph S. DeJarnette, a proponent for sterilisation and superintendent of the Western Virginia Hospital, even complained that “the Germans are beating us at our own game.”¹⁷ Further, America’s position in the eugenics movement would be used to justify the existence of the 1933 sterilisation law in the post-war period, becoming a significant source of difficulty for people seeking justice and reparations. The legality of American sterilisation was also used as a point of defence, albeit unsuccessfully, for Karl Brandt and his fellow defendants at the Doctor’s Trial in Nuremberg in 1947.¹⁸

Literature Review and Methods

Work on disabled people in the Holocaust began emerging in the 1990s, and the topic of sterilisation is most often studied in conjunction with the Nazi euthanasia program, often referred to by its code name, the T4 Program. Perhaps the most ground-breaking historian on the topic of disability in Nazi Germany is Henry Friedlander. In his book *The Origins of Nazi Genocide: From Euthanasia to the Final Solution* (1995), Friedlander asserts, against the historiography of his time, that people with disabilities were not only victims of Nazi oppression, but that Hitler’s campaign against disabled people provided a “test case” for the methods used in the Final Solution. Friedlander’s stance that people with disabilities do qualify as victims of the Holocaust, and are one of the first victims, has become widely accepted in Holocaust research and in many ways laid the groundwork for the historical study of disabled people in Nazi Germany at a time when disabled people were not considered in scholarship more broadly, either.¹⁹ Published a year earlier in 1994, Michael Burleigh’s work, *Death and Deliverance: 'Euthanasia' in Germany, c.1900 to 1945* followed the idea of the “mercy death” throughout German history, placing the concept of ‘euthanasia’ in a wider range of German historiography.

These historians were instrumental in bringing the oppression of disabled people to the realm of Holocaust Studies, but their works focus on the programs themselves rather than the legal implications in the aftermath of the Holocaust and people seeking reparations. For this, Ernst

¹⁶ Klautke, 27, 35-37.

¹⁷ Klautke, 26.

¹⁸ Klautke, 37.

¹⁹ The debate on whether disabled people are considered victims of the Holocaust was part of a larger debate on expanding Holocaust research to other groups, including Roma people. Friedlander’s most notable critic was Yehuda Bauer. See, for example, Yehuda Bauer and Sybil Milton. “Correspondence: ‘Gypsies and the Holocaust.’” *The History Teacher* 25, no. 4 (1992): 513–21. <https://doi.org/10.2307/494357>.

Klee,²⁰ Paul Weidling,²¹ Michael S. Bryant,²² and Margret Hamm²³ have done significant research to document the actions of medical personnel and the post-war legal processes. Their achievements cannot be understated, but they either focus mainly on reparations for Jewish victims of the Holocaust (in the case of Weidling) or have chronicled post-war justice strictly in West Germany (in the case of Klee, Bryant, and Hamm.)

This article provides a more comprehensive look at post-war justice by examining the issue of reparations in both West and East Germany, as well as the lasting effects and problems in Germany after reunification. By beginning with the debates surrounding the definitions of crimes against humanity and genocide at Nuremberg, analysing legal proceedings in the Bundestag, official communication between advocacy groups and government officials, the process of denazification, and first-hand accounts from survivors seeking reparations, this article reconstructs the complications of post-war justice specifically for disabled victims of National Socialism. At the same time, it pays attention to the details of post-war policy in both sectors of influence in Germany during and after the occupation and acknowledges the most recent actions concerning the ongoing issue of compensation in Germany. Moreover, it discusses not just the failure of Germany in this regard, but also places some responsibility on the Allied powers and the general attitude towards people with disabilities at this time around the world.

A Note on "Disability" during National Socialism

When referring to "disability" and "disabled people," this article relies on the classifications placed on individuals by the Nazi state. While these labels are dangerous, it is both impossible and impractical to try to trace the validity of someone's disability at this time, especially as labels of "idiocy," "feeble-mindedness," and "insanity" among others are now obsolete and hold no concrete definitions.²⁴ As such, this article assumes that those sterilised under the Law for the Prevention of Genetically Diseased Offspring were, in one way or another, deemed disabled by the Nazi state. The same assumption is made when discussing citizens who were institutionalised in homes for people with disabilities, hospitals, or other residential care centres. Based on legal criteria, people

²⁰ Ernst Klee, *Was sie taten, was sie wurden: Ärzte, Juristen und andere Beteiligte am Kranken- oder Judenmord* (Frankfurt am Main: Fischer Taschenbuch, 1986). Klee also authored numerous articles for the German newspaper *Die Zeit* on crimes against the disabled during Nazi times.

²¹ Paul Weidling, ed., *From Clinic to Concentration Camp: Reassessing Nazi Medical and Racial Research, 1933–1945* (London: Routledge, 2017).

²² Michael S. Bryant, *Confronting the "Good Death": Nazi Euthanasia on Trial, 1945–1953* (Boulder, Colorado: University Press of Colorado, 2005).

²³ Margret Hamm, ed., *Ausgegrenzt! warum? Zwangssterilisierte und Geschädigte der NS-"Euthanasie" in der Bundesrepublik Deutschland* (Berlin: Metropol, 2017).

²⁴ For more on the history of this terminology, see John Simpson, "Chapter 2: What's in a Name?," in *Supporting Individuals with Intellectual Disabilities & Mental Illness*, eds. Sherri Melrose et al. (Vancouver: BCCampus, 2015), 8–18.

sterilised under the Nazi sterilisation law were documented as having “feeble-mindedness,” schizophrenia, hereditary epilepsy, manic-depressive disorder, hereditary deafness, hereditary blindness, “severe malformation,” severe alcoholism, and Huntington’s Disease. Of these classifications, a diagnosis of “feeble-mindedness” constituted more than half of the sterilisations performed in 1934.²⁵

Similarly, children and adults with more severe disabilities such as “idiocy,” Down’s Syndrome, paralysis, Cerebral Palsy, and major deformities, among others, were killed through the Nazi “euthanasia” program.²⁶ These victims were deemed “lives unworthy of life.” This designation was lifted from attorney Karl Binding and psychiatrist Alfred Hoche’s book *Permitting the Destruction of Life Unworthy of Life* (1920).²⁷ It was distorted by Nazi propaganda to describe people considered useless, non-contributing members of National Socialist society. The original document contained notable differences from Nazi policy, such as the insistence of consent from a patient or a guardian when considering euthanasia, but the phrase is now synonymous with Nazism.²⁸

It is important to acknowledge the arbitrary and dangerous nature of these terms and to recognise that despite these guidelines, many people sterilised or killed under these laws would not have been or considered themselves disabled. However, it would cause far more confusion and be extremely problematic to redefine disability in this article. Therefore, distinctions between victim groups who received reparations are only made when it is abundantly clear that the German government is classifying a group as not having been sterilised based on disability for the purposes of determining compensation. Additionally, most of the personal stories throughout this article do not specify a survivor’s disability. This was not a deliberate choice, but rather because many survivors do not comment on their conditions, whether legitimate or perceived by the Nazi regime.²⁹

²⁵ Henry Friedlander, *The Origins of Nazi Genocide: From Euthanasia to the Final Solution* (Chapel Hill: The University of North Carolina Press, 1995), 29.

²⁶ Friedlander, 45.

²⁷ Karl Binding and Alfred Hoche, *Die Freigabe der Vernichtung lebensunwerten Lebens: ihr Mass und ihr Ziel* (1920) (Berlin: Berliner Wissenschafts-Verlag, 2006).

²⁸ Howard Brody and M. Wayne Cooper, “Binding and Hoche’s ‘Life Unworthy of Life’: A Historical and Ethical Analysis,” *Perspectives in Biology and Medicine* 57, no. 4 (2014): 500–511, <https://doi.org/10.1353/pbm.2014.0042>.

²⁹ For more on National Socialist notions of disability, see Staffan Bengtsson, “The Nation’s Body: Disability and Deviance in the Writings of Adolf Hitler,” *Disability & Society* 33, no. 3 (March 16, 2018): 416–32, <https://doi.org/10.1080/09687599.2018.1423955>.

Genocide and Crimes Against Humanity at Nuremberg

Any discussion of victimhood and genocide must begin in the place where definitions for genocide were first evoked to describe crime: at the Nuremberg Trials. The failure to consider disabled people, particularly those sterilised through the Law for the Prevention of Genetically Diseased Offspring, as victims of Nazi persecution lies largely with the Allied Powers and the restrictions put in place with the prosecution of Nazi criminals.³⁰ The way in which Nazi criminals should be prosecuted in the post-war era became a point of contention. Where Raphael Lemkin clearly expressed a desire for the concept of “genocide” to apply to crimes against groups of humans as broadly as possible, and for the prosecutions of the Nuremberg trials to encompass crimes that took place beginning in 1933 until the end of the war, the Allies used the word in a more limited sense. Sir Hartley Shawcross, who served as the main prosecutor for the British at Nuremberg, agreed that “genocide” was a crime against humanity that was exacerbated to the most extreme extent. However, he also inserted that for a crime to be considered genocide in the case of the Nazis, it had to be committed in connection with the war itself.³¹ This decision was part of a larger effort of reaching a compromise between the Allied Powers on exactly who the charges could be applied to in the post-war era and to what extent.

The biggest challenge facing the lawmakers behind the International Military Tribunal was the wording of Article 6 of the Nuremberg Charter. The charter itself was a collection of laws that would be used to prosecute Nazis, and Article 6 defined the bounds of the Tribunal and the charges of crimes against peace, war crimes, and crimes against humanity.³² Initially, Soviet representatives proposed a draft of international laws that would attach the criminality of waging aggressive wars specifically to instances where it was done “specifically on behalf of the European Axis powers.”³³ Without the distinction, they felt that the laws they drafted could potentially be used against the Allies for the extreme actions taken in their defensive measures. American delegates insisted that the laws they created had to be able to apply to any future nations who might break international law. Thus, they rejected the revision because it meant that by definition,

³⁰ The terms “disabled people” and “people with disabilities” are used interchangeably throughout this article. The author recognises the ongoing conversation about the usage of these terms and acknowledges the arguments made for the usage of both terms with no ill intent. For more information, see Krista L. Best et al., “Language Matters! The Long-Standing Debate between Identity-First Language and Person First Language,” *Assistive Technology* 34, no. 2 (March 4, 2022): 127–28, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10400435.2022.2058315>.

³¹ Philippe Sands, *East West Street: On the Origins of “Genocide” and “Crimes against Humanity,”* (New York: Alfred A. Knopf, 2016), 334–36.

³² ICRC Database, Treaties, States Parties and Commentaries, “Agreement for the Prosecution and Punishment of the Major War Criminals of the European Axis, and Charter of the International Military Tribunal.” (London, August 8, 1945.) Article 6, <https://ihl-databases.icrc.org/en/ihl-treaties/nuremberg-tribunal-charter-1945/article-6b>.

³³ Francine Hirsch, *Soviet Judgment at Nuremberg: A New History of the International Military Tribunal after World War II* (New York: Oxford University Press, 2020), 68.

the charges could only be applied to specific nations. Instead, American negotiator and Supreme Court judge Robert Jackson suggested that the preamble to Article 6 could establish the tribunal's jurisdiction as "on behalf of the European Axis powers."³⁴ By adding the limitations to the preamble rather than the definition itself, the Soviets received the protection they asked for without the problem of the Charter not being able to be applied to other countries in the future if needed.

At the same time, Jackson stood firm in his assertion that "crimes against humanity" had to be in connection with the crime of aggressive war, noting "regrettable circumstances" faced by minorities in his own country at the time. Soviet and British delegates supported Jackson against rejections from the French representative in this particular matter, but the Soviets remained doubtful that a preamble would protect them.³⁵ In the end, compromises were made. Jackson became less persistent that "aggression" had to be defined as a key distinction with other kinds of warfare, the Soviet delegation accepted that declaring jurisdiction be separate from legal definitions, and the French agreed to allow a restrictive definition of crimes against humanity that placed it dependent on both the timeline of the war and in connection to other crimes. These stipulations would prevail at Nuremberg. The implication, of course, was that any crimes committed before the invasion of Poland in September 1939 did not fall within the jurisdiction of the Nuremberg Tribunals.

In addition to the timeline, distinctions between genocide and crimes against humanity are at play. Initially, Lemkin wanted genocide to encompass crimes that aimed to destroy groups of human beings as broadly as possible in order to maximise the probability of delivering justice to as many victim groups of the Holocaust as possible. However, this was not the case, and the charge of genocide was employed sparingly during the Nuremberg trials.³⁶ Much more commonly used was Hersch Lauterpacht's term, "crimes against humanity."³⁷ Lauterpacht was a British international human rights lawyer who, like Lemkin, was personally affected by the Holocaust. Throughout the 1930s, he had already written many books on international law. "Crimes against humanity" importantly differed from "genocide" in that it stressed the importance of protecting the individual over the group. The idea was meant not only to protect people who may not fit under a defined group that was necessary for the charge of genocide to be applied, but it also stressed that individual criminals could be responsible for acts committed in the name of the state. For all the debate the distinction caused, the charge of crimes against humanity prevented the

³⁴ Hirsch, 70.

³⁵ Hirsch, 70.

³⁶ Sands, 335-336.

³⁷ Sands, 3-4.

Nazis on trial from being able to claim that they were not individually responsible for their own crimes because they were working on orders given by Hitler.

These two conditions, while they left plenty of room for the persecution of criminals who acted against defined victim groups—Jews, Poles, etc.—opened a door for the exclusion of disabled people. For one, the *Law for the Prevention of Genetically Diseased Offspring* was not considered a crime at all, as it was passed before 1939. While sterilisation was considered as an issue during the trials, and was later considered an aspect of genocide itself, the sterilisations considered at the trial were those that were conducted to destroy a racial, religious, or ethnic group in concentration camps, or the experimentation that often occurred alongside it as the Nazis attempted to create new scientific methods for the procedure. Sterilisations that happened outside the scope of the war were assumed to be against those who were considered disabled, and were not considered a crime in their own right, as nations reserved the right to pass sterilisation laws as a matter of routine public health.³⁸ Both of these considerations formed the basis under which Germany would justify excluding people with disabilities from the definition of who would be considered a victim of the Holocaust.

Legalities of Victimhood and Compensation in the Federal Republic of Germany

Despite the conditions set at Nuremberg, the Federal Act on Compensation for Victims of National Socialist Persecution (BEG) of 1953 passed in West Germany was intended to compensate a wider group of people, by offering compensation to all eligible groups who were targeted from January 1933 to May 1945.³⁹ However, under this law, people persecuted due to their disabilities were still not clearly considered victims of Nazi persecution. As per section one of the Federal Act on Compensation for Victims of National Socialist Persecution (BEG) of 1953, victims of National Socialism are classified as those who have suffered for “reasons of political opposition to National Socialism or for reasons of race, faith or belief and have suffered damage to life, body, health, freedom, property, assets, or in their professional or economic progress.”⁴⁰ In most cases, this included the surviving relatives of the victims and those who were injured by the Nazis for opposition against them as defined under §1, paragraphs one and two, quoted above.

³⁸ For more information on eugenic sterilisations in other countries, see Mark B. Adams, *The Wellborn Science: Eugenics in Germany, France, Brazil, and Russia* (New York: Oxford University Press, 1990), and Edwin Black, *War Against the Weak: America's Campaign to Create a Master Race* (New York: Four Walls Eight Windows, 2003).

³⁹ Bundesministerium der Justiz and Bundesamt für Justiz, “Bundesgesetz zur Entschädigung für Opfer der Nationalsozialistischen Verfolgung (Bundesentschädigungsgesetz - BEG)” (1953).

⁴⁰ “Bundesentschädigungsgesetz.”

Because disabled people were not listed explicitly as victims in these paragraphs, their families were often unable to claim reparations as well. Some succeeded via a revision passed in 1965 under §171, paragraph 4, no. 2, which stated that monetary compensation could be granted if it was reasonable to assume that the surviving dependent would be financially supported by the person who was killed if they were alive today. This, of course, was not possible for many when considering “life unworthy of life,” as the very reason for their persecution was their presumed inability to contribute to the nation economically.

The issue of compensation for people sterilised during the Nazi regime was broached in the Bundestag multiple times during the post-war era. In 1957 during parliamentary session 191 in Bonn, the discussion was driven mainly by the remarks of Heinrich Ritzel, a member of the Socialist Party of Germany (SPD) and Alfred Hartmann, a member of the Christian Social Union in Bavaria (CSU).⁴¹ Hartmann served as the state secretary of the Federal Ministry of Finance at the time, the legislative body responsible for handling compensation claims.⁴² When the question of compensation for those sterilised was raised, Hartmann responded by dividing the group of “sterilised people” into three groups: those who were sterilised because of their race, faith, or beliefs as outlined by the Compensation Law, those who were sterilised through unapproved methods, and those who were sterilised through approved methods because they were perceived as disabled under the Nazi state. Hartmann made it clear that when it came to sterilisation, the Bundestag specifically singled out the third group, those sterilised under the Law for Prevention of Genetically Diseased Offspring and denied them the possibility of receiving payments.⁴³

At this session, Hartmann gave four main reasons for the Bundestag’s refusal to compensate disabled victims of National Socialism. First, they continually argued that other countries had their own sterilisation laws in place, for example, the United States and Sweden.⁴⁴ While this point is certainly true, as Ritzel points out, the countries listed as justification never employed forced sterilisation as strictly or widespread as Nazi Germany had done. For example, between 1941 and 1976, approximately 63,000 people in Sweden were sterilised. In the United States, by 1960 approximately 61,540 people were sterilised under the law.⁴⁵ While none of these

⁴¹ This is a regional sister party of the Christian Democratic Union of Germany (CDU). The CSU operates only in Bavaria, while the CDU operates in the other German states.

⁴² From 1923–35 Hartmann served as senior governing council in the Ministry of Finance. Because he refused to join the Nazi party, he was first transferred to the tax office Berlin-Friedrichshain from 1935–1942, and then to the Federal Audit Court, where he was responsible for managing the special property tax on Jews, before being drafted in 1944. See Muzinger Internationales Biographisches Archiv 47/1967 (November 13, 1967.)

⁴³ “2. Deutscher Bundestag — 191. Sitzung. Bonn, Donnerstag, den 7. Februar 1957” (Deutscher Bundestag, 1957).

⁴⁴ “2. Deutscher Bundestag — 191. Sitzung.”

⁴⁵ Stephanie Hyatt, “A Shared History of Shame: Sweden’s Four-Decade Policy of Forced Sterilization and the Eugenics Movement in the United States,” *Indiana International & Comparative Law Review* 8, no. 2 (1998): 475–503.

countries demonstrate morally ethical medical practices, to compare them to the 400.000 people sterilised in Nazi Germany between the years of 1933 and 1945 explicitly dismisses the extreme intention and ideology held by Nazi Germany. When Ritzel brought this point up, Hartmann had no other explanations. He could not say for sure that the Bundestag representatives knew this or had taken it into consideration, and simply pressed further that no additional action was to be taken.

Hartmann continues by saying that, in addition to precedent, the Federal Compensation Act does not apply to non-material issues, except for when one's liberty is infringed upon. He insisted that sterilisation on its own does no physical damage to someone, and when done correctly only has the possibility of psychological damage, concluding this particular point by implying that this risk does not matter because, in the case of disabled people, those who were sterilised under the 1933 law were "essentially already mentally unstable."⁴⁶ In the fourth point, Hartmann encouraged people to file general claims of their sterilisations as "sacrifices" or to file claims for damages made during the sterilisation procedure when applicable, of which both options remained largely out of reach and defeated the goal of gaining recognition for those individuals and organisations who wished for sterilisation survivors to be added to the criteria of victims of National Socialism.⁴⁷ His motives for this denial on a personal level are unclear, as he continued to repeat that the Bundestag had no intentions or desires to pass further compensation acts, repeatedly citing that they had no obligation to do so because the sterilisation law of 1933 was in line with the laws of other nations at the time, and not an act of war.

The points raised by Hartmann would be repeated a multitude of times when post-war Germany repeatedly revisited the issue of compensation for forced sterilisation. The solidity of the argument as well as the people involved in it often raises questions about Germany's true commitment to making amends with the past. For example, the discussion resurfaced in 1961, when a group of lawmakers and seven "experts" in the fields of medicine and genetics met to discuss the possibility of expanding reparations and repealing the sterilisation law. Three of the seven people invited to give their professional opinions were former Nazi doctors who had supported the sterilisation law under Hitler. The biases that would obviously come with them seemed to be of minimal concern for the group, which ultimately decided once again that sterilisation ordered by hereditary health courts did not violate any international laws. Their reasoning was based again on the presence of sterilisation in other countries, and the fact that the Allies found the law constitutional during occupation because it was in line with the laws of other

⁴⁶ "2. Deutscher Bundestag — 191. Sitzung," 1087, section B.

⁴⁷ "2. Deutscher Bundestag — 191. Sitzung," 1087, section B.

nations at the time.⁴⁸ While true, this logic ignores the fact that sterilisation in Nazi Germany took place at an unprecedented rate in comparison to other nations.

Because of the widespread legitimisation of coerced sterilisation, compensation for victims was championed, for the most part, not as a mass group effort, but more commonly as smaller feats by individual organisations representing specific groups, often within their respective countries. For example, a French survivor's organisation, *Association nationale des anciennes déportées et internées de la Résistance*, succeeded in gaining the support of the UN in 1950, leading to the passing of an action that ordered Germany to issue reparations to women survivors of concentration camp experiments. While the compensation for sterilisation victims is minimal (around 3,000 DM), it is a notable achievement in comparison to the efforts made and attention gained by *the* League of Persons Damaged by "Euthanasia" and Compulsory Sterilisation (Bund der "Euthanasie"-Geschaedigten und Zwangssterilisierten, BEZ). This organisation, which tries to include all victims, even those whose sterilisations were deemed "routine," was not established until 1987, and had most of its attempts to obtain reparations for all rejected.⁴⁹

Highlighting the success of other groups in comparison to BEZ is not to suggest that victims sterilised outside of the confines of the Law for the Prevention of Genetically Diseased Offspring had an easy time obtaining reparations after the war. They, too, often received small payouts that did not make a significant impact. Many survivors who were sterilised using reversible techniques campaigned for the reversal to be attempted, and for the costs incurred to fall on the government. Their requests remained ignored despite having been offered as a genuine way for the German government to make amends without the need for continuous reparations.⁵⁰ Still, it is clear that international advocacy groups did not attempt, or at least were not as successful in their campaigns for disabled survivors, or the families of those subject to euthanasia.

Compensation for victims of sterilisation came slowly and was not uniformly based on the situation of the victim in question. From 1953 onwards, German sterilisation victims attempted to file claims as general victims of Nazi persecution but were given a plethora of reasons for rejection. The first revisions for payments made specifically to victims of coerced sterilisation were not established until 1980 under §171, paragraph four of the reparation regulations. This change was made only after pressure from victims and international groups forced German authorities to accept that Nazi-era sterilisations were criminal acts. However, this addition had notable

⁴⁸ "Protokoll der 34. Sitzung des Ausschusses für Wiedergutmachung," (Bonn: Deutscher Bundestag, April 13, 1961).

⁴⁹ Paul Weindling, "Too Little, Too Late: Compensation for Victims of Coerced Sterilization," in *Psychiatry and the Legacies of Eugenics: Historical Studies of Alberta and Beyond*, eds. Frank W. Stahnisch and Erna Kurbegović (Edmonton: Athabasca University Press, 2020), 181-98.

⁵⁰ Weindling, "Too Little, Too Late: Compensation for Victims of Coerced Sterilization," 188.

differences from the compensation laws passed previously. While the general applications that many filed in 1953 would have allowed survivors to receive payments for the rest of their lives as others had received, the program launched in 1980 allowed only a one-time payment of 5,000 DM.⁵¹ In 1988, this was extended to include a monthly payment of 100 DM, and in 1999 adjusted and increased to 120 Euros after the currency change.⁵² Today, this amount has been adjusted to a maximum payment of 2.556 Euros total.⁵³

Two-Sided Responsibility? Reparations and the Medical Sphere in the German Democratic Republic

The measures discussed in this article thus far concern only the actions taken either by the Allies in Germany as an occupied nation, or the responsibility taken by the Federal Republic after 1949. Despite the Soviet sphere being the only occupation zone to outlaw the sterilisation law under the pretence that it harboured antidemocratic and Nazi spirit, relatively little was done both concerning compensating victims of the Holocaust and putting an end to proponents for eugenic sterilisation.

Until the very end of its existence, East Germany rejected any responsibility for the crimes of the Holocaust, insisting that the people who were involved in the creation of the new State were anti-fascist and that East Germany was the 'rightful' Germany after the war. When faced with the discussion of reparations to any individuals or the State of Israel more broadly, the GDR continually cited that their obligations were only those agreed upon at Yalta (February 1945) and Potsdam (July 1945), which covered only reparations to be made by Germany to Allied nations.⁵⁴ As such, East German reparations came only in the form of investment and consumer goods that were shipped to the Soviet Union, such as machinery, sugar, and household chemicals.⁵⁵ East Germany did not reach any agreements for reparations towards the Holocaust until 1990, after the country's first and only democratic election as an independent nation. During this time, East Germany issued apologies for its continued refusal to cooperate with organisations that sought reparations and began acknowledging that it had a responsibility towards victims. However, even after this breakthrough, the East German government conducted agreements solely with the

⁵¹ "Wiedergutmachung - Regelungen zur Entschädigung von NS-Unrecht" (Bundesministerium der Finanzen, May 10, 2022), article no. BMF40106.

⁵² Weindling, "Too Little, Too Late: Compensation for Victims of Coerced Sterilization," 193-95.

⁵³ "Wiedergutmachung."

⁵⁴ Angelika Timm, *Jewish Claims Against East Germany* (Budapest: Central European University Press, 1998), 73-94.

⁵⁵ John P. Nettl, "Soviet Reparations Policy," in *The Eastern Zone and Soviet Policy in Germany, 1945-50* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1951), 199-238.

World Jewish Congress (WJC), speaking only of their commitment to Jewish victims of the Holocaust with no mention of further victim categories.⁵⁶

After reunification, Germany further addressed the lack of responsibility taken by the GDR through a series of updates and revisions made to their reparations law. In the added statements, the newly unified Germany claimed that in the GDR, victims of National Socialism received benefits such as general health care and pensions, both for their old age and for their status as survivors of Nazi tyranny, and “honour pensions.” These benefits were only paid to residents of the GDR, but no further details as to what the payments were or who was classified as a victim in these cases were explicitly given, beyond that they likely only went to those who were ‘viewed favourably’ by the socialist system. The same addition makes clear that separate restitution agreements were made between East Germany and the governments of Austria, Denmark, Finland, and Sweden for survivors who were residents of those nations, but again, no other defining details are given.⁵⁷ Survivors living in East Germany were only eligible to apply for reparations under BEG after reunification. They were also granted the opportunity to apply for restitution of property, an option that remained open to them until 1992 (real estate) and 1993 (movable property).⁵⁸ Despite the constant revisions given to the law, disabled people continued to have difficulty obtaining recognition because they were not added to the class of victims. The ability to open reparation claims again for East Germans because they were previously ineligible illustrates that the exclusion of disabled victims was done by choice, rather than need or circumstance.

Even though sterilisation was outlawed in East Germany, not everyone was in favour of such a move. Opinions on the matter remained mixed, and while no sterilisations took place, professionals in the country were certainly products of their time and some undoubtedly viewed sterilisation as a public health measure, even if they considered themselves anti-fascist. On the other hand, we also cannot assume that medical professionals in East Germany were vehemently anti-Nazi. Despite being regarded as the zone with the strictest denazification protocols, the medical sphere is one area in which relative leniency was shown.⁵⁹ Typically, a person’s job was not the first consideration made by the denazification commissions, but in the case of those in medical care and social work, this was a factor often put above someone’s political past. While this

⁵⁶ Ari L. Goldman, “Upheaval in the East: East Germany; East Germany Agrees to Pay Reparations to the Jewish Victims of the Nazis,” *The New York Times*, February 9, 1990. See also Ferdinand Protzman, “Upheaval in the East; The East Germans Issue an Apology for Nazi Crimes,” *The New York Times*, April 13, 1990.

⁵⁷ “Wiedergutmachung,” section 1.5.

⁵⁸ “Wiedergutmachung.”

⁵⁹ Timothy R. Vogt, *Denazification in Soviet-Occupied Germany: Brandenburg, 1945-1948*, Harvard Historical Studies, v. 137 (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2000), 158-60.

hierarchy of considerations obviously goes against the purposes of the denazification process, necessity was often cited as reasoning. To balance the need for well-trained medical personnel in a country already lacking with the pressures to thoroughly denazify the population, compromises were put in place that allowed doctors found guilty of Nazi sympathies to be moved to the public sector and restricted from operating their own private practices. Denazification cases involving doctors were asked to be treated with a heightened level of concern and consideration for the availability of doctors in the area. That is, the courts were asked to place a high level of importance not necessarily on the doctors' activities during the war, but rather on their actions and commitment to a democratic system since 1945. Doctors and medical personnel also qualified as part of a "special interest" group and were allowed to go through a special process of appeals.⁶⁰

In a sample compiled by Vogt, it was found that out of over 2.700 completed cases in the denazification courts in various districts, only 287 concerned healthcare workers or doctors to begin with. Of those, 9% of individuals were considered to be "activists" in favour of Nazism. 86% were declared only nominal supporters and given full approval to keep their positions, while the remaining 5% were given conditional approval. Further archival sources also report health and social services as having the highest acceptance rates compared to other professions, suggesting that the Soviet authorities, while banning further sterilisation, were less concerned with the wellbeing of Holocaust survivors who were subject to the procedures.⁶¹

Whether the sterilisation ban was made to establish the Eastern Zone as the place toughest on Nazi law or to discourage any further discussion of either positive or negative eugenics, justice for survivors was not any more of a priority for the Soviets than it was for the Western Powers, nor would it develop any smoother in GDR than in the Federal Republic after the official establishment of the two countries. Additionally, although a trial against key figures of the National Socialist hereditary health tribunal took place under Soviet jurisdiction specifically for sterilisation and crimes against humanity, the sentences given there were later dropped or significantly reduced.⁶² Unlike the Western Zone, there are no large activist groups present in East Germany to represent people who had been sterilised by the Nazis, nor is there any documentation of debates for financial compensation. Rather, the GDR's stance on sterilisation only went as far as outlawing the 1933 sterilisation law "because of its antidemocratic character and its fascist, tendentious

⁶⁰ Vogt, 159.

⁶¹ Vogt, 156–60. Statistics used here appear to be Vogt's own. Other statistics cited in Vogt are lifted from the Brandenburgisches Landeshauptarchiv. See *Denazification in Soviet-Occupied Germany* for more clarification on the collection process and criteria.

⁶² Weindling, "Too Little, Too Late: Compensation for Victims of Coerced Sterilization," 192.

presentation of theories about hereditary diseases.”⁶³ The only other statement concerning victims of Nazism with disabilities came in May of 1948, when a group of psychiatrists issued a statement rejecting sterilisation and euthanasia, in which they urged that “medical professionals should work in a social spirit of sacrifice to help ill people.”⁶⁴ No other mentions of disabled people in relation to compensation and Nazism are made, and this statement itself functions in a way that reinforces notions of the disabled body within socialist ideals rather than as citizens who are valuable as individuals.⁶⁵

Individual Attempts to Receive Compensation

Around 400.000 people had been forcibly sterilised under the Nazi regime and a further 300.000 were killed through euthanasia. Over the years, survivors have come out detailing their experiences or those of their loved ones.⁶⁶ Highlighting these stories demonstrates the kinds of excuses that were given by the federal government, as well as the normalisation of their exclusion from post-war justice.

Heinrich Lohne, Compensation for Survivors:

Heinrich Lohne began the process of being recognised as a victim of National Socialism in May of 1985. At the age of ten, Lohne was sent to the Kalemehof Institute for the Disabled, situated in Idstein, Hessen. There, he had worked as a carpenter’s apprentice and was forced to build coffins with unlocking bottoms, with the added responsibility of disposing of corpses. He, like the other residents of the institution, had been starved and beaten by staff during his time there. Lohne reports that towards the end of his time at the institute, he had been forced to dig a grave of his own, and recognising it was meant for himself, survived the war by first rushing to the doctor’s office. When he had realised the doctor would be no help, he escaped to a nearby barn where he had hidden from his oppressors until American troops arrived and liberated the surviving patients of Kalemehof.

Lohne requested status as a victim of National Socialism only so that his forced labour would be recognised as work time to be counted towards his retirement pension. Without it, his

⁶³ Sabine Hanrath, *Zwischen Euthanasie und Psychiatriereform. Anstaltspsychiatrie in Westfalen und Brandenburg: Ein deutsch-deutscher Vergleich, 1945–1964* (Paderborn: Schöningh, 2002), 202, quoted in Carol Poore, *Disability in Twentieth-Century German Culture* (Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press, 2007), 252.

⁶⁴ Poore, 251–54.

⁶⁵ For more on disability and socialism, see Poore, “Disability and Socialist Images of the Human Being in the Culture of the German Democratic Republic,” in *Disability in Twentieth-Century German Culture*, 231–72.

⁶⁶ Statistics from the Arbeitsgemeinschaft Bund der „Euthanasie“-Geschädigten und Zwangssterilisierten (BEZ).

monthly payments would be too low to support himself, and Lohne wanted to avoid drawing social assistance. The Hessian state insurance agency rejected Lohne's request on the grounds that he did not qualify under the definitions of Holocaust victims as laid out by the Federal Compensation Act. Additionally, they stated that Lohne had missed the deadline to file compensation anyway. Lohne was never made aware of the initial deadline, or his eligibility status until after it already passed.

In addition to the welfare organisations and the federal body that decides on compensation claims, Lohne caught the attention of the *Idsteiner Zeitung (Idsteiner Newspaper)*, which published his story and the problems he continually faced. In response, the Hessian state welfare organisation, which was responsible for the Kalemehof facility after the war, initially reached out and offered Lohne a one-time payment of 1.000 marks as a kind of 'mercy' for the abuse he faced in the institution and the trouble he had gone through to be compensated after the war. However, they later rescinded this offer, claiming that they were not legally or morally responsible for the damages, mental or physical, inflicted on Heinrich Lohne. Their reasoning? The organisation argued that it did not exist during the war, and it was only established in 1953.

For Heinrich Lohne, the issue was no longer about compensation at this point, but the recognition was denied. While his abusers easily obtained their full pensions, and the city of Idstein strongly campaigned for their pardons, Lohne is haunted both emotionally and physically by what was done to him, without ever being considered part of the persecuted.⁶⁷

Anonymous Citizens, Konstanz, Compensation Attempts by Family Members:

Along with survivors who had been sterilised, children and surviving family members of people killed through the euthanasia program were also excluded from receiving reparations under the criteria of the compensation act. Their attempts to get help through other means were rejected for multiple reasons, as shown by two women from separate families whose parents were killed through the euthanasia program.

In 1983, the city of Konstanz had discovered 193 urns of euthanasia victims in the basement of a local morgue. The surviving family members were searched for and contacted when possible. For one woman, this is how she learned that her mother had been killed in a gas chamber at the Grafeneck facility in 1940. Over 40 years later, the daughter processed the new information given to her and attempted to apply for compensation in March of 1984. The state officials in Baden-Württemberg rejected the application. According to the state compensation office, the

⁶⁷ Ernst Klee, "Geldverschwendung an Schwachsinnige und Säufer," *Die Zeit*, no. 18, April 26, 1986, 2-3.

deadline to file for reparations was at the end of 1969, and since then, they have been unable to file any new cases. The woman attempted to appeal the decision, explaining she had only just learned of her mother's fate, and did not know she had become a victim of National Socialism until 1983 when her mother's ashes were found. The compensation office responded, saying that these reasons were "insignificant," and an exception would not be made for her.⁶⁸

Another woman reports that her family was denied any compensation after her father had been killed in Grafeneck, and that interactions with the authorities continually burden her family emotionally. Her mother first applied for reparations in 1955 after the family escaped to the Federal Republic, but the continued rejections led her to give up entirely on receiving compensation. For the rest of her life, the woman's mother was bothered by the fact that her life and the lives of her children were ruined by National Socialism, and that they lived without recognition. This burden was passed to the daughter, who also failed to receive acknowledgement of their suffering.⁶⁹

In response to issues like this, the Federal Ministry of Finance reasoned that reparations were made to go to victims themselves, and this was impossible to do for victims of euthanasia. However, there was, theoretically, a way around this by filing for hardship compensation through §171, paragraph three, number two of the act. Such a request was only granted if the applicant could prove that they would be receiving financial support from the person who died, had they not been killed or injured by war.⁷⁰ Clearly, this "loophole" does not easily apply to those whose family members were considered "unworthy of life" due to their disabilities. As a result, even people's attempts to find ways to be recognized and compensated on an individual basis were oftentimes in vain.

The attempts made by the citizens described above are only a few of the hundreds of cases that were rejected because either the victim in question or the person applying for reparations did not meet the qualifications to be considered persecuted under National Socialism.⁷¹ The sources make it clear that the reasons given by the Federal Republic were arbitrary and shifted as the situation of the applicant changed. The loophole in place for hardship as it stood at the time reinforced ideas that citizens were only as valuable as the labour that they could produce that would turn into monetary support for their families. Further cases were collected and taken on by BEZ, but most of them were continually rejected. Consequently, despite the small steps that were taken to consider sterilised people for hardship compensation, their efforts to actually receive such

⁶⁸ Klee, 1.

⁶⁹ Klee, 2.

⁷⁰ Klee, 1–2; Bundesentschädigungsgesetz - BEG.

⁷¹ For more examples of individual cases, see Margret Hamm, ed., *Ausgegrenzt! warum? Zwangssterilisierte und Geschädigte der NS-"Euthanasie" in der Bundesrepublik Deutschland* (Berlin: Metropol, 2017), 177–80.

payments had little to no effect on the lives of survivors, as they often did not receive a positive response. Furthermore, in the rare situation where one did receive hardship pay, the amount was small and showed that victims of sterilisation were not held to the same level of regard as other victims of the Holocaust.

Recognition as a Continuing Issue

Recognition for sterilised victims and the family members of euthanasia victims remains an issue in Germany. The Law for the Prevention of Genetically Diseased Offspring was not repealed until 2007. While the law was never used in Germany after the war, this was the first time that the Bundestag explicitly ruled that it held no power in the country and repealed it entirely. In the session, the law is recognized as Nazi in nature and a component of the racial laws. People with disabilities, both those who are physically and psychologically disabled, are explicitly named as victims for the first time. Ultimately, despite this recognition by individual parties who worked with BEZ, such as the Left and Green parties, people with disabilities are not added to the definition of who is declared a victim of Nazism.⁷²

This is not to suggest that no progress has been made at all. In addition to the various revisions made in the 1980s and 1990s that were discussed earlier in this article, the Bundestag has made amendments throughout the 2000s to the current day. In 2002, children of euthanasia victims were first given the opportunity to apply for a one-time hardship payment of €2.556,46. To file the claim, surviving children needed to provide documentation of their parent's murder, and to have not reached adulthood at the time of the murder. The amendment continued to receive backlash from the League of Persons Damaged by "Euthanasia" and Compulsory Sterilisation, because it was not given with the recognition that the recipients suffered Nazi persecution as the organisation had urged. Instead, the one-time payment was given on the basis that parents had an obligation to provide financial maintenance to their children and were unable to do so because they had been killed.⁷³ Under §844 of the German Social Code, the party responsible for the murder is obligated to pay maintenance to the surviving beneficiaries; this law was the one the German government used as justification to grant payment for the surviving children of euthanasia victims.

⁷² "Plenarprotokoll 16/100, Deutscher Bundestag, Stenografischer Bericht, 100. Sitzung" (Berlin: Deutscher Bundestag, May 24, 2007), 10285.

⁷³ Margret Hamm, ed., *Ausgegrenzt! warum? Zwangssterilisierte und Geschädigte der NS-"Euthanasie" in der Bundesrepublik Deutschland* (Berlin: Metropol, 2017), 177-80.

In 2011, the hardship clause was retroactively amended from January 27, 2011, in honour of Holocaust Remembrance Day to state that monthly payments may go out to survivors of the euthanasia program. This is a very small group of people, five or ten individuals at the most.⁷⁴ The amendment applies to those who spent at least eighteen months in a euthanasia centre and were still alive at liberation. Given the minimal number of people who meet these criteria, the BEZ mistakenly assumed further payments would also go out to children affected by the murder of their parent(s), but this was not the case. While the criteria for children to receive the one-time hardship payment (€2.556,46) were adjusted to include children who had not yet reached the age of 21 or those who were still students who had not yet reached the age of 27 at the time of their parent's death, applications for ongoing payments for children were denied.⁷⁵ Upon the rejection of applications from the children of euthanasia victims, received only after the applicants provided extensive financial documentation, BEZ released a second press release and sent additional letters to the Bundestag, calling the “symbolic move” a “political stain” and an insult to those who had lost their parents, insisting that the true way to honour the victims of euthanasia would be to compensate the loved ones they left behind.⁷⁶

In 2013, members of the Left and Green parties submitted a series of questions related to previous attempts that were made in relation to considering victims of forced sterilisation, euthanasia victims, and their descendants as victims of the Nazis. In the appeal, the group pointed out that the hardship clause under which survivors and family members were being compensated was intended for damages that were considered general, routine wartime injuries. As such, placing victims of forced sterilisation and euthanasia under this category denotes that their injuries are somewhat “routine” in war and are a possibility to be expected, rather than an act of hatred that was a direct result of Nazi racial legislation. Additionally, they questioned first why Nazi ‘experts’ were invited to make the decision in 1961 when the Compensation Law was still amendable, and

⁷⁴ Margret Hamm, “Pressemitteilung: AKG Härterichtlinienänderung für Euthanasie-Geschädigte: und wieder werden NS Opfer diskriminierend ausgegrenzt” (Arbeitsgemeinschaft Bund der „Euthanasie“-Geschädigten und Zwangssterilisierten, June 8, 2011), https://www.euthanasiegeschadigte-zwangssterilisierte.de/texte-pdf/pm-08-06-2011_web.pdf.

⁷⁵ “Neufassung der Richtlinien der Bundesregierung über Härteleistungen an Opfer von nationalsozialistischen Unrechtsmaßnahmen im Rahmen des Allgemeinen Kriegsfolgengesetzes (AKG-Härterichtlinien)” (Berlin: Deutscher Bundestag, 2011).

⁷⁶ Margret Hamm, “Brief der AG BEZ an die Fraktionsvorsitzenden von CDU/CSU, FDP, SPD, Bündnis 90/DIE GRÜNEN und DIE LINKE. im Deutschen Bundestag zur Umsetzung der AKG Härterichtlinienänderung.,” June 22, 2011, <https://www.euthanasiegeschadigte-zwangssterilisierte.de/dokumente/ag-bez-brief-fraktionsvorsitzende-22-06-11.pdf>; see also Hamm, “Pressemitteilung: AKG Härterichtlinienänderung für Euthanasie-Geschädigte: und wieder werden NS Opfer diskriminierend ausgegrenzt.”

why the government was unwilling to make a law comparable to the original for this victim group if BEG must remain closed.⁷⁷

The questions were answered, but not in a manner that changed the situation for survivors or surviving dependants. Rather than addressing the discrepancies between those with and without recognition through BEG, the government responded that the amount received by survivors under the hardship act was increased in 2011 and that it was impossible to amend the Compensation Act because claims had closed. In response to the possibility of creating new compensation schemes for these groups, the government saw no differences on the political level between receiving payment and recognition through BEG than through the hardship act. They explained that negotiations for reparations that went to other groups were done with international organisations. In particular agreements with the State of Israel was named, along with general regard to other “global agreements with various states, foundations, etc.”⁷⁸ The implication of this statement goes back to the fact that no international bodies in the post-war period were considered the sterilisation of people with disabilities a crime, and the League of Persons Damaged by “Euthanasia” and Compulsory Sterilisation was not established until 1987, eighteen years after the closing of claims under the Federal Compensation Act. Regarding the refusal to add victims of sterilisation and euthanasia to the list of victims in 1961, the response was simply that the Federal Government is prevented from re-evaluating measures taken by the Bundestag, and no political assessment of the experts involved exists.⁷⁹

Since 2013, there has been little development in the situation for victims of sterilisation and euthanasia. The most recent measure passed in 2021 allows for the spouses of surviving Nazi victims to apply for temporary compensation—up to nine months after the survivor’s death—if they were eligible for a pension under the Federal Compensation Act or the General Consequences of War Act, the law which is responsible for paying hardship compensation to victims of euthanasia or sterilisation.⁸⁰ Since this addition, all further changes have been increases to the payment amounts under the hardship clause of the General Consequences of War Act.

⁷⁷ “Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Abgeordneten Ulla Jelpke, Dr. Ilja Seifert, Jan Korte, weiterer Abgeordneter und der Fraktion Die Linke. Entschädigungsleistungen für „Euthanasie“-Geschädigte und Zwangssterilisierte” (Deutscher Bundestag, February 19, 2013), <https://dip.bundestag.de/vorgang/entsch%C3%A4digungsleistungen-f%C3%BCr-euthanasie-gesch%C3%A4digte-und-zwangssterilisierte-nachfrage-zur-antwort-der-bundesregierung/50699>.

⁷⁸ “Antwort der Bundesregierung auf die Kleine Anfrage der Abgeordneten Ulla Jelpke, Dr. Ilja Seifert, Jan Korte, weiterer Abgeordneter und der Fraktion Die Linke.”

⁷⁹ “Entschädigungsleistungen für „Euthanasie“-Geschädigte und Zwangssterilisierte,” 5–6.

⁸⁰ “Richtlinie der Bundesregierung über Übergangsleistungen an hinterbliebene Ehegatten von NS-Opfern” *Bundesamt für zentrale Dienste und offene Vermögensfragen* (BADV), March 31, 2021), <https://www.badv.bund.de/DE/OffeneVermögensfragen/UebergangsleistungenEhegattenNSOpfer/start.html>.

With the latest developments, it seems that victims of euthanasia and forced sterilisation will remain under the class of victims who have had ‘general’ injuries due to war, rather than receiving their full recognition as victims of Nazi plans to ‘cleanse’ the nation of the sick and disabled. As of 2023, their payments have been increased to 600 Euros per month, but the changes made throughout the years came much too late to have an impact for significant numbers of people. As of December 31, 2022, the League of Persons Damaged by “Euthanasia” and Compulsory Sterilisation reports that only 29 victims of forced sterilisation are alive and eligible, along with one survivor of the euthanasia policies.⁸¹ The League continues to host conferences and projects relating to the exclusion of people with disabilities from post-war justice, but the progress that has been made is far too late. The vast majority of victims died without receiving any recognition of their suffering, and for those who died before 2007, in a country that still considered the law responsible for their suffering a routine health precaution rather than discrimination.

To this day, no official apologies have been made by the German government for the crimes committed against people with disabilities or their surviving family members. The only organisation to apologise thus far has been the German Medical Association, whose members not only committed crimes and participated in human experimentation during the Nazi times, but also used body parts harvested from victims for scientific study until the 1990s, sometimes longer.⁸² The apology, issued in 2012, was too late to be received by the people who deserved it, but is a welcome starting point for the recognition of these victims. As organisations previously involved in Nazi crimes finally shift from positions of denial to remorse, an opportunity is left open for the German government itself to finally recognize further groups of victims who were previously left unacknowledged. Further, the current state of research makes it clear that there is a massive disparity between scholarship on post-war justice in West and East Germany that is waiting to be filled.

Lastly, as this article has pointed out, the responsibility of justice for victims of sterilisation lies not with Germany alone, but also with the multitude of nations who have failed to acknowledge their eugenic practices of the past and offer some apologies or reparations to the surviving victims.

⁸¹ Hamm, *Ausgegrenzt! warum?*, 177–180.

⁸² Stephan Kolb, Paul Weindling, Volker Roelcke, and Horst Seithe, “Apologising for Nazi Medicine: A Constructive Starting Point,” *Lancet* 380, no. 9843 (August 25, 2012): 722–23.

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Engaging across the “Iron Curtain”: Transnational Student Exchanges between Czechoslovakia and the United Kingdom, 1948–1970⁸³

KLÁRA ŘIHÁKOVÁ

Master Student, University of Edinburgh

Abstract

This article examines transnational elements of university student exchanges across the “Iron Curtain,” more precisely between the United Kingdom and the Czechoslovak Socialist Republic. Drawing on a range of contemporary newspapers, like the mainstream The Guardian and The New York Times, alongside governmental documents from British and Czech archives as well as Czechoslovak student magazines such as Impuls and Student, the article examines the interaction opportunities between Czechoslovak and British students that were enabled through The British-Czechoslovak Cultural Exchange between 1948 and the 1970s. This article proves that student networks did not appear unexpectedly in the 1960s. It argues that Czechoslovak students were part of a wider, transnationally dynamic student network before 1968, thus challenging the notion of the impenetrability of the “Iron Curtain.” Moreover, the article not only considers the political events of the Prague Spring, but also draws attention to students who studied or found exile in Britain during the years both before and after 1968. In doing so, it highlights the response of the British student body to the Warsaw Pact invasion of Czechoslovakia in August 1968, which resulted in the launch of the Czechoslovak Students’ Scholarship Fund.

Keywords: Student Networks – Transnational History – Czechoslovak-British Relations – The 1960s – Czechoslovak Students' Scholarship Fund

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Introduction

The term “Iron Curtain” tempts us to believe that any movement across the borders of Western and Soviet blocs was impossible. However, historical research, especially on student activism, has been proposing otherwise for at least two decades.⁸⁴ For instance, Gildea, Mark and Warring point out that “the true 1968 was seen essentially as a Western phenomenon,” and they aim to transcend this notion by highlighting “the penetrability of the Iron Curtain in this period.”⁸⁵ This article aims to contribute to this literature by focusing on exchanges of university students between the Czechoslovak Socialist Republic and the United Kingdom. It suggests that the research on “student activism” can be vital for better understanding the present and future student unrest, as Caroline Hoefflerle maintains.⁸⁶ Centring the research around transnational student movements, such as that from Czechoslovakia, can equally contribute to this historical debate. By revealing possibilities for interactions across the borders of the Cold War, this paper further demonstrates that the notion of an impenetrable “Iron Curtain” is flawed and outdated.

The historiographical debate concerning worldwide student activism of 1968 had already begun in the 1970s not only by acknowledging the role of mass media and international meetings in accelerating the spread of student activism, but also by denying the existence of “real international student ‘movement’” as such.⁸⁷ Concerning protests that emerged in great numbers throughout the world and their connection to the rise of Détente, Jeremi Suri argues that the focus on the 1960s “reveals how ideas, institutions, and personalities transcended national boundaries.”⁸⁸ Suri’s argument thus gives this project the necessary impulse. It is due to boundary-outreaching institutions and individuals, that it is possible to learn about the British-Czechoslovak state-issued scholarship exchanges and students stranded in the United Kingdom after August 1968.

The historiography of the British student body and its activism in the 1960s argues “that the British student movement both responded and contributed to [...] international dissent movements in the era of the Long Sixties.”⁸⁹ Therefore, this article seeks to support this argument

⁸⁴ See for example Robert Gildea, James Mark, and Anette Warring, eds., *Europe’s 1968: Voices of Revolt* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013); Ronald Fraser, ed., *1968: A Student Generation in Revolt* (New York: Pantheon Books, 1988); Gerd-Rainer Horn and Padraic Kenney eds., *Transnational Moments of Change: Europe 1945, 1968, 1989* (Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2004); Richard I. Jobs and David M. Pomfret, *Transnational Histories of Youth in the Twentieth Century* (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2015); Richard Ivan Jobs, *Backpack Ambassadors: How Youth Travel Integrated Europe* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2017).

⁸⁵ Gildea, Mark, and Warring, eds., *Europe’s 1968*, 3, 328.

⁸⁶ Caroline Hoefflerle, *British Student Activism in the Long Sixties* (New York: Routledge, 2013), 2.

⁸⁷ Philip G. Altbach, “The International Student Movement,” *Journal of Contemporary History* 5, no. 1 (1970): 169, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/259987>.

⁸⁸ Jeremi Suri, *Power and Protest: Global Revolution and the Rise of Detente* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2005), 262.

⁸⁹ Hoefflerle, *British Student Activism in the Long Sixties*, 2.

by analysing responses of British students to the Czechoslovak experience of 1968.⁹⁰ It aims to do so by introducing the case of the Czechoslovak Students' Scholarship Fund.

As already proposed, this contribution takes a transnational approach to the histories of Czechoslovak students, and especially takes into account Pierre-Yves Saunier's approach to transnational history that "acknowledges and assesses foreign contributions to (...) domestic communities, politics and societies, and vice versa," and Gerd-Rainer Horn and Padraic Kenney's understanding of transnationalism "as the study of similarities, parallels, or connectors across national frontiers."⁹¹ It is, therefore, clear that the following discussion is not a comparative study, but rather an analysis of the Czechoslovak student movement's transnational dynamics with the United Kingdom and its student bodies.

Ludovic Tournès and Giles Scott-Smith's edited volume provides a great source for researching student exchanges, which, according to Tournès and Smith, "[have] not received the historical attention [they] deserve."⁹² Additionally, Rachel Applebaum's work captures the student exchanges between Czechoslovakia and the Soviet Union.⁹³ Consequently, this article aims to, at least partially, fill in the research gap of student exchanges between Czechoslovakia and the West. Therefore, drawing on the above-mentioned secondary literature, this article aims to contribute to the field of transnational history and position the history of the Czechoslovak student movement on the transnational scene.

The Cold War period witnessed a rapid increase in international student organisations, such as the World Federation of Democratic Youth (WFDY), set up in London in 1945, the International Union of Students (IUS), of which Czechoslovak student unions were part, and its rival organisation International Student Conference (ISC). The Soviet Union controlled both the WFDY and the IUS, which was founded in Prague in 1946, whereas, the CIA sponsored the ISC, which was founded in 1950 in Stockholm by twenty-one national unions that broke away from the IUS.⁹⁴ All of these organisations influenced transnational connections between Czechoslovak and

⁹⁰ For further reading on other transnational connections of Czechoslovak students, see Simon Hall, *1956: The World in Revolt* (London: Faber & Faber, 2016); Tom Junes, *Student Politics in Communist Poland: Generations of Consent and Dissent* (Lanham: Lexington Books, 2015).

⁹¹ Pierre-Yves Saunier, *Transnational History* (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2013), 3; Kenney and Horn, "Introduction: Approaches to the Transnational," in *Transnational Moments of Change*, xi.

⁹² Ludovic Tournès and Giles Scott-Smith, "Introduction: A World of Exchanges," in *Global Exchanges: Scholarships and Transnational Circulations in the Modern World*, eds. Ludovic Tournès and Giles Scott-Smith (New York: Berghahn Books, 2017), 2.

⁹³ Rachel Applebaum, *Empire of Friends: Soviet Power and Socialist Internationalism in Cold War Czechoslovakia* (Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 2019).

⁹⁴ Joël Kotek, *Students and the Cold War* (New York: St. Martin's Press, 1996), xii.

British students, for instance through the *First World Youth Festival* in 1947, or conferences, where students debated about politics and discussed their universal experiences.⁹⁵

Drawing on a range of contemporary newspapers and government documents from British and Czech archives as well as student magazines, this article examines transnational elements of student activism in the Czechoslovak Socialist Republic during the events preceding the social and political upheavals of the Prague Spring and the following crisis of August 1968. The first part covers student engagement through the programme of The British-Czechoslovak Cultural Exchange between 1948 and the 1960s, in order to argue that student networks did not appear unexpectedly in the 1960s as well as to demonstrate the opportunities for student interaction on an international level and for development of transnational networks. It suggests that the “Iron Curtain” was not as impenetrable as it might have seemed. The second part examines student transnational structures and their impact during the 1960s and the notorious Prague Spring with an emphasis on the role of the British student body in aiding Czechoslovak students in Britain through the *Czechoslovak Students’ Scholarship Fund* (CSSF). In doing so, the article illustrates the international solidarity among students and how transnational networks became beneficial at the time of crisis. It is, thus, clear that the article’s scope is marked by crucial events in Czechoslovak history in the twentieth century. These are the communist takeover in 1948, after which the Czechoslovak Republic essentially became a satellite of the Soviet bloc, and the Warsaw Pact invasion in 1968. Both events are thoroughly discussed below since this project also points out the Cold War’s influence on Czechoslovak student activism. Nevertheless, due to the availability of primary sources, this article follows only university students, mostly from Prague universities.

Czechoslovakia and the Student Exchanges after the Second World War

“Prague is now known to be one of the chief centres for indoctrinating youth (...)” states a letter from the British Foreign Office to the British Council in September 1949.⁹⁶ This notion formed an attitude towards the British Council scholarships for Czechoslovak students only a year and a half after the communist takeover of power in Czechoslovakia. However, this was not always the case. In 1943, “an exchange of students between the United States and Slavic countries was in existence prior to this [second world] war and had an important cultural and political function.”⁹⁷

⁹⁵95 Altbach, “The International Student Movement,” 169.

⁹⁶ The National Archives, Kew (hereafter: TNA), BW 27/16, British Council Scholarships for Czech students: policy, “Extract from a letter from J. P. G. Finch Esq., Foreign Office to R. Seymour Esq., C. B. E., The British Council,” September 8, 1949.

⁹⁷ Josef Brožek, “European Slavs and Student Exchange with the United States,” *Bulletin of the American Association of University Professors* (1915–1955) 29, no. 3 (1943): 387, accessed July 4, 2023, doi:10.2307/40220450. Additionally, for personal testimony about studying in the United Kingdom during the 1920s see Sylva Šimsová, *Zasviť mi, ty slunko zlaté:*

The same can be observed in the United Kingdom as well. A scheme from 1935 to 1936 by the British Council allocated bursaries for students from eleven countries, including Czechoslovakia, who “had expressed a desire for ‘furthering the study of English.’”⁹⁸ Additionally, it was proposed that Czechoslovakia was deserving of “special attention” in distributing the bursaries due to the influence of the first Czechoslovak president, Tomáš Garrigue Masaryk.⁹⁹ Clearly, there has been a tradition to follow after the end of the Second World War. This student exchange “trend” was renewed in 1945–1946 as the British Council assigned nine scholarships (out of one hundred) to Czechoslovakia.¹⁰⁰ Apart from official student exchanges, there were other opportunities for interaction between the students of Czechoslovakia and Britain. They illustrate the connectedness of young adults in the period before the 1960s. Students had opportunities to meet their peers, for example, at the *First World Festival of Youth and Students*, which was organised by WFDY and IUS in Prague, just a year before the communist coup, in 1947. More than twenty thousand young people from abroad attended the festival, which enabled them to establish some international student contacts.¹⁰¹

Nonetheless, as already apparent such exchanges were to be terminated. In 1946, the Czech Communist Party (Komunistická strana Československa, KSČ) won the first national elections after the Second World War, and its leader, Klement Gottwald became the prime minister. This victory of the Communist Party paved the way for a gradual takeover of political power in the country.¹⁰² Although the KSČ initially assembled a government with democratic parties, communist politicians increased pressure on the democratic ones which resulted in the demission of twelve democratic ministers on 20 February 1948.¹⁰³ These politicians counted on the support of other ministers from the government as they needed to have at least thirteen resignations to declare new elections. However, no other ministers resigned, therefore, communists took advantage of the political situation when Gottwald went to negotiate with the president, Edvard

Ze vzpomínek Jarky Maiwaldové a Sylvy Šimsově na Domov (Prague: Municipal Library in Prague, 2022), 98–102. Young Czechoslovaks were able to study abroad due to scholarships, such as the Rockefeller scholarship, as the case of Karel Maiwald demonstrates.

⁹⁸ Alice Byrne, “A ‘Sound Investment’? British Cultural Diplomacy and Overseas Students: The British Council’s Students Committee, 1935–1939,” *Contemporary European History* 30, no. 2 (2021): 271, doi:10.1017/S0960777321000072.

⁹⁹ Byrne, “A ‘Sound Investment’?,” 271.

¹⁰⁰ Zora Damová, “Československé školství ve Velké Británii (1940–1945),” (MA thesis, Charles University, 2013), <https://dspace.cuni.cz/handle/20.500.11956/52690>, 116. See also Jan Kuklík and Jan Němeček, *Osvobozené Československo očima britské diplomacie: zprávy britské ambasády z Prahy v roce 1945*, ed. Marie Bernardová, (Prague: Karolinum, 2010), 319–320.

¹⁰¹ Kotek, *Students and the Cold War*, 117.

¹⁰² Laura Cashman, “Remembering 1948 and 1968: Reflections on Two Pivotal Years in Czech and Slovak History,” *Europe-Asia Studies* 60, no. 10 (2008): 1646, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/20451652>.

¹⁰³ Václav Veber, “Jak to bylo s demisemi v únoru 1948,” *Paměť a Dějiny* 1 (2009): 6, <https://www.ustrcr.cz/data/pdf/pamet-dejiny/pad0901/005-010.pdf>.

Beneš, about forming a new, fully communist government. Gottwald succeeded on 25 February and became president on 14 June 1948, thus cementing the communist influence in the country.¹⁰⁴

The seeming unity of the international youth, apparent at the *First World Festival*, did not have a long duration and was put under pressure when the state police attacked Czechoslovak students during their protests in February 1948. The beating also influenced the British National Union of Students of England, Scotland and Wales (NUS) which discussed its possible withdrawal from the IUS at a Council meeting held at Oxford in July 1948, attended also by Czechoslovak students to testify about the situation in their home country.¹⁰⁵ This demonstrates the transnational dynamics of the Czechoslovak student movement as well as student structures since Czechoslovak delegates had a chance to attend a meeting of another country's national student union. Nevertheless, testimonies of Czechoslovak students did not make much difference in the NUS since it decided not to withdraw from the IUS yet. The decision to leave the organisation came only in February 1951 after yet another series of troubles within the IUS, among which was the increasing involvement of the Soviet Union in the IUS, and the issue of the Korean War.¹⁰⁶

Naturally, the transformation of the Czechoslovak political scene had an impact on its domestic and international policy. The altered travel policy and visa issuance also affected young people, especially students who wished to study abroad. After the coup, the new state government aimed to restrain the movement of citizens to foreign countries, so it produced a new set of policies dealing with trips abroad, visa issuance, and the arrival of foreigners in 1949.¹⁰⁷ The KSČ intended to minimise travel in both directions to "the smallest possible measure."¹⁰⁸ Some international connections were disrupted as the state began deciding who would be let to travel abroad. This was also the case of the British Council scholarships issued for Czechoslovaks and vice versa. Another letter from the Foreign Office to the British Council offers a useful insight into troubles that were caused by the shift of Czechoslovakia into the Soviet zone of influence, such as the fear of Czechoslovak authorities indoctrinating British students: "The harm done by letting Britons be indoctrinated in Czechoslovakia is greater than the harm Czech indoctrinators can do to our people during visits here."¹⁰⁹ This document also demonstrates that student and academic exchanges

¹⁰⁴ Cashman, "Remembering 1948 and 1968," 1647.

¹⁰⁵ Kotek, *Students and the Cold War*, 137. As mentioned below, policies restricting travel abroad, visas, and foreign visits were introduced only in 1949, thus enabling travel abroad in 1948. See footnote 106.

¹⁰⁶ Kotek, *Students and the Cold War*, 181.

¹⁰⁷ The party wanted to minimize the emigration of valuable citizens abroad. Jan Rychlík, *Cestování do ciziny v habsburské monarchii a v Československu: pasová, vízová a vystěhovalcká politika, 1848-1989* (Prague: Ústav pro soudobé dějiny AV ČR, 2007), 35.

¹⁰⁸ Rychlík, *Cestování do ciziny v habsburské monarchii a v Československu*, 36.

¹⁰⁹ TNA, BW 27/16, "British Council Scholarships for Czech students: policy," J. P. G. Finch, Esq. to R. Seymour, Esq., September 13, 1949.

became the centre of a dispute between the two countries after the February coup, additionally because of the problem with student selection – the countries were unable to agree if either the country providing the students, or the one receiving them, should select the student for exchanges.¹¹⁰ This was again a result of suspicion on both sides. Therefore, the communist government's reluctance to allow people to leave the country on one hand, and the British officials' fear of indoctrination of British students on the other, simultaneously affected state-issued exchanges.

Therefore, the Cold War climate clearly influenced the lives of students since they also suffered the consequences of cooling political relations. Tournès and Scott-Smith argue that scholarships during the Cold War were “ultra-politicized.”¹¹¹ It is evident that the same can be proposed about state-issued scholarships between Czechoslovakia and the United Kingdom. Eventually, due to the hesitance of the Czechoslovak government to grant passports to students who were chosen for the exchange by the British Council, and non-compliance with the agreement made between the two countries, the cultural relationships had been treated as “dead for the time being” since 1 May 1950.¹¹² Interestingly, the inability of governments to agree on new terms of cultural and academic exchange in the then-contemporary political situation disrupted possible transnational relations that students could have built. Furthermore, in 1952, changes to the visa policy produced a burst of bureaucracy requiring citizens to fill in numerous forms with reasonable explanations for their travels.¹¹³ Consequently, the difficulty surrounding travelling abroad became one of the complaints of the Czechoslovak student movement in 1956.

Change in Visa Policy and Travel: Renewal of Exchanges

The atmosphere of the 1950s was filled with fear as KSČ organised judicial show trials.¹¹⁴ The second half of the 1950s saw a slight relaxation after the death of the General Secretary of the Communist Party, Joseph Stalin in 1953. In the same year, President Gottwald's death as well as the Twentieth Congress of the Communist Party of the USSR in 1956 further affected the situation in Czechoslovakia. Despite the succession of anti-reform presidents, Antonín Zápotocký in 1953 and Antonín Novotný in 1957, Czechoslovak students became active in the production of so-

¹¹⁰ TNA, BW 27/16, “Anglo-Czechoslovak Cultural Relations: Scholarships,” R. A. Close, October 11, 1949.

¹¹¹ Tournès and Scott-Smith, “Introduction,” in *Global Exchanges*, eds. Tournès and Scott-Smith, 15.

¹¹² TNA, BW 27/16, “British Council Scholarships for Czech students: policy,” Confidential letter on British Council Scholarships from T. H. Sears to the Representative of the British Council in Prague, 1 May 1950. However, exchanges with the Soviet Union continued, see Rachel Applebaum, “The Land of Our Destiny,” in *Empire of Friends*, 50–80.

¹¹³ Rychlík, *Cestování do ciziny v habsburské monarchii a v Československu*, 40.

¹¹⁴ Pavlína Formánková, “Vypořádali jsme se s Horákovou, vypořádáme se i s americkým broukem!,” *Paměť a dějiny* 1 (2007): 20–41, <https://www.ustrcr.cz/data/pdf/pamet-dejiny/0701-20-41.pdf>.

called resolutions in the early spring of 1956.¹¹⁵ Students of the Faculty of Mathematics and Physics at Charles University in Prague were among the first to produce a resolution. The text not only called for improvements in the “system of electing candidates to the National Committee and National Assembly,” thus pointing out political reforms, but they also asked for the transformation of student life:

“We ask that travel to foreign countries be made possible other than through the Czechoslovak State Travel Agency. We urge special emphasis on exchange agreements, particularly those involving students, with minimalisation of foreign currency difficulties ... We also consider it necessary that procedures for obtaining permission to travel abroad (which at present require filling out fourteen forms) be significantly simplified.”¹¹⁶

This indicates that students were well aware of difficulties relating to studying abroad and wanted to gain new experiences and establish new connections in foreign countries. Consequently, the government considered the content of this and similar resolutions as “anti-state” and resisted the distribution of the texts through secret uncovering of the individuals who distributed resolutions resulting in “criminal liability and prophylactic measures.”¹¹⁷

It took three more years until the next communist government allowed changes to visa and travel policy. As Jan Rychlík points out, the initial alterations from 1956 were concerned with travel to “the Soviet Union and people’s democracies (...) and visits to the West were organised rather exceptionally.”¹¹⁸ He nonetheless confirms these tours were indeed taking place, although to a lesser extent than trips to the East. Moreover, the KSČ was especially concerned with sending the “right,” meaning verified, people to capitalist countries.¹¹⁹ This demonstrates that the Foreign Office’s anxieties about the indoctrination, discussed above, ahead of suspending the Programme of Cultural Exchanges with Czechoslovakia, were justified.

With a transformation of visa and travel policy, Czechoslovakia opened to travellers from all around the world. According to a report from 1958, there was an increase of “14.200 applications for travel documents” compared to 1957.¹²⁰ Although the mobility of young

¹¹⁵ Interestingly, in 1956, students also played a vital role in “drawing up a list of demands (...) which would become the manifesto of the Hungarian revolution”; See Hall, *1956: The World in Revolt*, 295. Additionally, Tom Junes argued that “the parallels between Polish, Czech, Slovak, and Hungarian student activism in 1956 suggest they bore some transnational generational characteristics”; see Junes, *Student Politics in Communist Poland* (Lanham: Lexington Books, 2015), 53–4.

¹¹⁶ “Resolution adopted by the School Organization of the Czechoslovak Youth Union, School of Mathematics and Physics,” Charles University, Prague, April 26, 1956, trans. by Professor Charles E. Townsend, Princeton University reproduced in *Majáles 1956: The Abortive Student Revolt in Czechoslovakia in 1956*, ed. John P. C. Matthews, (Brno: Prius, 2000), 39–45.

¹¹⁷ Archiv bezpečnostních složek, Prague (hereafter: ABS), A 6/3 i.j. 993, “Tajný rozkaz MV č. 51/1956: Rozpracování nepřátelských elementů z řad studentů – zajištění,” June 1956.

¹¹⁸ Rychlík, *Cestování do ciziny v habsburské monarchii a v Československu*, 55–57.

¹¹⁹ Rychlík, *Cestování do ciziny v habsburské monarchii a v Československu*, 57.

¹²⁰ Rychlík, *Cestování do ciziny v habsburské monarchii a v Československu*, 59.

people was a distinct feature of 1968, there is evidence of student travel from previous years as well. For example, representatives of Czechoslovakia attended the Tenth International Student Travel Conference in Edinburgh held in 1959.¹²¹ Additionally, Richard Ivan Jobs suggests that this “transnational mobility” aided in “invigorat[ing] local movements.”¹²²

Moreover, the above-mentioned exchange programmes for university students played an important role as well. These were mostly conducted through University Interchange Schemes, which were, in the case of the United Kingdom, a part of the Programme of Cultural Exchanges between Czechoslovakia and the United Kingdom. As is apparent from the previous section of this article, this programme was temporarily terminated in 1950. However, Czechoslovakia initiated talks about renewing this scheme in 1958, firstly in terms of university scholars.¹²³ The committee for the University Interchange Scheme saw such interaction as beneficial for establishing contacts between universities.¹²⁴ The Czechoslovak students, on the other hand, based their claims for less strict travel to the Western universities on reservations about “mechanically adopting the Soviet experience,” suggesting they wanted to gain experience also from other countries.¹²⁵ It could be therefore argued that the easing of the Cold War climate on both sides of the “Iron Curtain” and the developing political situation in Czechoslovakia influenced the change of travel policy, which greatly impacted opportunities for international student travel and consequently interactions.

Student exchanges: Scholarships and Summer Camps

The proposal for exchange between Czechoslovak and British universities was first discussed in terms of academic interchange and the Universities Advisory Committee of the British Council welcomed it.¹²⁶ However, it is not precisely clear when this scheme reopened as the correspondence between the British Embassy in Prague, which hosted members of the Czechoslovak Ministry of Education and Culture, and the British Foreign Office, spans until 1960. Nonetheless, it is safe to assume that an agreement was reached during the early 1960s since a letter from the Foreign Office, dated 15 January 1964, mentions arrangements for the same programme

¹²¹ “Student Travel: Conference Opens to Communists,” *The Guardian*, October 28, 1959, 3, <https://www.proquest.com/hnpguardianobserver/docview/184600490/citation/65CE396BF4704D1FPO/12>.

¹²² Richard Ivan Jobs, “Youth Movements: Travel, Protest, and Europe in 1968,” *The American Historical Review* 114, no. 2 (2009): 384, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/30223784>.

¹²³ TNA, BW 27/22, “University Interchange Scheme (1958–1968),” P. H. Moberly to Mr White, August 5, 1958.

¹²⁴ TNA, BW 27/22, “University Interchange Scheme (1958–1968),” Letter from S. W. White (Director, Universities and Adult Education Department) to Mr Moberly (British Embassy, Prague), October 31, 1958.

¹²⁵ “Resolution adopted by the School Organization of the Czechoslovak Youth Union, School of Mathematics and Physics,” Charles University, Prague, April 26, 1956, trans. by Professor Charles E. Townsend, Princeton University reproduced in *Majáles 1956*, ed. John P. C. Matthews, 39–45.

¹²⁶ TNA, BW 27/22, “University Interchange Scheme (1958–1968),” a letter from H. Harvey Wood, October 28, 1958.

from 1963/64.¹²⁷ Therefore, these materials indicate that “the impossibility of travelling to Western universities,” which for example Kristina Andělová identifies as one of the frequent complaints in numerous Czechoslovak student magazines, was not as great as emphasised in academic literature.¹²⁸ Moreover, the notion of the impassable “Iron Curtain” must be challenged here, as James Mark and Robert Gildea have done previously, when they argued that the “Iron Curtain” was permeable.¹²⁹

From 1963/64, exchanges operated on an annual basis as each year talks between representatives of Czechoslovakia discussed the issue with the United Kingdom. Section IV of an aide-mémoire produced on 26 February 1964 mentions that: “(...) both sides agree to facilitate exchanges of visits between groups of students and young people in which the visitors will be given opportunities to meet students and young people in the receiving country and to acquaint themselves with their work, studies, and social life.”¹³⁰ This section was added on the initiative of British representatives, despite their awareness of the Czechoslovak Youth Union (*Československý svaz mládeže*, ČSM) being under the direct influence of the KSČ.¹³¹ This demonstrates that although the suspicions resulting from the Cold War climate persisted, they no longer influenced the young people and students’ lives as the two parties continued a discussion about “the exact position of the CSM vis á vis the NUS.”¹³² It is significant that the governments of both countries consciously intended for students to interact since they must have known that this would lead to an exchange of ideas, such as that about political development, between the young people. Overall, it is apparent that the British side intended for student interaction in hopes of influencing them.

Furthermore, apart from student exchanges during the regular academic year, young people had also a chance to encounter their counterparts from across the “Iron Curtain” during summer camps. While it was argued that “Western communist youth engaged with their Eastern bloc comrades at summer camps on the other side of the Iron Curtain,” this interaction also functioned the other way around.¹³³ This can be observed from a correspondence relating to the Anglo-Czechoslovak Cultural Agreement from 1966–68, which states that nine places at summer

¹²⁷ TNA, BW 27/28, “UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1964–1965,” R. L. Speaight to C. C. Parrot, January 15, 1964.

¹²⁸ Kristina Andělová, “Czechoslovak Generational Experience of 1968: The Intellectual History Perspective,” *East European Politics and Societies* 33, no. 4 (2019): 892, [doi:10.1177/0888325419864418](https://doi.org/10.1177/0888325419864418).

¹²⁹ James Mark and Robert Gildea, “Conclusion: Europe’s 1968,” in *Europe’s 1968: Voices of Revolt* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2013), eds. Robert Gildea, James Mark, Anette Warring, 328.

¹³⁰ TNA, “BW 27/28, UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1964–1965,” Aide-mémoire, Section IV, February 26, 1964.

¹³¹ TNA, “BW 27/28, UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1964–1965,” a letter from R. L. Speaight to C. C. Parrot, February 27, 1964.

¹³² TNA, “BW 27/28, UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1964–1965,” Minutes of Talks, February 25–26, 1964.

¹³³ James Mark and Robert Gildea, “Conclusion: Europe’s 1968,” in *Europe’s 1968*, eds. Gildea, Mark, and Warring, 328.

camps were allocated to students from Czechoslovakia.¹³⁴ To give one example of the already mentioned summer camps, between 7 and 28 August 1966, ten students were received at the National Union of Students' Summer School Loughborough.¹³⁵

The British Council and the Ministry of Education and Culture agreed to operate a programme of cultural exchange similar to the ones from previous years between 1 April 1966 and 31 March 1968.¹³⁶ These university exchanges were promoted in student journals, such as *Impuls* (published by students from the University of Agriculture in Prague), which states that for 1968, "exchanges are planned with the University of Leeds and Scottish Agricultural College in Auchincruive."¹³⁷ Additionally, between the years 1966 and 1967, 80 young people participated in the student and youth exchanges with the "level of exchanges (...) slightly increased in comparison with the last year."¹³⁸ British institutions included in the programme at this time were, for example, the University of Leeds, the University of Strathclyde, Glasgow Veterinary College, Reading University and Birmingham University.

Therefore, students, and young people in general, had opportunities for interaction in the years preceding 1968. On these occasions, Czechoslovak and British students had opportunities to establish structures that became valuable after the August crisis in 1968, as is discussed below. These interactions mentioned so far, can be described in the words of Akira Irie and Pierre-Yves Saunier as "transnational processes of exchange" creating a distinct culture of the "Sixties" which translated itself into "social and cultural transformations."¹³⁹

It is thus evident that a discussion about the transformation of domestic policy in Czechoslovakia, namely the communist seizure of power in February 1948, is necessary to understand the conditions under which the Czechoslovak students were living. The global cooling of political relations between the Eastern and West blocs affected Czechoslovak students through the shift of Czechoslovakia behind the "Iron Curtain" which led to travel restrictions. Transnational structures of the Czechoslovak student movement, which might have found its roots already before the Second World War, or during the *First World Festival of Youth and Students*

¹³⁴ TNA, BW 27/30, "UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1966–1968," a letter from S. W. White, October 14, 1965.

¹³⁵ TNA, BW 27/30, "UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1966–1968," Anglo-Czechoslovak Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1965/66: Mid-year Report on the Progress of the Implementation of Exchanges, 12, September 30, 1965.

¹³⁶ TNA, BW 27/30, "UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1966–1968," a letter from S. G. West, March 29, 1966.

¹³⁷ "Zahraniční výbor," *Impuls* 4, no. 1 (November 1967): 24, accessed October 7, 2021, <https://www.libpro.cz/studentske-casopisy/>.

¹³⁸ TNA, BW 27/30, "UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1966–1968," Report on the Progress of the Implementation of Exchanges 1966/67, 13–14, June 1966.

¹³⁹ Akira Irie and Pierre-Yves Saunier, *The Palgrave Dictionary of Transnational History* (Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2009), 2.

in 1947, were disrupted. British-Czechoslovak student relations were utilised, for example, at the already mentioned NUS Conference in 1948, which some democratic Czechoslovak delegates attended.

Nevertheless, a major development of transnational connections between the student bodies of the two countries occurred during a period of relaxation of communist policy within Czechoslovakia in the late 1950s and early 1960s. The transforming policy of Czechoslovakia regarding travel and visas played a significant role in opportunities for students to interact with their peers from the United Kingdom. This transformation was accompanied by students' calls for the easing of travel restrictions, which is apparent from the 1956 student resolutions. As the Foreign Office documentation and British Council correspondence have demonstrated, there were several occasions during which students from both countries could have established useful networks. The summer camps and student exchanges were renewed practices since the early 1960s and offered students valuable insight into the experiences of their contemporaries. This suggests that the "Iron Curtain" was more prone to perforation than it seemed to be. Furthermore, the state's initiation of these connections suggests that the officials must have been aware of the different political influences that the chosen students were prone to encounter. However, it must be noted that the archival material did not mention any conditions under which the students from Czechoslovakia were allowed to travel abroad suggesting that only the students with early-Party affiliation were permitted to do so, since even the British Council anticipated that Czechoslovak university students either came from families with good Party record or were active in Party politics.¹⁴⁰ Nonetheless, transnational structures are evident from the discussion, thus, it can be argued that transnational elements of Czechoslovak student activism had developed during the 1960s and only reached their peak in 1968.

¹⁴⁰ TNA, BW 27/22, "University Interchange Scheme (1958–1968)," H. Harvey Wood's Telegram, October 28, 1958.

Transnational Dynamic of the Prague Spring

The Prague Spring

The term “Prague Spring” describes a period of implementation of liberal policies in politics, culture and economics unparalleled in Czechoslovakia before 1968.¹⁴¹ Although named “spring” the process of change can be most radically observed since January 1968, when Alexander Dubček replaced Antonín Novotný as the General Secretary of the KSČ. Additionally, Ludvík Svoboda succeeded Novotný as Czechoslovak president on 30 March 1968. These changes on the highest political level marked the beginning of the subsequent liberalisation. Reforms, which the so-called Action Programme of the KSČ from April 1968 articulated, “increased freedom of speech and the press, and introduced economic reforms to improve the quality and availability of consumer goods,” but still stressed the leading role of KSČ.¹⁴² Unsurprisingly, these policy changes caught the watchful eye of the Soviet Union, but also of the Western bloc. Students had their own perspectives on these reforms.

The Perspective of Czechoslovak and British Students

An important part of the development of the student movement in Czechoslovakia was the foundation of a new student union, namely the Union of University Students of Bohemia and Moravia (*Svaz vysokoškolského studenstva Čech a Moravy*, SVS). The SVS was established in late May 1968 in Olomouc, and it theoretically replaced the communist-overseen ČSM.¹⁴³ Additionally, student magazines, some of them in print since the mid-1960s, reveal information about student engagement in the social and political reformation of 1968. A journal called *Student*, for example, contained SVS’s appeal to the Czechoslovak government for improvement of democracy in the lives of the general public, but also demanded betterment of student experience, such as “allowing internships and stays abroad, regardless of the political system of the country visited.”¹⁴⁴ Thus, students acknowledged their part in wider society; however, they also saw an opportunity in the Prague Spring to benefit their own social group. In addition, as Galia Golan correctly suggests, students in 1968 served as a coercive and efficient body in society.¹⁴⁵

¹⁴¹ James R. Arnold, and Roberta Wiener, *Cold War: The Essential Reference Guide* (Santa Barbara: ABC-CLIO, 2012), 179.

¹⁴² Cashman, “Remembering 1948 and 1968,” 1648.

¹⁴³ Milan Otáhal, *Studenti a komunistická moc v českých zemích 1968–1989* (Prague: Dokořán, 2003), 19.

¹⁴⁴ “Voko Bere,” *Student* 4, no. 30 (24 June 1968), 2, accessed via Československé dokumentační středisko (hereafter: ČSDS), February 22, 2022, <http://www.cds.cz/cs/g6/5598-DS.html>.

¹⁴⁵ Galia Golan, “Youth and Politics in Czechoslovakia,” *Journal of Contemporary History* 5, no. 1 (1970): 15, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/259977>.

Nonetheless, the student experience of the Prague Spring had also its transnational dimension. Indeed, Czechoslovaks were experiencing unprecedented freedom of speech but also freedom of movement. The estimates state that “690.622 citizens travelled to the West” between 1968 and the spring of 1969.¹⁴⁶ However, the travel stream went also the other way around as Paul Hofmann noted in a 1968 article for the *New York Times*: “Young Czechoslovaks and young foreigners drink beer together in taverns, they go together to the movies and discuss them afterwards, they hold joint dances and folk song sessions.”¹⁴⁷ Nevertheless, not all the youth shared the same opinions. According to a British visitor, Nick Wright, who played a significant role in the Hornsey College of Art protest, Czechoslovak youth appeared to be idealising the West and when he returned from his travels, he “was firmly of the view that the Red Army needed to intervene.”¹⁴⁸

On the other side of the spectrum, Czechoslovak students often disagreed with their Western peers over the question of socialism, which many young activists in the West idealised.¹⁴⁹ Nonetheless, despite disputes, caused mainly by different life experiences, some activists held high promises of utilising these transnational connections. Richard Ivan Jobs reports the hopes of one activist who hoped that travel could enable Prague youth to access new experiences, ideas and interactions in the West and to incorporate itself into the Western “transnational movement for social change.”¹⁵⁰ Furthermore, the transnational interactions can also be demonstrated through the televised BBC debate panel for “Students in Revolt” which saw students from Belgium, Britain, Czechoslovakia, Italy, Japan, Spain, the United States, and Yugoslavia participating in a discussion about the student movement in a world-wide perspective.¹⁵¹ Interestingly, the Czechoslovak representative, Jan Kavan, who later emigrated to the United Kingdom and consequently benefited from the structures, observed a “gap between [student activists’] perceptions and aims” during the BBC programme, illustrating that the goals of each student leader in the debate differed based on the various “social systems.”¹⁵² Nevertheless, it is possible to argue that the Prague Spring

¹⁴⁶ James Mark, Anna von der Goltz, “Encounters,” in *Europe’s 1968*, eds. Gildea, Mark, and Warring, 134.

¹⁴⁷ Paul Hofmann, “For Those Under 30, Prague Seems the Right Place to Be This Summer,” *New York Times*, August 12, 1968, 13, <https://www.proquest.com/news/docview/118259636/abstract/C62E70946AC942C7PO/1>. Hofmann reports that the language barrier was not an issue since some degree of German, French and English was common in Prague.

¹⁴⁸ Mark and von der Goltz, “Encounters,” in *Europe’s 1968*, eds. Gildea, Mark, and Warring, 147. The Hornsey College of Art protest took the form of a sit-in on May 28, 1968. The students’ demands included the reform of higher education. Although this protest was eventually defeated, it inspired demonstrations at other art colleges. See Hoefflerle, *British Student Activism in the Long Sixties*, pp. 124–126.

¹⁴⁹ Paulina Bren, “1968 East and West: Visions of Political Change and Student Protest from across the Iron Curtain,” in *Transnational Moments of Change*, eds. Rainer Horn and Padraic Kenney (Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield, 2004), 132.

¹⁵⁰ Jobs, *Backpack Ambassadors*, 129.

¹⁵¹ Jobs, “Youth Movements,” 388. The roundtable was almost cancelled due to the fact that BBC acted without the government’s approval in inviting the student radicals to the UK.

¹⁵² Moreover, after the Velvet Revolution in 1989, Kavan became Czech Minister of Foreign Affairs (1998–2002) and represented the Czech Republic during its admission to NATO on 12 March 1999. Jan Kavan, “Czechoslovakia 1968: Revolt or Reform? 1968 - A Year of Hope and Non-Understanding,” *Critique* 36, no. 2 (2008): 295, doi:10.1080/03017600802185415.

facilitated the increase in the development of social contacts between students of different nationalities with diverse opinions on political reforms.

Warsaw Pact Invasion and its Effect on Students

Although the reforms put in place during the Prague Spring seemed promising for the public, the atmosphere of liberalisation did not last long. The reform process in Czechoslovakia was marked as an “internal counter-revolution” by the Soviet Union and used as an excuse for an invasion by armies of the Warsaw Pact on the night of 20–21 August 1968.¹⁵³

Some students were located outside of Czechoslovakia at the time of the invasion. Due to the unprecedented travel increase to and from Czechoslovakia, as described above, many students found themselves in the situation of emigrating or being stranded in foreign countries, such as the United Kingdom. It is estimated that around 2.600 Czechoslovak students were in Britain in August 1968.¹⁵⁴ The United Kingdom officially condemned the invasion and accepted numerous refugees, according to Milada Polišenská.¹⁵⁵ Almost a year after the invasion, newspapers reported that Britain, among Austria and Sweden, “took about 2.000 refugees.”¹⁵⁶ The demonstration in support of Czechoslovakia, which erupted in front of the Soviet Embassy in London on 21 August, included for example Tariq Ali, a significant figure in the British student movement at the time, who took part in the above-mentioned BBC panel “Students in Revolt” alongside the Czechoslovak citizen Jan Kavan.¹⁵⁷ Moreover, already on 23 August, newspapers informed about a “liaison committee to establish scholarships at the British universities for Czechoslovak students” and the information desk set up by the NUS.¹⁵⁸ Young Czechoslovaks immediately used the NUS helpdesk as they wanted “to know whether they would be allowed to take places in British universities,” similarly to Hungarian student escapees in 1956.¹⁵⁹ Furthermore, the NUS played

¹⁵³ Cashman, “Remembering 1948 and 1968,” 1648-49.

¹⁵⁴ Modern Records Centre, Warwick University (hereafter: MRC), “MSS.280/29/1, Czechoslovak Student Fund,” Memorandum on Czechoslovak Students in Great Britain, 4 November 1968.

¹⁵⁵ Milada Polišenská, “Postoj britského Foreign Office k československému exilovému hnutí,” in *Studie z dějin emigrace*, eds. Jana Burešová and Jana Pelikánová. (Olomouc: Univerzita Palackého v Olomouci, 2010), 10.

¹⁵⁶ Adolf Hermann, “Regretted in Prague but Welcomed Elsewhere”, *Financial Times*, June 11, 1969, <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/HS2304805045/GDCS?sid=bookmark-GDCS&id=9cef2307>.

¹⁵⁷ “Arrests in London Protest,” *The Times*, 22 August 1968,

<https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/CS17788694/TTDA?sid=bookmark-TTDA&id=0040b769>. Ali recalls that ‘five thousand demonstrators responded’ to the call for protest at the embassy. See Tariq Ali, *Street Fighting Years: An Autobiography of the Sixties* (London: Verso, 2005), 286.

¹⁵⁸ Dennis Barker, “Scholarship Scheme Afoot for Stranded Czechs,” *The Guardian*, August 23, 1968, <https://www.proquest.com/hnp-guardianobserver/docview/185281213/citation/65CE396BF4704D1FPO/14>.

¹⁵⁹ Pat Healy, “Students Want to Stay in Britain to Continue Courses,” *The Times*, August 24, 1968, <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/CS134573848/TTDA?sid=bookmark-TTDA&id=313d1bf2>.

also a crucial role in informing British authorities about students who wished to remain in the United Kingdom.¹⁶⁰

Additionally, the NUS alongside the Scottish Union of Students, the Welsh Union of Students, the British Youth Council, and the United Nations Student Association were at the birth of the *Czechoslovak Student's Scholarship Fund* (CSSF) which helped stranded students to complete their studies in the United Kingdom. Lord Murray of Newhaven launched the CSSF on 23 October 1968, and in its first year, it assisted almost 300 students while collecting over £100,000.¹⁶¹ Christopher Seton-Watson became The Chairman of the CSSF and World University Service administered the Fund.¹⁶² Interestingly, as Michael G. Thickett mentions in one of his letters on behalf of Ivan Hartel, a Czechoslovak student activist who “played a significant role in the student movement to democratic Czechoslovakia,” the NUS became involved in the CSSF “primarily because of people with records like his.”¹⁶³ Arguably, the fact that Czechoslovak student activists aimed their agenda on democratisation played a vital role in NUS’s decision. Additionally, the case of the already-mentioned Jan Kavan illustrates that those transnational structures became extremely beneficial after the August crisis. As mentioned above, Kavan took part in the BBC panel “Students in Revolt,” establishing networks that might have played a role while applying for grants from CSSF.¹⁶⁴ Moreover, not only the NUS was involved in helping Czechoslovak students abroad, but also kept in touch with the Czechoslovak SVS until its dissolution in the summer of 1969, as demonstrated by correspondence between presidents of the respective unions.¹⁶⁵ This shows that although the Czechoslovak and British student unions were not part of the same international bodies (ISC, IUS), they maintained transnational contacts, further illustrating the permissiveness of national boundaries and the “Iron Curtain.” The CSSF closed its application

¹⁶⁰ TNA, BW 27/31, “USSR Occupation of Czechoslovakia: Effect on British Council Activities,” September 12, 1968.

¹⁶¹ MRC, MSS.280/29/1, “Czechoslovak Student Fund,” Czechoslovak Students Who Choose Freedom in Britain, January 24, 1969. To compare, in the first year of the Soviet invasion of Hungary, British universities accepted around 150 Hungarian students and advertised the *Hungarian Student's Scholarship Fund*. See From Our Special Correspondent, “Students From Hungary,” *The Times*, January 2, 1957, <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/CS152786978/GDCS?sid=bookmark-GDCS&xid=d6b71e0a>; Ann Kneif, “After the Uprising of 1956: Hungarian Students in Britain,” *The Historian* 92 (Winter 2006): 26; Lindsay D. Keir, John F. Lockwood, and Stephen Spender., “Hungary,” *The Times*, November 16, 1956, <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/CS185816944/GDCS?sid=bookmark-GDCS&xid=7a90c0d3>.

¹⁶² MRC, MSS.280/29/1, “Czechoslovak Student Fund,” Letter dated 21 January 1969. Christopher Seton-Watson (1918–2007) was a historian of Italy, the son of a historian of Eastern and Southern Europe, Robert William Seton-Watson (1879–1951), who co-established the School of Slavonic and East European Studies at the University College London in 1915. See, for example, R. B. Betts, “Robert William Seton-Watson, 1879–1951,” *The Slavonic and East European Review* 30, no. 74 (1951): 252–55, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/4204301>; John Pollard, “Christopher Seton-Watson,” *The Guardian*, December 4, 2007, <https://www.theguardian.com/news/2007/dec/04/guardianobituaries.internationaleducationnews>.

¹⁶³ MRC, MSS.280/29/1, “Czechoslovak Student Fund,” letter dated December 16, 1968.

¹⁶⁴ MRC, MSS.280/29/1, “Czechoslovak Student Fund,” letter from Michael Thickett, July 1969. It must be noted here that Jan Kavan has not yet responded to the author’s efforts to interview him on benefiting from the CSSF.

¹⁶⁵ MRC, MSS.280/29/1, “Czechoslovak Student Fund,” letter dated June 14, 1969.

process towards the end of 1970.¹⁶⁶ Barbara Day suggested that “after the flood of generosity (...) for students trapped in Britain (...) sponsorship for Czechoslovak efforts became scarce.”¹⁶⁷ Nevertheless, archival materials suggest otherwise, as the CSSF continued providing grants during three academic years (1968–1971), it distributed over £143.000 to 639 students in need.¹⁶⁸

Regarding student exchanges, the British Foreign Office did not plan to abandon agreements under the Anglo-Czechoslovak Programme due to the lack of “any obvious sign of Soviet supervision or interference.”¹⁶⁹ Nonetheless, slightly later, signs of doubt about the continuance of the scheme started to spring to the surface on the Czechoslovak side.¹⁷⁰ Surprisingly for the Foreign Office, the Czechoslovak Ministry of Foreign Affairs banned “all students and journalists” from entering the country on 30 September 1968.¹⁷¹ This also included students under the cultural agreement. However, subsequent negotiations indicate the resumption of exchanges in the following years.¹⁷² Although the exchanges were temporarily postponed, the Warsaw Pact occupation did not lead to any withdrawal from agreements between the two countries.

This part of the article discussed the transnational student networks of the Czechoslovak student movement to demonstrate their usefulness in times of crisis. The NUS records have illustrated that activism enabled students in both countries to make transnational structures. These ties then led to significant help from British students to their Czechoslovak peers who emigrated or were stranded in the UK due to the occupation. *Czechoslovak Student's Scholarship Fund* helped students to study and consequently build a life in the United Kingdom. Therefore, it can be concluded that transnational connections enabled some student activists to overcome the unfortunate political situation.¹⁷³

¹⁶⁶ MRC, MSS.280/29/1, “Czechoslovak Student Fund,” *Czechoslovak Student's Scholarship Fund*, Second Annual Report, 1969–1970.

¹⁶⁷ Barbara Day, “The Democratic Exile Movement from the Soviet Bloc Countries in GB: An English Perspective,” in *Studie z dějin emigrace*, eds. Jana Burešová and Jitka Pelikánová (Olomouc: Univerzita Palackého v Olomouci, 2010), 28.

¹⁶⁸ MRC, MSS.280/29/1, “Czechoslovak Student Fund,” Third Annual Report, 1970–71.

¹⁶⁹ TNA, BW 27/31, “USSR Occupation of Czechoslovakia: Effect on British Council Activities,” letters from September 4–6, 1968.

¹⁷⁰ TNA, BW 27/31, “USSR Occupation of Czechoslovakia: Effect on British Council Activities,” F. D. Hughes' letter, September 19, 1968.

¹⁷¹ TNA, BW 27/31, “USSR Occupation of Czechoslovakia: Effect on British Council Activities,” telegram no. 476, September 30, 1968.

¹⁷² TNA, BW 27/31, “UK-Czechoslovakia Programme of Cultural Exchanges 1970–1972: Negotiations, Brief,” December 1, 1968 – December 31, 1971.

¹⁷³ However, it needs to be mentioned that the Soviet invasion of Czechoslovakia did not cause the termination of cultural agreements between Czechoslovakia and the United Kingdom, as the talks about university exchanges continued for the year 1969. See TNA, *Ibid.*

Conclusion

The discussed period of student activism remains a fascinating phenomenon for research not only from a national perspective but also from a transnational one. The interactions between Czechoslovak and British students began well before the Second World War. After the communist coup in 1948, and the consequent shift of Czechoslovakia behind the “Iron Curtain,” these structures were disrupted with the sole exception of Czechoslovak students opposing the February coup, travelling to the NUS conference in the United Kingdom to plead for help.

Student exchanges within the agenda of scholarships and summer camps function as another expression of transnational structures in the Czechoslovak student movement. The Programme of British and Czechoslovak Cultural Exchange resumed in the early 1960s, providing students from both countries with opportunities for interaction and for experiencing their contemporaries’ lives. It has, therefore, been demonstrated that the “Iron Curtain” was permeable. Furthermore, transnational ties between the two student bodies had gained momentum long before 1968 when they achieved their height.

Finally, the focus on the Prague Spring reform process is tied to the response of British students to the August invasion. The structures, established through the years preceding the occupation, were crucial in the decision of British students to help their Czechoslovak counterparts in times of crisis, thus illustrating transnational dimensions. As some students emigrated or were stranded in the United Kingdom, their British peers aided them through solidarity campaigns and the *Czechoslovak Students’ Scholarship Fund*, which over three years of its existence distributed around £143.000 to over six hundred Czechoslovak students in need. Furthermore, the archival material suggests that NUS and SVS maintained transnational connections despite operating in rival international student organisations. Thus, once again the permeability of the “Iron Curtain” has been highlighted.

Overall, this paper has demonstrated that despite diverse political persuasions and life experiences, Czechoslovak students were part of a wider, transnationally dynamic, student movement. Therefore, the study of transnational student movements, such as that from Czechoslovakia, can provide further nuance to our understanding of the Cold War.

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Romanian New Wave Cinema as Commemorative Critique of Communist Memory

BEATRICE LEEMING

PhD Candidate, University of Cambridge

Abstract

The Romanian New Wave cinema (RNW) has been recognised as many things: a medium that addressed the inconsistencies in the way people felt about their historical trauma, a vernacular insertion nuancing declarations that Ceausescu was a “megalomaniacal dictator,” and a means to both attract and negotiate international interest in the country’s cultural output. But as well as these functions, RNW was a subversive critique of the “Western” memory of Romanian Communism. This article explores the self-conscious rejection implicit in RNW of the way that the Romanian past is packaged by Western, and Eastern, Europeans. Drawing on film theory, the tension between collective and individual memory, as well as the millennial impulse to debase “memory,” I argue that RNW was a self-conscious and creative effort at commemorating a past relevant for a democratic debate about the ways in which the past bears upon the present. As Russell Kilbourn suggests in relation to postmodern cinematography, RNW overcame the binary between individual and collective memory by showing cultural memories that were contemporarily relevant.

Keywords: Romanian New Wave – Memory – Transition – Europe – Cinema

Introduction

“I had a beautiful childhood during Ceaușescu’s regime.”¹⁷⁴ “Everyone had work ... the freezers were full.”¹⁷⁵ “People took care of each other.”¹⁷⁶ These vernacular memories from Romanian individuals are a curious confrontation for anyone anticipating a satellite microcosm of the “Evil Empire.”¹⁷⁷ But vernacular memories were inscribed into the films of Romanian New Wave cinema (RNW), a filmic movement that worked against and drew inspiration from an official memory-culture uneasy with satirical self-criticism. RNW – made in the first decade of the twenty-first century when Romania was seeking European and trans-Atlantic approval via the EU and NATO accession processes, as well as during domestic debate about the narrative of the communist past – was a critique and a qualification of what was Romanian memory.¹⁷⁸ These films were a self-conscious commentary on the relationship between then and now, and an expansion of what liminality meant for a country whose transition from communism to capitalism, from dictatorship to democracy, has been an extended experience.

RNW is an opportune lens for considering the availability of narrating history and the problem of authentic commemoration. The relationship between cinema and commemoration has received considerable attention amongst memory scholars since at least the 1970s, and visual images are understood as shaping and enabling a vision of collective memory.¹⁷⁹ Films thus perform a vital function in enabling collective access to a collective past. In Romania, this was important because a multifaceted debate on Communist memory remained lacking.¹⁸⁰ In the 1990s, the past was guarded by politics characterised by what memory-scholar Simona Mitroiu called “a lack of moral responsibility.”¹⁸¹ Only in 2012 did the Romanian parliament allow for the

¹⁷⁴ A Romanian with a portrait of Ceaușescu tattooed on his back, interviewed in Marina-Alina Asavei, “Nicolae Ceaușescu: between vernacular memory and nostalgia,” *Twentieth Century Communism* 11 (2016): 37.

¹⁷⁵ “Ceaușescu Auction Points to Lingering Nostalgia Among Romanians,” *France24*, January 31, 2018. <https://www.france24.com/en/20180131-ceausescu-auction-points-lingering-nostalgia-among-romanians>.

¹⁷⁶ “Many Eastern Europeans Feel Nostalgia for the Communist Era,” *The Economist*, October 12, 2017. <https://www.economist.com/europe/2017/10/12/many-eastern-europeans-feel-nostalgia-for-the-communist-era>.

¹⁷⁷ Harold Jackson, “From the Archive, 9 March 1983: Reagan calls Moscow an Evil Empire,” *The Guardian*, March 9, 2012. <https://www.theguardian.com/theguardian/2012/mar/09/archive-1983-reagan-russia-evil-empire>.

¹⁷⁸ The Romanian New Wave has been the subject of multi-disciplinary enquiry. Consensus is broadly that the movement is a barometer of social and cultural change. It has been explored as a site of remembrance, a record of the changing relationship of the artist in relation to politics, and a commentary on the relationship between history, identity and pride. Please refer to Onoriu Colacel, *The Romanian Cinema of Nationalism: Historical Films as Propaganda and Spectacle* (Jefferson: McFarland and Company, 2018); Michael Gott and Todd Herzog, *East, West and Centre: Reframing Post-1989 European Cinema* (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2016); Anca Pusca, “Re-Thinking (Post) Communism after The Aesthetic Turn: Art and Politics in The Romanian Context,” *Journal of International Studies* 45 (2017): 233–240.

¹⁷⁹ Films provide us with the means to remember, making memories seem real, as Augustine understood: “Memory is not present to itself ... but only by means of an image of itself.” G. R. Edgerton and P. C. Rollins, eds., *Television Histories: Shaping Collective Memory in the Media Age* (Lexington: University Press of Kentucky, 2004), 8–12.

¹⁸⁰ Lavinia Stan, *Transitional Justice in Post-Communist Romania: The Politics of Memory* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2013), 8–9, 18–21.

¹⁸¹ Simona Mitroiu, “Recuperative Memory in Romanian Post-Communist Society,” *Nationalities Papers* 44, no. 5 (2016): 754.

prosecution of individuals associated with communist crimes. RNW straddled the official condemnation of the crimes of communism in 2006, when President Basescu invoked twenty-one charges against the regime, but these performances of restorative justice were hardly likely to accommodate a democratic coming-to-terms with the past. This is because, in the demographic of those who wield power, ex-communists continued to dominate. RNW, made in this political climate, afforded a space for reflection, representing the past not as a fixed psychological or sociocultural concept, but as a dialogic compromise between memories.

If memory is an act of redemption of how we want the past to have been as much as how it feels in the present, as film scholar Thomas Elsaesser suggests, RNW rescued memories via an emotional aesthetic that constructed, as much as deconstructed, the “truth” of the past.¹⁸² Of course, as film scholar Russell Kilbourn recognised, “there is no way of gauging [the] objective accuracy or veracity vis-à-vis the “actual” past” in films.¹⁸³ Memory scholars broadly acknowledge “actual” past is attained in continuous dialogic compromise with the present, and the idea that Basescu could “settle” its memory is deconstructed by public intellectual Susan Sontag in her theory of collective memory as only a will “to value one thing over many others.”¹⁸⁴ Not only were these films confronting a past treated as “difficult,” but they were made in a socio-political context when access to the truth was politicised. Filmmakers of the late-twentieth and early twenty-first centuries were responding to a liberation in talking about Romania’s past, but uncertainty about the version of the past that would stand as the collective memory of “modern,” European Romania. They commemorated Communism as neither all good nor all bad, reflecting the postmodern moment they were made in, termed by Fredric Jameson as a “vacillation between performative celebration and lament for what has been lost.”¹⁸⁵ By putting Communism on screen, but Communism as worthy of celebration *and* lamentation, RNW was not an attempt to monopolise a collective memory. Rather, the films were sites of “resistance” against the very problem of collective consensus.¹⁸⁶ By reflecting on the narration of Romanian history, RNW thus reflected on the patterns of historical narration more broadly, calling for diversity and discursivity in what is remembered, and by whom.

This article will consider films that are concerned with the experience of “transition” (from communism to capitalism, or from anticipated revolutionary change to recognition of a failed one) symbolic of RNW, as well as the parallel positionality of Romania in and against Europe. Whilst

¹⁸² Kilbourn, *Cinema, Memory, Modernity*, 60–62.

¹⁸³ Kilbourn, *Cinema, Memory, Modernity*, 159.

¹⁸⁴ Kilbourn, *Cinema, Memory, Modernity*, 228.

¹⁸⁵ Cited in Kilbourn, *Cinema, Memory, Modernity*, 186.

¹⁸⁶ Gabriel Moshenska, “Working with Memory in the Archaeology of Modern Conflict,” *Cambridge Archaeological Journal* 1 (2010): 37–40.

RNW has received considerable scholarly attention, this paper seeks to locate the “European Question” at the heart of RNW, exploring films made during the negotiation of Romania’s entry into the European Union, that were simultaneously implicated in the debate about Europe’s future and its past. It begins by considering what Europe meant for RNW. These films were made in a moment of transnational concern about Europe and its peripheries. As historian Cristian Cercel implies, RNW challenged conceptualising Western Europe as the measure against which Eastern European identities are compared.¹⁸⁷ The second section focuses on the cinematic grammar of RNW, asking *how* films told the Romanian past. These films were provocative interventions, “cinematic international relations,” discussing the past in relation to the present.¹⁸⁸ These films did not prescribe a new canon but proposed a democratised expansion of commemoration. The final section considers the authorial ownership of commemorative history by examining the reception of RNW. It asks whose pasts these films should represent, and to whom. RNW legitimised individual experiences, calling for meaningful commemoration. As Kilbourn suggests in relation to postmodern cinematography, RNW overcame the binary between individual and collective memory by showing *cultural* memories that were contemporarily relevant.¹⁸⁹ To argue that RNW represented a subversive critique of the memory of Romanian Communism, this article challenges sociologist Manfred Steger’s theory of a Global Imaginary.¹⁹⁰ He suggests that as the forces of globalisation have disrupted local loyalties, there has been a growing consciousness of the world as a single whole. However, the philosopher Charles Taylor’s “social imaginary” insists that the memory of the collective is fundamental to its own conceptualisation. With this in mind, I will argue that the global imaginary is not global in its memory of history, but the product of Western norms and notions.¹⁹¹ This is clear in the way the international community imagines Romanian history and in its responses to RNW. Anca Pusca, the Romanian theorist, suggests that the “global imaginary” of Romanian history exaggerates 1989 as the “ultimate framing mechanism.”¹⁹² I am interested in how RNW challenged this imaginary, and argue that RNW sought to reframe 1989 as *the* reference point, calling for an expansion of what Romania had become in the early twenty-

¹⁸⁷ Cristian Cercel, *Romania and the Quest for European Identity: Philo-Germanism without Germans* (Milton Park: Routledge, 2020): 65.

¹⁸⁸ Anca Pusca, “Restaging the 1989 Revolution: The Romanian New Wave,” *Cambridge Review of International Affairs* 24 (2011): 574.

¹⁸⁹ Kilbourn, *Cinema, Memory, Modernity*, 204.

¹⁹⁰ Manfred B. Steger, *The Rise of the Global Imaginary: Political Ideologies from the French Revolution to the Global War on Terror* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2008).

¹⁹¹ Guido M. Vaheeswiick, “The Philosophical Genealogy of Taylor’s Social Imaginaries,” *Journal of the History of Ideas* 78 (2017): 474–476.

¹⁹² Pusca, “Restaging the 1989 Revolution,” 576.

first century. Whilst the global imaginary is *meant* to convey a single whole, RNW implied that the memory of the global imaginary excludes other memories of Communist Romania.

The Negotiation of Europe

There is something “irresistible” about Europe.¹⁹³ Whether promising “unending progress,”¹⁹⁴ or “soap, comfort and urbanity,”¹⁹⁵ the European essence has acquired an affective presence. Europe is not just an important idea to negotiate, but an *inescapable* idea to contend with.¹⁹⁶ Importantly, Europe is often imagined as *something* more than *somewhere*. Its territorial extent has been inconsistent, but somehow “ever and over-present,”¹⁹⁷ and for that reason, “Europe” is better understood as an idea, the supposed endpoint on the universal march to the equally evasive concept of Progress. Its pervasiveness is so powerful that it has become the global imaginary through which every other identity must negotiate.

But what *is* Europe? For the historian Ezequiel Adamovsky, it is a discursive formation for proving shared superiority.¹⁹⁸ For the cultural historian Ella Shohat, Europe represents “embedded narratives, buried premises, and submerged metaphors” that have cumulatively shaped a “common sense.”¹⁹⁹ RNW negotiated Europe-as-metaphor, as well as Europe as supplemented by a literary, legal, and political common culture. Europe, and its American big brother, had “colonised” the world’s institutions, including those that finance and broadcast films, such that its “sense of innate superiority” is assured by economic, political, and techno-cultural monopolies.²⁰⁰

The meaning of Europe, the ongoing debate about its conceptualisation and the contemporary concern about its territorial limits, served as the background against which RNW was being made.²⁰¹ Eastern European politicians used Europe as a symbolic aspiration, as rhetoric

¹⁹³ Roumen Daskalov and Diana Mishkova, *Entangled Histories of the Balkans – Volume Two – Transfers of Political Ideologies and Institutions* (Leiden: Brill, 2013), 2.

¹⁹⁴ Franz Liszt urged for Hungarian emulation, as quoted in Ivan Berend, *History Derailed: Central and Eastern Europe in the Long Nineteenth Century* (Berkeley: California University Press, 2003), 1.

¹⁹⁵ Eugen Filotti as quoted in Daskalov and Mishkova, *Entangled*, 45.

¹⁹⁶ Rodica Ieta, “The New Romanian Cinema: A Realism of Impressions,” *Film Criticism* 34 (2010): 27.

¹⁹⁷ Diana Mishkova, *We the People: Politics of National Peculiarity in Southeastern Europe* (Budapest: Central European University Press, 2008), 5.

¹⁹⁸ Ezequiel Adamovsky, as quoted in Cercel, *Romania and the Quest*, 8.

¹⁹⁹ Ella Shohat and Robert Stam, eds., *Unthinking Eurocentrism: Multiculturalism and the Media* (Milton Park: Routledge, 2017), 364.

²⁰⁰ Shohat and Stam, *Unthinking Eurocentrism*, 1.

²⁰¹ Maria Todorova suggests that the Balkan identity was the “by-product” of constructing the European identity. She insists that the Balkan “space” was made in the minds of Western Europeans during the Enlightenment, and the force with which they insisted saw “Balkanism” established as a space and feeling synonymous with an *alter-ego* for the modern principles distinctive in the West. In this way, the “space” of Eastern Europe as a repository matters because it explains and exposes the prejudices applied to the region, as well as the semi-conscious re-enforcement of a strong “Western” identity. Maria Todorova, ed., *Balkan Identities: Nation and Memory* (London: Hurst and Company, 2004); D. Beyrau and M. Keck-Szajbel, “Eastern Europe as a ‘Sub-Germanic Space: Scholarship on Eastern Europe under National Socialism,” *Kritika: Explorations in Russian and Eurasian History* 13 (2012): 691.

to inflict national shame, absorbing its essentialism as well as the unequal relationship unavoidable when engaging with its institutional form.²⁰² The role of the filmmaker was subtle, distance from formal diplomatic negotiations gave space for satirising both the European idea, as well as its negotiation by state representatives. According to Roumen Daskalov there has been a continuum of engagement in cultural spaces, between wholesale emulation and total cultural autarchy.²⁰³ RNW represented one artistic space querying the Romanian relationship with the West but followed similar cultural endeavours. The *Junimist* columnist Constantin Radulescu-Motru called political aping of European practices “forms without substance” in the interwar period, and suggested Romania should forge its own culture.²⁰⁴ At the same time, Radulescu-Motru’s lament that Europe was embraced ineffectively has artistic and political precedents. In the 1920s, the Romanian literary scholar Eugen Lovinescu advocated cultural synchronism, believing that modernity would come through “adapting and processing” Western models.²⁰⁵ These anxieties were rhetorically dialled up in the twenty-first century by those concerned with the corruption of Romanian sensibility and used as more justification for European tutelage.²⁰⁶ This included the narration of European memory.²⁰⁷ Numerous scholars have recognised that the “self-evidential triumph” of the “West” has a “taken-for-granted quality,” 1989 elaborated according to the “coloniser’s model of the world.”²⁰⁸ “Qualification” for the EU, synonymous in parlance and politics as “proper Europe,” is based on measurable Europeanness (read Western-ness). It is presumed ECE fails *unless* and *until* it demonstrates sufficient “Europeanness.” Leaving aside the argument of Polish-American historian Piotr Wandycz that the “exceptional European” traits of the West owe considerable historic debt to the “East,”²⁰⁹ geographer Merje Kuus considers the enlargement of the EU and NATO as judged according to a “gradation of Europeanness or Eastness.”²¹⁰ The physical location of ECE states matters little, but the concept of Eastness means they are competing in the same “perceptual space” that has plagued them time immemorial.²¹¹ Success is conditional. In part, it

²⁰² Jussi Sakari Jauhianen, “New Spatial Patterns and Territorial-Administrative Structures in the European Union: Reflections on Eastern Europe,” *European Planning Studies* 22 (2014): 697–698.

²⁰³ Daskalov and Mishkova, *Entangled Histories*, 96.

²⁰⁴ Diana Stanciu, “Forms without Substance or Synchronism? Attempts to Define Culture and Civilisation in Early Twentieth-Century Romania,” *European Review of History* 20 (2013): 45–47.

²⁰⁵ Stanciu, “Forms without Substance,” 56.

²⁰⁶ Interview in Robert D. Kaplan, “The Fulcrum of Europe: Romania longs for the West, and the West needs Romania more than it knows,” *Atlantic Monthly* (1998): 28–36.

²⁰⁷ Explored in David Lowenthal, *The Past is a Foreign Country* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2015).

²⁰⁸ Mats Braun, “EU Climate Norms in East-Central Europe,” *Journal of Common Market Studies* 52 (2014): 447; J. M. Blatt in Shohat and Stam, *Unthinking Eurocentrism*, 2.

²⁰⁹ The connection between Lord Byron and Greek nationalism, and British Gladstonian politics and the impetus of Bulgarian nationalism, are explored in P. S. Wandycz, “The Price of Freedom,” 5.

²¹⁰ M. Kuus, “Europe’s Eastern Expansion and the Reinscription of Otherness in East-Central Europe,” *Progress in Human Geography* 28 (2004): 476.

²¹¹ A. Schwell, “Negotiating the Imagined Geography of Europeanness in Polish State Bureaucracies,” *Anthropological Journal of European Cultures* 24, no. 2 (2015): 128.

is accepting the Western model of democratisation and market capitalism.²¹² It is also, for political scientist Maria Mälksoo, about subscribing to “the European account” of history that removes any moral guilt in the West. The Estonian President Lennart Meri summarised this well in the 1990s by remarking that although everyone was talking about the death of communism no one had seen its body.²¹³ Ultimately, it seems, to be “European” is to *no longer be Eastern*. The concept of “overstretch,” attributed to the British historian Paul Kennedy, was in the rhetoric of the Chairman of the EU Convention in 2002: including Turkey would destroy the very “idea” of Europe.²¹⁴ Europe was a space and identity whose limits would stretch to include (and exclude) an ECE of artificial acceptability.

RNW, at the turn of the century, could be understood as literary scholar Michael Rothberg’s “art of transition,” an aesthetic for working through transitional periods. Western Europe, the EU, and NATO were blended in these films just as they were being blended in the geopolitical discourse regarding Romanian positionality vis-à-vis the “West.” As Cercel argues, RNW challenged conceptualising Western Europe as the measure against which identities are compared, thereby “not showing how European Romania is but rather showing how Romanian Europe is.”²¹⁵ Given that RNW films were being made as accession negotiations were at their peak, they were live commentary on the Romanian relationship with Europe, including its genealogy.

The Western imaginary of Communism is challenged in Cătălin Mitulescu’s 2006 film, *The Way I Spent the End of the World*. Told from the perspectives of two children, Eva and Lalailu, the film follows their schooltime experience before 1989. After Eva and her boyfriend accidentally break a bust of Ceaușescu, they are sent to a reformatory school where Eva meets Andrei, the son of dissidents, and the two begin training for their escape Westward. Lalailu prepares revenge on Eva’s behalf by conspiring to kill Ceaușescu. The warm palette of outside spaces, however, juxtaposes these plans against sunny summers. This is a pre-revolutionary past, full of love, rather than the evil applied broad-brush to pre-1989 Romania. Nonetheless, the suffering endured under Communism is recognised: food insecurity is remembered when a slice of cheese is split three ways.²¹⁶ Film historian Mihaela Petrescu thinks, therefore, that this film reveals the implausibility

²¹² A. Stenning, “Out There and in Here: Studying Eastern Europe in the West,” *Area*, 37 (2005): 380.

²¹³ Maria Mälksoo, “The Memory Politics of Becoming European: The East European Subalterns and the Collective Memory of Europe,” *European Journal of International Relations* 15 (2009): 661–663.

²¹⁴ Sami Moisiso, “Redrawing the Map of Europe: Spatial Formation of the EU’s Eastern Dimension,” *Geography Compass* 1 (2007), 98.

²¹⁵ Cercel, *Romania and the Quest*, 65.

²¹⁶ *The Way I Spent the Rest of the World*, directed by Cătălin Mitulescu, produced by In-Ah Lee, Philippe Martin, Catalin Mitulescu, Daniel Mitulescu and David Thion (*Les Films Pelléas*, 2006), <https://mubi.com/en/gb/films/the-way-i-spent-the-end-of-the-world>.

of nostalgic commemorations of Communist Romania. Indeed, nostalgia *had* to be pictured in summer: in winter, the average temperature inside a Bucharest apartment was eight degrees.²¹⁷

But the film challenges the self-appointed importance of the West. Eva changes her mind in attempting to cross the Danube, despite overcoming the intense cold-water training against hypothermia, which is perhaps symbolic of the conditionality for European access. Eva makes it eventually, pictured on a cruise ship heading west. Her expressions are remorseful rather than happy, in contrast to earlier scenes. As the director explained, “I wanted very much to see a film about the Ceaușescu era...we lived in those times and have those memories. At one point the revolution came over us...and we got lost.”²¹⁸ Andrei might have made it to Italy, but this no longer gives Eva a sense of purpose. We watch her contemplate the sacrifices required of leaving and the sacrifices of domestically “transitioning,” receiving news that Alex died in the revolution. This film suggests that the *dream* of the West is better than the West turns out to be.

Leaving to make it, or staying to save it, was an important concern in contemporary Romania, heightened in accession discourse emphasising an East-West slope and making real the chance to experience the long-imagined West.²¹⁹ Between 2000 and 2015, 15% of the population left to go abroad, suggesting that the West remained “the land of abundance in the Romanian imagological consciousness.”²²⁰ Therefore, *The Way* looked to the past to communicate with the present. Eva sends back remittances, which hints at post-communist inflation and unemployment. Her coming-of-age coincided with Romania’s transition, but Eva does not transition to a promised land. She, like Romania in 2006, is lost, approaching the West according to the deadline of the Thessaloniki Summit, but not necessarily the better for it.

Eva’s tension between wanting to reap the benefits of the European “lifeworld,” and resistance to absorbing its account of the past is also clear in accession negotiations.²²¹ Amongst politicians, there was an explicit embrace of all things Western, premised on legitimating Romania’s synonymity via rhetoric pretending a temporal lag in development. In the words of one official, Romania needed tutelage to turn a “nation of weak, fuzzy institutions” into members of the “family” of civilised countries.²²² This included playing into a “domestic orientalism” surmountable

²¹⁷ “Remembering life in Romania under communist rule,” *The Economist*, September 1, 2015, <https://www.economist.com/prospero/2015/09/01/remembering-life-in-romania-under-communist-rule>.

²¹⁸ Pusca, “Restaging the 1989 Revolution,” 581.

²¹⁹ Cercel, *Romania and the Quest*, 11–14.

²²⁰ UN Report in Adriana Cordali Gradea, “The Rhetoric of leaving, or the mirage of the fetishized West in Cristian Mungiu’s *Occident*,” *Journal of European Studies* 48 (2018): 251.

²²¹ Alexandra Gheciu, “Security Institutions as Agents of Socialisation? NATO and the ‘New Europe,’” *International Organisation* 4 (2005): 979; Constantinescu, as quoted in Kaplan, “The Fulcrum of Europe,” 34.

²²² Civil servant Dorel Sandor, as quoted in Kaplan, “The Fulcrum of Europe,” 32.

by self-stereotyping “ostensibly at their own collective expense.”²²³ Getting into Europe required internalising its spatial moral language. However, Eva, and RNW, showed that hearts and minds did not automatically change in the process.

Image 1: Luci and Sorina discuss the advantages of staying or leaving in Cristian Mungiu’s 2002 film, *Occident*.

Cristian Mungiu’s *Occident* more explicitly challenged the problem of existential choice that envisions the West as the dreamland in a precarious post-communist landscape.²²⁴ The tragicomedy is concerned with the experience of young people moving to the West to overcome the difficulty of employment and financial success in Romania. *Occident* was made in 2002, before Romania’s successful bid for EU membership. Three episodes explore the binary position that if the “East” was home, then the “West” was the fix. In the first episode, Luci and Sorina wrestle with unemployment, and Sorina starts looking for a rich Westerner, an undefined symbolic gateway, “anywhere but this shitty place.” Luci continues his struggle in Romania, therefore only able to “*imagine* how it would be like to eat at McDonald’s every Saturday!”²²⁵ Figure One evidences

²²³ M. Buchowski’s concept, then M. Herzfeld, both as quoted in in Schwell, “Negotiating the Imagined Geography,” 143.

²²⁴ Rodica Ieta, “The New Romanian Cinema,” 26.

²²⁵ *Occident*, directed by Cristian Mungiu, produced by Dan Badea and Dan Bade (Temple Film, 2002), <https://mubi.com/en/gb/films/occident>.

the unlikely chance of finding a hamburger.²²⁶ Certainly, Communism is not remembered as the solution to present-day malaise: shots of socialist-era apartment blocks symbolise the struggle Romania has passed through. *Occident* queries the fetishization of the West as redemptive. Focusing on personal encounters with the East/West question, Mungiu reminds the audience that “the microcosm of the everyday individual is always in relationship with the larger social body” and the complexity of life is navigated at the individual as much as the ideological level.²²⁷ These characters are disappointed by New Europe and contemplate leaving because “their [own] lives seem futureless.”²²⁸ Luci’s brother Nica does leave, but remains absent, symbolic of the immaterial imaginary of the West. News of his death shatters the idea of the West as paradise, but the East is not much better. Luci only finds employment in a full-body beer bottle suit via nepotistic bribery. As he hums the Communist propagandistic song, “*Did you ever expect the year 2000 to look this way?*,” the hollowness of the West as redemptive is laid bare.

In the second episode, the West is represented as the land of opportunity via the Marriage Bride Agency, a match-making service for Eastern brides and Western grooms. For Mihaela, it is also the place where she might receive recognition for her poetry. A belief in the liberating modernity of Western culture encouraged an exodus in the late nineteenth century when creatives sought cultural education in Paris. She dreams of escape via the “French gateway,” like her parents in their attempt to find her a partner.²²⁹ Again, Romania’s present-day failings are interrogated as much as the perception of a Western solution. Playing into contemporary agonies, corruption is made evident in gifts to the agency, and the state is presented as pitifully weak via the dishevelled appearance of the police. This film captures the retrogression of the new world, which, still in 2020, frustrated one politician as “demotivated.” The police in *Occident*, like the Romanian bureaucracy, “don’t give a fuck about anything.”²³⁰

The historian Diana Georgescu offers an interesting reading of the symbolic coding in the gendered experiences in *Occident*, vis-à-vis Europe. She finds encrypted critique on the negotiation of the European “marriage” of background geopolitics. The Romanian male characters are presented as failing to live up to the role of romantic heroes, or to financially provide for their

²²⁶ Image taken from “Cristian Mungiu’s *Occident* (2002),” *East European Film Bulletin*, December 9, 2017, <https://eefb.org/retrospectives/cristian-mungius-occident-2002/>.

²²⁷ Angelina Ilieva and Esther Peters, “Interview with Lenuta Siukin on The Romanian New Wave,” *East from Chicago*, March 30, 2018, <https://lucian.uchicago.edu/blogs/eastfromchicago/2018/03/30/interview-with-lenuta-giukin-on-the-romanian-new-wave/>.

²²⁸ Julie Paulesc, “Between Eastern Roots and Western Wings: (Re)Mapping the Pursuit of Happiness in Cristian Mungiu’s Movie *Occident*,” *Economics, Management, and Financial Markets* 6 (2011): 236.

²²⁹ Adela Beiu, “The Nation and the Absurd: A Romanian Story of Modernity,” *Modernism/modernity* 21 (2014): 961–978.

²³⁰ “Why Balkan doctors head for western Europe,” *The Economist*, December 16, 2020, <https://www.economist.com/europe/2020/12/16/why-balkan-doctors-head-for-western-europe>

families. They symbolise a weak nation in contrast to the Western men, who arrive in shiny cars and as prospective, professional spouses.²³¹

Mihaela and her family anticipate marriage with the West, but they are shocked when the West arrives as a Mozambique-born Italian citizen. However, his ability to understand the family (thanks to the Latinity of the Roman language) reverses the framework dividing West and East into territorial and ideational certainties. His meeting with the dolled-up Romanian representative takes place over dinner in the family's house, redecorated to stress the origin of the Romanian nation within Europe with two portraits, one of the Dacian king, Decebalus, and the other of the Roman emperor, Trajan. For Georgescu, these portraits, in the context of EU accession, "are meant to strike a balance between the indigenous and the broader European components in national identifications."²³² The performance of the family is similarly framed in mainstream geopolitics about Romania "winning" its seat in the Western socio-cultural imaginary, welcoming "foreigners with an absurd mixture of imbecility and kindness."²³³ Marriage into male Europe is in dialogue with contemporary discourses, that Romania somehow fails its obligation to provide for its people the life they want without Western wedlock. *Occident* challenges these frames by offering neither happy marriages nor easy answers, engaging with Romanian-ness in relation to her European fiancée.

In *Occident* the West is not imagined as redemptive to domestic ills and nor is the Western imaginary. As the cultural theorist Adriana Cordali Gradea argues, the compilation into three unresolved stories that all revise 1989 as the harbinger of progress mirrors the splintering of rhetorical master-narratives behind labels like "pre" and "post" Communism. Communism, transition and democracy, concepts applied by EU diplomats to explain Romania's present and summarise Romania's past, are challenged in cinema undermining the ideological framing of binaries behind East and West.²³⁴

Ultimately, RNW mirrored its context in challenging the idea of Europe. At the political level, calls to remake the European memory were necessarily judicious. Eastern Europe had no shared past that could match the strength-in-consensus of the long maturation of the Western counterfactual.²³⁵ 1989 meant something local, the following decade something national, and the experience of socialism was remembered, according to the historian Claudia-Florentina Dobre

²³¹ Diana Georgescu, "Marrying into the European Family of Nations: National Disorder and Upset Gender Roles in Post-Communist Romanian Film", *Journal of Women's History* 23 (2011): 137-145.

²³² Georgescu, "Marrying into the European Family," 142.

²³³ Ieta, "The New Romanian Cinema," 28.

²³⁴ Adriana Cordali Gradea, "The Rhetoric of Leaving," 250.

²³⁵ Malgorzata Pakier and Joanna Wawrzyniak, eds., *Memory and Change in Europe: Eastern Perspectives* (New York: Berghahn Books, 2015).

explores, as “a scale from black to pink to grey.”²³⁶ To challenge the European discourse of the twentieth century was “awkward,” because it meant “reminding the West of their co-responsibility for the complexity of the region’s immediate past.”²³⁷ Strategic subversion was clear in the content of RNW. These films explored Western discourses on Communist memory and its prejudices in relation to life pre-1989. Ironic self-abasing was a foil for these bigger questions. As the historian Lucian Boia points out: “there is a long way to go before “Romanians will be able to regard Westerners with the same detachment (or indifference) with which the Westerners regard them.”²³⁸ Attempts to be counted as European, or to make Europe count, exposed the centrality of the European idea. However, the aesthetics of the films, the subject of the next section, exposed the fragility of the European idea, suggesting a self-awareness that the West meant more than its own self-definition.

Ambivalent Aesthetics

If Hollywood histories “puree” the past into “digestible bits of information,”²³⁹ RNW films are quasi-inedible. Its grammar, for film scholar Karl Schoonover, “turns boredom into a kind of special work,” in which “seeing becomes a form of labour.”²⁴⁰ Fast-paced narratives and easy answers were rejected. Filmmakers preferred the affective intimacy of slow cinema and associative minimalism, demanding an attentive spectator.²⁴¹ Communist memory was approached with post-modern non-judgement, the personal past the privileged subject. RNW reconstructed, empathetically, stories “to convey how historical people witnessed, understood, and lived their lives.”²⁴² Several filmmakers associated with RNW explained their practices as attempts to honour individual memories. Radu Muntean called for a restoration of authenticity, his film *The Paper Will be Blue* (2006) which was about the night of the revolution in Romania, was “made not to discover the truth about the revolution” but “to tell the story of [its] people.”²⁴³ Mitulescu wanted to “tell” the Ceaușescu era, but also “the [stories] of my childhood” and “the happiness and sadness that

²³⁶ Claudia-Florentina Dobre, “Uses and Misuses of Memory: Dealing with the Communist Past in Postcommunist Bulgaria and Romania,” in *Memory and Change*, edited by Pakier and Wawrzyniak, 300–310.

²³⁷ Mälksoo, “The Memory Politics of Becoming European,” 653–680.

²³⁸ Lucian Boia in Gott and Herzog, eds., *East, West and Centre*, 156.

²³⁹ Frank Sanello in Marnie Hugh-Warrington, *The History on Film Reader* (Milton Park: Routledge, 2009), 1.

²⁴⁰ In Anne Fuchs, *Precarious Times: Temporality and History in Modern German Culture* (Ithaca: Cornell University Press), 119–120.

²⁴¹ Raluca Jacon, “Romania: Transnational and National Tensions Beyond the New Wave,” in Lydia Papdimitriou and Ana Grgic, *Contemporary Balkan Cinema: Transnational Exchanges and Global Circuits* (Edinburgh: Edinburgh University Press, 2020), 173.

²⁴² R. J. Raack, “Historiography as Cinematography: A Prolegomenon to Film Work for Historians,” *Journal of Contemporary History* 18 (1983): 418.

²⁴³ Staff writer, “Reconstruirea Atmosferei Capitalei Din Decembrie 1989,” *Cinemagia* (2006).

came with them.”²⁴⁴ Corneliu Porumboiu was not seeking absolute truth in his film about the memory of the revolution, *12:08, East of Bucharest* (2006), but was interested in why 1989 still “percolates in people’s minds.”²⁴⁵ These films were not prescriptive histories, but mediums for *discursive* representation.

RNW filmmakers used the past to communicate with the present, which was an established idea in memory scholarship of Romanian history, especially at the turn of the century.²⁴⁶ The post-1989 project, which the German writer Peter Schneider believed was only ever about “dreams of European hegemony,” had failed.²⁴⁷ But rather than blame the past, RNW visualised a period let down by the so-called promised land. RNW mirrored nineteenth-century nostalgia, a longing for an irrecoverable moment, but was postmodern in its self-awareness about the absurdity of searching for the lost time of the Pitesti experiment.²⁴⁸ Hence, nostalgia was “ironised,” in the words of Linda Hutcheon, which remembers the past not to restore Friedrich Nietzsche’s monumental past, a “greatness that once existed,” but to critique its context.²⁴⁹ RNW addressed history but did so to disrupt the idea that history is prescribed in pursuit of a non-specific trans-Atlantic teleology.

Image 2: The family discuss how best to kill the pig without attracting unwelcome attention, in *The Legend of the Greedy Policeman*, the fourth episode in Mungiu’s 2009 collection, *Tales from the Golden Age*.

²⁴⁴ Pusca, “Restaging the 1989 Revolution,” 580.

²⁴⁵ Pusca, “Restaging the 1989 Revolution,” 579.

²⁴⁶ Andreas Huyssen, “Present Pasts: Media, Politics, Amnesia,” *Public Culture* 12 (2000): 21–38.

²⁴⁷ Peter Schneider, “The Other Europe,” *Salmagundi*, no. 166/167 (2010): 22–37.

²⁴⁸ The Pitesti Prison was the location of the notorious “re-education campaign” in which prisoners were subject to methods of torture.

²⁴⁹ Friedrich Nietzsche, *Untimely Meditations*, 2nd Edition (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1997): 69.

The collection of six shorts set in late communism, *Tales from the Golden Age* (2009), invites an expanded memory of the Communist period. Each one revolves around contemporary “legends” of the time, its title referencing the propagandised “Golden Age” and its content exposing the challenges of reality. The memory-scholar Eyal Zandberg suggests that commemorative discourse plays a distinctive role in performing cultural trauma and a vital one recuperating from it. Comedy insists on a rebellion against the given.²⁵⁰ *Tales* rebels with humour, conveying the depth of past tragedy and failure of the present by eliciting laughter as catharsis. Deliberately ironic and replete with invitations for inference, Communism is performed as a “Kafkaesque territory of inane party activists, inept yet feared policemen, intrepid small-time dealers, and harassed citizens.”²⁵¹ No episode condemns the past, but they commemorate it in carnivalesque good cheer. Implicit is the insistence that the Communist memory should accommodate the perspectives of harassed citizens too.²⁵²

In *The Legend of the Greedy Policeman*, familial cooperation juxtaposes with the candours of Communism, when a brother delivers a pig to his brother’s apartment. His family are only partly pleased: figure 2 shows the tension between gifts and gratitude in a society rife with jealousy over food availability, because of rationing enforced in the 1980s.²⁵³ The industrialisation of the 1970s following Ceaușescu’s pursuit of unabridged socialist modernity triggered mass urban migration. However, these populations remained dependent on the countryside to be fed, especially because Ceaușescu responded to increasing international debts by exporting all agricultural produce.²⁵⁴ The resulting intimacy of a semi-urban, semi-rural state is given tragicomic treatment via images of decaying apartment blocks, and the contrasting costumes of the policeman and his brother. However, comedy pervades the legend: to enjoy the gift of a pig involves gassing it to death. The absurdity of the system, when neither urban nor rural realities functioned properly, is embodied when the family blows up their apartment, having failed to empty the canister. This is a whimsical treatment of the Communist version of a Golden Age. It might have been full of greyness and gas, but it was also replete with gaiety.

²⁵⁰ Eyal Zandberg, “Ketchup in the Auschwitz of Tomatoes’: Humour and the Collective Memory of Traumatic Events,” *Communication, Culture and Critique* 8 (2015): 108–111.

²⁵¹ Monica Filimon, “Reviewed Work(s): *Tales from the Golden Age* by Cristian Mungiu, Oleg Mutu, Ioana Uricaru, Hanno Höfer, Razvan Marculescu and Constantin Popescu,” *Cineaste* 37 (2012): 54.

²⁵² *Tales from the Golden Age*, Dir. Hanno Höfer, Cristian Mungiu, Constantin Popescu, Ioana Uricaru and Răzvan Mărculescu, Produced by Cristian Mungiu, Pascal Caucheteux and Oleg Mutu (Mobra Films, 2009), <https://mubi.com/en/gb/films/tales-from-the-golden-age>.

²⁵³ Image taken from “Where There’s Pomp ... Cristian Mungiu on *Tales from the Golden Age*,” *British Film Institute*, April 29, 2014. <https://www2.bfi.org.uk/news/where-there-s-pomp-cristian-mungiu-tales-golden-age>.

²⁵⁴ “Remembering Life in Romania Under Communist Rule,” *The Economist*, September 1, 2015, <https://www.economist.com/prospero/2015/09/01/remembering-life-in-romania-under-communist-rule>

In *The Legend of the Party Photographer*, a desperate attempt to satisfy a state that cared more about presentation than performance is captured in hurried revisions of a newspaper to ensure a photograph of Ceaușescu next to the French president sees him with an equally authoritative hat. However, Ceaușescu ends up wearing *and* holding a hat, hinting at a disorganised state in disarray. Most screen time is given to long shots of the corridor, following middlemen as they trip shuffle between implicated offices. Unlike Western aesthetics that, according to film-scholar Mary Doane, deals with “duration” by condensing it to become “eminently meaningful,” these characters squander time in luckless confusion.²⁵⁵ A committed spectator is demanded by such authentic treatment of time, unfamiliar for those used to its capitalist commodification in entertainment.²⁵⁶ This episode offers nostalgic, well-intentioned cooperation, achieved in the multi-layering of scenes and the noisiness of the revision process. Taking overt manipulation of the “truth” as its subject, it implicitly queries the futility of searching for a single truth at all.

By combining multiple vignettes, folkloric in their celebration of Romanian camaraderie, *Tales* inscribed oral history onscreen. Non-linear scenes reject the hero-dominated narratives of Hollywood fare. Villagers, policemen, and interns all have stories worth remembering in realism-without-borders, the idea that everything is worthy of being the subject of a film. *Tales* is not confrontational, but it questions the pursuit of any single past, suggesting that polyphonic pasts deserve legitimation.

What deserves commemoration is similarly revised in *12:08, East of Bucharest*. Specifically, the movie questions whether the Romanian Revolution *was* a revolution, and whether Romania overcame Communism. In asking questions that periodically resurface in contemporary forums, the film scholar Dominique Nasta considers the film a comprehensive study of the post-communist psyche.²⁵⁷ Set in a Moldavian town, the film explores the feeling of change for people outside Bucharest via a TV call-in show, a pensioner, a journalist and a teacher standing in for all those left out of the “Issue of the Day.”²⁵⁸ *12:08* is about being lost in transition. That little has changed is inscribed in the film’s opening and closing in the same faded, desaturated cityscape. The poverty-stricken town on both sides of the accounts of the past queries the significance of 1989 as pre-revolutionary and post-revolutionary realities appear blurred. The amateur camerawork in the studio means that the questions surrounding the revolution appear “almost as

²⁵⁵ Mary A. Doane, *The Emergence of Cinematic Time: Modernity, Contingency, the Archive* (Cambridge: Harvard University Press, 2002): 163.

²⁵⁶ Tinda Kendall’s concept as quoted in Fuchs, *Prekarious Times*, 119.

²⁵⁷ Alan Riding, “Cameras were Ready: The Revolution Wasn’t,” *New York Times*, June 3, 2007, <https://www.nytimes.com/2007/06/03/movies/03ridi.html>.

²⁵⁸ *12:08, East of Bucharest*, directed by Corneliu Porumboiu, produced by Daniel Burlac (42 Km Film, 2006), <https://mubi.com/en/gb/films/1208-east-of-bucharest>.

a joke, an opportunity to distract oneself from the otherwise obvious lack of change.”²⁵⁹ Like the cameraman, who lets his camera fall, the viewer is not offered an absolute answer. They infer, though, that whether one was a “doer” or a “non-doer” in this supposedly seminal moment, no single memory permits knowing whether Romania has arrived in its post-Communist Promised Land.

The staging of the conversation in a TV studio is important because it was on television that most people witnessed the revolution. However, *12:08* reviews the role of the camera, suggesting it be less an “investigative” tool than a “recovery” tool, enabling recovery from framing the revolution as defining Romanian history.²⁶⁰ The media is presented as a space for democratic discussion, call-ins indulging nostalgia as well as ex-Radio Free Europe listeners. No real answers emerge, and the audience hears how the guest Piscoci spent *his* 12:08: giving magnolias to his wife, “the very same day some people appeared on TV to tell us revolution had won.” It is hard not to read from the host’s sarcastic comment of the camerawork, “At last, a close-up!,” that *12:08* offers a close-up of the diversity of Romanian individuals in 1989, who were so much more than what one reviewer imagined as “passively swept up in historical events, like crumbs pushed along by a ragged broom.”²⁶¹

This film suggests that different questions need to be asked about post-communist lives. Indeed, the characters become more concerned with justifying their post-communist existence. 1989 might have been symbolic, briefly, but for many Romanians, it was a long way from their preoccupations. The talk-show host’s stutter, especially over “exceptionality,” invokes the revolution’s framing, as does the teacher’s instruction, “I don’t want to ruin your Christmas time. Write about what you know—the French Revolution is okay, if nothing else works for you.” The past does not need to ruin the present, once shackled of its exceptionality.

The symbolism of 1989 is similarly revisited in *The Death of Mr. Lazarescu* (2005). Set in 2000, but with evidence of a staid, neo-communist healthcare system, the film follows Lazarescu through institutions unable to offer the attention he needs.²⁶² Ironic codes of continuity are revealed in Lazarescu’s apartment where he sits amongst prominent gas pipes, a reminder of disruptions to central heating during the 1980s. In the hallway the characters are indifferent to the lights turning off, perhaps used to the socialist illumination systems when light and darkness ran

²⁵⁹ Alice Baran, “Aftereffects of 1989,” 16.

²⁶⁰ Robert A. Rosenstone, “History in Images/History in Words: Reflections on the Possibility of Really Putting History onto Film,” *American Historical Review* 93 (December 1988): 1173–85.

²⁶¹ Andrew O. Scott, review: In “12:08 East of Bucharest a Romanian Town Slouches Toward Revolution and Beyond,” *New York Times*, June 13, 2007, <https://www.nytimes.com/2007/06/06/movies/06scot.html>.

²⁶² *The Death of Mr. Lazarescu*, directed by Cristi Puiu Prods, Alexandru Munteanu, Bobby Păunescu and Anca Puiu (Mandragora, 2005), <https://mubi.com/en/gb/films/the-death-of-mr-lazarescu>.

on schedule according to infrequent supply.²⁶³ Not much has changed, then. Certainly, the effectiveness of healthcare has not. In 2019, one in four Romanians had insufficient access to healthcare, according to *The Economist*.²⁶⁴ Indeed, the European liberation from Communism to capitalism has not resolved the health crisis, membership enabling a mass exodus of professionals: since joining the EU, 20,000 doctors have left to work abroad. A dire conclusion in real life is reflected in *Lazarescu*: “Better not get ill in Romania.”²⁶⁵

But *Lazarescu* is a funny film. In a society undergoing transitions, this is the humour of lost confidence and disorientation. The apartment scene is replete with black humour, his neighbours are more interested in how to cook quince jelly than helping Lazarescu. Mostly, the camera ignores him. Even when he vomits blood, the neighbour’s offer of pork moussaka is comic rather than concerning, thus disabling him any real sympathy. Perhaps avoiding intimacy with Lazarescu’s illness confirms Charlie Chaplin’s diagnosis of the aesthetics of tragicomedy: “Life is a tragedy when seen in close-up, but a comedy in long-shot.”²⁶⁶ However, this film also provides a close-up of the tragedy of the Romanian present. *Lazarescu* was intended as a morality tale, a representation of “Love Thy Neighbour,” exploring the tension of living virtuously in a liminal and lonely society. Mioara, the ambulance driver, serves as the Good Samaritan. She accompanies Lazarescu as he is turned away by crowded, or complacent, hospitals, but becomes attached to his frailty. As does the viewer. For Paul Arthur, the crowded frames and claustrophobic camerawork stimulate a “sense of urgency about what *isn’t* being done.” The viewer is trapped in traffic too, in a state of “general intellectual angst,” as the system fails Lazarescu. Waiting with Mioara, as in image 3, “Time doesn’t simply hang, it crushes.”²⁶⁷

²⁶³ Alina Haliliuc, “What Is So Funny about *The Death of Mr Lazarescu*?” *The Journal of Popular Culture* 48 (2015): 161.

²⁶⁴ “Romania’s health-care system, the EU’s worst, struggles to reform,” *The Economist*, November 21, 2019, <https://www.economist.com/europe/2019/11/21/romania-health-care-system-the-eus-worst-struggles-to-reform>.

²⁶⁵ “Romania’s health-care system,” *The Economist*.

²⁶⁶ Harry M. Geduld, ed., *Charlie Chaplin’s Own Story* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2019), 156.

²⁶⁷ Paul Arthur, “Habeas Corpus: A Mediation on *The Death of Mr Lazarescu* and Corporeal Cinema,” *Film Comment* 42 (2006): 44–49. Image taken from “The Death of Mr. Lazarescu (Cristi Puiu, 2005),” *Senses of Cinema*, <https://www.sensesofcinema.com/2017/cteq/the-death-of-mr-lazarescu/>.

Image 3: Mioara becomes the sole charge for Lazarescu's treatment, in Puiu's 2005 film, *The Death of Mr Lazarescu*.

In neorealist style, this film captures human kindness alongside institutional crisis, choreographed to implicate the viewer. In some ways, the film could be read as concerned with blame. Lazarescu's suffering increases as people attribute his condition to drinking. Perhaps this blame, and absence of sympathy, is code for Western treatment of Romania, past and present, in its conditionality for creating a European Family. Indeed, as Georgescu theorises, "ironic messages are characterised by a certain richness that allows them to perform memory work and socio-political critiques simultaneously."²⁶⁸ *Lazarescu* is about fellowship, which the West *should* pay to its Eastern neighbour. The film does not depict a glorious capitalist modernity and the closing shot of Lazarescu's corpse confronts the film's namesake. "Lazarus" is not revived but left to die by a system distracted by other crises, and the viewer is left confronting what it means to be an individual in the post-socialist world.

However, nostalgic redress for a disappointing present is challenged in Mungiu's *4 Months, 3 Weeks and 2 Days* (2007), which explores the claustrophobic reality of living in a pro-natalist and hyper-surveillant state. Ceaușescu enforced an aggressive policy that criminalised abortion. His aim was to reach a population of 25 million and the biopolitics of his regime represented

²⁶⁸ Diana Georgescu, "Ceaușescu Hasn't Died: Irony as Counter-memory in Post-Socialist Romania," as quoted in Maria Todorova and Zsuzsa Gille, eds., *Post-Communist Nostalgia* (New York: Berghahn Books, 2012), 171.

motherhood as a patriotic duty.²⁶⁹ Indeed, members of the Western Bloc praised Romania for its resurgence in population when the World Population Conference was held in Bucharest in 1974. Unsurprisingly, legislation forced abortions dangerously underground, and abortions became the leading cause of mortality among fertile women between 1966 and 1989.²⁷⁰ Mungiu remembers this tragedy.

The film arrives immediately in the drama, with no backstory about Gabita's pregnancy or friendship with Otilia.²⁷¹ This immediacy is intensified by frequent silence. This is destabilising and asks us, according to Mungiu, "to wrestle with our thoughts, as they wrestle with theirs."²⁷² After the abortion, and after the rape of both women by the doctor, the camera focuses for fourteen seconds on Otilia's bowed head, and it is another fourteen minutes before she speaks again. Silence demands we watch without distraction, experiencing the brutality and extent of female subjugation.²⁷³ Rather than witness the "action," we witness the emotional impact of Otilia and Gabita's realities. During the rape of the women, the viewer experiences close-ups of the other woman's facial expressions. So too for the abortion itself, which is seen through Otilia's anxiety as she is trapped at a dinner party with her boyfriend's family. The camera alternates between front- and back-shots, suggesting a vulnerability as observed by the guests as much as the state. Women were day-to-day victims of the policies of the same Communist Romania that the "West" praised in 1974.

This vulnerability is also discernible in the spaces the women are pictured in. The film scholar Anna Batori suggests that the camera materialises the fear of the regime via a grey palette, narrow streets, and dilapidated buildings.²⁷⁴ But the camerawork also materialises the specific *female* experience. In the opening scene, symbolic windows of escape, including a window and a suitcase, jar with the entrapping fishbowl. Gabita is only captured in interior spaces, invaded by frontal camera shots and over-the-shoulder frames, suggesting an intrusive and omnipresent surveillance. The scenes with Dr Bebe convey this oppressive inescapability. Not only does his frame dominate the twenty-minute shot preceding the abortion, leaving the women peripheral in frame and freedom, but Laura Ceia argues that the viewer is invited to feel disgusted by his explicit biological

²⁶⁹ Anna Batori, "Power and acts of resistance in Cristian Mungiu's *4 months, 3 weeks, 2 days*," *Studies in Eastern European Cinema* 7 (2016): 130.

²⁷⁰ Valerie Palmer-Mehta and Alina Haliliuc, "The Performance of Silence in Cristian Mungiu's *4 Months, 3 Weeks, and 2 Days*," *Text and Performance Quarterly* 31 (2011): 114.

²⁷¹ *4 Months, 3 Weeks and 2 Days*, directed by Cristian Mungiu, produced by Oleg Mutu (Mobra Films, 2007), <https://mubi.com/en/gb/films/4-months-3-weeks-and-2-days>.

²⁷² Palmer-Mehta and Haliliuc, "The Performance of Silence," 111, 121.

²⁷³ Deb Margolin as quoted in Palmer-Mehta and Haliliuc, "The Performance of Silence," 177.

²⁷⁴ Batori, "Power and acts," 136.

language.²⁷⁵ Disgust is prompted by the hyper-real sounds of latex and, as an affective emotion, insists on a reckoning with the normative realities of the time.

Image 4: Otilia invites the audience to confront alternative memories of Communism, in Mungiu's 2007 film, *4 Months, 3 Weeks and 2 Days*.

432 exemplifies Roumania Deltcheva's "cinematic remembrance," calling for a confrontation with the Romanian past.²⁷⁶ If films can be persuasively affective, as Laura Ceia suggests, this one *persuades* of untold dramas outside the purview of the narrative.²⁷⁷ These women symbolise all women "raped" by the Communist state. An invitation for moral contemplation is explicit in the final scene when Otilia looks directly at the camera (Figure 4), introducing the possibility of the viewer's own complicity: a sense of guilt in watching what "usually goes neither acknowledged nor understood."²⁷⁸

RNW remembered Communism as everything from pro-natalist brutality to bureaucratic absurdity. In capturing such diversity, RNW legitimised alternative relationships with

²⁷⁵ Laura Ceia, "Flee, Avoid, Ignore, Suppress: Physical and Socio-moral Disgust as quoted in Cristian Mungiu's *4 Months, 3 Weeks and 2 Days*," *Journal of Research in Gender Studies* 1 (2011): 176.

²⁷⁶ Roumania Deltcheva, "Reliving the Past in East European Cinema" in *Eastern European Cinemas*, edited by Aniko Imre (Milton Park: Taylor and Francis, 2005), 204–210.

²⁷⁷ Ceia, "Flee, Avoid, Ignore, Suppress," 166.

²⁷⁸ Roxana Cazan, "Constructing Spaces of Dissent in Communist Romania: Ruined Bodies and Clandestine Spaces in Cristian Mungiu's *4 Months, 3 Weeks, and 2 Days*" and Gabriela Adamesteanu's "A Few Days in the Hospital," *Women's Studies Quarterly* 39 (2011): 94; Kilbourn, *Cinema, Memory, Modernity*, 202. Image taken from Chen, Xi. "How '4 Months, 3 Weeks, and 2 Days' Tells a Story," *Physician Writer*, June 29, 2021, <https://medium.com/physician-writer/how-4-months-3-weeks-and-2-days-tells-a-story-27e8e7556469>.

Communism, contemporary realities, and concomitant commemoration. Mungiu, like his compatriots, called for a restoration of the individual, inscribing in his films “the idea that something very small that happens to you is as good a subject as a saga.”²⁷⁹ The next section qualifies the extent to which his call was answered.

The Reception of RNW

RNW films were important cultural capital, serving to project an identity on an international stage. They fared inconsistently, but generally received less domestic acclaim, scholarly hypotheses for this apathy ranged from ordinary Romanians uninterested in seeing their realities on screen, unable to access one of only 68 cinemas in 2010 (the same year the *Los Angeles Times* gushed that Romania could not make a bad film), or suspicious that RNW undermined the politics of clamouring for international recognition.²⁸⁰ A *Palme d’Or* is hardly redemptive for the 22% of the population living below the poverty line.²⁸¹ This section suggests that diverse responses point to the way that memory functions: filmmakers did not make authoritative memories, but the spectators co-authored what was commemorated, taking from these films what they wanted to find meanings that served their present.

The negotiation of commemorating Communism in RNW depended on the spatial and temporal distance of the viewer. Media and memory scholars suggest that “what is personal in our own memories is confirmed by the memories of others,” and what constitutes the collective memory of the past is negotiated in its collective consumption.²⁸² Films form part of this discourse, viewership part of the textual community demanded of collectives. The inescapability of the West extended to the dissemination of films, film festivals being important spaces to legitimise the artistic value of Romanian cinema.²⁸³ Extensive reliance on technological expertise and funding also hinted at the power of Europe in tangible relationships.²⁸⁴ The extent to which the West commands the global imaginary of Romania was further complicated by this pragmatic reliance regarding the cinema industry. As much as RNW queried the relationship Romania has with its past and with Europe, *Eurimages* endowments came with European expectations.

²⁷⁹ Karin Badt, “Interview with Cristian Mungiu,” *Film Criticism* 34 (2010): 105.

²⁸⁰ Elena Roxan Popan, “Recent Romanian Cinema: Is it a Real New Wave or Just a Splash in the Water?” *The Communication Review* 17 (2014): 229–232; David Lindvall, “Film International 55: The Romanian New Wave,” *Film* (2012) <http://filmint.nu/?p=4264>; Bogdan Popa in Constantin Parvulescu and Turcus Turcus, “Devices of Cultural Europeanisation,” *Studies in Eastern European Cinema* 9 (2018): 9–11.

²⁸¹ Marissa Field, “Top 10 Facts about Living Conditions in Romania,” *Borgen Project*, accessed on July 14, 2019, <https://borgenproject.org/top-10-facts-about-living-conditions-in-romania/>.

²⁸² John Storey and Andrew Hoskins, as quoted in Kilbourn, *Cinema, Memory, Modernity*, 26, 144.

²⁸³ Rodica Ieta, “The New Romanian Cinema,” 30–34.

²⁸⁴ Diana Iordanova, “East Europe’s Cinema Industries Since 1989: Financing Structures and Studios,” *Journal of the European Institute for Communication and Culture* 6 (1999): 47–54.

The reception and consumption of film intersects with memory, in that people watch films not so much to expand perceptions, but to have them confirmed. Hugo Mercier's exploration of "myside bias," that we seek evidence that accords with existing beliefs, is relevant in the way that audiences have approached RNW.²⁸⁵ However, the aesthetics through which commemoration was articulated in RNW, as well as the subjects of commemoration, confronted the "myside bias" of the West, and problematised the "dominant opinions" of the Romanian past.²⁸⁶ That said, international audiences have also been willing to watch films that trouble their preconceptions. RNW, by articulating memories that insisted on a constitutive gap between reality and its cinematic representation, offered possibilities to audiences navigating historical memorialisation in postmodern, transnational spaces. In some ways, the success of RNW was the cause and consequence of broader revisions to commemorative discourse. The awards heaped on RNW suggest the films epitomised a moment in which the right to narrate the past was no longer reserved for academic and political elites.²⁸⁷ Revisions to historical truths have been taking place in various spaces, suggesting a common calling for the democratisation of history and a receptive public.²⁸⁸ The calls RNW made were the early stages of a global chorus. *Lazarescu* alone received an *Un certain regard* at Cannes (2005), *The Silver Orb Award* (Alba Regia 2005), *The Golden Tower* (Palic 2005), *The Grand Prix of the Jury* at the International Copenhagen Film Festival (2005), and many more. Audiences, at least those acclimatised to arthouse aesthetics, found in RNW a grammar that "felt" true.

However, some reviews hint at the prevalence of the condemning imaginary of Romanian history, Romania as incapable of cultural creativity, and Romania as filtered through politicised discourse. Patronising pejoratives that films were "slow-paced and unexciting" (*12:08*), suggest audiences wanted more from history being made "by the humble and foolish."²⁸⁹ Others found respite via "exotic rides into ... forbidden territory," appreciable only from the position of a non-implicated subject.²⁹⁰ The lives in *Tales* were golden, with their "sour beauty" and glimpse into the "Romanian spirit" of camaraderie, but only because their "absurdity and distance from today grant

²⁸⁵ Hugo Mercier and Dan Sperber, *The Enigma of Reason* (London: Allen Lane, 2017).

²⁸⁶ Chun Cheng, et al., "Social bots and mass media manipulated public opinion through dual opinion climate," *Chinese Physics B* 31 (2021): 3.

²⁸⁷ Zandberg, "Ketchup in the Auschwitz of Tomatoes," 111.

²⁸⁸ Johanna Zetterstrom-Sharp and Chris Wingfield, "A "Safe Space" to Debate Colonial Legacy? The University of Cambridge Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology and the Campaign to Return a Looted Benin Altarpiece to Nigeria," *Museum Worlds: Advances in Research* 7 (2019): 1–9.

²⁸⁹ Anthony Kao, "Review: *12:08, East of Bucharest*," *Cinema Escapist*, January 30, 2015, <https://www.cinemaescapist.com/2015/01/review-1208-east-of-bucharest-romania-2006/>; Don Groves, "If I Want to Whistle, I Whistle Review," *SBS*, June 10, 2010, <https://www.sbs.com.au/movies/review/if-i-want-whistle-i-whistle-review>.

²⁹⁰ Filimon, "Reviewed Work(s)," 55.

it a nostalgic aura.”²⁹¹ Reviews seem to reveal a pervasive perspective that Romanian films were too homemade for audiences acclimatised to particular cinematic norms. Interestingly, the trailer of *432* in America metamorphosed the film into an action movie, selling a fast-paced narrative revolving around a secret, quasi-murder mystery, *à la* James Cameron. Faintings at screenings hint at an unpreparedness for a film more concerned with an exploration of the repressed realities of private life that Mungiu called to “Remember” when it was broadcast in Romania.²⁹² Realities were packaged according to a global aesthetic and a global narrative, and then contextualised. The Romanian revolution, supposedly a “historical novelty,”²⁹³ was, for Peter Bradshaw, confirmed as significant in *432*: “On Marinca’s face there is spiritual devastation ... It was from wretchedness and rage such as this that bred the uprising that changed Romania and the world.”²⁹⁴ He seems to miss the coded commentary of the consequences of female suppression.

These selective “accommodations” of RNW confirm the theory of Hegemonic Ideology outlined by film scholar Todd Gitlin, which he understands as the reproduction of a dominant narrative via cultural mediums.²⁹⁵ RNW, concerned with a past outside the global imaginary, had to balance between guessing at audience desires and tolerances if they wanted to “speak to them.”²⁹⁶ But tolerances are hard to shift, especially because the value-laden attributes Cristian Tileaga finds applied by post-Communist memory politics were *constituted* by the finality of the Tismăneanu Report.²⁹⁷ Communism had been first, silenced, and second, categorically demonised, and so audiences lacked the *capacity* to absorb messages that destabilised dominant systems of meaning. Therefore, whilst the hegemonic system is not “cut-and-dried,” it processes non-hegemonic ideology into the hegemonic system precisely so it remains hegemonic. The West digested RNW to fit their preconceptions, celebrating some aspects, or excluding material that was too “oppositional” in form, returning it “to the cultural margins from which it came.”²⁹⁸

Such moulding is explored by the cultural historians Oana Godeanu-Kenworthy and Oana Popescu-Sandu in relation to the American reception of *432*. The film was broadcast when reproductive rights were potent in political debates. They suggest that the American public

²⁹¹ Filimon, “Reviewed Work(s),” 55.

²⁹² Dominique Nasta, *Contemporary Romanian Cinema: The History of an Unexpected Miracle* (New York: Columbia University Press, 2013), 197.

²⁹³ Timothy Garton Ash in Stefano Bottoni and Sean Lambert, *Long Awaited West: Eastern Europe Since 1944* (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 2017), 177.

²⁹⁴ As quoted in Nasta, *Contemporary Romanian Cinema*, 197.

²⁹⁵ Todd Gitlin, “Prime Time Ideology: The Hegemonic Process in Television Entertainment,” *Social Problems* 26 (1979): 251–252.

²⁹⁶ Gitlin, “Prime Time Ideology,” 263.

²⁹⁷ Cristian Tileaga, “Communism in Retrospect: The Rhetoric of Historical Representation and Writing the Collective Memory of Recent Past,” *Memory Studies* 5 (2012): 466.

²⁹⁸ Gitlin, “Prime Time Ideology,” 264.

transformed the film into “the controversial nature of particular individual choices within the liberal capitalist paradigm,” politicised in an atmosphere of pro-life-pro-choice controversy.²⁹⁹ That the film was used on both sides of the abortion debate is interesting, because it illustrates the individuality of filmic deconstruction. It could be a “pro-choice film” by displaying the traumatic options left when women are denied options, but it could equally be enlisted by the National Right to Life website as an invitation to consider that “an abortion not only costs a helpless victim his or her life but also extracts a considerable chunk of humanity of those who take that life.”³⁰⁰ Godeanu-Kenworthy and Popescu-Sandu conclude that global entertainment has not eroded place- and space-specific spectatorship: *432* shows that stories “are filtered twice: first through their own cultural lens, and then through that of the destination country.”³⁰¹

At the domestic level, *432* was consumed differently. Contemporary commentator Christina Anghelina found a warning against nostalgia in the unflinching exposure of tragedy, and for present-day audiences, it is an instruction “that the solution for the problems of the present is not and can never be found in the past, but in the future.” The writer Iulia Blaga thought it exposed the unresolved legacy of moral corruption. Maria Andries, writing in the mainstream press, finds comment on the lack of restorative accountability: “The victims, socialized in an ancient culture of guilt, won’t talk. And the culprits count on it, as they always do.”³⁰² Pro-choice is not the lens through which the film was filtered in Romania, but the relationship the present has with the past. Romanian audiences were sometimes contemptuous of the RNW movement. On the one hand, this was because the grim aesthetics that troubled a positive self-image were “doomed to lose” against Hollywood fare.³⁰³ On the other hand, it was because Communism had left the film industry gutted, and therefore guaranteed a legacy of uncompetitive production companies.³⁰⁴ Indeed, to finance *12:08* Porumboiu had to persuade a milk factory and a bakery to cover his costs.³⁰⁵ For others, especially generations whose memories of Communism were formed in the 1950s and therefore before state censorship had exorcised the Gulags from public consciousness, nostalgic renderings like those offered in *Tales* were not only inappropriate but fetishized falsities. Mungiu himself said that “for us it was half funny that the lights would be cut off for two hours

²⁹⁹ Godeanu-Kenworthy and Popescu-Sandu, “From Minimalist Representation,” 225.

³⁰⁰ D. Andrusko, “The most persuasive anti-abortion argument, ever?” *National Right To Life News* (2008), www.nrlc.org/archive/news/2008/NRL03/Argument.html.

³⁰¹ Godeanu-Kenworthy and Popescu-Sandu, “From Minimalist Representation,” 244.

³⁰² All in Godeanu-Kenworthy, “From Minimalist Representation,” 235.

³⁰³ Imre, *East European Cinemas*, 1.

³⁰⁴ Iona Uricaru, “Follow the Money: Financing Contemporary Cinema in Romania,” as quoted in Aniko Imre, ed, *A Companion to Eastern European Cinema* (New Jersey: John Wiley and Sons, 2012), 6.

³⁰⁵ Andy Ridley, “California Dreamin,” *Socialist Review*, June 1, 2008, <http://socialistreview.org.uk/326/california-dreamin>.

in the night ... and we wouldn't have to do our homework."³⁰⁶ This attitude, and its presentation in film, was insensitive for Smaranda Vultur: "To me, they seem to belittle the evil of that time, to dismiss as derisive the things that literally ruined my life."³⁰⁷ Disenchantment with RNW and what it called to commemorate is confirmed by viewing figures: domestic films had just 2.5% share of the market in 2010.³⁰⁸ RNW revised a past and critiqued a present that some of its people preferred to ignore.

The context in which RNW was being made and consumed also explains their initial domestic rejection. For the film-scholar Doru Pop, these films struggled because they were perceived as denigrating Romania on the international stage, a stage upon which post-communist Romanians searched for their national brand.³⁰⁹ This self-presentation concerned both national patriotism and international promotion, amplified in the \$20-million touristic campaign in 2004, "*The always surprising Romania*." But this did not trickle into self-confidence: an IRES study in Mary 2013 showed almost 60% of Romanians believed Romania was negatively perceived in Europe.³¹⁰ Pop suggests that due to the international receptivity and consequent visibility of RNW, films were part of the problem. RNW satirised Romanian history in self-effacing discourse and ridiculed present-day Romania as lacking rules and morals. RNW, by pedalling a "runner-up" attitude, confirmed the imaginary that Romania was a space of parody.³¹¹ Given that parody works when it contains an element of truth, ironized nostalgia for Communism may have been uncomfortable domestically *because* it was appropriate in relation to the present. For Romanians interested in positive projections, these films were an unwelcome confirmation of "how the continent has struggled to shake off the legacy of dictatorship."³¹² At the same time, the approval of Western audiences for RNW played into the need for recognition. Better to be seen as intrepid idiots that not be seen at all. Paradoxically, RNW was both a source of tension and tribulation when understood as contributory to the European framework.

³⁰⁶ Nick Bradshaw, "Where There's Pomp ... Cristian Mungiu on Tales from the Golden Age," *BFI*, April 19, 2014, <https://www2.bfi.org.uk/news/where-there-s-pomp-cristian-mungiu-tales-golden-age>.

³⁰⁷ Smaranda Vultur, "Daily Life and Constraints in Communist Romania in the Late 1980s: From the Semiotics of Food to the Semiotics of Power" as quoted in Maria Todorova, Augusta Dimou, and Stefan Troebst, eds., *Remembering Communism: Private and Public Recollections of Lived Experience in Southeast Europe* (Budapest: Central European University Press, 2014), 175.

³⁰⁸ "Cinema of Romania", *Wikipedia*, accessed September 5, 2022, [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cinema_of_Romania#Romanian_cinema_\(1990%E2%80%93present\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Cinema_of_Romania#Romanian_cinema_(1990%E2%80%93present)).

³⁰⁹ Doru Pop, "An Analysis of Romanians' Self-Image in Contemporary Cinematographic," *Metacritic Journal for Comparative Studies and Theory* 1 (2015): 139.

³¹⁰ Pop, "An Analysis of Romanians' Self-Image," 143.

³¹¹ Daskalov and Mishkova, *Entangled Histories*, 36.

³¹² R. Jefferson and A. Timu, "Most Shocking Revolution of 1989 Still Casts a Shadow on Europe," *Bloomberg*, November 6, 2019, <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/features/2019-11-06/romania-news-30-years-after-fall-of-communism-remains-unsettled>.

Romanians did begin to enjoy RNW, at least the cosmopolitan members from whose ranks such films were coming. Cultural historian Onoriu Colacel suggests that Romanian films foster an internal culture of belonging.³¹³ The linguist Rodica Ieta argues that RNW enabled audiences to practice critical intellectual engagement, celebrated as a rejection of socialist realism having suffered it for so long.³¹⁴ The neorealist metaphors were, for Shohat, affective for communities that felt unrepresented in a transnational context, analogical identifications offering a “compensatory outlet.”³¹⁵ Nonetheless, positive feelings for RNW were rare. Films that showed “truth 24 frames/second,” often exposing the truth of the present, could hardly be popular whilst the present *was* dissatisfying.³¹⁶ The aesthetics of minimalism, with its “gloomy mix” of angst and sadness touched too close a nerve,³¹⁷ and dark and desperate films alienated a public “ashamed of being a Romanian.”³¹⁸ Puiu recognised this tension: “This is the commercial recipe...you go to the movies, watch Steven Seagal saving the world and return home serene. What about when he does not save it; now you've got a problem! Commercial cinema cannot solve your own drama.”³¹⁹ Hollywood heroes might not solve twenty-first century Romanian realities. But RNW reminded and remembered too many dramas for a public desperate to move on.

³¹³ Onoriu Colacel, *The Romanian Cinema of Nationalism: Historical Films as Propaganda and Spectacle* (Jefferson: McFarland and Company, 2018), 167.

³¹⁴ Rodica Ieta, “The New Romanian Cinema,” 29.

³¹⁵ Shohat and Stam, *Unthinking Eurocentrism*, 351.

³¹⁶ Alexandru Leo Serban, Ramona Uritescu-Lombard, Rodica Ieta and Maria Ionita, “Romanian Cinema: From Modernity to Neo-Realism,” *Film Criticism* 34 (2010): 17.

³¹⁷ Serban et al., “Romanian Cinema,” 4.

³¹⁸ Dan Berindei as cited in Imre, *A Companion*, 7.

³¹⁹ Puiu as quoted in Lindvall, “Film International 55.”

Conclusion

What next for RNW? What next for the memory of Romanian history, in and outside Romania, in and from films? Has RNW invoked a reassessment of what counts as the Romanian past and democratised the construction of what constitutes cultural memories? RNW is over. Whilst films are still being made and legitimated, the commitment to reframing a troubled past, as well as the specific context of negotiating a European space, have faded. Audiences everywhere are increasingly willing to treat history critically. RNW was contextual, made when this willingness was embryonic, evidenced by the criticism some of the films received. The appropriateness of irony was a response to a particular millennial moment, a society responding to a contextual set of pressures about Romania in Europe and dealing with the fallout of a failed revolution, at least one that had failed to bring about the transformation expected of it.

However, Romania is still being framed as a backwater by stakeholders in the European Project, be they journalists, populist politicians, or public figures. These perspectives continue to be felt *in* Romania. The framing of such perspectives continues to be within a dialogue of blaming a Communist past for a failed capitalist present.³²⁰ In 2012, the film-scholar Antonia Kovacheva remarked, “there is still an expectation of sad movies originating in the shantytown ghetto South-East from Vienna.”³²¹ As long as these frameworks persevere, there remains a space for films that critically commemorate what it means to be Romanian. RNW might have finished, but its legacy need not. We should keep thinking about Romanian memory, and its articulation, in a “new wave” way. This means neither amnesia nor anamnesis but accommodating both official and vernacular dimensions of Communist memory. The writer Mohai Rusu calls this type of commemoration “comprehensive memory,” and, in Romania, this means the de-exceptionalisation of Romanian Communism as the history of trauma and tragedy. If 41% of Romanians did not feel that the regime was a criminal one in 2010, then it was not the “devil in history” right-wing intellectuals had insisted.³²² Rusu says that the German Sabrow-Kommission should be the model for “working through” Communism, but Romania hardly needs to look West for its prototype.³²³ RNW offers a domestic blueprint for a critical historicization of Communism. “New wave” commemoration means bottom-up history and individual memories, it means nuance in the construction of cultural

³²⁰ “Huge protests force Romania’s government to reverse itself on corruption,” *The Economist*, February 11, 2017, <https://www.economist.com/europe/2017/02/11/huge-protests-force-romanias-government-to-reverse-itself-on-corruption>.

³²¹ As quoted in Lindvall, “Film International 55.”

³²² Report in Mihai Stelian Rusu, “Transitional Politics of Memory: Political Strategies of Managing the Past in Post-communist Romania,” *Europe-Asia Studies* 69 (2017): 1272.

³²³ Rusu, “Transitional Politics of Memory,” 1270–1276.

collectives, and it means confronting the framework that decides who and what counts as the past, and who and what counts as its lyricists.

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Natural History and Circulation of Knowledge in the Writing of Friar João dos Santos (Eastern Africa, 1586–1609)

MORENO STEDILE

MA Student, University of São Paulo

Abstract

*This paper has as its main thread a case study on Friar João dos Santos' *Etiópia Oriental*, acknowledging its relevance and singularity as regards the production of knowledge about Eastern Africa observed on the trajectory of the book since its publication in 1609 to the present day, in Iberian or African studies. From the analysis of textual forms of epistemic validation, we have been able to observe the meanings of knowledge that comes from experience in the Early Modern Period, especially concerning the knowledge that articulates cartography, natural history and travel literature. This reflection leads to the production of knowledge connecting metropolitan centres to the frontiers of maritime Empires, which reveals dynamics that are characteristic of contact zones and regimes of circulation related to imperial networks. From the Dominican missionary's biodiversity descriptions, mainly the depictions of African animals, we have been able to observe the multiple forms of local agency and engagement that have combined in the production of such knowledge. We have also sought to observe the local networks in which the Dominican is embedded; who his informants are, and the negotiated dimension of this movement. This has led us to investigate the modes of mediation, translation, and the possibilities of using a European source to apprehend African interests, perspectives, and knowledge; with a view to understanding these subjects not as passive informants, but as active agents who negotiate their forms of engagement and imprint their mark upon the production of scientific knowledge.*

Keywords: Travel Literature – Natural History – Eastern Africa – Early Modern Period – History of Science

Introduction and Methodology

The “Scientific Revolution” was a powerful historiographic narrative crystallized in the Western *curriculum* in the first half of the twentieth century. Differently from “the Renaissance” or “modernity,” concepts that existed from the sixteenth century onwards, the notion of “revolution” at that time was more related to the cyclic conception present in the work *The revolutionibus orbium coelestium* (1545) by Copernicus. With the rise of cultural studies and criticism in the 1980s, the whole idea of a “Scientific Revolution” was rejected as a “grand narrative” of the West. The notion of “science” itself was put under suspicion. This criticism gave way to a proliferation of case studies, giving rise to the necessity of reevaluating the level of the local production of knowledge, and the aspects of its circulation. In addition, social, material and literary practices that surrounded knowledge production became objects of study. The notions of a centre and a periphery were reevaluated, as well as the dichotomy colonizer-colonized, emphasising the necessity of understanding local forms of mediation, negotiation and translation, situated in their social, economic and cultural patterns.³²⁴

This paper builds on these developments of historical research, having as its main thread a case study on Friar João dos Santos’ work, *Etiópia Oriental e Varia História de Cousas Notáveis do Oriente*, in particular his depictions of natural history regarding African animals, which remained the more important source, under the corpus of European sources, in that field until the late nineteenth century. The role of those depictions in his work (a huge publication from the Dominican Convent from Evora, printed in the year 1609) is related to the connections between natural history and travel literature in the early modern period. Since it is not a scientific treaty, but a book that organizes from a cartographic perspective (at least in the first volume) a diversified collection of experiences and knowledge locally gathered during the author’s stay in Eastern Africa, from 1586 to 1597, and later in Goa until 1600. As characteristic of travel literature in that period, it draws on the fields of religion, ethnography, commercial information, political history, curiosities, etc. The Dominican friar presents the work as a result of his “eye-witness testimonies,” a result of the eleven years he lived on the African continent, which would assure the “credit” of that knowledge.³²⁵

³²⁴ Federico Palomo, “Production et circulation des savoirs dans une monarchie polycentrique: Goa, la chrétienté éthiopienne et l’empire portugais du XVIIe siècle,” *Annales. Histoire, Sciences Sociales*, 78 (2022): 429, 430; Antonio Sanchez Martinez, “La ‘Atlantización’ de la ciencia ibérica: el mundo atlántico visto desde la historia de la temprana ciencia moderna,” *Anuario de Estudios Atlánticos* 60 (2014); Fa-ti Fan, “The Global Turn in the History of Science,” *East Asian Science, Technology and Society: An International Journal* 6 (2012).

³²⁵ João dos Santos, *Etiópia oriental e varia história de cousas notáveis do Oriente*, (Lisbon: Biblioteca dos Clássicos Portugueses: 1891 [1609]), 40.

New perspectives of the history of science and modernity lead to a reflection on the local production of knowledge, the role and “activities of various intermediaries, brokers, go-betweens and translators, without whom the colonial institutions or the religious orders could have successfully interacted with the local communities, nor gained access to their set of practices and knowledge.”³²⁶ We have observed how the status of “eyewitness testimony” is extended to other subjects, and those who are considered “credible people” are not necessarily European. Actually, knowledge production happens through networks that surpass cultural boundaries. The origin of these individuals could come from an “extreme diverse cosmos, with varied cultural, religious and linguistic backgrounds, building many dimensions of sociability, sharing knowledge and other cultural features.”³²⁷ For example, on the religious matter, João dos Santos affirms having interrogated “honorable kaffirs” on their notions of God and creation.³²⁸ Elsewhere, he refers to having been cured from a sickness by a Muslim woman from the Quirimbas, who is referred to as a “great master.”³²⁹ The stories told by people considered “credible” permeate the entire work of João dos Santos, fitting into a movement of much more fluid circulation between writing, imagery, and orality, which were not yet hierarchized as they later would be in the eighteenth century. In truth, “memory” continued to be the primary form of knowledge in the early modern period. The local collecting of information emphasizes the transcultural character of the knowledge produced in colonial territories.

While living in Goa, João dos Santos got in touch with members of the intellectual environment to which Garcia Orta had previously belonged. Studies have asserted the Dominican’s relation to Goa’s erudite circles, namely his relation to Diogo do Couto, who held an important library in the capital of the Portuguese State of India.³³⁰ It was an important centre for the circulation and concentration of knowledge from all around the Indian Ocean, since the Portuguese networks, along with many religious orders, went from Eastern Africa to China and up to Japan. Returning to Portugal, João dos Santos wrote his work under the auspices of the Dominican Convent of Évora, his hometown. The publication of the book resulted in his return to Africa, as chief of a mission to what was believed to be the silver mines of Chicova, near Tete, up the Zambezi River. Many other works were consulted to write the book, in libraries in Goa, Lisbon and Évora. Particularly, the Dominican refers to other travellers, who could give fresh and consistent information, based on experience. This paper concentrates its analysis on the first three

³²⁶ Amelia Polónia et al., eds., *Cross-Cultural Exchange and the Circulation of Knowledge in the First Global Age* (Porto: CIHCEM, 2018), 7.

³²⁷ Polónia et al., *Cross-cultural Exchange*, 7.

³²⁸ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 70.

³²⁹ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, vol 2., 245.

³³⁰ Rui Manuel Loureiro, *A biblioteca de Diogo do Couto* (Macau: Instituto Cultural, 1998).

books of *Etiópia oriental*, which offer an account of the author's personal contribution, from his personal experience as a missionary in Eastern Africa.

Early Modern Knowledge

This form of validating the knowledge produced by the author's "eye-witness testimonies" draws on the notion of "experience" from the early modern period. Differently from the Middle Ages, when the eyes, and generally, the external senses, were discredited as misleading (when true knowledge came from the Bible and the Church authorities), one of the characteristics of the modern period was a reshaping of human vision as a category of cognition. This was not incompatible with a religious vision of the world, or with a Catholic cosmovision;³³¹ on the contrary, Adam's myth was reevaluated in the Renaissance, combined with Prometheus', recognizing in each man, one reflection of God's image, God's capacity of creation.³³² Particularly, Iberian knowledge in modern times put even the Classics' authority into question. Strong ideas from classic authors were debunked, such as the torrid zone, its inhabitability and navigability, and the existence of antipodes, besides the discovery of a whole new continent (America) and the Southern Hemisphere with its new constellations. This consciousness was expressed in a letter by Italian scholar Tommaso Campanella, which recognises that authorities such as Saint Augustine were turned into "liars [*buggiardi*]" by a "simple mariner" [*un mariano*] with his "eye-witness testimonies [*testimoniari de visú*]."³³³

The first consciousness of superiority of the moderns over the ancients was forged in the Iberian Peninsula in the sixteenth century, as per authors such as José Antonio Maravall, from Spain, and José Sebastião da Silva Dias, from Portugal.³³⁴ Nevertheless, these catholic roots of modernity were obscured by the grand narrative of the "Scientific Revolution" that emphasised Protestant and northern European trajectories in the shaping of modern knowledge.³³⁵ Such consciousness is particularly expressed in Portugal by Garcia Orta, and others from his generation, in his important work *Colloquies on the Simples and Drugs from India*, first published in 1563. This work

³³¹ Traditional sociologic and historical approaches of European history have emphasised the differences between rationalism in the protestant North and religious thought in the Catholic South. Newer approaches tend to relativise such dichotomy, understanding that a Catholic worldview was not incompatible with scientific thought, on the contrary, Italy and the Iberian Peninsula continued to be important centres of knowledge production and diffusion, even to Elizabethan England.

³³² Ernst Cassirer, *O indivíduo e o cosmos na filosofia do Renascimento* (São Paulo: Martins fontes, 2001).

³³³ Quoted in José Sebastião da Silva Dias. *Os descobrimentos e a problemática cultural do século XVI* (Lisbon: Presença, 1962), 119.

³³⁴ José Antonio Maravall, *Antiguos y modernos* (Madrid: Sociedade de Estudios y Publicaciones, 1966); Silva Dias, *Os descobrimentos e a problemática cultural do século XVI*.

³³⁵ Jorge Cañizares-Esguerra, *Nature, Empire and Nation: Explorations of the History of Science in the Iberian World* (Stanford: Stanford University Press, 2006).

is an important example of the role of Iberian knowledge and its circulation in modern Europe. It was successively republished in Antwerp, in 1567, 1582, 1586 and 1593, twice translated and published into Latin, in 1582 and 1593, not to mention Italian (1595) and French (1619), in a fifty-year interval following its publication – a best-seller from the period that Benedict Anderson called “print-capitalism.”³³⁶

In terms of publications, other Portuguese works from the time have followed the same path, as shown by Silva Dias. Fernão Lopes de Castanheda’s history from India, published in 1551, was translated into French (1553), German (1565), and English (1582). Fernão Mendes Pinto’s travel book, called *Peregrinações* – revealing information from all parts of the world visited or not by the author – was also widely translated. Similar to other Portuguese authors João dos Santos’ work would have a significant of European translations, which will be exposed at the end of this article. Travel literature was a successful editorial genre in the Early modern period. Take, for example, Hans Staden’s *True History* of his travels to Brazil. Despite not being an Iberian author, he gives an account of experiences that took place in Portuguese America. They were first published in German and translated into many languages and successively republished, along with the original prints that revealed scenes of cannibalism among the Tupinamba.³³⁷

Garcia da Orta is an important author because of the consciousness he expresses of modern notions of knowledge through experience, as well as for having taken to India his project of natural history knowledge-gathering, collaborating with local interlocutors in Goa, where he kept an important botanic garden in the middle of the sixteenth century. It is important for our purpose to understand Orta’s thought because he and his generation directly inspired the kind of erudition expressed later by João dos Santos. In early modern Europe, natural history was comprised not only of fauna, flora and minerals (as in the latter Enlightenment notion), but also of medical knowledge, therapeutic uses of the natural world, which could include even miraculous sources. Orta expresses the continuation of a field of natural history shaped in Portugal by Amato Lusitano, who collected in the markets of Lisbon plants and spices from different parts of the world, registering and researching their uses. Connected to the more radical humanist movement in Portugal, Amato Lusitano, a *cristão-novo* (“new-Christian”), publicly returned to Judaism and fled to the Netherlands in 1559. Orta took that project to India. In his *Colloquies*, organised as a dialogue

³³⁶ In the first chapter of “Imagined Communities,” Benedict Anderson defines “print-capitalism” as the editorial boom that followed the invention of the press and the many possibilities it opens, which according to him played an important role in the rise of national identities and State, in the Renaissance and the Reformation, and the transformations that characterised modern era. Benedict Anderson, *Imagined Communities: Reflection on the Origins and Spread of Nationalism* (London: Verso, 1983), 9-37.

³³⁷ Silva Dias, *Os descobrimentos*, 107; Luciana Villas-Boas, *Encontros escritos: semântica histórica do Brasil colonial* (Rio de Janeiro: Editora UFRJ, 2017).

where he opposes two characters: Dr Ruano and Dr. Orta. The prior, a former student from Salamanca and a typical erudite with a trove of memorised quotations from classic authors the latter, Dr. Orta himself, the practical man, traveller and observer, who founds knowledge on experience. Orta says to his interlocutor:

“Do not scare me with Dioscorides or Galen, because I will not say anything except the truth and what I know. (...) I will not say anything is good unless it is witnessed by my own eyes [testemunho de vista] or trustworthy people [pessoas de crédito]. (...) As a witness of my own eyes [testemunho de vista], although lower than all the doctors, I will be given more faith than those priests of Greek medicine who wrote based on false information.”³³⁸

João dos Santos, when introducing his book and supporting his arguments, directly incorporates this passage from Orta, emphasizing that everything he was going to say was a result of his “eye-witness testimony” [*testemunho de vista*] or told by “trustworthy-people” [*pessoas de crédito*]. Despite the Dominicans being the managers of the Inquisition in Portugal, João dos Santos reveals his relations with the canons of Portuguese humanism, quoting passages from Orta, and even from more radical Amato Lusitano, who was already censored at the time and is briefly quoted in the second volume. Also, D. João de Castro, the Viceroy of India, is brought up as an exemplar historic character in the Dominican’s narrative. Beside Orta and Lusitano, the Viceroy was another canon of the time of king. João III. In a letter written from Mozambique to the king in August 1538, Castro reveals having used the shadow instrument developed by cosmographer Pedro Nunes to take measures from different parts of the Indian ocean, its latitudes, while also taking notes on the sea currents, winds, and, particularly, on animals from the sea and land.³³⁹ In *Etiópia Oriental*, D. João de Castro is remembered as a “prudent captain,”³⁴⁰ not for any military action or conquest, but the example evoked by his good administration consists in discovering through experience the real cause of the redness of parts of the Red Sea. In the book, after considering many theories about the origin of that name, from classic authors, such as Aristotle and Pliny, João dos Santos asserts that “all these opinions (despite coming from such grave authors), were refuted and dismissed with the following [opinion] secured, corrected and *verified through experience*.”³⁴¹ This verified opinion belonged to the Viceroy, which is quoted from his *Geographic Commentaries* and said

³³⁸ Quoted in Silva Dias. *Os descobrimentos*, 97, 98 [translated].

³³⁹ Silva Dias, *Os descobrimentos*.

³⁴⁰ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 465.

³⁴¹ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 464, 465, highlights added for emphasis [original: “todas estas opiniões (posto que sejam de tão graves autores) se podem refutar, e desfazer com a seguinte, segura, correta e verificada pela experiência”].

to have wandered different parts of the Red Sea, sending divers to collect material from the bottom, replicating this experience in different parts of the Sea.³⁴²

João dos Santos: a Dominican Traveller in Eastern Africa

Following the example of figures such as Orta and Castro, João dos Santos put his effort into producing knowledge during his trip and missionary work in Eastern Africa. This knowledge is organised in a way of writing that is typical of the travel literature of that time, which combined different literary genres and a particular kind of exoticism. Basing the validity of his writing on experience, the author emphasizes the locally-gathered dimension of the knowledge, constantly bringing up his travel experiences. His travel itinerary is the guiding line of the narrative, that is organized in a cartographic way. The narrative begins with his departure from Lisbon, in 1586, answering the Bishop of Malaca's call for missionaries to the Indian Ocean. Arriving in Mozambique, his first mission was to serve as a clerk in the church of Sofala, responsible, as he put it, for "600 confessing souls, comprised of Portuguese, *mestiços*, and people of the land".³⁴³ This passage already exhibits the transcultural networks in which the Dominican is embedded. Sofala was an ancient Swahili port in the mouth of the Buzi River, long recognised in Arabian cartography as the main source of gold in the Indian ocean trade. This trade was related to the connections developed by the Swahili with the Shona societies from the hinterland.³⁴⁴ The first book of *Etiópia oriental* is dedicated to Sofala, its hinterland, comprising a description of the societies, people, mores, the history of Portuguese presence, trade information, as well as many animal depictions.

Even though the gold trade there still existed, in the sixteenth century a major part of it was diverted to the route of the Zambezi River, accessing directly, through the cities of Sena and Tete, in the Botonga territory on the margins of that river, the Zimbabwe plateau, where the main gold bazaars were located, namely in the Mwenemutapa, which was recognized at the time as the great African kingdom from the hinterland. João dos Santos took that route in 1590, reaching the city of Tete in 1591.³⁴⁵ The second book of his work describes the Zambezi valley and the Zimbabwean plateau; this is a very relevant part of his work, because it was the first erudite description of the interior of Central-Eastern Africa, and lasted for a long time as one of the main sources of information to Europeans about that land.³⁴⁶ David Livingstone, in the nineteenth

³⁴² Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 465.

³⁴³ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 46. "600 almas de confissão, em que entravam portugueses, mestiços e gente da terra."

³⁴⁴ Maylin Newitt. *History of Mozambique*. (London: Hurst, 1995).

³⁴⁵ S. I. G. Mudenge, *A political history of Munhumutapa*. (Harare: Zimbabwean Press, 1988).

³⁴⁶ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 163–256.

century, would still follow the Dominican's path, travelling through the Zambezi and reaching the plateau through Tete.³⁴⁷ Again, in this book, different literary genres and topics are combined: many chapters are dedicated to the mores of the Mwenemutapa, from political protocols to religious information. Trade routes and the presence of Portuguese and *mestizo* communities are also described. Besides that, João dos Santos does not omit the depiction of animals, talking about the animals from the river and the hinterlands.

Later in 1592, João dos Santos was redesignated as a clerk in the church of Ibo, an island in the Quirimbas archipelago, south of the Rovuma River, on the northern shore of contemporary Mozambique. This was a complex of 31 islands along the shore of the African continent, divided by short intervals of sea and mangrove. In the third book of his work, the Dominican describes the Portuguese presence along the chain of islands and their interaction with the Swahili Muslim community.³⁴⁸ This presence was mostly related to the ivory trade from the coast. Historian Edward Alpers estimates that the ivory trade in colonial Mozambique in the late sixteenth century could result in the killing of around 1000 elephants a year.³⁴⁹ The depictions of animals from this area provide lots of information on maritime animals, acknowledging the intense relations of that society with the sea, but also concentrating on describing the hunting of elephants.

The consideration of knowledge produced in this colonial and missionary context brings to the surface the relation between science and Empires, or, in other words, the issue of how science is produced through colonial networks. Natural history was not a *naïf* interest on the part of João dos Santos, but an expression of the awareness of its importance to European knowledge about the world in the early modern period. On many occasions, he expresses notions of modern political thought, mostly the ideas of good government. As revealed in the example of D. João de Castro, evoked in the work in a typical use of exemplarity under the notion of *historia magistræ vitæ*, a good colonial agent should be eager to consistently gather information about the land, in which the knowledge of fauna and flora was particularly important. These were important elements of cartographic knowledge, essential to governing distant and scarcely-known territories. Pragmatic aspects of those natural depictions' primary use for survival in foreign lands were eating and medical use. The former consisted of a vulnerability of Portuguese presence in fortresses in different parts of the Indian Ocean that depended on the food supply coming from local economies. The latter consisted of the knowledge of maladies and their forms of healing that were

³⁴⁷ David Livingstone, *Missionary travels and research in South Africa, including a sketch of sixteen year's residence in the interior of Africa* (London: J Murray, 1857), 712.

³⁴⁸ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 257-339.

³⁴⁹ Edward Alpers, "Moçambique marítimo (sécs. XIV-XXI)," *Revista de História*, 178 (2019): 16.

basic for surviving in different lands and climates. The knowledge of local diseases and their forms of healing is a typical example of transcultural knowledge production.³⁵⁰

Mermaids and Manatees

Another strong component in natural history treaties in the Friar's narrative is the association between mermaids and manatees. Mermaids and diverse forms of hybrids of women and fish are present in very different cultures, and particularly in European folklore since Ancient times, traversing the Middle Ages. Their persistence in natural history treaties, still in the eighteenth century, are a proof of the continuities with older traditions, like the medieval *bestiaries*, especially during the early modern period. In Europe, sirens “were portrayed in church iconography, in the artwork and architecture of aristocratic homes, commercial wares, handicrafts and in cabinets of curiosities (...) they appeared frequently among the pages of early modern printed texts, were visually represented in illuminated manuscripts and maps and the subject of literary, scientific and religious texts.”³⁵¹ According to Cristina Brito:

“The definition-defying and boundary-crossing mermaid offers a fascinating window into the malleability of early modern concepts such as sex and gender, selfhood and mystery, as well as natural and unnatural. This is similar to the construction of the concept of (early) modern zoology or natural history, where nature and culture were co-players and knowledge production was hybrid and connected.”³⁵²

In reprising the topic of connecting the myth of mermaids to describing mammals that were exotic animals to the Europeans, João dos Santos particularly reveals the literary making of natural history through a travel narrative, and the role of the Ancients, even when they might be incorrect. Probably he refers to *dugong* (name of Malaysian origin), a specific type of mammal from the Indian Ocean that lives near the shore and is currently threatened with extinction due to massive fishing. The Friar declares he very often eats the animal's meat, together with cabbage, when in Sofala, having learned from fishermen of its characteristics and habits. The fish is said to be very similar to humans from the belly to the neck, having arms (but not hands, nor fingers, reminds the author), a deformed face and a mouth full of teeth. Because of such similarities, the Friar considers that

³⁵⁰ Maria Cristina Wissenbach, *Ares e azares da aventura ultramarina: matéria médica, saberes endógenos e transmissão nos circuitos do Atlântico luso-afro-americano. O Império por escrito – formas de transmissão da cultura letrado no mundo ibérico, sécs. XV-XVIII*, eds. Megiani et al. (São Paulo: Intermeios, 2020).

³⁵¹ Cristina Brito, “Connected margins and disconnected knowledge: exotic marine mammals in the making of early modern European natural history,” in *Cross-Cultural Exchange and the Circulation of Knowledge in the First Global Age*, eds. Amélia Polónia et. al., (Porto: CIHCEM, 2018), 104.

³⁵² Brito, “Connected margins,” 105.

these mammals might be the mermaids or tritons that “the ancients *confabulated*.”³⁵³ At this point, the description of the animal is interrupted, giving way to a long digression on the ancient myths and poems about mermaids, reprising classic authors and, particularly, Ulysses’ tale, which is told by the Friar, evoking the episode in which the Greek captain covered his mariners’ ears with wax and tied himself to the mast to avoid being enchanted by the mermaids’ singing. After spending much ink on these tales, the Dominican resumes his description of the animal, asserting that those are all “tales of poets, but the truth is that the mammal from its nature is created and conceived in the sea, just as the other fishes.”³⁵⁴ The tale of the mermaids singing, he considers, might be related to the fact that he learned from fishermen that the fish, when removed from the sea, screams and cries, resembling the crying of a human.³⁵⁵

Cultural Intermediaries

In Sofala, one of the Dominican’s main informants was Rodrigo Lobo, who is described as a “wife of the king,” referring to the African chief in the territory. This term was a translation that indicates the way the Shona used the metaphor of marriage and, above all, of kinship, as a structural element of power relations. That title indicates one who had status, controlled land and had slaves. Rodrigo Lobo is a typical go-between, someone who moved around by way of mediations between the Portuguese and the African worlds. He is described by João dos Santos as someone who knew how to speak the language of the so-called “kaffirs” well. The author acknowledges that Rodrigo Lobo controlled an island upon the Buzi River, where he lived with forty slaves.³⁵⁶ The development of a sociability circuit between Friar João dos Santos and Rodrigo Lobo allowed the Dominican to access the latter’s African network. He went to the island to catechize and baptize his slaves, but also went there for pleasure, because it was a place of “great recreation,” as he put it, going on hunts or animal observations – on these occasions, natural history depictions took place.³⁵⁷

João dos Santos talks about a pig hunt organized by the island’s owner in order to please him. Here we can observe a first movement from Rodrigo Lobo towards the Dominican. The slaves were a necessary and constant presence in the Europeans’ penetration of the African interior, as carriers and for the safety of the trip, because the presence of large animals such as

³⁵³ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 150, 151. Translated. “Eu cuido que estas devem ser as Serêas e os Tritões, que os antigos fingiam (...).”

³⁵⁴ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 153. Translated. “Tudo isto são fingimentos de poetas: mas a verdade é, que o peixe-mulher de sua natureza é gerado e creado no mar, como os demais peixes.”

³⁵⁵ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 153.

³⁵⁶ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 114.

³⁵⁷ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 118.

elephants and rhinoceros could be a threat to a human traveling alone. One of dos Santos' important animal depictions is that of the hippopotamus, which was scarcely known in Europe at the time. He wrote a long chapter to visually describe the animal, resorting to many elements of medieval bestiaries. The animal is depicted as a fierce, scary and admiring animal, bigger than two horses, with short and thick feet, a head the size of three oxen, a big torn mouth full of teeth, with four curved horns coming out of it, two going up, and two going down.³⁵⁸

After this description, the Dominican tells a story that can be used to measure the level of interactions between the Portuguese and nature in this African space. He said that he went for recreation and fishing along the Buzi river with two Portuguese men from the fortress. For that purpose, he says, many slaves came together. They were surprised by a couple of hippopotamuses, which ran toward their group, at which point the slaves that had come with them began to cry and to shoot their arrows, in order to scare them, acknowledging that the situation was very dangerous, as the enormous animal could have trampled them. At this point, the author starts describing the techniques of hunting hippopotamuses, which is said to be very hard and tiresome, but an occasion of great joy for the African hunters, who go on hunting trips in great groups, like the one that he once crossed paths with along the Zambezi river made up of a dozen boats with hunters.³⁵⁹

The presence of enslaved people together with the Portuguese spending time off at the river is an important element of the narrative. Though the slave trade in the Indian ocean is ancient, it was never as massive as the Atlantic slave trade before the nineteenth century. Also, slavery inside African territories responds to different parameters than those in the plantations, which meant different margins of negotiation by enslaved people. The collaborative relationships with enslaved people in the production of knowledge about natural history opens up an interpretive path to try to understand the agency of enslaved people in the production of scientific knowledge. Like the go-betweens, enslaved people were privileged intermediaries to the Europeans in foreign territories, especially those enslaved by religious orders. They could act as translators, guides through the hinterlands, or even as transmitters of knowledge and worldviews. It is known that after rounding the Cape of Good Hope, a Moorish slave captured on the African coast guided Vasco da Gama to India. Among João dos Santos' confessing souls, surely there were the enslaved people of the Dominican order, the Sofala fortress, and the Portuguese, all of whom were subjected to the obligation of confession. We can observe the importance of slaves in the local dynamics of knowledge production in *Ethiopia orientalis* in many passages describing animals.

³⁵⁸ Santos. *Ethiopia orientalis*, 170.

³⁵⁹ Santos. *Ethiopia orientalis*, 173.

In one of those, João dos Santos was again on Rodrigo Lobo's island, sitting at his home, when one of his slaves showed up and invited the friar to watch six lions that were crossing the river, which he said was a feast for the eyes.³⁶⁰ The Dominican hesitated, but having been assured that it was safe, he agreed to tag along. We can observe how the slave identified the author's curiosity about nature. In another passage, the Friar describes an animal called *nbaçara*. In many cases, he offers both European and African names for the animal, in some he gives only a Portuguese name, but, in this case, he offers only the African one. By analysing his depiction, one can understand he is talking about the pangolin. He describes its size, skin and claws used for digging and eating ants. As it was often the case, his depiction moves from external aspects to the inside of the animal. Yet again the cultural mediators appear, capturing the animal, opening and cleaning it and saying if it can or cannot be eaten. Many times, the Dominican confirms or denies the good taste of it. In the case of the pangolin, another interesting piece of information is provided: acknowledging that the animal's stomach was empty, the African hunters that accompanied the Dominican offer an explanation that comes from their ancestors, according to which the animal fed itself only from air and could be seen open-mouthed while facing the wind.³⁶¹ This is only a small example of how African perspectives of the natural world can appear in this source.

Lion Hunt

A more significant one is when, during a hunt promoted by Rodrigo Lobo, someone violated the local African law prohibiting lion hunting, which is explained by the connection between this animal and the royal ancestor, *mbondoro*; this was very risky and could result in the confiscation of his land. But Rodrigo Lobo knew how to manipulate the local cultural grammar well, as we have observed above, to the point where he reached the prestigious position of "wife of the king."³⁶² So he produced a pompous grave to the lion, covering it with fabrics (which was the main trading currency in Africa), and sent it to the Shona chief along with a message saying that he, Rodrigo Lobo, wife of the king, had killed that lion in honour of his husband, because the animal was being discourteous to his wife. According to João dos Santos, the Shona chief received the gift and sent a message saying that it was right to kill the lion because it was being impolite to his wife.³⁶³ This story exemplifies to the Dominican how well Rodrigo Lobo manipulated the kaffir's language, as

³⁶⁰ Santos. *Etiópia oriental*, 120.

³⁶¹ Santos. *Etiópia oriental*, 126, 127.

³⁶² Santos. *Etiópia oriental*, 114.

³⁶³ Santos. *Etiópia oriental*, 117.

he put it. Going beyond his interpretation, the data indicate how well this go-between agent understood and manipulated the Shona interpretation of the natural world and the language of their political power. Something that the Dominican acknowledged and is confirmed by later narratives and present-day ethnography is the relation between south-eastern African chiefs and lions. In the Bantu cosmivision, the most important religious entities are the ancestors, which have direct agency over the earthly world; among the Shona monarchies, the dead chief turns into a specific ancestor who shows up like a lion, which is called a *mbondoro*. The *mbondoro* cult lies at the root of Shona political traditions; it is said to have been initiated by Matope, one of the founders of Munhumutapa State.³⁶⁴

Other examples, through the narrative of João dos Santos, can be provided regarding the association of African power and animals, which can open a path to understanding African notions of nature. Brazilian anthropologist Eduardo Viveiros de Castro has pointed out the difference between multinaturalism in the Western cosmivision, and multiculturalism in the Amerindian cosmivision; whereas the Westerners see a world defined by a unity of nature and a variety of cultures, the Amerindians understand a variety of natures and a unified culture. That unity of culture is a unity of spirit that connects the different bodies present in space, human and non-humans, each one characterized by its particular way of acting in the world.³⁶⁵ For our purposes, it is significant how Viveiros de Castro epistemologically incorporates Amerindian perspectivism, translating and validating this way of thinking about the natural world beyond the Western opposition between nature and culture and using it to rethink some principles of anthropology itself as a discipline. The possibility of decoding and reconstructing ways of thinking from an African cultural grammar appears in the work of Friar João dos Santos, for it is the result of encounters and translations between cultures and networks characteristic of contact zones.

In the Central African cosmivision, a core metaphor is one of cure and disease, which worked within an anthropological tradition called the “fortune-misfortune complex.”³⁶⁶ The medical knowledge and its practices were developed by individuals that were specialists in connecting with the spiritual world. When talking about religious knowledge, dos Santos reveals having been in touch with such specialists.³⁶⁷ A characteristic aspect used in Central African therapeutics for combating diseases (which was socially understood: slavery and war could be diseases, and therefore also healed) was the manipulation of poison. This use of poison appears in

³⁶⁴ Mudenge, *A political history*, 44.

³⁶⁵ Eduardo Viveiros de Castro, “Perspectival Anthropology and the Method of Controlled Equivocation,” *Tipiti, Journal of the Society of Anthropology of Lowland South America* 2, (2004).

³⁶⁶ Willy de Craemer, Jan Vansina, and Renée Fox, “Religious movements in Central Africa: a theoretical study,” *Comparative Studies in Society and History* 18, (1976).

³⁶⁷ Santos. *Etiópia oriental*, 70.

pre-colonial and colonial documentation. Particularly, it was manipulated as an instrument of power by the head of the African state, through their use in ordeals.³⁶⁸ In dos Santos' narrative, significant information is provided in the making of poison, for example, from the crocodile's liver. According to him, one part of liver led to poison, and the other, to an antidote.³⁶⁹ Lots of information on the production of antidotes is provided, under the field of therapeutic knowledge, which was part of natural history. Even if the origin of that knowledge was not provided, we can understand it, by comparing it with other parts of the work where those networks are more explicit. He acknowledges being healed by African healers, and collects information on animals and plants among African interlocutors. It is important to observe that those interlocutors had important margins of negotiation and agency, since they were essential for Europeans to move into those territories. Besides that, African political protocols, including the use of ordeals and poison, are described in the book. The knowledge of those protocols was also essential for the Portuguese presence and trade. For example, the killing of the snake called *ruça inbanga* is forbidden, according to João dos Santos, because its very strong poison was used in the confection of arrows, thus leading to a monopoly of the poison by the chiefs. Additionally, he draws on elements from medieval bestiaries, attributing emblematic meanings to those slaves, depicted as evil-characters.³⁷⁰

Another example of the association of animals with political power is the bird called *curuane*, which is compared to the crane, only much more beautiful since it is almost entirely black, as if it were made of silk, but with a white belly, thus resembling a white mushroom or *sombrero*. This resource for comparisons, as we can observe, is frequent, and other birds are used for describing other parts of the animal, such as its red feathers in the face, that are said to be akin to those of the goldfinch. Due to its beauty, it would be considered by the Africans as the "king of birds" and used as a symbol by various important chiefs in the region.³⁷¹

Layers of Circulation

Concerning the circulation of knowledge through local networks that links the Dominican friar to African informants, it is important to observe the use and incorporation of African vocabulary, mostly Shona, throughout his work. This occurs not only when it comes to naming animals and plants that didn't exist in Europe and were common in that African society, but also in other fields, such as religious knowledge, material culture (for example musical instruments, hunting and

³⁶⁸ John Janzen. *Lemba, 1650-1930: A Drum of Affliction in Africa and the New World* (London: Garland, 1982).

³⁶⁹ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 144.

³⁷⁰ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 130.

³⁷¹ Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 136.

navigating, military), geographic knowledge, trade institutions, among others. When giving toponyms, João dos Santos usually gives both Portuguese-attributed and local names: he registers the local name Zambezi for what the Portuguese called *Cuama rivers* (from Arab name, *Kwama*); also, he gives the name Madagascar to what the Portuguese unanimously called the island of Saint Lourenço. One important passage of the work reveals his understanding of the different dialects of Shona: he says that in Munhumutapa, the Shona language is more politely spoken than elsewhere in that region, because it contains a gracious, soft and whistled sound, very different from what he calls the scratchy sound of Arabic, that sound as if the words are being vomited out of the speaker's mouth, according to his depiction.³⁷² Of course, this statement from friar João dos Santos is full of political meanings, and we cannot unravel them here in each historical layer of this representation. Our goal here is to measure his grasp and level of understanding of the Shona language, in order to better observe the modes of mediation and translation and the role of African interlocutors and go-betweens in the production of knowledge.

We can observe how many African names are incorporated in the description of animals, including a big diversity of fishes and birds. One bird, named *sazy*, is said to feed on wax, often entering the church from Sofala to eat the wax from their candles, being captured there by the sextons for their meat. Another, named *minga*, is said to be similar to the pigeon, and is very fat and tasty. Also on fishes the author offers very precise local denominations: a fish called *macone*, frequently eaten by the locals, is very fresh, but unsavoury; the Dominican says he ate it many times. Another, named *munemune*, has such a strong smell that only locals can eat it. It is important to gauge the use of those terms because João dos Santos' work would be used by cartographers and naturalists throughout the eighteenth and the nineteenth centuries as the most important source on Eastern Africa. The knowledge produced through his African networks would have great influence on the shaping of European knowledge, due to the circulation of his work and his capacity of validating the information provided. Through the work of João dos Santos, for example, many African toponyms entered European cartography. Additionally, naturalists such as Georges Louis Leclerc, the count of Buffon, heavily relied on travel literature in their project classifying the world's nature.³⁷³

³⁷² Santos, *Etiópia oriental*, 223.

³⁷³ Buffon, George Louis Leclerc. *Histoire naturelle, générale et particulière, avec la description du Cabinet du Roi* (Paris: Imprimerie Royale, 1749-1767).

Reception

It is important to point out the later trajectory of *Etiópia oriental* in order to gauge its circulation and impact on knowledge production. After the publication in the Dominican Convent of Évora in 1609, we can already observe the first reception, for the author was sent back to Eastern Africa, given that the eleven years that he had spent there were mentioned, in the royal decision from 1611. Another text from 1618, by Francisco Avellar, demonstrates the work's circulation. Also a Dominican friar, he wrote, based on João dos Santos' work, a settlement plan for the Zambezi valley.³⁷⁴ In 1622, significant excerpts from *Etiópia oriental* were translated to Latin by Afonso de Sandoval, a translation that was made available to European erudite circles.³⁷⁵ A few years later, in 1625, it was also partially translated into English, by Samuel Purchas, in his *Hakluytus Posthomus or Purchas his Pilgrims*. Purchas was the successor of Richard Hakluyt, the famous travel-literature-compiler from Elizabethan England. These collections, as well as Giovanni Ramusio's *Navigazione et viaggi*, show the interest early modern Europe had in Portuguese information regarding the unknown world, which was expressed particularly through travel literature. At the end of the seventeenth century there would still be two French editions of João dos Santos would exist: the first published in 1684 by Gaétan Charpy, dedicated to Colbert, and widely circulated; the second one, from 1688, however - which remained an anonymous manuscript, was much more precise than the former, and was kept in the archives of French Ministry of Foreign Affairs.³⁷⁶

In the eighteenth century, despite not being reedited, dos Santos' work was still in use. Historian Júnia Furtado has shown that it was largely used by Enlightenment cartographer Jean Baptiste Bourguignon d'Anville, who accessed many Portuguese sources in collaboration with the Portuguese ambassador in Paris, D. Luís da Cunha, who participated in the negotiations of the border limits between Portuguese and Spanish America, and cultivated a project connecting the African colonies of Angola and Mozambique by land.³⁷⁷ At the end of the eighteenth century and the beginning of nineteenth century, it was also used by Scottish Enlightenment cartographer John Pinkerton, who translated and published some passages of the work in his *General Collection of the Best and most interesting Voyages and Travels in all Parts of the World*. This version was published in London between 1808 and 1814, with the title *History of Eastern Africa: Originally written in Portuguese*

³⁷⁴ Florence Pabiou-Duchamp, "João dos Santos: un dominicain portugais dans le Sud-Est africain" (PhD Diss., University of Paris Sorbonne – Panthéon 1, 2007), 171–73.

³⁷⁵ Ivana Muscalu, "Da boa guerra nasce a boa paz: a expulsão dos portugueses do planalto da Zambézia (1603–1695)," (PhD Diss., University of São Paulo, 2017), 138.

³⁷⁶ Pabiou-Duchamp, "João dos Santos," 173–75.

³⁷⁷ Júnia Furtado, *Quebra-cabeça africano* (Belo Horizonte: Miguelin; Odisséia, 2022).

language by the Reverend Father Joano dos Santos, for the order of St. Domingo, and published in Paris in the year of 1684. The title indicates the use of Gaétan Charpy's version in the translation.³⁷⁸

During the nineteenth century, the work was still consulted by researchers and explorers connected to geography societies, like David Livingstone and John Sutherland in his *Memoirs Respect the Kaffirs, Hottentots and Bosejmans of South Africa* (1845).³⁷⁹ Nevertheless, it was not reprinted, becoming a rare book, sold at elevated prices among bibliophiles and collectors. It would wait until the end of the century to be republished, both in Portuguese and English, in the context of the dispute between these two nations for the colonial division of Africa. The introduction and notes in the Portuguese edition of 1891 are evidence of that political context. Luciano Cordeiro, the editor, was the head of the Portuguese Geography Society and in his introduction, he attacks the greed of the British who want to erase Portuguese rights regarding the map of the "Dark Continent."³⁸⁰ Cordeiro also raises João dos Santos as a hero of Portuguese discoveries and regrets his being forgotten, indicating that at that time only three original editions of the Dominican's work remained available in Portugal. Despite already being used by the English, as Cordeiro's text makes clear, a new English edition was introduced in this context, in 1901, by George McCall Theal, a South-African missionary and British colonial official, in his massive work *Records of South-Eastern Africa* which compiled and translated sources.³⁸¹

In a very different context, another English edition came out in the twentieth century. *Etiópia Oriental* was again partially translated and published in 1962 by Freeman-Greenville in his *The East Africa Coast. Selected Documents from the First to the Earlier Nineteenth Century*. This was the context of the development, in the 1960s, of the History of Africa as an academic discipline. In the *General History of Africa*, published in those years with the support of UNESCO, dos Santos' work is substantially used in the chapters that concern the Eastern African coast and the Zambezi valley and plateau, mostly quoting the translations by McCall Theal and Freeman-Greenville. Portuguese historians would continue to work, even if scantily, with Cordeiro's edition, until 1989, when historian Luís de Albuquerque would edit and republish it in another collection of texts from the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries connected to Portuguese explorations and discoveries. This edition still presented problems such as changes in the order of the chapters and the removal of some passages. Ten years later, though, the first critical edition would appear in 1999, edited by historian Manuel Lobato, sponsored by the National Commission for Celebration of the

³⁷⁸ Pabiou-Duchamp, "João dos Santos," 173.

³⁷⁹ John Sutherland, *Memoirs respect the Kaffirs, Hottentots and Bosejmans of South Africa* (Cape Town: Pike & Philip, 1845).

³⁸⁰ Luciano Cordeiro, ed., *Etiópia Oriental e Varia História de Cousas Notáveis do Oriente* (Lisbon: Biblioteca dos Clássicos Portugueses, 1891), 7.

³⁸¹ George Mc Call Theal, *Records of South Eastern Africa* (Cape Town: C. Stuijk, 1964), 9 vols.

Portuguese Discoveries, which republished a plethora of texts and studies. This is the most recommended edition for research, although it still has some problems, for example the non-modernization of African words and toponyms, instead of the Portuguese ones. Finally, a last edition in French was done in the context of a PhD research project at University of Paris 1 – Panthéon Sorbonne, presented in 2007 by Florence Pabiou-Duchamp. This thesis resulted in another publication in French in 2011, edited by Pabiou-Duchamp, published by the Chandeigne publishing house, in a travel literature collection from the sixteenth to the eighteenth century. In a review of this edition, historian Thomas Vernet pointed out the potentialities of João dos Santos' work, observing that no other source before the end of eighteenth century can offer a such an expressive view on cultural exchanges in that region.³⁸²

³⁸² Thomas Vernet, "Ethiopia orientale. L'Afrique de l'Est et l'océan Indien au XVIe siècle. La relation de João dos Santos (1609)," *Journal des Africanistes sur le pas de Geneviève Calaume-Griaule* 85 (2011): 460.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is important to observe how the knowledge produced in the work of João dos Santos has reverberated from the time of its publication to present-day historiography. If that which is considered “modern science” originated in the “scientific revolution” of the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, when observing the nature of that knowledge and the material conditions of its production, one cannot assume it is a purely Western creation. In reality, that knowledge was produced through transcultural networks. However, it is not enough to identify the role of local informants, as if they were a passive information resource. When looking at the margins of negotiation and the local conditions of European presence in colonial territories, it is possible to identify local forms of agency and how those populations (“subaltern” at the level of representation) imprint their marks on the production of scientific knowledge. This led to hybrid forms of knowledge production, as this paper tried to demonstrate in the work of João dos Santos, where multiple forms of translations, mediations, misunderstandings take place, producing a diverse and heterogenous body of knowledge that is both African and European. While João dos Santos’ work on regional Eastern Africa history is widely known, it was generally used as a source of political history, and sometimes of the history of religion, his natural history descriptions are mostly ignored. This paper’s goal was to bring those accounts to the centre of our analysis, bringing up questions raised by recent perspectives on the history of science. Most importantly, we ought to unravel the many layers of representation contained in the Dominican’s narrative in order to understand the other voices and forms of local engagement contained in that writing.

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First Pādishāh Begum of the Mughal Empire: Āka-jānam Khānzādā Begum³⁸³

Unravelling the Veiled Histories of the Mughal Harem
by Analysing Literary and Visual Culture

CHANDINI JASWAL

Master student, Panjab University, India

Abstract

The history of India will be synonymous with the grandeur of the Mughals and their significant contributions to the social, political, economic and cultural aspects of India, which are widely acknowledged and well-regarded. Like many other dimensions of human sociocultural existence, however, the craft of history-writing has also been synonymous with “his-story”. While a plethora of research has been undertaken on the lives of the great Mughal emperors, little is known about the women behind their lives and the role the harem collectively played in the political dynamic of the Mughal empire. Through this essay, I attempt to provide a biographical account of one such veiled woman—Khānzādā Begum, the elder sister of Bābur, the first Mughal emperor. A few scholars who know about her sacrifice of leaving her homeland and getting married to the ‘enemy’, the Uzbek Chief, Shaybānī Khān, have rightly characterised it as a key factor in the establishment of Bābur’s empire. An even lesser-known fact is that when she returned from her ‘exile’ from the Uzbek land, Khānzādā played a significant role on the political scene of her brother’s empire. Although she never penned a memoir, Khānzādā was mentioned or discussed in various contemporary accounts written by members of her family. Using primary sources such as Bābur’s autobiography “Tūzūk-i Bābrī,” Gulbadan Begum’s memoir “Aḥvāl-i Humāyūn Pādshāh,” Mīrzā Ḥaydār’s “Tārīkh-i Rashīdī,” and Shaybānī Khān Uzbek’s “Shaybānīnamah” and by analysing paintings depicting her, I argue that even though Khānzādā was deeply respected by many people, she was systematically obliterated from the records of one of the most documented histories, namely, the Mughal Empire, possibly because her sacrifice became a source of humiliation to the royal court. In the second half of this essay, I indicate some reasons why the Mughal harem has become synonymous with promiscuity in popular thought by reviewing contemporary accounts written on the Mughal harem in the pre-modern period as well as current historiography. I demythologise the term “harem” itself and analyse how royal women subtly exercised their political ambitions from behind the veil of the harem — which was a product of their genius as individuals as well as their Timurid heritage.

³⁸³ An early version of this research has appeared as “Behind the First Great Mughal: Khanzada Begum” in the KMC Journal of Asia, 2022. I am grateful to Dr Ankur Barua, Senior Lecturer, University of Cambridge and Mrs Poonam Devasher, Former Head of Department, MCM DAV College, India, for reading the drafts of this paper. Thanks are also due to the reviewers at Carnival for their input and the participants of all conferences for their comments.

Keywords: Mughals – Khānzādā Begum – Harem – Visual Culture – Veiled History

Image 1: Genealogy of Khānzādā Begum (1748–1575).

Introduction: The Myth of the Harem

“For many,” Annemarie Schimmel writes in *The Empire of the Great Mughals: History, Art and Culture*, “The Taj Mahal, the lily-white mausoleum built by Shāh Jahān for his wife Mumtaz Mahal symbolises Mughal India, in fact, the whole of India.”³⁸⁴ Shāh Jahān, the distraught Mughal emperor, has become an eternal symbol of grief and the departed wife who had the “greatest symbol of love”³⁸⁵ built for her the ideal of a beloved companion from a bygone era — an image quite at odds with the role women played in the Mughal harem, the name ascribed to the secluded living quarters of the womenfolk of Muslim emperors and kings. A similar style of romanticisation applies to various other pre-modern Muslim dynasties. However, in many of these social contexts, princesses played a much more active role than simply sitting pretty within the comforts and luxury of the harem, a place which came to be regarded as a “sequestered, sexualised domain” for all the womenfolk of the emperor in the Western fantasy.³⁸⁶ Indeed, according to F. Mernissi, “After the

³⁸⁴ Annemarie Schimmel, *The Empire of the Great Mughals: History, Art and Culture* (London: Reaktion, 2004), 143.

³⁸⁵ “Taj Mahal: The Symphony of Love,” *Google Arts & Culture* accessed November 27, 2023, <https://artsandculture.google.com/story/taj-mahal-the-symphony-of-love/WAUxKuf8iRyglA>.

³⁸⁶ Reina Lewis, “The Harem: Gendering Orientalism,” in *Orientalism and Literature*, ed. Geoffrey P. Nash, 166.

Mongol invasion [under Genghis Khān], the thrones of Muslim states were occupied by an impressive number of women with privileges of the *Khuṭba*³⁸⁷ and the coining of money.”³⁸⁸

This, one must be mindful, was particularly true for the nomadic Mongols, and not their contemporaries in the Perso-Islamic world. As M. Szuppe observed, “Turco-Mongol nomadic cultural tradition³⁸⁹, as compared with Irano-Islamic customs of settled people, gave a much larger place to women's social and political activities and family blood ties on both paternal and maternal sides... Among the Mongols and Īl-khānids [of the thirteenth and fourteenth centuries] ... women were entitled to a share of war booty and had the right to participate in the *quriltay*, the all-Mongol assembly. Not only did they become regents of their minor sons, but also under certain circumstances, they could themselves lay claim to the throne. Even after Islamisation progressed among the Turco-Mongol tribes, women retained much of their social position.”³⁹⁰ For example, the Kutlugh-Khānid dynasty in Kimran, Persia. In the fourteenth century, this province was ruled by Kutlugh Khātūn (also called Turkhān Khātūn in some documents) and later by her daughter Pādishāh Khātūn (also mentioned as Safwat al-din Khātūn).³⁹¹

Beyond the Mongols, one finds examples of female leadership in the Arab world. In Yemen, after the advent of Islam, even though several women held political power, the names of Malika Asma and Malika ‘Arwa from the eleventh century stand out, for they alone enjoyed the unquestioned privilege of the head of state, namely, the *khuṭba* was proclaimed in their name in the mosques. Mernissi notes that no other “Arab women had this honour in any Arab country after the advent of Islam.”³⁹² Closer home, that is, in India, one is reminded of Raziya Sulṭān. A thirteenth-century ruler of the Mamlūk Dynasty of the Delhi Sulṭāns in Northern India, chosen purely on talent, her femininity became her greatest obstacle in ruling the Sultanate. So, she is said to assumed to discarded the “female attire” entirely — she sat in the open without a veil and wore the “trappings of masculinity” in body and spirit.³⁹³ No other instance of any lady Sulṭān in the Delhi Sultanate is found thereafter. Her successors, the Mughal princesses, though influential, did not go so far. The Mughals in India did not even have a woman installed as the *Pādishāh*, that is,

³⁸⁷ *Khuṭba*- Prayers which acknowledge the legitimate ruler of the kingdom uttered at the time of the weekly congregational Friday prayers. (See Richards, *The Mughal Empire*).

³⁸⁸ Fatima Mernissi, *The Forgotten Queens of Islam*. (Minneapolis: Univ. Minnesota Press, 2009), 99.

³⁸⁹ Dr Ankur Barua, in personal correspondence, noted that this relative form of greater independence and power enjoyed by the ‘nomadic’ Turko-Mongol women vis-à-vis the ‘settled’ Iranian women was also possibly true of women in “early” Vedic semi-nomadic milieus (c.1500 BCE), although not in “established” Vedic societies (c.200 CE).

³⁹⁰ Maria Szuppe, “Status, Knowledge and Politics: Women in Sixteenth Century Safavid Iran,” in *Women in Iran: From the Rise of Islam to 1800*, eds, Guity Nashat and Beck Lois, 141.

³⁹¹ Mernissi, *Forgotten Queens*, 99.

³⁹² Mernissi, *Forgotten Queens*, 123.

³⁹³ Alyssa Gabbay, “In Reality a Man: Sultan Iltutmish, His Daughter, Raziya, and Gender Ambiguity in Thirteenth Century Northern India,” *Journal of Persianate Studies*, 4 (January 2011): 1, 45- 63.

emperor (save perhaps Nūr Jahān, who, Ruby Lal claims acted as a co-sovereign with her husband Jahāngir (r.1505–1527 CE), the fourth Mughal emperor).³⁹⁴ Nonetheless, the harem played, from the outset of the Mughal empire, i.e. c.1500 CE, a significant role in its socio-political dynamics. The tradition of a strong female presence started with Bābur himself, the first Mughal emperor.

Zahiru'ddīn Muḥammad Bābur (1483–1530 CE) came from, what the fifteenth century Central Asia is regarded, as an enviable and distinguished lineage. A Timurid (descendant of Tīmūr) on his paternal side and a Chingissid (descendants of Chingis Khān) on his maternal side, Bābur was only eleven years old when he ascended the throne of Fergana (a valley in present-day Uzbekistan) in 1494 CE. His tender age was not the only problem; Bābur had inherited an extremely unstable empire. By the late fifteenth century, a struggle between members of three lineages - The Timurids, The Chaghatai Mongols and Uzbeks ensued over control of the *Mā warā' al-Nahr* (Transoxiana) region, once entirely under Tīmūr's son Shāhrukh (r.1407–1447), and which had by the 1490s been divided among these three political powers. To complicate matters, animosity brewed between the Timurids themselves. Bābur's father, Umar Shaykh Mīrzā (d.1494 CE) was one of the four brothers descended from Tīmūr's third son, MiranShāh. For Bābur, contestation also came from the Chaghatai Mongols, whose leader was his maternal uncle, Mahmud Khān (d.1509). However, the greatest threat to both the Timurids and Mongols came from Shaybānī Khān, the Chinggisid leader of the powerful Turko-Mongol Uzbek tribal confederacy who had originated in Qipchaq Steppe and had a stronghold in Merv [present-day Turkmenistan]. The Uzbeks had been raiding Timurid territories for decades before they began moving towards the principal Timurid territories in *Mā warā' al-Nahr* and Iranian Khorāsān, precisely when Bābur's reign began.³⁹⁵

In such a precarious political situation, the young Bābur was strongly guided by his maternal grandmother, Aisan Daulat Begum (d.1505 CE).³⁹⁶ A woman of extraordinary intellect, she acted as a regent to Bābur after his father died. She legitimised his accession when there were doubts about a mere boy being able to rule while the 'Uzbek threat' loomed large. Bābur acknowledges this influence in his "*Tūzūk*" (diary), also called the "Vaḡayī" (events):

"Few women were my maternal grandmother's equal in judgement and counsel. She was very wise and farsighted, and most of my affairs were conducted with her advice."³⁹⁷

³⁹⁴ See Ruby Lal, *Empress: The Astonishing Reign of Nūr Jahān* (Delhi: Penguin Viking, 2018).

³⁹⁵ See Stephen F Dale, *Babur: Timurid Prince and Mughal Emperor, 1483–1530*. (New Delhi: Cambridge University Press, 2018), 34–35.

³⁹⁶ Also spelled as 'Esan' Daulat Begum in some texts.

³⁹⁷ Dilip Hiro, ed., *Bābur Nama: Journal of Emperor Bābur*, translated by Annette Beveridge (Gurgaon: Penguin Books, 2006), 19–20.

A Mughal painting from the late sixteenth century commemorating the significant influence that the Aisan Begum enjoyed exists (see image 2). Note the body language of the main characters—Bābur (left) and his grandmother Aisan Daulat Begum (right). As opposed to the standard rules of gender, it is the young boy here who is sitting with his body slightly inclined— as if searching for his grandmother’s approval whilst the grandmother sits upright, her hand below her chin as if contemplating the final decision. Also, note the facial expressions of the women who surround them— who probably constituted the council of Aisan Daulat Begum— many weighing in on the discussion, some even contributing to it.

In this context, we should also note Bābur’s mother, Qutlugh Nigar Begum (d.1505 CE), who accompanied him on several campaigns across Timurid land and later into Hindūstān. However, the most underrated woman in Bābur’s harem was his elder sister Khānzāda Begum, who is today called the “First Lady of the Empire.”³⁹⁸ The most surprising aspect of Khānzāda’s life is how little is written or known about her even when her brother Bābur, most known for his autobiography and conquests, is one of the most studied personalities in an extensively discussed period of Indian history.³⁹⁹ No details about her birth and childhood exist except her birth year (1478 CE). This essay, built on a study of some primary and secondary sources, will trace her life from 1500 CE, that is when she was in her early twenties (since this is when a mention of her is first found) to her death in 1545 CE, and also present arguments as to why she has remained “veiled” to present-day historians despite her remarkable contributions to her brother’s empire. A separate section is devoted to understanding, critiquing and decoding the Mughal harem by discussing other women of the harem.

³⁹⁸ Schimmel, *The Empire of the Great Mughals*, 145.

³⁹⁹ Although, neither Bābur’s mother nor grandmother have yet been subjects of intense research, they still find due mention in contemporary records — their names are known and their contribution acknowledged. As Dilip Hero notes in the introduction to the *Tūzuk-i Bābrī* or the *Bāburnāma* (“Book of Babur”): “Women are conspicuous in the *Babur Nama* by their absence. Sure enough, they appear in the text as wives, grandmothers, aunts, concubines and slaves. But they are little more than shadowy figures — bar one: Babur’s maternal grandmother Aisan Daulat Begum ...” See Hiro “Introduction,” *Bābur Nama: Journal of Emperor Bābur*, xxxi.

Image 2: “Bābur Seeks His Grandmother’s Advice,”
painting from the *Baburnama*, ca. 1590–92 CE, 44 x
29,4 cm.

The Life of Khānzādā Begum (1478–1545 CE)⁴⁰⁰

A Narrative of Sacrifice and Exile

In 1500 CE, the seventeen-year-old king of Fergana seemed to have done the impossible: amidst intense political tension and competition, Bābur had somehow occupied the prized Tīmurid territory, Samarkand (a city in present-day Uzbekistan). However, this success was short-lived. Soon, Bābur was surrounded by the troops of “his greatest rival, the Uzbeks, led by the formidable Mohammed Shaybānī Khān.”⁴⁰¹ (See image 3) With no reinforcements or help, Bābur was at the Khān’s mercy. It is in these circumstances that we first hear of Khānzādā: for the vanquished Bābur was offered ‘peace’ only if his sister was betrothed to the Uzbek Chief.⁴⁰²

Image 3: Portrait of Muhammad Khan Shaibani, the Uzbek (d.1510), opaque watercolour and gold on paper, ca. sixteenth century.

⁴⁰⁰ Also spelled as ‘Khānzadeh’ Begum in some texts.

⁴⁰¹ Hiro, ed, *Bābur Nama*, xv.

⁴⁰² Dale mentions that this matrimonial alliance was accepted only after their mother Qutlugh Nigar Begum had approved. Although *Shaybānīnāma* calls it a “love-match,” Bābur’s fear of acknowledging this marriage can only be seen as a compromise for which Khānzādā paid. See Dale, *Babur*; Sunita Sharma “The Exponential Role of the Women Protagonists in the Formative Years of Babur — Linkages Revisited,” *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress*, 361–62.

Bābur's narrative is slightly different: "Umar Shaikh Mīrzā's eldest daughter was Khānzādā Begum, my full sister, five years older than me. When I had come to abandon Samarkand in 905 AH/1500 CE after a five-month siege by Mohammed Shaybānī Khān (Uzbek), she *fell* to him."⁴⁰³ It is certain that when the twenty-three-year-old Khānzādā "fell to the enemy," she was not an unmarried woman. In a separate entry, Bābur clearly notes: "As soon as Mohammed Shaybānī Khān Uzbek captured Herat, he took Muzaffar Mīrzā's wife, Khānzādā Begum...and married her, ignoring the *adat* [al-'idda: religious decree in Islam], according to which remarriage is unlawful within a certain period of divorce or widowhood."⁴⁰⁴

Shaybānī Khān also divorced his previous wife, Khānzādā's maternal aunt, Mihr Nigar Chaghatai, to marry Khānzādā. Together the couple had a son, Khurram Shāh (c.1501–12 CE).⁴⁰⁵ Dale argues that although Shaybānī Khān assured peace, Bābur did not believe in his word.⁴⁰⁶ Nonetheless, Khānzādā was still left behind with the "enemy" and the rest of Bābur's harem was allowed to leave the occupied city unharmed – a truce made possible only because of what I characterise as her "sacrifice" on the planes of realpolitik.

Against this historical backdrop, I argue that Bābur's silence about his sister's role in these peacemaking engagements in an otherwise lucid and detailed autobiography has nothing to do with women being *pardah-gīyan*.⁴⁰⁷ If that were the case, Bābur would not have specifically mentioned his grandmother Aisan Daulat Begum or his beloved wife Māham Begum either. Therefore, I read this silence as an indication of his embarrassment relating to his failure to protect his sister. While brothers are traditionally supposed to be protectors of their sisters, he offered his sister as a sacrificial goat for his and his clan's safety. As Mīrzā Ḥaydār, a cousin of Bābur, declares unequivocally: "Bābur Pādishāh gave up Khānzāda Begim in exchange for his own life and escaped."⁴⁰⁸

Sunita Sharma believes that Khānzāda had been treated well during her marriage to Shaybānī Khān owing to her highly respected Timurid lineage. However, Sharma calls this forced matrimony a "mismatch" owing to the couple's cultural differences and political animosity, causing

⁴⁰³ Hiro, ed, *Bābur Nama*, 12.

⁴⁰⁴ Hiro, ed, *Bābur Nama*, 184.

⁴⁰⁵ Khurram was entrusted with the territory of Balkh when he was about five years old (c.1505), he died at the age of twelve. See Sharma, "Exponential Role," 361–2.

⁴⁰⁶ Dale, *Babur*, 56.

⁴⁰⁷ As Mika Natif wrote, "The notion of invisibility and seclusion of Mughal ladies from the male eye due to *pardah* [veil] is related to their rank and status at the Mughal court." This began steadfastly with the reign of Akbar (r.1556-1605). *Pardeh-gīyan* meant both literal and metaphorical exclusion of women from public view. See Natif "Preliminary Thoughts on Portraits of Mughal Women in Illustrated Histories," in *Reflections of Mughal Art and Culture*, ed. Roda Ahluwalia, 45.

⁴⁰⁸ As quoted by Ira Mukhoty, *Daughters of the Sun: Empresses, Queens and Begums of the Mughal Empire*. (New Delhi: Aleph, 2018), 6. Mīrzā Ḥaydār, who wrote *Tārīkh-i Rashīdī*, was Bābur's cousin and was with him in Kabul. See Bamber Gascoigne, *A Brief History of the Great Moghuls* (London: Robinson, 2002), 250.

a lot of anxiety to Bābur and their mother, Qutlugh Nigar Begum. However, since no records devoted to Qutlugh Nigar Begum exist, it is difficult to gauge how she might have reacted to this matrimonial alliance.⁴⁰⁹

Reunion with Kinsmen

In one of the retellings of Khānzādā's life, Khānzādā is depicted as voluntarily deciding to stay back in Samarkand for her clan's safety. However, we will probably never know how she responded to this forced matrimony, because we do not have a memoir or diary of her.⁴¹⁰

Image 4: What the journey might have looked like, tracing Khānzādā's migration from 1500–1510 CE.

⁴⁰⁹ Sharma, "Exponential Role," 361–62.

⁴¹⁰ Here, I am specifically referring to a newspaper article in the Children's editorial. See, Pavithra Srinivasan, "Heroine's Tale," *The Hindu*, June 28, 2019, sec. "Children," <https://www.thehindu.com/children/heroines-tale/article28201559.ece>.

We hear of Khānzāda only a decade later when Bābur notes:

“In 916 AH/1510 AD, she was in Merv [Turkmenistan today] when Shāh Ismā'il [of Iran] defeated Shaybānī Khān Uzbek. For my sake, Shāh Ismā'il treated her well, giving her sufficient escort to Qunduz [Afghanistan today] where she rejoined me. When I went to see her, neither she nor those around her knew us, although I spoke. They recognised us after a time.”⁴¹¹ (see image 4)

Bābur notes that he learnt of the news of Shaybānī Khān's death when his Timurid cousin sent a messenger with the news also telling him that 20,000 Mongols – previously subjugated by the Uzbeks – had arrived in Qunduz. It is at this junction that Khānzāda Begum arrived in Qunduz. According to Azfar Moin, Shāh Ismā'il later used “this favour” he had done to Khānzāda, and her brother Bābur, to exact the latter's help in conquering Samarkand since Bābur was a Timurid, who was experienced and motivated in taking this important city in Transoxania. Bābur did deliver on this promise in 1511 CE albeit not very successfully, for he was able to occupy Samarkand only for a brief time before he was ousted again within a few months of his arrival.⁴¹²

This reunion has been captured in an imaginative portrait commissioned by Akbar, much after both Bābur and Khānzādā were dead (see image 5). According to Mehreen Chida-Razvi, this painting is one of the earliest representations of elite women in the Mughal court. While the figures lack “individualisation” – no unique facial features are drawn for any character in the painting (this artistic evolution, that is, the development of verisimilitude portraiture, happened under Jahāngir and continued under the patronage of his son Shāh Jahān⁴¹³) — it is the symbolic attributes that make this painting significant for our purposes in this essay. In a clear departure from the precedent set for royal paintings and portraits in Central Asia, it is not the emperor, but his sister who occupies the central stage. Khānzādā is depicted holding a commanding hand high in the air, while the rest sit around her reverently.

Her figure overshadows everyone else in size including her brother, the emperor Bābur — a clear acknowledgement of her sacrifice by the royal court and more significantly by her descendants.⁴¹⁴ Khānzādā Begum, now nearly thirty-three years old (considered middle-aged in the

⁴¹¹ Hiro, ed, *Bābur Nama*, 12.

⁴¹² Azfar Moin, *The Millennial Sovereign: Sacred Kingship and Sainthood in Islam*. South Asia across the Disciplines (New York: Columbia University Press, 2012), 84. Upon personal correspondence with Dr Moin, he further explained that the Shāh of Iran stood to benefit immensely from this favour he had done to Bābur, because the Safavids, like most Central Asian kingdoms at that time, worked mostly through vassal relationships, especially if this were to govern places far from their capital cities. Political alliance with Bābur, who had occupied Kabul by now and was looking to India as well as was clearly not strong enough to challenge the Safavids, was almost an ideal alliance.

⁴¹³ Mika Natif, *Mughal Occidentalism: Artistic Encounters between Europe and Asia at the Courts of India, 1580-1630* (Boston: Brill, 2018), 205-260.

⁴¹⁴ The comments about the size of figures in the portrait are my own. Comments by Chida-Razvi were taken from her lecture on “Women and the Arts at Mughal South Asia.”

Mughal era) returned as a twice-widowed lady. Shaybānī Khān, mistrustful of her loyalty, had divorced her within a couple of years of their marriage. Scholars argue that this divorce happened because the Begum overtly supported her brother in the Uzbek court. Nonetheless, Shaybānī Khān “gave her” (i.e. married her off) to another official in his court, Sayyid Hada.⁴¹⁵

Hada later died along Khān’s side in the Battle with the Shāh of Iran in 1510 CE. It was in the aftermath of this battle that Khānzādā returned to her brother aided by the Shāh of Iran. Soon after, Khānzādā was married again, and this time to Mahdī Khwāja, one of Bābur’s most trusted *begs* (noblemen) who had fought in the Battles of Panipat (1526 CE) and Khanwa (1527 CE) and was also made the commandant of Etawah and Bianah (towns in present-day Uttar Pradesh).

Image 5: Painting from the *Baburnama*, Ladies of the Court in an Encampment outside a Citadel, ca. 1590 CE, painted in watercolour on paper, 25,4 x 14 cm.

⁴¹⁵ Sharma, “Exponential Role,” 361.

According to Beveridge, Khānzādā could have been married to Khwāja anytime between 1510 and 1519 CE, a period of which no record is known to have survived, including the most important source on Khānzādā, her brother's diary, *Tūzūk-i-Bāburi*.⁴¹⁶ No information on progeny from this union exists.

Moreover, the future of this marriage is unclear because Khwaja had opted to leave Hindūstān for Kabul when Bābur permitted his nobles to do so after his decisive victory in 1527 CE.⁴¹⁷ However, it is certain that Khānzādā had not left Hindūstān with Khwaja. In a correspondence written in February 1529 CE, Bābur clearly states: "I have summoned my elder sister [Khānzādā] and wives to Hindūstān... Directly as this letter arrives, you must get [them] out of Kabul ..."⁴¹⁸

Image 6:
The Princes of the
House of Timur,
attributed to Mir
Sayyid Ali ca. 1550–
1555 CE, paint on
cotton, 108 x 108,5
cm.

⁴¹⁶ Hiro, ed., *Bābur Nama: Journal of Emperor Bābur*, 12.

⁴¹⁷ There is some confusion among historians over the nobles Khānzādā married. Dale argues that Sayyid Hada was Khānzādā's second husband and Mahdī Khwāja her third. (See Dale "Bābur," 96; 156). Sharma believes that Khānzādā was married to Mahdī Khwāja when she was betrothed to Shaybānī Khān and that on her return the marriage was renewed. See Sharma "Exponential Role," 361. However, in Beveridge's *Bāburnama* the first husband mentioned is one "Muzaffar Mīrzā." See Beveridge, (1902), 1.

⁴¹⁸ Hiro, ed, *Bābur Nama: Journal of Emperor Bābur*, 327-328.

Rise to Power and Later Years

Khānzādā's return to the harem⁴¹⁹ was not deeply contested or stigmatised. On the contrary, she was held in the highest esteem. In the winter of 1530 CE, when Bābur knew his end was near, he had asked Khānzādā to arrange marriages for his daughters, Gulrang Begum and Gulchira Begum, instead of the girls' mother (i.e., Dildār Begum) or his favourite wife Māhim Begum. Bābur was succeeded by Humāyūn in 1530 CE. It was in 1532/33 CE, about twenty-two years after her return, Khānzādā became the first "Pādīshāh Begum," the principal lady of the palace of her nephew and the second Mughal Emperor, Humāyūn (1508–56 CE). As Pādīshāh Begum, Khānzādā arranged for celebratory feasts (called *tüy*)- a Timurid symbolic tradition through which senior women in the harem exhibited their influence and authority.⁴²⁰

Khānzādā steered the celebrations for the wedding of her nephew Hindāl (*tüy-i Mīrzā Hindāl*) in November 1533 CE.⁴²¹ Hindāl's bride, Sulṭānim, the younger sister of her third husband, Mahdī Khwāja, who was now Khānzādā's sister-in-law, had been under Khānzādā's care since she was two years old. Gulbadan Begum, Bābur's daughter, writes about her aunt in her memoir titled *Aḥvāl-i Humāyūn Pādīshāh*⁴²² in these terms:

"Āka-jānam had taken care of Sulṭānim as though she were her child... Khānzādā Begum gave everything she had collected, and she arranged a feast such as had not been made for any other child of my royal father. She planned it all and carried it all out."⁴²³

⁴¹⁹ Harem, an anglicisation of the Arabic term "haram" (tr. a sanctuary), was a space where the womenfolk of the emperors and ruling elite lived. The harem was a residence to their wives, sisters, mothers, daughters as well as concubines and the maidservants. The space of the harem was sacred and only the ruler/noble or those men he most trusted were allowed access. Interestingly, especially in India, the practice of sequestering the women, i.e. establishing the harem, was also adopted by the non-Muslim nobles and provincial rulers. It must be noted that the connotations of the Arabic "haram" is markedly different from the English "harem" — which has evolved over centuries to become synonymous with scandal, especially for the "Gunpowder Empires": the Mughal Padshahs of India, the Safavid Shahs of Iran and the Ottoman Sultans of Turkey. For a detailed discussion about the Mughal Harem and the evolution of its meaning, see page 110 of this article.

⁴²⁰ *Tüy* (or *tooy*): A Central Asian-Timurid institution observed by the Early Mughals was a celebration to mark important events like weddings or circumcision where patrons provided food and entertainment over several days followed by games. See Ebba Koch, *Planetary King: Humayun Padshah, Inventor and Visionary on the Mughal Throne*. (Ahmedabad: Mapin Publishing, 2022), 125.

⁴²¹ There is some discrepancy amongst scholars about the date of Hindāl's wedding. Koch (2022) notes that it is November 1533, whereas Parodi (2007) dates it to 1534. I am using the date mentioned in the most recent publication, i.e. the one by Koch. See Koch, *Planetary King*, 125 and Laura Parodi "Of Shaykhs, Bībīs and Begims," 7, 13, 18.

⁴²² The *Aḥvāl-i Humāyūn Pādīshāh*, also called *Humāyūnnāma* ("the Book of Humāyūn") was written by Gulbadan Begum (d. 1603 CE), the third daughter of Bābur. It is the first female-authored account of life at the Mughal Court. R. Gould notes, "Although best classed as historiography, the *Book of Humāyūn* is a genre-crossing historiographic memoir. It dwells not on battles and royal genealogies, as did its male-authored predecessors, but rather on domestic scenes of birth, death, anger, love, and other aspects of daily life, especially as experienced by women." See Rebecca Gould, "How Gulbadan Remembered: The *Book of Humāyūn* as an Act of Representation". *Early Modern Women: An Interdisciplinary Journal* 6, 186-187.

⁴²³ Hiro, ed, *Bābur Nama*, 125-126.

Gulbadan gives a detailed list of the lavish gifts Khānzādā presented to the couple which included nine sets each of jewellery, shawls, robes, handkerchiefs, towels, cushions, horses with jewelled saddles, parasols, slaves of Ethiopian, Circassian, Turkish descent, and so on. The inauguration of the Mystic Palace⁴²⁴ (*tūy kbāna-i tilsim*), built in Agra on the banks of river Yamuna happened around the same time as Hindāl's wedding. This inauguration was celebrated before the wedding: this procedure does not seem to follow protocol but was a decision entirely in Khānzādā's hands – this is another indication of the significant authority she enjoyed. Ebba Koch in her most recent scholarship describes the seating arrangement in detail:

“At both festivals [inauguration and wedding reception], the main gathering took place in the first octagonal hall [of the Mystical Palace in Agra] ... In the vestibule (*pīshgāh khānā*) of the central octagonal hall, Humāyūn sat with his aunt Khānzādā Begum on a gem-studded throne (*takht-i-murassa*) ...”⁴²⁵

The authority to answer questions as who organised the feast, who sat closer to the *Pādishāh*, the order of the feasts, etc., reflected one's seniority in the harem. Although Koch notes that Khānzādā had presided over the celebrations in place of Māhim Begum (Humāyūn's birth mother and Bābur's chief queen) who had died in May 1533, this was probably because Māhim had adopted and raised the groom, Hindāl, just as Khānzādā had raised Sulṭānim and not because the former held any precedence over the latter. Khānzādā had probably been declared “*Pādishāh Begum*” during Māhim's lifetime. The dynamic becomes clearer on close reading of Gulbadan's memoir. In this conversation between the Emperor and the Begum over scheduling the feasts (as recorded by Gulbadan), note how Khānzādā helms the entire discussion — subtly overpowering the Emperor, Humāyūn, himself:

“Dearest lady (Khānzādā Begum) said to his Majesty [Humāyūn]: ‘When will you make Mīrzā Hindāl's marriage feast?’ His Majesty replied: ‘B’ismu-l-lah.’ When Mīrzā Hindāl was married, my lady (Māhim) was living, but there was a delay in arranging the feast.

According to Ruby Lal, the original memoir uses the word “Akum,” which has wrongly been translated by Annette Beveridge as “My lady” or “Dearest Lady” in her translated works. Lal argues that ‘Akum’ was a more personal term of address than that. See Ruby Lal, “Historicizing the Harem,” 601.

In her most recent scholarship, Ebba Koch furthers this argument and states that Gulbadan called Khānzādā by the same epithet as her father Bābur – since *Āka-jānam* was probably a Turkish title for “my elder sister.” See Koch, “Planetary King,” 125.

⁴²⁴ The Mystic or Talismanic Palace is called “the most intriguing of Humāyūn's inventions.” Khwandamir, a chronicler in Humāyūn's reign refers to it as “pleasing palace” and “delightful palace” — its reconstruction has proven difficult. Abu'l Fazl, Akbar's court chronicler never mentions the palace probably because its layout was too “eccentric” for him. It was possibly devoted to Humāyūn's occult interests. For a detailed discussion of its architecture, see Koch, *Planetary King*, 123–37.

⁴²⁵ Koch “Planetary King,” 125.

(Khānzādā Begum) said: ‘The things for the Mystic Feast are also ready. Let us first celebrate this, and afterwards Mīrzā Hindāl’s.’ His Majesty said: ‘Let whatever my royal aunt wishes be done.’ She replied: ‘May God bless it and make it good.’⁴²⁶

Even though no painting commemorating Hindāl’s wedding or inauguration of the Mystic Palace exists, in the painting titled *The Princes of the House of Timur* (see image 6), one of the few paintings commissioned and painted in Humāyūn’s reign depicts a celebration in motion. Although, it was severely overpainted under subsequent Mughal emperor to include their likeness, for the purpose of this essay, the original setting and roles are crucial. Originally titled “Humāyūn’s Garden Party,” it depicts a reception by Humāyūn for his closest followers, as indicated by the characteristic headgear worn by Humāyūn and his guests — the *Tāj - i ‘Izzat*, a hallmark for special favour in Humāyūni court. Note the seating arrangement — sitting in the garden pavilion, Humāyūn now faces three of his descendants — Akbar, Jahāngir, Shāh Jahān all added in the seventeenth century. Also note the elaborate cooking arrangements in the background, helmed by servants in Central Asian clothes.⁴²⁷ Dating this unnamed celebration depicted has proven difficult, however, if this celebration were organised under Humāyūn before 1545, it would undoubtedly be organised by Khānzādā.

Her most significant political contribution, however, was her mediation between her warring nephews. In the 1540s, when Kāmṛān and Askari had rebelled against their brother Humāyūn, it was Khānzādā who the *Pādīshāh* (Humāyūn) had requested to intervene. Ruby Lal gives a detailed description of this episode: “Khānzadeh Begum travelled from Jun to Kandahar.... Kāmṛān urged [Khānzādā] to have the *Khuṭba* read in his name. She advised him as follows: ‘As His Majesty (*Firdaus-makāmī*) [Bābur] decided and gave his throne to Emperor Humāyūn, and as you, all of you, have read the *Khuṭba* in his name till now, so now regard him as your superior and remain in obedience to him.’⁴²⁸ Such was her authority within the harem that when Kāmṛān had approached Dildār Begum (Bābur’s widow, Hindāl and Gulbadan’s mother, Kāmṛān’s stepmother and a highly respected figure in the Mughal court) with the same request, that is, to have the *Khuṭba* read in his own name, Dildār Begum promptly asked him to convince Khānzādā first.

According to L. Balabanlilar, this intervention was ultimately unsuccessful. Nonetheless, Khānzādā, apparently for her unflinching support for Humāyūn, was appointed as the ambassador

⁴²⁶ Gulbadan Begum, *The History of Humāyūn: Humāyūn-nama*, translated by Annette S. Beveridge (London: Royal Asiatic Society, 1902), 117–118.

⁴²⁷ Crill Rosemary and Kapil Jariwala, *The Indian Portrait: 1560-1860* [Exhibition, London, National Portrait Gallery, 11 March-20 June 2010] (Ahmedabad: Mapin publishing, 2010), 50.

⁴²⁸ Ruby Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2005), 61.

of the territory between Kandahar and Sindh, shortly before her death.⁴²⁹ Indeed, according to Sharma, Khānzādā was “the first woman from the Mughal dynasty [who was] entrusted with the official diplomatic task. The trend set by her was followed in later times.”⁴³⁰

According to Gulbadan’s memoir, when the Mughals had to flee from their Empire after Shēr Shāh Suri took over in 1540 CE, unlike the other harem inmates who had chosen relatively safer places like Lahore or Sindh, Khānzādā had chosen to follow Humāyūn who was on the run from the Afghani Shāh. Perhaps a last act of bravery, the sixty-seven-year-old Khānzādā travelled from Sindh to Kandhar to negotiate safe passage for Humāyūn through the Safavid territories. She probably died soon after, because Beveridge notes that Khānzādā died at Qabal-Chak [Kandahar?], “after a life full of sorrows and chagrin” in 1545 CE.⁴³¹ Parodi mentions that Khānzādā died at Gilchak [Qabal-chak] while accompanying Humāyūn on his way to Kabul (she had been sent by Kāmṛān as a mediator).⁴³² According to Misra, “except Khānzādā Begum, there does not seem to be any other lady who played any significant role in contemporary politics during the reign of Humāyūn.”⁴³³ Today, this powerful woman lies buried along with her brother Bābur, nephew Hindāl and niece Gulbadan in the *Bagh-i Bābur* (Gardens of Bābur) in Kabul, Afghanistan; with Khānzādā buried on a higher terrace, reserved for female burials.⁴³⁴ The *Bagh-i Babur* continued to be used as a cemetery for select members of the Timurid family long afterwards.

How “Feminist” was Khānzādā Begum? - A Discussion

Upon discussion about Khānzādā, a question I have commonly encountered from discussants is that if she was indeed empowered to officiate on certain public occasions, why did she not step out of a system founded on various types of androcentric presuppositions? Why did she not become independent, instead choosing to remain “veiled” behind the emperors — her brother and later her nephew?

⁴²⁹ Lisa Balabanlilar, “The Begims of the Mystic Feast: Turco-Mongol Tradition in the Mughal Harem,” *The Journal of Asian Studies* 69, no. 1. (2010), 133. According to Gulbadan, this appointment was made ‘for her service of peace between Kāmṛān and Humāyūn, after the latter had returned from his Persian exile (1545)’. See Hiro, *Bābur Nama: Journal of Emperor Bābur*, 34) Interestingly, Ebba Koch notes that when Humāyūn succeeded to the throne, he faced opposition from a high-ranking amir who wanted Mahdī Khwāja, Khānzādā’s third husband to become the next *Pādīshāh*! However, we find no mention of Khānzādā supporting her husband’s succession to the throne. See Koch, “Planetary King,” 31.

⁴³⁰ Sharma, “Exponential Role,” 362.

⁴³¹ Hiro, ed, *Bābur Nama*, 251.

⁴³² A reverse mediation tactic seems to be in play here: it seems as if Khānzādā now [ie in 1544–45] mediated for Kāmṛān, who had inherited the Kabul region. Humāyūn, who had lost the throne of Hindūstān by now to Shēr Shāh, probably desired that his brother hand over Kabul to him, which Kāmṛān refused — just three years after he had reluctantly settled in Kabul — wanting to become *Pādīshāh* instead. See Parodi “of Shaykhs, Bībīs and Begims,” 131.

⁴³³ Rekha Misra, *Women In Mughal India 1526-1748* (Delhi: Munshiram Manoharlal Publishers, 1967), 20.

⁴³⁴ Gascoigne, *The Great Moghuls*, 32. Gascoigne wrongly mentions, “two of his [Bābur’s] children Hindāl and Khānzādā are buried nearby ...” Whereas it should have been sister and son or “Hindāl” and “Gulbadan.”

Scholars in the field of women's studies often encounter questions of this type. The scholarly exercise of retrieving the voices of women such as Khānzādā may be categorised as “feminist history,” but this description would be problematic — not only since the English word “feminism” originated sometime during the nineteenth century, but also because the European sociocultural frames from within which it emerged were significantly different from those of Mughal India.

Certainly, women have been marginalised in societies everywhere—be it in the past or the present. However, unlike in some Western social contexts, where feminists have taken the radical step of criticising marriage as an institution, sometimes even calling for its abolition, the case in contemporary India is different.⁴³⁵ For instance, in some rural settings, women who “rebelled,” by eloping with lovers despite being married, were not hunted down or killed upon being caught but were re-absorbed into the social network after an elaborate “purification” process — her “bad behaviour” attributed to the machinations of an “evil spirit.” This way, the system could continue without its cracks bursting open.⁴³⁶

A popular female reaction against social oppression emerged in the voice of Mirabai, a Rajput princess who did not obey her husband or immolate herself on his funeral pyre, but, adopting the simple lifestyle of a widow, intermingled with some male saints. According to R. Varghese, she resisted the norms that “limit a woman to her role as a domesticated woman, a silent woman...The Mira, who spoke, became the collective voice of the marginalised after she was popularised through literary renditions” —Mirabai's social trajectories indicate some possibilities of opposition available to elite women in north-western India in the sixteenth century.⁴³⁷

In both cases, India or Europe, some women have indeed exercised their their agential capacities in various settings – however, if we were to view Khānzādā from the “premodern” Mughal Empire as “feminist” in its literal, dominant sense, without contextualising the term, we may be disappointed or disillusioned. The significations of the term “feminism” can vary significantly across the field of critical feminist theory, and it should not be applied uncritically to past epochs or non-European social milieus.⁴³⁸ However, feminism is not the only European idea

⁴³⁵ Clare Chambers, “Feminism, Liberalism and Marriage,” (previously “Recognising Marriage as a Symbolic Institution,” unpublished paper, Brown University, 2013) accessed May 12, 2024, <https://www.brown.edu/Research/ppw/files/Feminism,%20Liberalism%20and%20Marriage.doc>.

⁴³⁶ I am thankful to Dr Priyatosh Sharma, Head of Dept of History, Panjab University, India for sharing this insight into rural social culture and practices from his fieldwork in the hills of Northern India.

⁴³⁷ Ritu Varghese, “Mirabai in Popular Imagination: Reading Bhakti Canon in Contemporary Context,” *Artha Journal of Social Sciences* 19, no. 2 (2020): 74. It should be noted that Mira was indeed a Rajput princess who had rebelled. However, most of the stories/legends now ascribed to her in popular thought have transformed her into a literary tradition — the coalescing rebellion of several women in sixteenth-century North-West India.

⁴³⁸ Here, it is important not to essentialise “feminism.” There is a wide spectrum of feminist standpoints in contemporary critical studies. According to *some* of these standpoints, Khānzādā was sufficiently feminist for her times.

which should not be superimposed onto Mughal India; likewise, we should not unreflectively project our contemporary notions of “secularism,” “toleration,” and “orthodoxy” onto the reign of emperors such as Akbar, Aurangzeb, and others.⁴³⁹ Thus, in our case, the expectation that a Mughal princess would openly revolt against a patriarchal system would be far-fetched — this is not to say that Khānzādā was not capable of doing so, but simply that such a rejection was not required of a woman of her time. She had readily been accepted back into the court despite her “tainted past” of being married to the “enemy” and she enjoyed a very comfortable and powerful position within the social space of the harem.

This exploration of the meanings of feminism leads us to another significant question: if the harem was an important social arena where some women exercised their prestige and authority, what factors are responsible for the notoriety one popularly associates with the harem today? To understand Khānzādā’s achievements, demythologising the harem becomes important and to do so, one must, at this juncture, step back from Khānzādā’s life and analyse the harem and its prejudices as a whole.

Demythologising the Harem

Interrogating the Prejudices: “Haram” vs “Harem”

In one of the few academic studies on the Mughal harem, note how the scholar describes the space of the harem:

“The Mughal harem conjures up a vision of a sequestered place ensconcing beautiful female forms in mysterious magnificence. It was indeed made so by the great Mughal Emperor Akbar ... He brought in a large number of inmates to adorn it. He provided them all kinds of luxuries and made elaborate arrangements for their seclusion and security...The inmates of the harem dressed well, ate well and tried to enjoy as possible...Elder ladies would not have shared with the young ones their problems of life or secrets of love; talk about sex was taboo for the young in the medieval world ... Still, let us say that the young girls were not exposed to all the celebrations in the Mahal in which sex orgies dominated or the master bargained for beauty and love on occasions like Nauroz and Khushroz ... Naturally, every lady of consequence tried to win the master’s undivided love and openly competed to gain ascendancy in the harem. Women’s beauty gave them power as undefined as unique.”⁴⁴⁰

⁴³⁹ Richard Maxwell Eaton, *The Lotus & the Lion: Essays on India’s Sanskrit & Persianate Worlds* (Delhi: Primus Books, 2022).

⁴⁴⁰ KS Lal, *The Mughal Harem* (New Delhi: Aditya Prakashan, 1988), 19,135.

For another scholar notes:

“Noble households were divided into the external, more public areas, dominated by men, and the interior, secluded space reserved for women ... The wives, concubines, and female relatives of the *master* were ranked by seniority, blood ties and favour in a strictly prescribed hierarchy. Ideally, the harem provided a respite, a retreat for the nobleman and his closest male relatives — a retreat of grace, beauty, and order designed to refresh the males of the household.”⁴⁴¹

Even though Nath cautions his readers in his work *Private Life of the Mughals of India* that “It is a general misconception that every woman of the Mughal *harem* served a sexual purpose ...”⁴⁴² The promiscuity that is generally associated with the harem (apparent also in the title of this work), is also visible here, for Nath notes that:

“... it goes to the credit of the Mughals that they could manage their harem efficiently... It was Akbar who founded the customs, traditions and institutions which guided and regulated the course of Mughal life and culture ... Though Akbar never indulged in excessive sex, he had a taste for young beautiful women whose company he liked ... Jehangir was a sensuous person and he excessively indulged in both wine and women ...”⁴⁴³

As Ruby Lal remarks in the introduction of her pioneering work on the Mughal Harem, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, “This account might be dismissed as the view of a somewhat traditional historian, were its assumptions not so widely and consistently shared.”⁴⁴⁴ Harem, an anglicisation of the Arabic term “haram” that means “a sanctuary,” it is also related to the word “harim,” meaning female members of the family and “haraam” meaning forbidden.⁴⁴⁵ However, the connotations of the Arabic “haram” is markedly different from the English “harem” — which has evolved over centuries to not only refer to a secluded building occupied by elite Muslim women shielded from the public, but has also notoriously become synonymous with scandal – a place where a promiscuous “Emperor was surrounded by thousands of nubile young women competing for his attention.”⁴⁴⁶

The origin of “harem” can be dated to the late sixteenth and the early seventeenth century — this was the time of significant internal and external developments. Internally, the Mughals had begun consolidating their power in India, their residence became “more permanent” and even

⁴⁴¹ John F Richards, *The Mughal Empire* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 1993), 61–62.

⁴⁴² Ram Nath, *Private Life of the Mughals of India (1526 - 1803 A. D.)* (New Delhi: Rupa, 2005), 19.

⁴⁴³ Ram Nath, *Private Life of the Mughals of India (1526 - 1803 A. D.)* (New Delhi: Rupa, 2005), 11, 19, 28, 29.

⁴⁴⁴ Ruby Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2005), 2.

⁴⁴⁵ Jonathan Gil Harris, *The First Firangis: Remarkable Stories of Heroes, Healers, Charlatans, Courtesans & Other Foreigners Who Became Indian* (New Delhi: Aleph Book Company, 2015), 152.

⁴⁴⁶ Ira Mukhoty, *Daughters of the Sun: Empresses, Queens and Begums of the Mughal Empire* (New Delhi: Aleph, 2018), xi.

though the women became restricted to the secluded quarters of their harem, this did not alter their importance or role in imperial traditions like the *tüy*.⁴⁴⁷ Simultaneously, this was also the time when the West began taking an increasing interest in India: missionaries and travellers flocked to the “Moghul Empire” in large numbers and constituted the first of the “eye-witness accounts” of India. The “Harem” particularly had caught their fancy since it was veiled from the public. For example, an English merchant William Finch (d.1613) imagined Jahāngir in the harem “like a cock of the game... where he may crow over all.”⁴⁴⁸ In another instance, Father Rudolf Aquaviva, one of the Jesuit missionaries from Italy, who had tried albeit unsuccessfully to convert Akbar to Christianity wrote letters back home explaining the reasons of his failure, one of which was:

“He [Akbar] has so many hobbies and at least a hundred wives...Part of the time he spends with the numerous women he keeps in his house, so that he has no time available to care for what is of consequence to him ...”⁴⁴⁹

Thus, the failure to convert was blamed at the emperor’s weakness of character, women being one among several reasons responsible. Here, one must remember that the focus for the missionaries was propagation of Christianity, and not the harem, thus comments about women appear hurried and indiscriminate. No effort was made, for example, by the missionaries to contextualise Akbar’s “hundred wives” — a product of fostering political unions to win allies in expanding the Mughal Empire, than for pleasure. As M. Moneta remarks, “European [witnesses] were not inclined or able to decipher the contents and values of this [Mughal] civilisation...and failing in their attempts to impose their own ideas, they (especially the missionaries) soon developed a superior attitude ...”⁴⁵⁰ As a final case study, note how Francisco Pelseart, a Dutch merchant, who travelled to India in early seventeenth century, described the Mughal harem:

“Their mahals [harem] are adorned internally with lascivious sensuality, wanton and reckless festivity, superfluous pomp, inflated pride, and ornamental daintiness ...”⁴⁵¹

Most of these assumptions were based largely on market gossip since seldom were stranger men allowed into royal women’s residences. Only the most trusted European physicians (only two - Nicolò Manucci and François Bernier) working in the mid-eighteenth century, were allowed on rare occasions to treat the royal women. Manucci, who worked as a physician in the Mughal court

⁴⁴⁷ Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, 22.

⁴⁴⁸ As quoted by Gil Harris, *The First Firangis*, 153.

⁴⁴⁹ As quoted by Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, 33.

⁴⁵⁰ Marco Moneta, *A Venetian at the Mughal Court: The Life and Adventures of Nicolò Manucci* (Gurugram: Vintage, an imprint of Penguin Random House, 2021), xi.

⁴⁵¹ As quoted by Nath, “Private Life,” 30.

in the late seventeenth century, describes the procedure of tending to the women of the harem in detail, how he was never allowed to see his royal patients:

“I did my utmost to get an examination before I began the treatment. Mohammedans are very touchy in the matter of allowing their women to be seen, or even touched by the hand; above all, the lady being of royal blood, it could not be done without express permission from the king ...”⁴⁵²

Even the seemingly “first-hand” witnesses did not have access to the harem to properly be able to view and study its culture. This lack of access did not stop Manucci and others from commenting on the lifestyle of the harem. Thus, the description of the harem so offered is disapproving and sometimes even titillating:

“Some of the women in the harem, being shut up with this closeness and constantly watched, and having neither liberty nor occupation, think of nothing but adorning themselves. Their minds dwell on nothing but malice and lewdness... There are some who from time to time affect the invalid, simply that they may have the chance of some conversation with, and have their pulse felt by, the physician ... The latter stretched out his hand inside the curtain; they lay hold of it, kiss it, and softly bite it ...”⁴⁵³

Some of these accounts later formed the basis of the earliest history books penned by British colonial writers in the nineteenth century.⁴⁵⁴ This is precisely how paintings like the one drawn by Stifter (see image 7) who had not have even travelled to India, let much alone visited a harem, gained currency and legitimacy in popular European imaginations. Scholars believe that much of current-day prejudice springs from the European and Orientalist perspectives — reiterated and repeated so often in traditional histories of India (as in the three excerpts from books written in late twentieth century), that they were accepted as the truth. As Jonathan Gil Harris aptly remarks in his work, *The First Firangis*: “What exactly is the harem? Perhaps the most accurate answer is that it is a space of western fantasy ... The space of the has morphed into something rather different in the Western Imagination than what it was in reality.”⁴⁵⁵

⁴⁵² As quoted by Moneta, “Venetian at the Mughal Court,” 79.

⁴⁵³ As quoted by Moneta, “Venetian at the Mughal Court,” 91–92.

⁴⁵⁴ For example, James Mill writes in his well-known *The History of British India* (1815), “It is not surprising, that grossness, in idea and language, respecting the intercourse of the sexes, a uniform concomitant of the degraded state of the women ...” or Stanley Lane-Poole writes in *Aurangzib* (1893): “His [Shāh Jahān] favourite wife [Mumtaz Mahal], the lady of the Taj, had died in 1631, in giving birth to their fourteenth child and her husband had centred his affection upon his eldest daughter, Jahanara, with so much fervour as to cause no little scandal, while he also denied himself none of the more transitory joys of the zenana ...” For a more detailed discussion on the European perspective on the Mughal harem, see Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, 25–49.

⁴⁵⁵ Gil Harris, *The First Firangis*, 152.

Image 7: *In the Harem*, attributed to Moritz Stifter, ca. 1890, oil on panel, 33 x 40,7 cm.

Image 8: *Birth of Prince Salim*, attributed to Bishandas, ca. 1620, ink, colour, gold and silver on paper, 38.9 × 29 cm.

Decoding the "Real" Harem

Now that we have established that the harem, contrary to some colonial tropes, was a dynamic space (called *Mahal* in the Mughal period), it is also important to note that it was not entirely devoid of controversies. The task of decoding these intricacies is especially difficult owing to the meagre first-hand sources available to us: Gulbadan Begum's memoir *Aḥvāl-i Humāyūn Pādshāh*, being the only exception until now.

Scholars believe that harem was instituted under the Mughals only after Akbar, the third Mughal emperor, ascended the throne. Nath argues that the peripatetic residences of the first two Mughal emperors, Bābur and Humāyūn, made of tents and ravaged by poverty⁴⁵⁶, did not technically qualify as a harem: not just because the number of women who cohabitated with the emperors was much smaller, also because during their reigns "harem" was a technical term for a stationary and ordered institution which was governed by rules and officers.⁴⁵⁷ These peripatetic women's quarters were in line with the "Timurid" way of living, which the Mughals, especially, Bābur and Humāyūn, had "clung on to relentlessly."⁴⁵⁸ A vivid description of the Timurid living space by Ruy Gonzales de Calvijo, a Castilian envoy to Tīmūr's court in 1404, gives us an idea of the luxurious encampments that the womenfolk of Tīmūr lived in, which the Mughals, as direct descendants had inherited:

"... [there] is erected an awning of many coloured silk cloth: this shades the door, and prevents the sun from shining on any one at the place of entrance: further this awning can be moved about to face this way or that, and so keep the sun's rays from falling within the tent. Of these two great Enclosures with many tents within them is that belonging to the chief wife of Tīmūr, who is known as the Great Khānum or Lady, while that second Enclosure belongs to his second wife who is called the Kuchik-Khānum, meaning the Little Lady ... All of these Enclosures were occupied either by the wives of Tīmūr, or by the wives of his grandsons, and these princes and princesses have their abode therein, as does also his Highness likewise, both summer and winter."⁴⁵⁹

⁴⁵⁶ For example, in the aftermath of the Battle of Chausa, fought between Humāyūn and Shēr Shāh in 1539, as Humāyūn fled for his life, his eight-year-old daughter Aqiqa Sultan Begum drowned and three of his wives went missing. See Laura E. Parodi, "Of Shaykhs, Bibīs and Begims: sources on early Mughal marriage connections and the patronage of Babur's tomb," *Mediaeval and Modern Iranian Studies: Proceedings of the 6th European Conference of Iranian Studies (Vienna, 2007)*, eds. Maria Szuppe, Anna Krasnowolska and Claus Pedersen, *Cahiers de Studia Iranica* 45 (2011), 128.

⁴⁵⁷ Nath, *Private Life*, 25-26. Kishori Saran Lal also attributes the small size of the Harem to their nomadic and short reigns. See Kishori Saran Lal, *The Mughal Harem* (New Delhi: Aditya Prakashan, 1988), 19-20.

⁴⁵⁸ Balabanlilar, "The Begims of Mystic Feast," 127.

⁴⁵⁹ Ruy González de Clavijo, *Embassy to Tamerlane: 1403-1406* (London: Routledge Curzon, 2005), 127-128.

In these luxurious garden encampments, the Timurid begums hosted elaborate feasts, drank alcohol in mixed groups with men and wore the “thinnest of gauzes” that allowed the observer to clearly see their features.⁴⁶⁰

Thus, the respect that the Mughal harem enjoyed was also unique to their heritage. Scholars have repeatedly stressed on the Timurid tradition making it possible for women to be independent in the Mughal harem. As Balabanlilar notes, “even through the stable and highly institutionalised years of the Mughal seventeenth century, at a time when the public roles of their contemporaries, Ottoman and Safavid dynastic women, were becoming increasingly limited and narrow, the dynasty’s allegiance to Timurid culture and values remained central to their imperial institutions, and the walls of the royal harem of Mughal India remained, for the most part and for generations, porous and nuanced in the model of their Timurid ancestors.”⁴⁶¹

It can, therefore, be assumed that the womenfolk of Bābur and Humāyūn, like the focus of this study, Khānzādā Begum, were quite independent individuals. Though they observed *pardab* (veil) which did invariably signify some measure of seclusion, they certainly enjoyed more freedom than the womenfolk of the preceding rulers, namely, the Delhi Sultanate. Ashraf even claims that Humāyūn’s womenfolk freely mixed with male friends and visitors, and some of them dressed in male garments and played polo.⁴⁶² This is not to say that the Mughal women of the later centuries, ie the descendants of Bābur and Humāyūn, did not enjoy influence. The “covert methods of participation” mentioned above had slightly transformed as the enclosure became cemented.

According to N. Arbabzadah, this “high status” enjoyed by the women of the Mughal harem also granted them the ability to play a significant role in religious life through patronage—aided as much by their Turco- Mongol heritage, as by the tenets of Islam. “The Sharī‘ah laws of inheritance and property, enabled them to have their own private wealth and...the importance of almsgiving (*ṣakat*) as one of the main pillars of Islam further encouraged such patronage activity

⁴⁶⁰ Even though Babur ruled “by lineage and in the tradition of Tamerlane,” a slight shift in culture had certainly taken place. For example, almost a century after Clavijo feasted and drank alcohol with Timor’s wives and daughters-in-law, Bābur, wrote in astonishment at a woman’s request to join him at his drinking party [*majlis-i sharb*] because he had never seen a woman drink before. This is not to say that “conservativeness” had crept into the harem of Timūr’s descendants, but just to caution that whilst Bābur may have embraced Timurid traditions, with time, norms in the harem had changed. Other Timurid traditions, for example, organising Tūy by important women of the harem or the importance of maternal lineage had continued unaltered. See Balabanlilar, “The Begims of Mystic Feast,” 126-130.

⁴⁶¹ Balabanlilar, “The Begims of the Mystic Feast,” 126.

⁴⁶² KM Ashraf, *Life and conditions of the people of Hindūstān (1200-1550 A.D.): Mainly based on Islamic sources*. (New Delhi, India: Gyan Pub. House, 2000), 170. Ashraf was in particular referring to two women - Shad Begum and Mihrangaz Begum who, Gulbadan avidly describes were “adorned by various accomplishments, such as the making of thumb-rings and arrows, playing polo and shooting with the bow and arrow...” According to L.Balabanlilar, Gulbadan’s acute interest in these women suggests that these “polo-players, dressed in male garments” women were not a social norm in the Mughal harem. However, what is more noteworthy is that these women were not treated as eccentrics, but were honoured guests at the royal family’s feasts. See Balabanlilar, “The Begims of the Mystic Feast,” 125.

by adding a dimension of religious duty to the elite practice of patronage. These traditions later continued among Timurid women in Mughal India, as in the case of Princess Jahānara (d. 1681 CE), the daughter of Shah Jahān and patron of various Sufis, who was buried at the Sufi shrine of Nizam al-Din Awliya (d. 1325), in Delhi.⁴⁶³

Jahānara Begum, for example, patronised a mosque for a spiritual guide, Mullah Shāh Badakhshi in Srinagar and another Jami Masjid (congregational mosque for the Friday prayers) in Agra. However, it is the inscription on the central ivan of the Agra mosque, which gives us another example of how royal women expressed their “power” and “prestige” through socially acceptable means, for the inscription notes:

“It [the Jami Masjid] was built by her order who is high in dignity, who is as elevated as the firmament on which it sits, screened with curtains bright as the sun, possessing a glorious palace as illuminated as her wisdom, veiled with chastity, the most revered of the ladies of the age, the pride of her gender, the princess of the realm, the possessor of the three domes as worldly crowns, the chosen of the people of the world, the most honoured of the issue of the head of the Faithful, Jahānara Begum.”⁴⁶⁴

Bokhari notes that though the mention of a “princess’s name” as well as profuse eulogisation in a public building in the capital city is a certain indication of how ineffectual the *ulema* (Islamic theologians) had become by Shāh Jahān’s reign in mid seventeenth century (r. 1627 - 1658), it is more telling of how an imperial female could be transparently present — her veil almost not visible — when she presented herself as a spiritual exemplary.

This visibility of females becomes especially important, since a deliberate anonymisation of the imperial women in the official chronicles had begun earlier.⁴⁶⁵ Placed behind their grand titles: for instance, Ḥamidā Bānū Begum, became “Maryam Makānī” after her son Akbar became emperor; Jahāngir’s Rajput mother, was called “Maryam uz Zamani and the harem was collectively called *ʿIsmat qubab* (“cupola of chastity”)⁴⁶⁶ and ensconced within the tall walls of the harem guarded by faithful of eunuchs, Mughal princesses gained an education in calligraphy, poetry and the Qur’an, usually under a governess addressed as “Atun Mama.” Gulbadan, Salima Sultān, Nūr Jahān, Jahānara are a few outstanding and prominent female scholars of this royal house. Mughals princesses were magnificent calligraphers too. Folios of the Qur’an, calligraphed by Zeb un-Nisā’

⁴⁶³ Nushin Arbabzadah, “Women and Religious Patronage in the Timurid Empire,” in *Afghanistan’s Islam*, ed. Nile Green (California: University of California Press, 2017), 71.

⁴⁶⁴ Afshan Bokhari, “The ‘light’ of the Timurid: Jahān Ara Begum’s Patronage, Piety, and Poetry in 17th-Century Mughal India,” *Marg, A Magazine of the Arts* (2008): 55.

⁴⁶⁵ Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, 183.

⁴⁶⁶ Akbarnamah as quoted and translated by Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, 182.

and Zinat un-Nisā', Aurangzeb's daughters, in the Nasq script, have also been found.⁴⁶⁷ Many of these princesses, along with other non-royal, educated women of the harem (milk-mothers?) would participate in secluded poetry recitations (Mušā'ira). Jahānara authored two texts, *Mu'nis-al-Arwāḥ* and *Risālah-i Šāḥibīyah* about her involvement with Sufi orders, in addition to patronising architecture (as discussed above).⁴⁶⁸ Many princesses, as noted earlier, remained spinsters as Mughal Emperors could not find grooms "worthy" of their daughters. However, those who did get married, usually did so much later than girls from ordinary households of that time. For example: 'Āi'sha Sulṭān, Bābur's first wife and daughter of his paternal uncle, Sulṭān Ahmad- Mīrzā, though betrothed to him at five, only began cohabitating after she had turned sixteen. All of Bābur's daughters were married between thirteen to nineteen — as opposed to the public who married their daughters between six to ten years.⁴⁶⁹ Subsequently, as the empire expanded, Mughal princesses remained unmarried — for example, Jahānara Begum and Roshanara Begum, Shāh Jahān's daughters. This was more because the Mughals, as emperors of the land, would not marry their womenfolk to less aristocratic households; since no royal family existed in Hindūstān which could match their prosperity, some Mughal princesses ended up as spinsters rather than making the choice to be one. In mediaeval Indian society, the status of a woman reached its zenith when she became a mother. Mothering a prince, "the source of continuity of the dynasty" was especially a different kind of a maternal role "since the woman also had to be a bodyguard — necessarily suspicious and paranoid, ever vigilant to threats against her son's life and always apprehensive about possible traitors close by..."⁴⁷⁰ Under the Mughals, stepmothers, foster mothers, milk-mothers and at times even mothers of an enemy were treated with veneration. For instance, Bābur is said to have provided "a mansion, revenue worth 70,000 *tankas* and servants" to the mother of his rival, the slain Sulṭān Ibrahim Lodhi, even though she had tried to poison him.⁴⁷¹

This is where some complexities come into play for even motherhood was not without hierarchy in the harem. According to Natif, amongst the royal mothers, those who bestowed "Timurid" or "Persianate" prestige upon the Mughal bloodline held a higher status and enjoyed more powerful positions in the court.⁴⁷² For example, in her article, *Of Shaykhs, Bibis and Begims*, Parodi convincingly argues that Humāyūn's fixation on marrying Ḥamīda Bānū was not the

⁴⁶⁷ The folios can be accessed at the Khalili Collections, QUR 417, fold. 1b-2a and fold. 197b-198a.

⁴⁶⁸ Even though poetry recitation and writing were in keeping with the Timurid tradition, the female literary voices in the Mughal world were few. Women came into their own when the Persian hegemony broke, and Urdu and Hindi recitations became popular in the late eighteenth century. See Sunil Sharma, *Mughal Arcadia: Persian Literature in an Indian Court* (Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press, 2017), 31–32.

⁴⁶⁹ Sudha Sharma, *The Status of Muslim Women in Medieval India* (New Delhi: SAGE, 2016), 48–49.

⁴⁷⁰ Munis D. Faruqi, *The Princes of the Mughal Empire, 1504–1719* (New York: Cambridge University Press, 2015), 68, 72.

⁴⁷¹ Sharma, *The Status of Muslim Women in Medieval India*, 64–65.

⁴⁷² Natif, "Preliminary Thoughts," 40.

outcome of a “romantic *coup de foudre*” but a political convenience, since Ḥamīda Bānū was a descendent of the Shaykhs of Jām and for Humāyūn, who had by this time lost his empire to Shēr Shāh, this alliance with the lineage of Aḥmad-i Jām (who the Ṭimurids had patronised throughout the fifteenth century) was the best way to reassure his followers.⁴⁷³ This connection, Parodi writes, “also accounts for the saintly aura posthumously attributed to Humāyūn, upon which Akbar [the third Mughal emperor and son of Humāyūn and Ḥamīda Bānū] based his own claims to spiritual charisma, reinforced but not exclusively provided by his maternal descent.”⁴⁷⁴ Thus, spiritual pedigree was equally honoured.

This hierarchy became more pronounced once Mughal emperors began marrying local Indian princesses, who ended up being relegated to a lower position, much less dignified than the wives who came from Central Asian and Ṭimurid lineage, as a consequence of Akbar’s ‘Rajput Policy’ (cultivating marital alliances with native royal families). For example, in the painting the *Birth of Prince Salīm* [the future Jahāngir], (see image 8), note how Ḥamīda Bānū, the Mughal Mother with “Persianate” pedigree is centre-stage (seated on the chair), whereas, the new mother, a Rajput Princess, the future Queen Mother, is relegated to the sidelines even though it is the birth of Jahāngir that is depicted here. Better lineage, also meant a better position as a wife to the *Pādishāh*. For example, Bābur’s first marriage to his paternal cousin fell apart in three years — this was because his wife Āi’sha’s “left him.”⁴⁷⁵ Though this signified the importance that wives enjoyed in the harem, one must not forget that the authority to take this decision was possible only because Āi’sha was of a respectable lineage.⁴⁷⁶ However, above all existential or social factors, the one that contributed the most to a woman’s prestige was wisdom gained through experience, which is probably why Khānzādā became the *Pādishāh* Begum and not one of Humāyūn’s wives.

As Ruby Lal notes: “The respect that Dildār and Khānzādā acquired was one that came with age. This is a point that emerges repeatedly in the narratives. It was the senior generation that was revered, especially influential mothers, not the ‘favourite’ wives.”⁴⁷⁷ The harem was not a space meant to enhance the individual ambitions of women, certainly not those of innovative young

⁴⁷³Laura E. Parodi, “Of Shaykhs, Bibīs and Begims: Sources on Early Mughal Marriage Connections and the Patronage of Babur’s Tomb,” *Mediaeval and Modern Iranian Studies: Proceedings of the 6th European Conference of Iranian Studies (Vienna, 2007)*, ed. Maria Szuppe, Anna Krasnowolska and Claus Pedersen. *Cahiers de Studia Iranica* 45 (2011), 127.

⁴⁷⁴ Parodi, “Of Shaykhs, Bibīs and Begims,” 130.

⁴⁷⁵ Parodi, “Of Shaykhs, Bibīs and Begims,” 128.

⁴⁷⁶ The reason for this decision could either be the death of their only child, a daughter, Fakhr-un-Nissa, a month after her birth or Bābur’s behaviour with Āi’sha, or perhaps both. By his own admission, Bābur writes, “I was not ill-disposed towards her [Āi’sha Sulṭān]. But this being my first marriage, out of modesty or bashfulness, I used to see her once in fifteen days or so.” See Hiro, *Bābur Nama*, 60.

⁴⁷⁷ Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, 125.

women. But it was a place where women could take pleasure in everyday exchanges, in watching the stars, in gazing at the flow of the Jamuna ...⁴⁷⁸

Conclusion

The essay sought to establish two things: one, provide a biographical account of a Mughal princess almost forgotten both in the Mughal world as well as current-day scholarship — Khānzādā Begum (1478–1545).

I argued that this absence in contemporary records, the most important being her brother Bābur’s diary, has indirectly become an acknowledgment to her significant yet humiliating “sacrifice” in 1501 CE — getting married to the “Timurid enemy,” the Uzbek chief, Shaybānī Khān. Ultimately, this “sacrifice” made the foundation of Mughal empire possible in Hindūstān, twenty-five years later. Even though she remains relatively undiscussed in literary records, the visual culture of Mughal world — paintings and portraiture, proved helpful in analysing Khānzādā’s relevance to future emperors of the empire. Khānzādā’s life and subsequent return to her brother’s empire ten years later after “exile” in the Uzbek land, was never stigmatised. She was made *Pādīshāh* Begum — the principal lady of the Mughal harem and her roles and responsibility transcended the realms of the harem — and included counselling the emperor and acting as his representative, as Khānzādā did for her nephew Humāyūn towards the end of her life.

In the second section of the essay, we took a step back from Khānzādā’s life and analysed the space that she belonged to and subsequently became the supervisor of — “the Harem,” an anglicisation of the Arabic “haram” and discussed how apart from the corruption in spellings, the connotations and significance of the space also changed with the arrival of the Europeans, who unfamiliar with the concept of the “haram” and debarred from entering its premises soon began to weave fanciful narratives — reiterated so often in scholarships, that they were accepted as the truth well until the end of the twentieth century.

My ongoing research on the life of Khānzādā Begum has led me to realise that several statements used to describe the harem both in contemporary European accounts as well as the traditional history books are ideologically and factually wrong. In the excerpts reproduced in the section “Interrogating the Prejudices,” note the use of the term “master” to describe the relationship between the emperor and all inmates of the harem — inherently associating subservience with the ladies — a direct contrast to how, for example, Bābur relied on the counsel

⁴⁷⁸ Lal, *Empress: The Astonishing Reign of Nūr Jahān*, 98.

of his grandmother, or *Pādishāh* Begum Khānzādā guided Emperor Humāyūn or came to his aid during rebellions.

Thus, women of the harem, especially the Mughals, did participate in the functioning of the empire, however, owing to the sequestered nature of their living (which became pronounced once Akbar ascended the throne, as sacrality was imposed on the women's quarters ⁴⁷⁹) or perhaps due to the supposed "passive participation"⁴⁸⁰ expected from women due to their gender — these women often devised a complex and covert method of participation. By acting as diplomats or counsellors to the emperor or by taking up the "domestic" tasks of arranging important feasts, these women developed some ingenious ways of exercising their ambition in political matters, while never compromising on their "sacred seclusion" i.e., the harem. This is ultimately what I learnt during the course of my research and is what this essay hopes to have highlighted by now,

However, to properly understand the harem in the Mughal period, one needs to keep in mind that it was a space for leisure, scholarship, culture and learning. To acknowledge that these women lived a life of relative luxury does not amount to stigmatising them as long as we recognise that they were also engaged on political, cultural, and economic fronts.⁴⁸¹

First Pādishāh Begum of the Mughal Empire: Āka-jānam Khānzādā Begum is an attempt to highlight that life in the Mughal Harem was not as one-dimensional as some recent depictions have led us to believe. Despite its secrecy and complexities, it is a much more dynamic space than how it is often characterised. Khānzādā Begum is just one of the many veiled women of this glorious and yet much-misunderstood institution. Hopefully, with greater research, we will soon be able to see beyond the "myth of harem" and study their inmates more empathetically.

⁴⁷⁹ Lal, *Domesticity and Power in the Early Mughal World*, 181–182.

⁴⁸⁰ The concept of active participation, as has been discussed by L. Balabanlilar, was unique to the Mughals: "Among them [the Mughals] remained a Timurid understanding of the rights and roles of elite women — not only with regard to their artistic production and patronage, but also, in marked contrast to their contemporaries, the Ottomans and the Safavids, the power offered to the young, even childless, royal women and their active participation in dynastic survival and political success." See "Mystic Feast," 123.

⁴⁸¹ I am grateful to Dr Mehreen Chida-Razvi for sharing her insight on the Mughal harem.

List of Illustrations

Image 1: Genealogy of Khānzādā Begum, drawn by the author.

Image 2: The Trustees of The Morgan Museum and Library, New York, MS M.458.18, <https://www.themorgan.org/collection/treasures-of-islamic-manuscript-painting/75#overlay-context=collection/treasures-of-islamic-manuscript-painting/75>.

Image 3: Courtesy of The Metropolitan Museum of Art, New York, Cora Timken Burnett Collection of Persian Miniatures and Other Persian Art Objects, Bequest of Cora Timken Burnett, 1956, accession number 57.51.29.

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Image 4: *Google Maps*, labelling by the author.

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Image 7: Provided by [Wiki Gallery](#), part of a private collection.

Image 8: Courtesy of The Museum of Fine Arts, Boston, accession number 14.657, <https://collections.mfa.org/objects/148503/birth-of-prince->

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Thomas of Aquinas and Boethius of Dacia on the Eternity of the World

TVRTKO SRDOC

MA Student, CEU Vienna

Abstract

This article deals with the question of the eternity of the world in the works of two authors from the thirteenth century, Thomas Aquinas (ca. 1225–1274) and Boethius of Dacia (d. ca. 1280). It is an analysis of their views in two works which share the same name: De Aeternitate Mundi. The analysis is appropriate because of the chronology and the political circumstances they share. Namely, both works were written around the year 1270, at the time of the debate over the appropriation of the newly introduced Greco-Islamic knowledge, which led to frequent condemnations by the Church. After giving a general introduction about the topic of the paper and the works analysed (including the main historiographical debates), each of them will be given a thorough examination. This examination will take into consideration the text structure, the different arguments presented therein, and the relevant secondary literature. Finally, possible answers to the questions posed in the Introduction: Firstly, can philosophy prove that the world was created in time?, and, secondly, Could God have created the world as eternal? will be given in the Conclusion, according to the views of the aforementioned authors.

Keywords: Thomas Aquinas – Boethius of Dacia – Eternity of the World – Medieval Philosophy – History of Philosophy

Introduction

After Aristotle's texts started getting translated into Latin in the second half of the twelfth century, from Arabic and Greek, various questions occurred when it came to “appropriating” Aristotle and the Catholic dogma and tradition in the Latin West. The understanding of Aristotle’s *Metaphysica* and the *Logica nova* was an easier task, especially when it came to the identification of Aristotle's Prime Mover with the Christian God.⁴⁸² However, it seemed that some theories of Aristotle that generally belong to his philosophy of nature were at direct odds with the Catholic teaching. One of these was Aristotle's position that the physical world and all the matter contained in it was eternal (existed forever), which he expounded in his *Physica*.⁴⁸³ At face value, this theory directly contradicts the Genesis creation story, in which God⁴⁸⁴ creates the material world out of nothing (*ex nihilo*).⁴⁸⁵ Among others, this must have been the reason behind the frequent condemnations of Aristotle’s doctrines (especially those pertaining to his philosophy of nature) throughout the thirteenth century.⁴⁸⁶ The most famous condemnation was that of 1277 in Paris, when bishop Etienne Tempier (d. 1279) issued 219 theses, out of which at least five had directly attacked the view that the world and matter contained in it are eternal.⁴⁸⁷ However, as Pearl Kibre and Nancy G. Siraisi point out, even though Aristotle’s natural philosophy was formally condemned throughout the thirteenth century, he was widely read, studied, and soon considered “the Philosopher” (e.g. in Oxford and Paris).⁴⁸⁸ This essay will deal with the eternity of the world, a particular thesis mentioned both in the 1270 and the 1277 Condemnations. More precisely, the views on the eternity of the world of two philosophers from the thirteenth century, Thomas Aquinas (d. 1274) and Boethius of Dacia (d. ca. 1280) will be analysed.⁴⁸⁹ After the *Introduction*, a

⁴⁸² Cf. Michael Camille, “Illustrations in Harley MS 3487 and the Perception of Aristotle's Libri Naturales in Thirteenth-Century England,” In *England in the Thirteenth Century: Proceedings of the 1984 Harlaxton Symposium*, ed. W.M. Ormrod (Suffolk, 1986), 37.

⁴⁸³ *Physics* I, 7.

⁴⁸⁴ In this work I chose to capitalise the *nomen sacrum* of the Christian Triune God, and His actions (so as to differentiate them from human actions), since it is capitalised both in the primary sources used, and in all of the secondary literature.

⁴⁸⁵ *Genesis* I, 1.

⁴⁸⁶ Firstly in 1210 and 1215, then in 1231 and in the famous condemnations of the bishop of Paris Etienne Tempier in 1270 and 1277. In this work, I will not be dealing with the political circumstances of the debate, nor the transmission of the translations of Greek sources. This is because my goal is primarily that of analysing the arguments themselves, rather than of what made them possible in the first place. For a succinct overview of the political issues involved with the condemnations, please refer to Fernand von Steenberghen, *The Philosophical Movement in the Thirteenth Century* (Edinburgh: Nelson, 1995), 45-46.

⁴⁸⁷ Cf. e.g. 52nd, 87th, 93rd, 98th, and 107th propositions, Edward Grant, *A Source Book in Medieval Science* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 1974), 12-13.

⁴⁸⁸ Kibre, Pearl and Nancy G. Siraisi, “The Institutional Settings: The Universities” in *Science in the Middle Ages*, ed. D. C. Lindberg: 133.

⁴⁸⁹ The primary sources used are the translations of Aquinas’ and Boethius’ homonymous *opusculae* entitled *De Aeternitate Mundi*, using Miller’s and Wippel’s translations, respectively. Cf. Robert T. Miller, trans., “On the Eternity of the World,” Fordham University, <https://sourcebooks.fordham.edu/basis/aquinas-eternity.asp#f1> and trans. John F. Wippel, *On the Supreme Good: On the Eternity of the World; On Dreams* (Toronto: Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies, 1987).

general background of the question at hand and a short discussion about the proposed chronological dates of their writing will be discussed. Following this a detailed study of each work will be given. In the conclusion, I will give possible answers to these two research questions.

1. Can philosophy prove that the world was created in time?
2. Could God have created the world as eternal?

An Overview of the Problem

In the *Timaeus*, which was available in the Latin speaking world through Calcidius' fourth century translation alongside his commentary, Plato differentiates between two kinds of eternity, *aeternitas* (a-temporal eternity) and *aevum* (temporal eternity).⁴⁹⁰ In order to properly understand the eternity of celestial bodies and angels, Augustine of Hippo (354–430) added a third category of duration, which was outside of time, but not a-temporal.⁴⁹¹ Boethius (d. 524) contrasted the a-temporal simultaneously full and perfect possession of interminable life which pertains solely to God with the temporal (eternal or finite) duration which pertains to all other beings. Most early medieval authors, such as John Scotus Eriugena (ca. 800 - ca. 877), held a threefold differentiation of duration.⁴⁹² Namely, between eternal, which did not have a beginning or an end, perpetual, having a beginning, but not an end, and temporal, having both a beginning and an end. This threefold differentiation minimised Boethius' distinction between the a-temporal God and the temporal creation, thus laying the ground for the frequent late-medieval (Scholastic) understanding of all three levels (eternal, perpetual, and temporal) as existing on the same ontological level, something Boethius would have rejected.⁴⁹³

By the beginning of the thirteenth century, the terminology was further complicated by the circulation of two other terms, *saeculum* and *sempiternitas*, which both had roughly the same meaning as Plato's (i.e. Calcidius') *aevum*.⁴⁹⁴ Therefore, the complexity of terminology was very apparent by the second half of the 13th century. As was mentioned in the introduction of this article the idea of the world's eternity was a much debated topic in the 13th century, as seen by the frequent condemnations of that view. Dales speculates that Bonaventure of Bagnoregio (1221–1274) was the one who stirred up a lot of the inimical polemics that would follow, by announcing that such a view (i.e. the possibility of eternal creation) could not reasonably be held.⁴⁹⁵ In essence, there

⁴⁹⁰ Cf. Richard C. Dales, "Time and Eternity in the Thirteenth Century," *Journal of the History of Ideas* 49, no. 1 (1988): 27

⁴⁹¹ Dales, "Time and Eternity," 28.

⁴⁹² In his *De divisione naturae* written in the 860s.

⁴⁹³ Dales, "Time and Eternity," 29.

⁴⁹⁴ Dales, "Time and Eternity," 30.

⁴⁹⁵ Cf. Richard C. Dales, "Early Latin Discussions of the Eternity of the World in the Thirteenth Century," *Traditio* 43 (1987): 197.

were two questions that were at issue, the first of the relationship between time and eternity, and the second of the possibility of an eternally created world.⁴⁹⁶ The first question relates to the possibility of God, being a-temporal, relating to the temporal realm. In other words, how is God's "now" compatible with the temporal "now" that humans experience? The second question is related to the possibility of the world being created eternally. Here it is important to note that the world being created in time, but existing eternally in the future, was not accepted by any author of this period. This is because it would directly contradict the Christian teaching of the Last Judgement. Within the second question, which is the topic of our present study, the two main positions regarding the approach of reason⁴⁹⁷ to the eternity of the world were: 1. That the finite (or non-eternal) creation of the world is demonstrable by reason, and 2. That reason cannot prove that the world must have been created neither as eternal nor as finite.⁴⁹⁸ The main protagonists of the first view were St. Bonaventure, Henry of Ghent (1217–1293), and John Peckham (ca. 1230–1292).⁴⁹⁹ Who, and in which way exactly, falls under the second view, is very much a question of debate. Be that as it may, after the 1250s, the question of the possibility of eternal creation was much discussed, as seen from the writings of Henry of Ghent, Godfrey of Fontaines (d. 1309), Giles of Rome (1243–1316) and others.⁵⁰⁰

The answer to this possibility seems to have expanded further from the bounds of philosophical argumentation. In other words, the answer to this and other questions (such as there being only one active intellect in all humans) was also an answer to the acceptance or rejection of new Greek and Islamic influence, and the general relationship between philosophy and theology.⁵⁰¹ That could be the reason that Boethius of Dacia, as will be seen below, discusses the general relation between faith and reason (and subsequently theology and philosophy) within the treatise on the eternity of the world. In any case, according to their attitude both toward particular philosophical questions, the relationship between philosophy and theology, and to the acceptance or rejection of Aristotle, Steenberghen has differentiated three groups emerging within this debate, the "extreme left" of the "radical Aristotelians" (most prominently the faculty of arts masters Siger

⁴⁹⁶ Dales, "Early Discussions," 195.

⁴⁹⁷ By "reason" here it is meant that specifically human faculty which differentiates the species "human" from all other species and by which humans are able to do such things as form concepts and infer conclusions from premises. For an introduction to the Scholastic meaning of human rational faculties (such as *ratio*, *cognitio*, and *intellectus*), cf. Deborah L. Black, "The Nature of Intellect," in *The Cambridge History of Medieval Philosophy*, ed. Robert Pasnau (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010), 320-334.

⁴⁹⁸ Cf. Luca Bianchi, *L'errore di Aristotele: La Polemica Contro L'eternità Del Mondo Nel XIII Secolo* (Florence: Nuova Italia, 1984), 166.

⁴⁹⁹ John F. Wippel, "Introduction," in *On the Supreme Good: On the Eternity of the World; On Dreams*, ed. John F. Wippel (Toronto: Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies, 1987), 15.

⁵⁰⁰ John F. Wippel, "Did Thomas Aquinas Defend the Possibility of an Eternally Created World? (The De Aeternitate Mundi Revisited)," *Journal of the History of Philosophy* 19, no. 1 (1981): 22.

⁵⁰¹ Bianchi, *L'errore*, 164.

of Brabant and Boethius of Dacia), the “extreme right“ of the Theology masters (John Peckham, Henry of Ghent) and the Thomistic tradition in the middle (Thomas and his inheritors, such as Giles of Rome or Peter of Auvergne).⁵⁰²

When it comes to the life and works of Boethius of Dacia, our knowledge is very scarce. The only things we know for certain is that he was of Danish origin, became a Dominican friar later in life, and died probably around 1280.⁵⁰³ The dating of the *Liber de concordia fidei christianae et philosophiae de aeternitate mundi* – the full name of the treatise, which is also indicative of its content⁵⁰⁴ – is likewise not certain. Weisheipl thinks it cannot be placed “better than in 1270”.⁵⁰⁵ This view, however, is no longer taken as a fact, especially with the existence of Mowbray's articles.⁵⁰⁶

It does not seem important to go over Thomas Aquinas' biography, since much has been written about it, and it does not directly touch on our topic.⁵⁰⁷ However, a couple of short remarks will have to be said with regards to the historiographical debate over the datation of Thomas' *De Aeternitate Mundi* and the general character of the work. After Mandonnet's *Des écrits authentiques de S. Thomas d'Aquin* from 1910, and Grabmann's *Thomas von Aquin. Eine Einführung in seine Persönlichkeit und Gedankenwelt* from 1912, most of historiography after Mandonnet and Grabmann (*pace* Pelster)⁵⁰⁸ before Bukowski's 1970 article *An Early Dating for Aquinas' 'De aeternitate mundi'*, accepted 1270–1272 as the timeframe for the writing of the treatise. Bukowski's argument relies on the analysis of certain phrases in Thomas' *De Aeternitate Mundi* which purports to show that *De Aeternitate Mundi* is closer to his *Scriptum super librum Sentiarum* (written in the 1250s) than the *Summa Theologiae* (began in 1265). What Bukowski draws from this is that *De Aeternitate Mundi* is an earlier and less developed work, whereas the ideas are further elaborated in the *Summa Theologiae*. The second argument is the debate with Bonaventure which must have taken place in the 1250s, and not later. Therefore, Bukowski asks, why would Thomas have waited twenty years for the response?⁵⁰⁹

⁵⁰² Cf. Steenberghen, *The Philosophical Movement*, 98.

⁵⁰³ Cf. Soren Skovgaard Jensen, “On the National Origin of the Philosopher Boetius de Dacia,” *Classica et mediaevalia* 24 (1963): 232–41.

⁵⁰⁴ Cf. Jakob Hans Josef Schneider, “The eternity of the world Thomas Aquinas and Boethius of Dacia,” *Archives d'histoire doctrinale et littéraire du Moyen Age* (1999): 138.

⁵⁰⁵ Cf. James Athansius Weisheipl, “The Date and Context of Aquinas' De Aeternitate Mundi,” in *Essays in Ancient and Medieval Philosophy Presented to Joseph Owens, C.Ss.R.*, ed. Lloyd P. Gerson (Toronto: Pontifical Institute of Mediaeval Studies, 1983), 245.

⁵⁰⁶ Cf. Malcolm de Mowbray, “1277 And All That — Students And Disputations,” *Traditio* 57 (2002): 217–238, and Malcolm de Mowbray, “The De Aeternitate Mundi of Boethius of Dacia and the Paris Condemnation of 1277,” *Recherches de Théologie Et Philosophie Médiévales* 73 (2006): 201–253.

⁵⁰⁷ Cf. Jean-Pierre Torrell, *Saint Thomas Aquinas: The Person and His Work*, trans. by Robert Royal (Washington, D.C: Catholic University of America Press, 2005); James Athanasius Weisheipl, *Friar Thomas D'Aquino: His Life, Thought, and Works: With Corrigenda and Addenda* (Washington, D.C: Catholic University of America Press, 1983).

⁵⁰⁸ Franz Pelster, “De Concordantia Dictorum Thomae: Ein Echtes Werk Aus des Letzten Lebesjahren des hl. Thomas von Aquin,” *Gregorianum*, 4 (1923): 72–105.

⁵⁰⁹ Cf. Thomas Bukovski, “An Early Dating for Aquinas' 'De Aeternitate Mundi,’” *Gregorianum* (1970): 303.

The answer to Bukowski's challenge was given by many scholars.⁵¹⁰ Torrell, Wippel, and Weisheipl all rightly point out that Bukowski's analysis is flawed. Namely, it does not take into consideration the most apparent fact of *De Aeternitate Mundi* when compared to other of Thomas' works which mention eternity, which is that Thomas expounds the view of the possibility of eternal creation only in *De Aeternitate Mundi*, and in no other works. If *De Aeternitate Mundi* was an earlier work, one would expect Thomas to have the same position on the possibility of eternal creation in both of his *Summae*, and the *De Potentia*, which supposedly came after *De Aeternitate Mundi*. Also, the large similarity between *De Unitate Intellectu* (written in 1270) and *De Aeternitate Mundi* is not explained if one accepts Bukowski's chronology. Furthermore, the idea that Thomas waited twenty years to respond to Bonaventure is not really an issue. This is because, it is most likely not Bonaventure, but Peckham who Thomas was answering to, and in that case, he answered shortly after Peckham's initial accusation.

Thomas Aquinas' *De Aeternitate Mundi*

De Aeternitate Mundi starts by asserting that the eternity of the world with all its parts is not a true position because of the creed of the catholic faith. Nonetheless, Thomas asks a counterfactual question concerning the eternity of the world: Could God have created the world as eternal? Here he makes two distinctions.

If "eternal" implies something that always existed and is not caused by God, then this kind of eternity is impossible. He does not go into more detail here. However, it seems that this is rejected because of the essence-existence differentiation, which posits the actualisation or the "unification" of every essence to existence by the one whose essence is to exist. Therefore, everything that has being (i.e., that exists), must receive it from the being which most truly is.

Secondly, is there something intrinsically faulty in the idea of the creation of an eternal being? What is implied when one says that an eternal thing cannot be made? Thomas answers: Either an absence of a passive potentiality or a contradiction in terms.⁵¹¹ Because angels are not material, it seems that they either do not have passive potentiality, and thus are necessarily actual, or their passive potentiality is somehow coeternal with God. The second option is swiftly rejected by Thomas, without further clarification. From the belief that angels exist, Thomas concludes that

⁵¹⁰ Cf. Weisheipl, "The Date and Context," Wippel, "Did Thomas Aquinas;" Torrell, *Saint Thomas*, and Ermengildo Bertola "Tommaso d'Aquino e il problema dell'eternità del mondo," *Rivista di filosofia neo-scolastica* (1974): 312-355.

⁵¹¹ Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 3. I will be citing Miller's translation according to the structure given by the translator. Namely, he divides *De Aeternitate Mundi* (which was written as a single *opuscula* and thus without further division into chapters) into twenty chapters.

God creates them without passive potentiality.⁵¹² This argumentation may be the weakest part of the whole treatise since it relies on the belief that God actually created angels (in a certain way). Be that as it may, angels are not actual in the same way that God is. Namely, in angels, the difference between essence and existence still exists, and so their essence still has a sort of passive potentiality to existence, whereas God's essence is his existence.

Here it may be worth pointing out the two different types of contradiction in *De Aeternitate Mundi*. The first is between the things which the propositions describe (e.g. God's activity and the creation of angels) and the second is between the propositions stated, without having in mind those things which they describe in the world (e.g. "being created by God" and "being eternal" taken as propositions).⁵¹³ Thomas remarks that some people think that God could make contradictories true, while others think that it is not possible. The first view, held by some "pious men," probably Peter Damian (1007–1072), is deemed not heretical, but false.⁵¹⁴ Then he deals with the contradiction in terms. Namely, is the proposition "X does not have a beginning in time" contradictory to the proposition "X was created by God"? Here one must agree with Bertola in asserting that "The whole question comes down to determining whether "being created by God" and "not being temporal" is contradictory".⁵¹⁵ If this is a contradiction, it is so either because the efficient cause precedes the effect temporally or because non-being (non-existence) precedes being (existence) in time.⁵¹⁶

The first of these, according to my interpretation of Thomas, is false because of four reasons. Firstly, the way God produces an effect is not similar to motion (i.e. in time) but rather like fire (i.e. instantaneously). In other words, the effect exists simultaneously with the cause; thus, no precedence in time is posited. Secondly, even those things which produce forms (like the Sun) do not precede their effects in time. More so is this true for God, who is the producer of substances. Thirdly, when the effect ceases to exist simultaneously with the cause, such a lack of simultaneity is because "something complementary to that cause is lacking."⁵¹⁷ However, nothing is missing from the supreme cause which is God, and therefore its effects are simultaneous with its existence. The fourth reason says that God having free will does not lessen His power to create

⁵¹²Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 4.

⁵¹³ Cf. Ian Wilks, "Aquinas on the Past Possibility of the World's Having Existed Forever," *The Review of Metaphysics* 48, no. 2 (1994): 307.

⁵¹⁴ Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 5.

⁵¹⁵ Bertola, "Tommaso d'Aquino," 348. Translation of my own.

⁵¹⁶ Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 6.

⁵¹⁷ Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 112.

(cause) instantaneously. This is because free will in God does not presuppose deliberation, which would make the effect non-simultaneous.⁵¹⁸

Thomas then deals with the second half of the dilemma. Namely, the idea that eternal creation necessarily presupposes non-being preceding being in time. The first reason he gives against this view is a quote from Anselm of Canterbury (ca. 1033–1109) that asserts that creation *ex nihilo* does not imply temporal primacy of non-being. In other words, there was not a time when there was no being. An important thing to point out is that here time is understood in a relative, and not absolute sense. This means it does not exist as separate from the relative motions of created creatures but only insofar as there is motion. Secondly, if “creation out of nothing” is understood as “creation after nothing,” then a distinction between the order of time and order of nature has to be made. Thomas says that creation *ex nihilo* does not imply the order of time, but of nature and gives a particularly illuminating example of the Sun and the air.

If we assume that the Sun is eternal, then there was not a time in which the air was not made luminous by the Sun. However, had the Sun not existed, then the air would not be luminous, but dark. Therefore, no precedence of non-being to being in time is posited, but only precedence in nature. In order to better understand this, one must remember that in Aristotle’s metaphysics there exists only the differentiation between form and matter, where form is that which actualises the matter (makes the matter exist), and it does not make sense to ask about the being of this composite itself. In Thomas, alongside the matter-form differentiation, there is a difference between essence (“what a thing is,” which is form and matter for material things and solely form for immaterial) and being or existence. Therefore, the existence of angels, which are not matter-form composites, and their diversity from God cannot be explained without this Thomistic “double-layered” metaphysics, which makes God the sustainer of all being, whether material or not.⁵¹⁹

After this, Thomas refutes the idea that the created world is coeternal with God by using the Boethian distinction between being a-temporal (which corresponds to God) and being eternal in time (which corresponds to angels and heavenly bodies). In other words, creatures created eternal by God are only thus in time and not outside of it. In the end, Thomas gives two reasons against the actual existence of an infinite number of souls that supposedly follows accepting the eternity of the world. He says that, even if one accepts that the world is eternal, that does not mean that there should exist an eternal number of souls because God could have either created men

⁵¹⁸ Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 12.

⁵¹⁹ Cf. Fernand Brunner, “Über die thomistische Lehre vom Ursprung der Welt,” *Zeitschrift für philosophische Forschung* H. 2 (1962): 256.

without souls or created the world eternally, but men only from a certain point.⁵²⁰ Lastly, Thomas regards the impossibility of an actual infinite not to have been proven: “Furthermore, it has not yet been demonstrated that God cannot cause an infinite number of things to exist simultaneously.”⁵²¹

Thomas develops a nuanced view on the question of the eternity of the world. On the one hand, he rejects the idea that the world is necessarily eternal (which would have been directly deemed heretical and contrary to reality); since that directly contradicts the Genesis account and makes God's efficient and final causality secondary to his creation. In this respect, he is similar to most other thirteenth century philosophers in giving a “defence” of the faith against Aristotle. However, Thomas believes that, although an eternally existing world is not necessary, it was certainly not impossible for God to have created it as such. He demonstrates this by rejecting all possible counterarguments that purport to show that God could not have created the world as eternal. Firstly, there is nothing lacking in God which would make God not be able to create an eternal world. Secondly, there is nothing contradictory in an eternal world being created by God. This is demonstrated by showing that eternal creation does not need to imply temporal precedence of the cause to the effect or of non-being to being. Therefore, even though the truth of faith teaches that the world was created as finite, there was no rational necessity to the way in which it was created. This is because it was a free choice of an absolutely free God. As regards the general character of the work, I agree with Aertsen⁵²² in saying that it is a philosophical work (*contra* Grijs),⁵²³ although it mentions the article of the faith at the beginning. This is because the main *crux* of the treatise is the incompatibility of two propositions (1. Being created by God, and 2. Being eternal), and not a theological question. Rather, the philosophical method is here used to explain the nuances and consequences of a theological belief, something that would fall under natural theology in scholasticism, and under philosophical theology in today's academic classification.

⁵²⁰ Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 19.

⁵²¹ Thomas Aquinas, *On the Eternity of the World*, 19.

⁵²² Cf. Jan Adrianus Aertsen, “The eternity of the world: The believing and the philosophical Thomas. Some comments,” in *The Eternity of the World in the Thought of Thomas Aquinas and his Contemporaries*, ed. J.B.M. Wissink (Leiden: Brill, 1990): 12–18.

⁵²³ Cf. Grijs, de Ferdinandus JA, “The Theological Character of Aquinas' ‘De Aeternitate Mundi,’” in *The Eternity of the World in the Thought of Thomas Aquinas and his Contemporaries*, ed. J.B.M. Wissink (Leiden: Brill, 1990), 1–8.

Boethius of Dacia's *De Aeternitate Mundi*

Boethius starts his treatise by asserting that it is foolish to seek rational argumentation for things that do not admit of it. It is equally problematic to believe something that admits rational investigation only through faith. Boethius' goal for this work is threefold: 1) to defend the Catholic faith, 2) to defend natural philosophy and 3) to show that there is no contradiction between faith and philosophy.

Boethius starts by giving eleven arguments that prove the world had a beginning in time. The first proposition states that the creation of the world must come after the existence of its cause. The second proposition is linked to the first. It simply states that, if the world were eternal, it would be coeternal with God, which is taken to be impossible. The third proposition rests on a hierarchy of causes. Namely, on the idea of the heavens as the causes of time in the world. However, since the heavenly bodies are finite, they cannot produce an infinite effect. Therefore, the world cannot be infinite. The fourth proposition starts by asserting that God is prior to the world by nature. Since nature and duration are the same in God, he must also be prior to the world by duration. Along with this, I think that Boethius holds the idea that God is absolutely simple, and therefore his attributes do not point to any real distinction in Him, but only a rational distinction in our minds.⁵²⁴ The fifth proposition asserts that, because creation *ex nihilo* implies priority of nature on the part of God, it must also imply temporal priority of God to its creation. Boethius does not supply further argumentation for this claim but gives us a tautology: “[T]o begin to be and to be eternal are mutually exclusive for one and the same thing.”⁵²⁵

The sixth proposition starts from the observation that, unlike infinity, previous time can be added on to. Since this is possible in our world, time that has passed cannot be infinite. The seventh proposition relies on the absurdity of an infinite number of past generations. More concretely, there would need to be an infinite number of any kind of animal, for there to be animals today. This argument is similar to the infinite number of passed moments that needed to be traversed up to the actual moment, which would amount to an absurdity. However, this argument is weaker, since it relies both on the absurdity of the infinity of past time and also on the equal infinity of the generation of animals and the world itself. The eighth proposition cites Aristotle's Sixth book of the *Physica* in which the Stagirite asserts the convertibility of magnitude, motion, and time. Following this, since magnitude is finite, the same must hold for motion and time. The ninth proposition is the famous argument for the finitude of the world from the infinity of actually

⁵²⁴ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 37.

⁵²⁵ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 38.

existing souls. Namely, since rational human souls are immortal, if the world were eternal in the past, then an infinite number of actually existing rational souls would have to exist at this moment. The tenth proposition is something that was already mentioned in the seventh proposition. It is a Bonaventurian argument from the impossibility of infinite previous moments having passed before arriving at the actuality of the current moment. Finally, the eleventh proposition states that everything which has a cause must also have a beginning. Because the world has a cause, it must also have a beginning.

After eleven arguments against the eternity of the world (a), Boethius gives five arguments for the possibility of an eternal creation (b), thirteen for the statement that it is actually the case that the world was created eternally (c). Boethius gives his solution followed by detailed answers to the last thirteen arguments, i.e. the position (c).⁵²⁶ The first argument for the possibility of an eternal world is that the first cause does not need to precede its effect in duration, but only in nature.⁵²⁷ The second argument, using Aristotle's example of a triangle that eternally has three sides, reinforces the first argument. Namely, even if something is eternally true, it does not follow that it cannot also be caused. The third argument is that of the Sun and the lucid air.⁵²⁸ The fourth argument is the same as the third, only the Augustinian variant with the eternal foot and its coeternal footprint. The fifth is from the comparison with the eternal future. Namely, as Christian doctrine teaches, the future of each individual is eternal. Therefore, if God could have made the future as eternal, there could be nothing preventing Him in making the past eternal as well. Now Boethius turns to the thirteen arguments that purport to show the world to have actually, and not just possibly, been created as eternal. The first argument can be summed up as follows:

1. Everything incorruptible is eternal,
2. Everything that is not generated is incorruptible,
3. The world is not generated, *ergo*
4. The world is incorruptible. (from 1, 2, 3), *ergo*
5. The world is eternal (from 1, 4).⁵²⁹

The second argument says that, since time is the measurement of motion, there could not have been any time before the world was made. Therefore, the world must be eternal. The third argument starts by asserting that the underlying principle of a thing's existence is matter. But, if

⁵²⁶ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 39.

⁵²⁷ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 40.

⁵²⁸ Cf. Thomas' argument in the previous chapter.

⁵²⁹ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 41.

the world was created in time, then there could not be any matter preceding it.⁵³⁰ The fourth says that, since every change requires a subject, matter, and a certain potency, and since creation *ex nihilo* could not involve any of these, the world must be eternal. The fifth argument states the impossibility of the world existing as soon as time “started” to be. In other words, “[T]hat which begins in any duration must come to be within a part of that duration.”⁵³¹ The sixth argument starts from the process of generation and corruption. Since every generation follows upon corruption, and every corruption necessitates a prior generation, there could not have been a “first” generation, since corruption would have needed to precede it. The seventh argument is the argument from the absolute sufficiency of the first cause. Boethius sums up this argument exquisitely:

“A being which is eternal both in terms of its substance and in terms of its every disposition, to which nothing is added in the future and from which nothing is lacking in the past of that whereby it would produce its effect, produces its immediate effect as coeternal to itself.”⁵³²

The eighth argument goes like this: Because God had the power and the will to act in order to create the world from eternity, and because every agent that has the power and the will to act to create an effect does so, God did create the world as coeternal to himself. The ninth argument states that since every new effect requires something new on the part of its principles, and since nothing new can be added to the supreme cause that is God, all his effects must be coeternal with Him.⁵³³ The tenth argument tries to prove the necessity of the first mover being eternal in motion by saying that all other motions depend on the first, and since an *ad infinitum* series of causes is impossible, the first cause must be eternal in motion. The eleventh argument states that every postponed willing awaits for something. However, the divine will did not have to await for anything to create. His effects are not postponed and, therefore, are coeternal with Him. The twelfth argument is in line with the seventh onward. Namely, between the first cause and its creation there couldn’t have been time or eternity. Therefore, the cause and its effect must be eternal. We might say that the thirteenth and final argument is a summary of the last group of arguments. It states that every effect must be preceded by change, and since there was no time before the *ex nihilo* creation, there could not have been change either. As conclusion, creation must be understood as eternal.

⁵³⁰ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 42.

⁵³¹ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 42.

⁵³² Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 42.

⁵³³ Cf. Thomas' argument of similar nature above.

Before the solution and the answers to the thirteen arguments for the eternity of the world, Boethius presents an interesting *intermezzi* in his argumentation. This is my reconstruction of the argumentation that Boethius lays down before his solution:

Thesis 1) The effect of an eternal cause does not need to be coeternal with it since the eternal cause could have willed to create his effect in time.⁵³⁴

Contra Thesis 1) (1): Since *Thesis 1)* relies on inferring about the reasons behind the actions of the divine cause, it is just as probable to suggest that the divine cause willed to create its effect eternally.

Contra Thesis 1) (2) If God willed from eternity to create the world in a certain temporal moment, then He would not be able to create it at another time. This is unacceptable with regards to God's omnipotence and freedom of will.

Thesis 2) The idea that God eternally willed to create the world at a certain moment does not lessen his omnipotence or freedom of will. This is because God was open to eternally willing the temporal creation of the world at any given moment in time, but He chose a certain moment in time, thus necessarily eliminating the possibility of temporal creation in all other temporal moments.

Contra Thesis 2) (1) God could not have been open to eternally will any certain moment for the creation of the world since God's will is eternal and unchangeable.

Contra Thesis 2) (2) For every effect, there needs to be change, either in the agent or in the subject. Since there could be no change in the divine will and since there is no proper subject of creation before the creation itself, creation needs to be understood eternally.⁵³⁵

Contra Thesis 1) (3) Every new effect requires some change, in at least one of three ways: 1) In the one who wills, 2) in the subject willed, or 3) in the moment coming to pass. In the creation *ex nihilo* neither of the three requirements are met. Namely, the divine will cannot change (1), the subject of the divine will does not properly exist (2), and since there is no time before creation, the moment cannot come to pass (3). Therefore, since every effect requires some change, and since temporal creation does not involve change, it is impossible that an eternal being willed from eternity to create in a certain moment in time.

At the end of this exposition, Boethius adds that these arguments are those that the heretics use to prove that the world is eternal and thus they contradict the Christian faith. Precisely because of this, it is important to know how to answer them, and this is what Boethius will do after the Solution.⁵³⁶

⁵³⁴ Boethius of Dacia, On the Eternity of the World, 45.

⁵³⁵ Boethius of Dacia, On the Eternity of the World, 45.

⁵³⁶ Boethius of Dacia, On the Eternity of the World, 47.

Boethius starts the Solution by asserting the importance and legitimacy of philosophy. Because philosophy deals with all types of being (natural, mathematical, and divine), and because all that is part of being can be determined by arguments, philosophy must deal with everything that falls under the scope of argumentation. He adds a strong word against those that would like to limit the scope of philosophy and philosophers.⁵³⁷ The main claim of the Solution is that none of the three “disciplines” of philosophy can in fact show by argumentation that the first motion and the world was created. Boethius lays down two important presuppositions. The first one concerns those claims that any one kind of science can make. Namely, anything that “one that does science” (*facit scientiam*) can “prove, concede, or deny,”⁵³⁸ he can do only within the principles of his own science (*principiis suae scientiae*).⁵³⁹ The second important presupposition is that the results of natural philosophy are not absolute, but are nevertheless true within the scope of natural principles.

After giving these two important caveats, Boethius intends to show why neither of the three types of philosophers can show that the world had a beginning in time. Within the scope of natural principles, the natural philosopher cannot prove that the world had a beginning. Boethius spends the most time on this, and less time on the inability of the mathematicians and the metaphysicians of doing the same. Firstly, every change in motion requires the previous motion as its cause. However, for the first motion to exist, it - *per definitionem* - cannot be preceded by a previous motion. This goes against the principles of natural philosophy and is something that a natural philosopher cannot prove. Secondly, change in the effect requires novelty in one of its principles. But, the novelty in the principles cannot be posited without change in the principles. Therefore, nature cannot produce change without previous change. But, since an actually existing series of changers *ad infinitum* is impossible, there still needs to be a first cause. That is why Aristotle concludes that the first motion must be eternal. What follows from the first two arguments is that the natural philosopher cannot deal with creation. Namely, nature produces all its effects from a subject and from matter. This production is called generation and is the proper object of natural philosophy. On the other hand, creation *ex nihilo* does not involve neither matter nor a subject. Creation does not fall under the scope of natural principles, and since each science can only deal

⁵³⁷ Boethius of Dacia, On the Eternity of the World, 47.

⁵³⁸ Boethius of Dacia, On the Eternity of the World, 47.

⁵³⁹ In my reading of Boethius of Dacia, “science” (*scientia*) is a part of philosophy, which is why the natural philosopher is also called the “one who does science.” This *scientia* is understood as a series of truth-claims which rely on first principles and subsequent deductive argumentation. The difference between, e.g. the natural sciences (that are done by the natural philosopher) and theology (which is also taken by Boethius to be a science, different from the catholic faith itself) is that natural sciences rely on first principles which are demonstrable (such as mathematical truths). Theology, on the other hand, takes its first principles from the articles of faith, which are not demonstrable. However, all the subsequent “truths” of theology are thought to be deduced by the same procedure as in other sciences.

with those things which pertain to its own principles, natural philosophy cannot explain creation. Natural philosophy is also unable to explain the existence of the first man,⁵⁴⁰ since the first man was created, and not generated.⁵⁴¹ What should a natural philosopher say about those teachings of the Catholic faith that are not demonstrable within his own science? As long as they are not contrary to the principles of his science and do not “destroy” his science, he should not deny them. Boethius takes the Catholic teaching of the resurrection of every man after death as an example. According to the principles of nature, something corrupted cannot be generated again as numerically the same. Therefore, the natural philosopher claims that the resurrection of man after death is not possible according to the natural principles.

Boethius holds that both the natural philosopher and the believer are right in asserting their claims. The natural philosopher can claim that, according to the principles of nature, it is impossible that numerically the same man would be resurrected. The believer can claim that this is possible through a supernatural cause. Thus, there is no contradiction between the two claims, and the so-called theory of double truth⁵⁴² is not claimed in this text (*contra* the 1277 Condemnation). The same logic applies to the question of the eternity of the world.⁵⁴³ After giving a detailed account as to why a natural philosopher 1) cannot prove that the world is eternal and 2) does not contradict faith, Boethius goes to show that the same is true for the mathematician and the metaphysician. The metaphysician cannot establish neither that the world is eternal or finite. This is because all such reasoning presupposes the knowledge of the free intention of the divine will:

“To say that the metaphysician could demonstrate this is not only like a figment [of the imagination] but is, in my opinion, akin to madness. From whence does this reasoning come to man, by which he might perfectly investigate the divine will?”⁵⁴⁴

Boethius’ reasoning is against those that would like to rationally prove the finitude of the world, but also those that reason in favour of the eternity of the world. Boethius’ maxim is clear: There are truths of the Catholic faith which one needs to hold but cannot rationally prove. One of these is that the world was created as finite.

⁵⁴⁰ In the translation used, John F. Wippel uses the term “man.” However, the term used in the original is “homo” which can mean both man and human. The first created (according to the book of Genesis) is man, so that must have been the reason why Wippel translated it in such a way. Linked with this Here, it seems that Boethius writes about the creation of the first human, which is taken to be Adam.

⁵⁴¹ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 50.

⁵⁴² What Bianchi calls the “Mostro che si chiama ‘teoria della doppia verità’” (Monster which is called ‘the theory of double truth’], cf. Bianchi, *L’errore*, 180.

⁵⁴³ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 53.

⁵⁴⁴ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 54.

Sophistical, dialectical, and demonstrative argumentation should not be used where they do not yield concrete results. Rather, one should accept that there are parts of the law (i.e. the Christian faith) that are non-demonstrable, which is precisely what makes it a creed, and not a science. Although Boethius intends to answer all the three different types of arguments given above (1. For the temporal creation of the world, 2. For the possibility of the eternal creation of the world, and 3. For the actual eternal creation of the world), he only gives the answers to the position that the world was created as eternal (3).

As regards the first argument, Boethius lays down the distinction between “incorruptibility” taken narrowly and broadly. Understood narrowly, it involves those things whose matter does not undergo corruption. In this sense, we might say that the world is incorruptible, and thus eternal. However, if “incorruptibility” is understood broadly as that which can exist without being caused to be by another, it does not apply to the world. This is because, the eternal world is caused and kept in being by God, who is the only being that is incorruptible in the broad sense, because it is not kept in being by another. Boethius calls the keeping in being the principle of conservation. Replying to the second argument, Boethius attacks the idea of the eternal being as “that which admits of no duration before itself,”⁵⁴⁵ because, although there is no time before the world, there is [divine] eternity. Furthermore, he disagrees that a being which is preceded by eternity cannot exist. Suppose the world is actually eternal, says Boethius. Then, if a being will start existing in three days, before that happens, the whole of eternity will have to be traversed. Nonetheless, it does not make sense to say that this being would not exist.⁵⁴⁶ Boethius does not delve into why this *non sequitur* is in fact impossible. My interpretation is that he relies on the fact of experience. Namely, we see new beings being generated and existing, and that would be the case even if the world were eternal. Therefore, every new generation does not presuppose the necessity of traversing the whole of eternity.

Boethius replies to the third argument by stating that, although there was no matter before creation, there was a different type of potency. This potency (*potentia*) is in the agent (God), because He needed to have this to create the world. His reply to the fourth argument is that change is necessary for generation, but not creation. Against the fifth argument, Boethius clears up the terminology by stating that the world was not created *in* time, but *with* time, thus dispelling the objection that the world could not have started when time started. As a response to the sixth argument, Boethius rejects the principle which states that every corruption is preceded by a generation, because this would negate the possibility of the existence of a first man. According to

⁵⁴⁵ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 60.

⁵⁴⁶ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 60.

natural causes, this principle is correct. However, in light of creation, this principle cannot be defended. Boethius' response to the seventh argument is similar to the sixth. Namely, he grants the principle that every new effect follows from something that is missing in the agent. This he only grants partially, concerning natural causes and effects. God, as a supernatural cause, can create out of his free will. To the eighth argument, Boethius answers that the prerequisites of action existed in God, but only at the moment of creation, and not before. Thus, there is no necessity in God's creation, since it is limited to the moment of creation. To the ninth argument, Boethius answers that there does not need to be a new principle in every cause of an effect, but only in natural causes. This is because non-natural causes have free wills, which can decide despite their natural principles (or lack thereof).

To answer the tenth argument, Boethius denies that every motion must start in an eternal motion. Rather, every motion must start in a first motion that does not necessarily need to be eternal. In the eleventh argument, Boethius argues against the idea that, if God decided to create the world temporally, then there would have needed to be postponement in the will. Boethius says that this is correct for a will in time. However, since the eternal will is outside time, postponement that includes duration does not apply. Boethius rejects the conclusion of the twelfth argument. Namely, because there cannot be time or eternity between God and creation, creation has to be coeternal with God. This is rejected using the Boethian distinction between the eternal now, and the a-temporal now.⁵⁴⁷ As regards the thirteenth argument, Boethius asserts that positing an intention in God to create the world in a certain moment in time is not sophistical, because not everything that cannot be rationally demonstrated is a figment of imagination.⁵⁴⁸ Against the thirteenth argument, Boethius states that the necessity of change prior to every effect does not apply to the divine will.

Afterwards, he again asserts that both the arguments for and against the eternity of the world are sophistical. At the end, Boethius asserts his teaching on the difference between philosophy and Revelation. He uses the teaching on the Resurrection of man, which is impossible according to the Philosopher, but true according to the Catholic faith. However, they are both in the right, since it is in fact impossible to prove this according only to natural causes, and thus a supernatural cause is needed.

⁵⁴⁷ Here I am referring to the early medieval Boethius, Anicius Manlius Severinus Boethius (d.524). He makes this distinction in the Fifth Book of his *De Consolatione Philosophiae*.

⁵⁴⁸ Boethius of Dacia, *On the Eternity of the World*, 64.

Conclusion

In the Conclusion, I will give the answers to the proposed research questions given in the Introduction, based on the analyses of the primary sources in the main part of the paper.

The first question was: “Can philosophy prove that the world was created in time?”

Thomas rejects this possibility. He does this by showing that creation does not necessarily suggest a temporal precedence neither of cause to effect, nor of non-being to being. Furthermore, Thomas thinks that the argument against the actually existing infinity of souls is inconclusive, and therefore does not prove the finiteness of the world.

Boethius also rejects this possibility, but in a slightly different way. Namely, Boethius thinks that no *scientia*⁵⁴⁹ (and thus also no natural philosophy) can inquire into the ways in which God created the world. This, then, excludes both the philosophical arguments for the eternity and for the finiteness of the world. What natural philosophy can prove is only that, within the principles of nature, God could not have created the world as finite. This statement is in fact correct, even under the scope of theology.

The second question was: “Could God have created the world as eternal?”

For Thomas the answer to this question is positive. By rejecting all the possible counter arguments for the opposite position, Thomas arrives at the conclusion that it was possible for God to have created the world as eternal, although He did not do so. Therefore, by imploring the philosophical method, Thomas gives an affirmative answer to this question.

On the other hand, Boethius does not touch on this question directly. Instead, he takes an agnostic stance on the matter. Namely, the will of God, in the process of creation is not knowable to humans. That being said, one who believes knows by faith (because God revealed it to humanity) that God did in fact create the world as finite. Reasonings, both for and against the possibility of the world being created as eternal, are deemed “sophistical and weak” by Boethius. Therefore, I believe that the contrafactual question posed by Thomas would be deemed “sophistical” by Boethius of Dacia.

⁵⁴⁹ Cf. fn. 59.

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Bodies as rhetorical devices in Salimbene de Adam's Cronica: The case of Alberico Da Romano

DAVIDE POLITI

MA student, CEU Vienna

Abstract

As an experienced narrator, Salimbene de Adam (d. 1288) presents himself as a neutral author while constructing, in his chronicle, a sort of anti-hagiography of the Ghibelline lord Alberico da Romano (d. 1260). Utilising the recurring metaphor of the body, Salimbene delineates an interplay of intertextual references. By analysing and unravelling this narrative, I show the manifold meanings that could be contained within the metaphor of the body in the Middle Ages, spanning through all the stages of the spectrum which goes from sacred to profane, and revealing the techniques employed by the author to manipulate the reactions of his audience.

Keywords: Narratology – Salimbene de Adam – Alberico da Romano – Bodies – Middle Ages

Introduction

Due to the close relationship between human bodies and the personhood they externally manifest, narratives focusing on bodies hold significant power and versatility. Authors, throughout history and into the present, have depicted and narrated bodies to construct and communicate their discourses to a targeted audience. A prime example of this can be found in the opening of Michel Foucault's *Discipline and Punish*, which recounts with gruesome details the 18th-century execution of Robert-François Damiens for his attempted assassination of king Louis XV.⁵⁵⁰ Few other scenes could have enabled Foucault to captivate and impact readers so profoundly, whilst simultaneously exemplifying his conception of physical punishment in the *ancien régime*. Similarly, pre-modern authors frequently employed bodies within their texts as conceptual frameworks, navigating across a thematic spectrum that includes the sacred, the secular, and even the grotesque.⁵⁵¹

Owing to the narrative and rhetorical versatility inherent in the concept of “bodies,” historians can fruitfully examine texts which describe them, in order to gain insights into the mentalities of the respective authors, as well as to understand the broader socio-cultural contexts from which these works emerged.

An ideal example to demonstrate this theory is found in Salimbene de Adam's *Cronica*, penned around the 1280s.⁵⁵² An Italian Franciscan friar, Salimbene composed his chronicle with a focus on the historical events of Northern Italy, particularly underscoring the conflicts between the imperial and ecclesiastical factions, also known as Ghibellines and Guelphs, respectively. He predominantly conveys a viewpoint that favours the latter faction.⁵⁵³ Unfortunately, no other works by Salimbene survived, and even the *Cronica* itself is incomplete, with its initial sections missing. Nevertheless, in the part that survives, this chronicle provides an account of events spanning from 1168 to 1287.⁵⁵⁴

⁵⁵⁰ Michel Foucault, *Discipline and Punish: The Birth of the Prison*, trans. Alan Sheridan (New York: Vintage Books, 1995). The description of the execution takes place on pp. 3–6.

⁵⁵¹ An extensive scholarly work dealing with the importance in the middle ages of the holy relics and of the sacred bodies they represented is Patrick J. Geary's *Furta Sacra: Thefts of Relics in the Central Middle Ages* (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1991). The grotesque aspect of the bodily metaphor, linked especially to descriptions of bodily fluids, has instead been analysed by Mikhail Bakhtin in his seminal work *Rabelais and His World*, trans. Helene Iswolsky (Bloomington: Indiana University Press, 1984).

⁵⁵² For an in-depth biography of Salimbene please refer to Enrico Menestò, “La figura di Salimbene de Adam,” in *Salimbene de Adam e la “Cronica”* (Spoleto: Fondazione CISAM, 2018), 1–20. It is worth noting that, while the final entries in the *Cronica* date back to 1287, the year prior to his death, Salimbene likely dedicated many years of his life to this composition, possibly incorporating even earlier writings into the final work.

⁵⁵³ Menestò, “La figura di Salimbene de Adam,” 7.

⁵⁵⁴ Menestò, “La figura di Salimbene de Adam,” 5–6.

As a Franciscan friar, Salimbene was also a preacher, and he displays his narrative expertise in the extensive digressions he takes in the midst of his annalistic narration.⁵⁵⁵ In one such digression, he delves into the story of Alberico Da Romano, the Ghibelline lord of Treviso and a staunch adversary of the ecclesiastical faction.⁵⁵⁶ Whilst Salimbene frequently asserts his own neutrality as a historian, it becomes apparent that he skilfully manoeuvres the narration to convince the audience of Alberico's malevolent character, thus subtly aligning his account with the propagandistic efforts of the ecclesiastical faction.⁵⁵⁷

In the following analysis, I adhere to the sequence of Salimbene's narration as presented in the *Cronica*, augmenting it with my own commentary and contextualisation. My goal is to trace the process by which the author, an expert narrator as I will show, constructs his discourse, and to speculate on the meanings Salimbene might have attempted to convey and the reactions he likely expected to provoke in his audience.⁵⁵⁸

My work is particularly indebted to two scholarly papers published by Claudia Sebastiana Nobili, which dissect the narrative strategies employed by Salimbene.⁵⁵⁹ Notably, Nobili underscores how Ezzelino Da Romano (d. 1259), Alberico's brother, is portrayed by Salimbene as in opposition to Francis of Assisi, providing a stark contrast to both characters. By observing this rhetorical construction, Nobili highlights how Salimbene's narration is deliberately and carefully weighted to ensure that the audience perceives Ezzelino as genuinely evil.⁵⁶⁰

The narrative regarding Alberico appears to pursue a similar goal to that of Ezzelino, but is notably more focused and confined to just a few pages. I also posit that Salimbene's portrayal of Alberico not only serves its own purpose, but also plays a crucial role in further contributing to the development of the characterization of his brother, Ezzelino. This aspect of the narrative, however, is elaborated upon towards the conclusion of this paper.

⁵⁵⁵ Pascale Bourgain, "Langue et style chez Salimbene, entre prétentions savantes et spontanéité," in *Salimbene de Adam e la "Cronica,"* 149.

⁵⁵⁶ Alberico Da Romano, a descendant of a noble Northern Italian family aligned with the imperial cause, served as the podesta of Treviso and died in 1260. The entirety of the story of Alberico analysed is edited in Salimbene de Adam, *Cronica*, ed. Giuseppe Scalia (Bari: Laterza, 1966), 528–533. For his biography, see Dario Canzian, "Romano, Alberico da," in *Dizionario Biografico degli Italiani* (Rome: Istituto dell'Enciclopedia Italiana, 2017).

⁵⁵⁷ On Salimbene's professed neutrality please refer to Claudia Sebastiana Nobili, "La Cronica e la pluralità dei generi letterari," in *Salimbene de Adam e la "Cronica,"* 236.

⁵⁵⁸ In this paper I use the term "audience" rather than "readers" to underscore that medieval books were usually read out aloud, sometimes in the presence of the very author who would clarify any doubts regarding their content. Therefore, they were not just directed at those who could read. Salimbene himself illustrates this process in his *Cronica*, at p. 298, when he describes the Franciscan friar Giovanni da Pian del Carpine who "wrote a great book [...] and he had that book read, as I heard and saw several times [...] and when those who read marveled or did not understand, he would explain and discuss the individual things" ([S]cripsit unum magnum librum [...] et faciebat illum librum legi, ut pluries audivi et vidi [...] et ubi mirabantur vel non intelligebant legentes, ipse exponebat et disserebat de singulis).

⁵⁵⁹ These are: Claudia Sebastiana Nobili, "La costruzione del personaggio fra letteratura e storia: Salimbene da Parma e Dante," in *La letteratura e la storia*, eds. Elisabetta Menetti and Carlo Varotti (Bologna: Gedit, 2007), 315–336; and Nobili, "La Cronica e la pluralità dei generi letterari," 233–250.

⁵⁶⁰ Nobili, "La Cronica e la pluralità dei generi letterari."

Salimbene introduces Alberico Da Romano in the course of his narration and in a subtle way, almost in passing. In a specific paragraph, he lists the lords who reigned in the regions of Lombardy and Romagna. However, while all the other noblemen are merely mentioned by their name, Salimbene elaborates on Alberico with an extended commentary, writing that this imperial vicar and podesta of Treviso was a true *membrum diaboli*, just like his brother Ezzelino, and that for this reason, he met a tragic fate, along with his wife and his offspring.⁵⁶¹ The epithet *membrum diaboli* is the first bodily metaphor in this narration and literally translates to “a piece of the devil’s body,” an expression which in the context of medieval literature could imply an act of “conscious separation from the body of Christ through sin.”⁵⁶²

The Execution

Following this introduction, Salimbene describes the death of both Alberico and his family. He narrates a harrowing scene where the people of Treviso, after having captured their former podesta, tore off the limbs of his sons and used them to strike his face.⁵⁶³ I suggest that in this, as in other passages, Salimbene considers the entire family as an extension of Alberico’s body. Indeed, the notion of a collective familial body is reinforced in a later passage, when Salimbene states that Alberico’s family was doomed to suffer because of the sins of its patriarch.⁵⁶⁴ The specific manner in which Salimbene chooses to motivate the fate of the other members of the Da Romano family suggests that he views them as fundamentally intertwined with, and enduring the consequences of, Alberico’s own actions, while also implying that their suffering is not separate, but an extension of the punishment meted out to Alberico himself. The motif of collective identity and of familial fate tied to that of the patriarch is, after all, a recurring element in the analysed narration, which will be explored in greater detail further on in the paper. Thus, the act of the sons’ limbs striking the father would mainly symbolise the metaphorical body of Alberico’s family as in revolt against itself.

Subsequently, Salimbene describes the burning at the stake of Alberico’s wife and of his daughters. The young girls, in particular, are described as beautiful and innocent, yet still having to share the retribution for their father’s sins. Salimbene’s omission of the names of any other member of the family, except for Alberico’s, further strips them of their individual identities, rendering them once again as a mere extension of Alberico’s persona. The climax of this tragic

⁵⁶¹ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 528.

⁵⁶² Gustav Zamore, “A peripheral Heretic? An Early Fourteenth-Century Heresy Trial from Sweden,” *Historical Research* 93, no. 262 (November 2020): 614, footnote 76.

⁵⁶³ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 528.

⁵⁶⁴ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 531, where the Venetians call for the death of Alberico and his family. Additionally, for a more comprehensive analysis of this incident and its implications, please refer to the section titled “The Crusade” in this paper.

episode has the people of Treviso gruesomely tearing away Alberico's flesh with pincers, until his entire body was "destroyed with mockery, infamy and terrible torment."⁵⁶⁵

Whilst Salimbene's account of this public execution provides a detailed depiction, it is not the sole contemporary record of these events. The chronicler Rolandino of Padova (d. 1276) too recounts the final moments of Alberico's life. In contrast to Salimbene's account, Rolandino provides the names of Alberico's wife and sons, and Alberico himself is humanised by being portrayed as hoping for his family's survival, so that they could have perpetuated his lineage. Notably, Rolandino also recounts the final act of mercy granted to Alberico by his executioners: to have the restraints on his mouth removed to allow him to confess and receive an absolution from a Franciscan friar present at the scene. On the other hand, Rolandino's description of the execution itself lacks the extensive and gruesome detail found in Salimbene's version.⁵⁶⁶

It is plausible that Salimbene was aware of these events, as he too references Alberico's final act of repentance. However, he chooses to mention this detail only after concluding the main narrative, which is predominantly focused on Alberico's crimes and punishment.⁵⁶⁷ This structuring suggests that Salimbene's primary intention was to underscore the gravity of Alberico's transgressions and the consequent retribution, with the acknowledgement of his repentance serving only as a secondary note.

Alberico's gory death brings to mind the already mentioned execution of Robert-François Damiens as recounted by Foucault: Alberico's body too is "effaced, [...] destroyed piece by piece," and here too an institutional authority decrees a death sentence and the manner of its implementation.⁵⁶⁸ Salimbene characterizes the wrath of the citizens as divine retribution which he justifies by listing the crimes that Alberico committed: he killed many of their relatives, and he asked for too many tributes. Furthermore, according to Salimbene, Alberico feigned a war against his brother Ezzelino to steal and destroy even more than he was already doing.⁵⁶⁹ Thus, through the "infinitesimal destruction of the body" of Alberico and his family, the tyrant's power is also destroyed.⁵⁷⁰ The intention to delete Alberico's power by annihilating his family is probably what

⁵⁶⁵ "[E]t sic destruxerunt corpus eius ludibriis et opprobriis et gravibus tormentis," Salimbene, *Cronica*, 528.

⁵⁶⁶ Rolandino of Padova, "De factis in Marchia Tarvisina libri XII," ed. Felice Osio in *Rerum Italicarum Scriptores*, ed. Ludovico Antonio Muratori (Milan, Stamperia della Società Palatina: 1726), 8:358.

⁵⁶⁷ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 533. Perhaps Salimbene knew that repentance happened precisely because there were Franciscans witnessing the execution. On the sources used by Salimbene, mainly first-hand accounts by other Franciscan friars, please refer to Nobili, "La costruzione del personaggio," 333.

⁵⁶⁸ The quotation comes from Foucault, *Discipline and Punish*, 50. For the death sentence of Alberico and his family issued by the city of Treviso see Gian Battista Verci ed., "Sententia Marci Badoarii Potestatis Tarvisii contra illos de Romano," in *Storia degli Ecelini* (Bassano: Remondini, 1779), 3:421–423. Both Salimbene's and Rolandino's accounts differ from what was established by this document, according to which the male members of the family were simply to be hanged.

⁵⁶⁹ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 528.

⁵⁷⁰ The quotation comes from Foucault, *Discipline and Punish*, 51.

motivated the actual sentence in the first place, for the connection between those bodies and the power of the da Romano house must have been clear to the citizens of Treviso.⁵⁷¹

The Hanging

According to Nobili's analysis, characters in the *Cronica* can be classified according to their complexity. Some of them are "flat," static, and easily defined with few epithets, while others are "round," dynamic, and during the narration undergo a significant transformation.⁵⁷² Alberico's literary character would certainly fall into the former category, as his whole persona can be summarised in just a few sentences. Salimbene refers to him as "the cursed Alberico," unchanging in his deviancy.⁵⁷³ Yet, a degree of dynamism is still added to the story by reversing the chronological order of events, thanks to progressive flashbacks which set up a climax of depravity, and effectively offer a justification for the brutal execution described at the outset. Therefore, by initially detailing the execution and then methodically revealing Alberico's transgressions, Salimbene first piques the audience's curiosity about the reasons behind such extreme violence, and then satisfies it with a narrative structure which gradually guides towards an understanding and eventual endorsement of his moral condemnation against Alberico.⁵⁷⁴

Salimbene continues the story by recounting that, during his rule as podesta of Treviso, Alberico ordered the execution by hanging of twenty-five prominent men, suspecting them of conspiracy. Additionally, he also intended to mutilate the noses of their female relatives but was dissuaded by the intervention of an unnamed man Alberico believed to be his illegitimate son.⁵⁷⁵ Salimbene points out that this man was not Alberico's actual son, and this clarification might serve a precise function: all those who were related to Alberico ended up participating in his suffering, as if they were part of his own body. Therefore this man, who would later be spared because of his show of piety, could not have been a member of the ill-fated Da Romano lineage, not to break the thematic consistency constructed by the narrative. As the story progresses Alberico, diverging from his initial cruel intention, ordered instead the women's dresses to be cut just above their breasts, leaving them naked below that point, while also subjecting the condemned men to witness this act of humiliation. Such forceful undressing is an ancient and unequivocal method of shaming, particularly for women. In the Bible, this act is likened to the degradation reserved for prostitutes,

⁵⁷¹ Cf. "Sententia contra de Romano," 421–423.

⁵⁷² Nobili, "La costruzione del personaggio," 320.

⁵⁷³ "[M]aledictus Albricus," Salimbene, *Cronica*, 531.

⁵⁷⁴ Cf. Nobili, "La Cronica e la pluralità," 237, 239.

⁵⁷⁵ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 529.

a detail which foreshadows some further elements of the narration, and which connects this passage to the conclusion of Alberico's story.⁵⁷⁶

It has been noted that "the clothed body in medieval literature promotes a civilised social identity."⁵⁷⁷ Salimbene himself links clothing to feminine identity, noting in another, distinct passage of his chronicle the adverse reaction of some noblewomen to sumptuary laws that banned long dresses, a prohibition which, he says, they found "more bitter than death."⁵⁷⁸ Additionally, those same women were forced by law to wear veils on their head, reflecting the contemporary conception that hair was a symbol of feminine sexuality.⁵⁷⁹ Consequently, it is significant that the women humiliated by Alberico retain their headdresses, maintaining a symbol of their still-intact womanly virtue. Yet, their forceful undressing still removes them from the sphere of civilised society, and they lose their social identity, if not for a figment of their dignified self which is implied in their covered hair.⁵⁸⁰

The women, now stripped of their garments, were forced to walk beneath the hanging men, and as they passed, those who were dying struck their relatives with their feet, in their involuntary, final spasms.⁵⁸¹ This scene could be interpreted as a recurring metaphor, symbolically conveying that the women experienced the death of their relatives through their own physical suffering, mirroring the fate of Alberico's family. Additionally, the kicks by their family members that they endure echo the already depicted scene where Alberico is battered with the limbs of his own sons. Salimbene employs these subtle but constant references to Alberico's execution as narrative tools, ensuring that the audience remains engaged and attentive to the thematic thread he unwinds.

Ultimately, the women were abandoned in the wilderness, wearing just the tattered remnants of their garments, which they repurposed to cover their genitalia.⁵⁸² Salimbene draws

⁵⁷⁶ Ez 16:39. In the *New International Version Bible* this passage reads "Then I will deliver you into the hands of your lovers, and they will tear down your mounds and destroy your lofty shrines. They will strip you of your clothes and take your fine jewelry and leave you stark naked." However, in the *Biblia Sacra Vulgata*, the Latin edition of the Bible, this passage is somewhat different: "Et dabo te in manus eorum, et destruent lupanar tuum, et demolientur prostibulum tuum: et denudabunt te vestimentis tuis, et auferent vasa decoris tui, et derelinquent te nudam, plenamque ignominia." Instead of "mounds," here we find the word *lupanar*, which unequivocally means "brothel," establishing a direct association between forceful undressing and prostitution.

⁵⁷⁷ Rihanne Whitney, "Undressing Medieval Bodies: Exploring Sin, Shame and Sexuality through Representations of Nudity and Nakedness in the Middle Ages," (MA thesis, University of Leiden, 2021), 4; cf. Leora Auslander, "Deploying Material Culture to Write the History of Gender and Sexuality: The Example of Clothing and Textiles," *Clio* 40 (2014): 158-159.

⁵⁷⁸ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 246.

⁵⁷⁹ Marian Bleeke, Jennifer Borland, Rachel Dressler, Martha Easton, and Elizabeth L'Estrange, "Artistic Representation: Women and/in Medieval Visual Culture," in *A Cultural History of Women in the Middle Ages*, ed. Kim M. Phillips (London: Bloomsbury 2013), 197.

⁵⁸⁰ Whitney, "Undressing Medieval Bodies," 54.

⁵⁸¹ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 529-530.

⁵⁸² "Operuerunt sibi membra genitalia, id est pudenda," Salimbene, *Cronica*, 530.

poignant parallels between their ordeal and the plights of biblical figures such as Susanna, whose honour was compromised but later restored, and the adulteress whom Jesus saved from stoning.⁵⁸³ Furthermore, he also mentions the prophet Isaiah, who was brutally killed by being sawn in half by soldiers.⁵⁸⁴ These scriptural references serve a dual purpose in Salimbene's narrative. Firstly, they anchor the author's account to revered biblical passages, lending it an aura of authority. Secondly, the mention of these distressed biblical women evokes once again the traumatic experience suffered by the women of Treviso. Additionally, the reference to Isaiah's martyrdom in this passage, and to his body being effaced by his torturers, also serves as a foreboding echo of the grim fate that would befall Alberico. Through these parallels and repetitions, Salimbene effectively sustains and enlivens the prevailing theme of the body.⁵⁸⁵

Monsters on the Shore

Salimbene continues his story by introducing a fisherman who initially mistook the naked women for "illusions of demons, ghosts, or sea monsters."⁵⁸⁶ This association emphasises the profound loss of social identity and human status that has been forced upon the women, who are transfigured into monstrous creatures. Indeed, in the Middle Ages nudity was generally associated with exotic otherness, while being clothed was considered to be the natural state of the socialised human being.⁵⁸⁷ Furthermore, the anxiety for covering exposed genitalia displayed by the women echoes the biblical narrative of the expulsion from Eden, when Adam and Eve found themselves in need to cover their exposed nakedness. This allusion situates the women in a context akin to humanity's fall from grace, symbolically reverting them to what was considered to be the most grievous moment in human history, at least according to the canonical Christian perspective.

The Crusade

The narration continues with the fisherman eventually approaching the women and aiding them in reaching the nearby city of Venice. There, a new character takes the stage: archbishop Ottaviano degli Ubaldini (d. 1273), a papal legate representing the ecclesiastical faction's interests, and an opponent to Alberico, who belonged to the rival faction. Thus, on the following day, Ottaviano gathered the populace in San Marco's square to publicly display the women, still naked as Alberico

⁵⁸³ The first episode refers to the narrative of Susanna and the Elders, in the thirteenth chapter of the Book of Daniel. The episode of the adulteress, instead, comes from John 7:53–8:11.

⁵⁸⁴ The death of Isaiah is not described in the canonical Bible. Instead, Salimbene refers to extrabiblical narrations.

⁵⁸⁵ On the use of repetitions in Salimbene's narratives, please refer to Nobili "La Cronica e la pluralità," 236; Nobili, "La costruzione del personaggio," 320.

⁵⁸⁶ "[I]llusiones demonum seu fantasmata aut certe monstra marina. Horribiliter timuit," Salimbene, *Cronica*, 530.

⁵⁸⁷ Whitney, "Undressing Medieval Bodies," 8, 32, 53.

had left them.⁵⁸⁸ This sight incited a vehement response from the Venetians, who cried out in outrage: “Death, death to that cursed man, and may he be burned alive with his wife and with all his children.”⁵⁸⁹ A crusade was thus proclaimed to avenge the hanging of those men and the shaming of those women, a detail that Salimbene repeats in full, deliberately reminding its significance for his audience.⁵⁹⁰

The promptness of the reaction of the Venetian population demonstrates just how straightforward the outrage generated by such a scene could have been for the medieval public. Nevertheless, as the noblewomen were exposed to everyone’s sight without any regard for their dignity, it is possible that their shame may have lied not so much in nudity per se, but in the violence they endured by being degraded to sub-human status through forceful undressing.⁵⁹¹

The Ultimate Sin

Although the crusade inflicted substantial harm on Alberico, it did not result in his complete defeat, which instead would come at a later point, a fact that Salimbene reminds to an audience which already knows this, thanks to the first part of the narration.

However, to further justify the extreme retribution which led Alberico’s family to be eradicated, Salimbene narrates a final anecdote: once, during a hunt, upon losing his falcon Alberico even dared to show his ass to God in an extreme act of defiance.⁵⁹² Furthermore, upon returning to the city, he committed an even more blasphemous act inside the cathedral: he desecrated the altar by defecating on it, in the very place where the holy host was consecrated.⁵⁹³

Defecation was an unambiguous act of defilement in the Middle Ages,⁵⁹⁴ and Salimbene himself employs the same metaphor elsewhere, when describing a bishop whom he considered to be a grave sinner, recounting that “a dog shat on him after he was buried [...]. He should have been buried in a dunghill.”⁵⁹⁵ While in medieval texts, bodily functions held a comical undertone too, Salimbene seems to be markedly serious in telling of Alberico’s sins.⁵⁹⁶ Any mockery present here

⁵⁸⁸ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 530.

⁵⁸⁹ “Moriatur, moriatur maledictus ille et vivus ardeat cum uxore, et tota eius progenies de hoc seculo extirpetur,” Salimbene, *Cronica*, 531.

⁵⁹⁰ Cf. Nobili, “La Cronica e la pluralità,” 244.

⁵⁹¹ Cf. Whitney, “Undressing Medieval Bodies,” 10, 34.

⁵⁹² “[C]um tota sua progenie penitus est deletus [...]. [E]xtraxit sibi bracas et culum ostendit Deo in signum opprobrii et convitii atque derisionis,” Salimbene, *Cronica*, 532.

⁵⁹³ “[C]accavit super altare, in eo loco proprie ubi consecratur Dominicum corpus.” Salimbene, *Cronica*, 532.

⁵⁹⁴ Bakhtin, *Rabelais and His World*, 147-48.

⁵⁹⁵ “[E]t scio quod canis cacavit super eum, postquam sepultus fuit [...]. Revera dignus erat in sterquilinum sepeliri,” Salimbene, *Cronica*, 758.

⁵⁹⁶ On the comical undertone of bodily functions please refer to Bakhtin, *Rabelais and His World*, 151-52.

is directed not at the act itself, but at Alberico's audacity in assuming that he could have behaved in such a way towards God without suffering any consequence.⁵⁹⁷

Finally, and to reinforce this anti-hagiography with one last detail, Salimbene further adds that Alberico's wife used to call other noblewomen "whores and harlots," a behaviour that her husband did not challenge.⁵⁹⁸ The accusation implied towards Alberico here seems to be that of failing to adhere to the societal expectation of maintaining order within his household, flouting the established gender norms. Additionally, this account provides an additional reference to the treatment that Alberico reserved for the women from Treviso: he treated them like prostitutes, and his wife proves to be no different, even if only through words. Thus, even with this last passage, Salimbene ensures that the audience fully grasps the intended moral condemnation towards Alberico.

The Body of Christ and the Body of the Devil

Alberico's act of desecration against what was considered to be the holiest of relics, the eucharist, could be interpreted in relation to the epithet *membrum diaboli* assigned to him at the beginning of the story. This couple of words set up a critical juxtaposition: rather than partaking in the holy communion and becoming one with Christ, a member of His body, Alberico defiles the holy host and becomes a member of the body of Christ's enemy, as if he had performed a perverse inversion of the communion ritual.⁵⁹⁹

Thus, the narrative arc reaches its culmination with Alberico's ultimate sin against the body of Christ, representing the gravest possible transgression. Consequently, Alberico pays the price for his actions with his own body. In a metaphorical replication of his own rebellion against the Eternal Father, he also experiences torment by being struck by the limbs of his own sons. The recurrence with which the same images are repeated demonstrates a deliberate intent on Salimbene's part in weaving a coherent narrative rich in internal references.⁶⁰⁰

⁵⁹⁷ I capitalise the initial letter of God and referrants to him here and elsewhere out of my personal convictions.

⁵⁹⁸ "[D]ominas et matronas appellabat putanas et meretrices." Salimbene, *Cronica*, 532.

⁵⁹⁹ Cf. Zamore, "A peripheral Heretic?" 614: "Instead of becoming a member of the body of Christ through consuming the consecrated host, Botulf has, through 'vomiting forth his error,' become a member of the body of the Devil, separated from the body of the faithful."

⁶⁰⁰ Nobili, "La costruzione del personaggio," 329.

The Repenting and the Tale of Ezzelino

Contrasting with the extensive narrative dedicated to the more (in)famous Ezzelino, the account on Alberico is confined to just a few pages, and his name is scarcely mentioned elsewhere in the *Cronica*, as if the obliteration of his body had been so absolute that not even his memory had survived it. However, it is likely that Salimbene's primary purpose in introducing Alberico in these pages is to set the stage for the subsequent account of Ezzelino, providing a term of comparison to magnify the enormity of the latter's crimes: while Alberico hanged twenty-five men, Ezzelino burned 11,000 men in a single day.⁶⁰¹ Moreover, while Alberico repented just before his death, Ezzelino persisted in his wickedness until the end.⁶⁰² This stark contrast is seemingly designed to impress upon the audience that Alberico's tale is merely a prelude to the truly heinous character of his brother, thereby amplifying anticipation for the ensuing passages about Ezzelino.

As Ezzelino's story takes the stage, Alberico fades into the background and is never referred to again, despite having, in reality, outlived his brother. The fleeting mention to Alberico's repentance suggests that Salimbene was likely aware of more than he chose to disclose, probably owing to the testimony of the Franciscans who, according to Rolandino of Padova, were present at the execution. Salimbene's selective narration can be interpreted as a deliberate decision to avoid humanizing Alberico, in order to maintain the moral thrust of his tale. Thus, the nuanced tragicity of Alberico's character as depicted by Rolandino finds no place in Salimbene's chronicle.

⁶⁰¹ Salimbene, *Cronica*, 533.

⁶⁰² "However, upon his death, Alberico completely repented, while Ezzelino never went back to God" (Verumtamen in morte Albricus optime fuit contritus. Icilius vero nunquam est reversus ad Deum). Salimbene, *Cronica*, 533.

Conclusion

In this concise segment of his narrative, Salimbene demonstrates a masterful use of the metaphor of the body, imbuing it with multifaceted meanings. Alberico atones for his sins with his own body, a body which is also a symbol of power and that grows to encompass his entire family, unifying them as a singular entity. Furthermore, I have highlighted how forced undressing, but not necessarily nudity itself, could have been associated with humiliation and degradation in this particular context. Finally, Salimbene also uses the metaphor of the body to stage an intricate and allegorical perversion of the communion in the body of Christ.

These thematic elements are hardly coincidental; each aspect is carefully interwoven with the others, creating a complex tapestry of cross-references that engage the audience and subtly direct their moral discernment.⁶⁰³ Consequently, Salimbene's account is fictionalised at least to some extent, as it is strategically crafted to influence the audience's ethical conclusions, demonstrating in the process the prowess of the author as a storyteller, as well as his astute comprehension of the body as a potent rhetorical device.⁶⁰⁴

⁶⁰³ Nobili "La Cronica e la pluralità," 242, 246.

⁶⁰⁴ Nobili "La Cronica e la pluralità," 250; and Nobili, "La costruzione del personaggio," 330.

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Saxa loquuntur: Understanding ordinary people through the tales of stones

JELENA VUKOJEVIĆ

PhD Candidate, University of Belgrade

Abstract

Our knowledge of ancient history and classical antiquity, in general, depends largely on the accuracy and soundness of documentary evidence. The importance of epigraphic sources for our knowledge of the ancient world is undeniable. Inscriptions represent an essential primary source that stands before us as inscribed thousands of years ago. They contain thoughts that have not been distorted by copying errors and misinterpretations typically associated with manuscript transmission. A valuable resource for historians, archaeologists, and other fields of research, inscriptions provide data on a wide range of topics, including the history and organisation of the vast Roman Empire, laws, administration, religion, emperors, military, socioeconomic relations, and so on. However, epigraphy also provides insight into the lives of ordinary people and gives voice to those who have been brushed aside throughout history. Communities, families, and individuals who do not play a major role in politics or social upheaval, who care for their families and loved ones, who worship gods or a god, who experience loss and death, and who fulfil their duties, come alive before us thanks to epigraphic material. The purpose of this essay is to demonstrate the ways in which epigraphic corpora can enrich our understanding of the daily lives of people whose actions have left no lasting impression on the pages of history. We should take the opportunity to gain insight into their family dynamics, their views on family, religion, and duty. The stones also bring out their views on death, loss, and love, which make them seem not so distant. Loyal colleagues and friends, dutiful soldiers and citizens, grieving parents and loving spouses speak to us through inscriptions from all corners of the Roman Empire.

Keywords: Epigraphic Sources – Latin Inscriptions – Ordinary People – Grief and Loss – Microhistorical Perspective

Introduction

Numerous scholars emphasise the profound significance of ancient inscriptions as invaluable historical artefacts. Latin inscriptions, in particular, are unparalleled reservoirs of information concerning ancient Rome, a fact widely acknowledged within scholarly circles.⁶⁰⁵ They offer insights into various facets of Roman society, including social, vocational, familial, and religious dimensions. These inscriptions grant us a unique perspective into the microcosms of families, social circles, and smaller communities within the Roman Empire, shedding light on the lives of ordinary citizens.

Scholars increasingly use inscriptions to illuminate overlooked aspects of antiquity, particularly the lives of Roman women. Hemelrijk's comprehensive work is notable for consolidating inscriptions from Latin-speaking provinces, supported by illustrative examples culled from the sources pertinent to each of the findings.⁶⁰⁶ Similarly, the collection "Women's Lives, Women's Voices" is a successful interdisciplinary study, integrating inscriptions with visual and archaeological evidence from Pompeii and Herculaneum.⁶⁰⁷

Analysing inscriptions from specific provinces, municipalities, or cities, whether extensive or limited, offers a unique opportunity. It allows for a detailed examination, providing a comprehensive view of seemingly inconspicuous segments of the Empire. The following analysis adopts a microhistorical approach, delving into the daily lives of ordinary citizens within a developing Roman settlement. This challenges conventional historical perspectives that prioritise major political events and figures. It is posited that a thorough exploration of specific locales lays a robust foundation for a nuanced history of everyday life. By gathering comprehensive data from a single location, this approach fosters greater confidence in our findings, in that it allows us to scrutinise the societal roles, interpersonal dynamics, and values of its inhabitants, drawing insights directly from the records and remnants left behind by the very individuals whose lives we seek to illuminate. This stands in stark contrast to approaches reliant on generalisations drawn from selectively chosen materials across regions, where conclusions are often filtered through the historian's lens, taking into primary consideration the implications of such data on major historical events.

⁶⁰⁵ "The value of inscriptions as historical material is immense. They are contemporary and authoritative documents, whose text is a first-hand record- ... They are the most important single source for the history and organisation of the Roman Empire; and their cumulative and comparative value ... is astonishingly great." R. G. Collingwood and Ian Richmond, *The Archaeology of Roman Britain* (London: Methuen & Co. Ltd, 1969), 193.

⁶⁰⁶ Emily A. Hemelrijk, *Women and Society in the Roman World: A Sourcebook of Inscriptions from the Roman West* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2020).

⁶⁰⁷ Brenda Longfellow and Molly Swetnam-Burland, eds. *Women's Lives, Women's Voices: Roman Material Culture and Female Agency in the Bay of Naples* (Austin: University of Texas Press, 2021).

This research also places a crucial emphasis on studying emotions due to their potential influence on individuals' behaviour, choices, and interactions. By employing the framework of the history of emotions, historians aim to explore how societies perceived and valued emotions in specific historical periods, tracking the evolution of these concepts over time. This essay specifically delves into understanding how societal norms, religious beliefs, and political events impacted the emotional experiences of individuals or communities, with a particular focus on instances of love and grief. In this approach, the scarcity of reference material presents a common challenge, especially when dealing with marginalised subjects who left limited traces or documents detailing their lives and experiences. Despite this, epigraphic material as a primary source proves valuable, as it primarily provides unaltered information. The subjects provide insights in their own words, forming a direct dialogue with the researcher, even when mediated by a third party, like a stonemason shaping their thoughts.

This essay delves into a limited corpus of inscriptions from Sirmium, situated in Lower Pannonia. Due to its historical importance in the late Roman Empire, ample information about its public affairs is accessible. This makes it an apt subject for our examination, which extends beyond mere historical data. Despite its modest size, this corpus holds significance, enriching existing datasets and offering a nuanced portrayal of Sirmium's multifaceted existence.

Moving beyond traditional perspectives, a detailed examination of limited epigraphic corpora unveils insights into religious institutions, customs, and the reciprocal influence of new and old cultures, including potential syncretism between paganism and Christianity. This method confirms instances of laws and administrative regulations, providing a nuanced understanding of the balance between magistrates' formal duties and private lives. Funerary inscriptions also reveal family structures, allowing a focus on individuals' intricacies. Through a comparative study, we confirm the social and cultural development of a specific place, going beyond individual dynamics and challenges. This approach, inclusive of religious practices and cultural phenomena, prevents oversight during a focus on significant historical moments. At the core of this exploration is the individual, and examining how they navigated professions, communities, religions, and families is crucial. While the traditional approach, which prioritises onomastic and prosopographical analysis of inscriptions to extract historical evidence for reconstructing political, social, and economic aspects of ancient societies, has deepened our understanding of major changes, a novel perspective offers insights into the personal experiences of those impacted by them.

In this essay, I will rely primarily on funerary inscriptions. These form the majority of surviving inscriptions and yield extensive details about the dedicator(s) and honorand(s). Epitaphs reveal identities, family ties, occupations, social backgrounds, and ages at the time of passing. They

also commemorate relationships with friends, heirs, and patrons. Funerary monuments sometimes include depictions of the deceased and individuals with whom they shared significant bonds, thereby embedding the individual within a well-defined social and cultural milieu.⁶⁰⁸ While some inscriptions may be embellished for self-glorification, many sought to memorialise cherished family members and close associates. This sentiment extended beyond those in public life. The ostentatious tombs in prominent locations, once common, gradually diminished, especially in late antiquity. So much so that references to the tomb's commissioners eventually vanished.⁶⁰⁹

Sirmium

Sirmium, located on the marshy banks of the Sava River, held strategic advantages behind the Danubian *limes*. It was integrated into the Roman realm between 13 and 9 BCE under Octavian Augustus. Swiftly gaining military importance, Sirmium attained colonial status following the conclusion of the Domitian Wars along the Pannonian border.⁶¹⁰ Its peak came in the latter half of the third century, during a period of heightened frontier threats. Sirmium served as a vital hub for imperial activities, including troop gatherings, supreme command, imperial residence, and ceremonies.⁶¹¹ It gained the status of an imperial city and became the administrative centre for the province of Second Pannonia during the Tetrarchy, eventually extending its jurisdiction to the Illyric Prefecture.⁶¹² Its status as a significant Christian centre in the fourth and fifth centuries is also noteworthy.

Despite extensive excavations, only a fraction of Sirmium's history is known. Roman and Italian settlers, along with native Latin speakers, were present from the first century CE,⁶¹³ indicating the widespread adoption of the Latin language and culture. The embrace of Latin often coincided with adopting epigraphic practices, resulting in a valuable source of information. The Sirmium inscription corpus, comprising approximately three hundred inscriptions, varies in preservation, stone quality, length, dating, and typology.⁶¹⁴ Inscriptions are predominantly characterised as private in nature. As anticipated, a substantial portion of the corpus is constituted

⁶⁰⁸ Maureen Carroll, "Memoria and Damnatio Memoriae: Preserving and Erasing Identities in Roman Funerary Commemoration," in *Living through the Dead: Burial and Commemoration in the Classical World*, eds. M. Carroll and J. Rempel (Oxford: Oxbow Books, 2011), 65.

⁶⁰⁹ Jean-Marie Lassère, *Manuel d'épigraphie romaine I-II*, (Paris: Picard, 2005), I 238.

⁶¹⁰ András Mócsy, *Pannonia and Upper Moesia (Routledge Revivals): A History of the Middle Danube Provinces of the Roman Empire* (London: Routledge 2014), 112–113.

⁶¹¹ Miroslava Mirković, *Sirmium: its history from the First century AD to 582 AD* (Novi Sad: Faculty of Philosophy, Department of History, Centre for Historical Research, 2017), 11–12.

⁶¹² Mirković, *Sirmium*, 79.

⁶¹³ Mirković, *Sirmium*, 22.

⁶¹⁴ For further insights into the epigraphic habit, refer to Ramsay MacMullen, "The Epigraphic Habit in the Roman Empire," *The American Journal of Philology* 103, no. 3 (1982): 233–46.

by votive and funerary inscriptions, with a notable inclusion of nearly a third being Christian inscriptions.

Votive inscriptions manifest a dedicated focus on venerating the Capitoline triad, Mars, Neptune (a predictable homage considering the city's geographical context), and Mithras. A noteworthy observation is the prevalence of inscriptions and monuments commissioned by city magistrates (such as *beneficiarii consulares* and *decuriones*). In addition to these, the corpus includes numerous military inscriptions, those dedicated to the emperor's well-being, and a few milestones. Turning to the realm of funerary inscriptions, they come in various forms, composed and commissioned by individuals from diverse social, economic and educational backgrounds, primarily for family members. Notably, a limited number of epitaphs feature fragments of funerary poetry and verses in metre, adding a literary dimension to the corpus.

The majority of inscriptions are preserved inscriptions are in Latin, ranging from the first to the fifth century, with fewer fragmentary Greek inscriptions from the fourth century onward. Therefore, this paper will focus exclusively on the Latin inscriptions in this corpus.⁶¹⁵ Among them, a few inscriptions were selected. These, in relatively concise passages, provide details about the deceased and their lives while also hinting at specific social or religious implications. These include different social strata, the representation of the Christian community, its members, organisational aspects, the operation of legal inheritance rights, military careers, and similar themes. In briefer discussions, intriguing individual stories will be presented. Even without delving into socio-political, cultural, and other implications, these stories would significantly enhance the portrayal of the city's life.

⁶¹⁵ All inscriptions in the paper will be transcribed following the Leiden guidelines.

Artemidora

*Ego Artemidora feci viva me memori am ad dom(i)num | Synerotem int{e} | rantem ad dexte | ram inter Fortuna | ta{ne}m et d<e=I>siderium.*⁶¹⁶

While still alive, I, Artemidora, set up this monument in the basilica of master Syneros. It is located on the right side upon entering, situated between Fortunata and Desiderium.⁶¹⁷

Let us begin by examining a Christian funerary inscription in white marble, commissioned by a certain Artemidora for herself while she was still alive, within the Basilica of St. Syneros. This monument, taking the form of a plaque with meticulously arranged text and embellished with pilasters, can be traced back to the fourth or fifth century. From this inscription, we discern Artemidora's profound commitment to Christianity, as she ensured her resting place well in advance. Beyond manifesting her religious fervour, her final sepulchre bespeaks her elevated standing. Interment within a basilica, especially one housing the tomb of a Christian martyr (in this instance, Syneros), denoted a privilege granted to certain Christians in contrast to those interred outside the basilica, as such a space required purchase.⁶¹⁸

Basilicas functioned as collective commemorative structures; they were not designed to accommodate individual households or families but rather members of the same church community. Thus, through this inscription, Artemidora distinctly designates the location of her mortal remains (between Fortunatus and Desiderius). Yet, this detail does not primarily aim to distinguish and honour her as an individual. Instead, it underscores her integration into the Christian community of Sirmium and its collective identity. Consequently, a single sentence from the inscription vividly portrays an esteemed member of the local Christian community, who garnered ample influence and resources to be interred near a significant Christian martyr. Although she did not specify the precise span of her life, the fact that she secured a burial place for herself even during her lifetime suggests a lifespan of at least thirty years, characterised by devoted participation in church rituals and a prosperous occupation, potentially belonging to either her or members of her household.

⁶¹⁶ CIL III 10233 = ILCV 218.

⁶¹⁷ If not otherwise indicated, all translations are mine.

⁶¹⁸ Ann Marie Yasin, "Funerary Monuments and Collective Identity: From Roman Family to Christian Community," *The Art Bulletin* 87, no. 3 (2005): 446.

Christiani parvuli

*Hic duo innocentes | quiescunt Petrus et | Victorinianus fideles vixit Petrus an(no) uno | mense(m) dies VIII
Victori|nianus vixit an(nos) IIII m(enses) VII | dies XV.*⁶¹⁹

Resting here are two innocent and faithful souls, Petrus and Marcus. Petrus lived for 1 year, 1 month, and 8 days, while Victorinianus lived for 4 years, 7 months, and 15 days.

A modest rectangular marble slab unveils the profound tragedy of the premature demise of two young boys and the grief-stricken parents they left behind, evidently a single family. This epitaph commemorates Petrus, who graced the world for just over a year, and Victorinianus, who never reached his fifth year. The precise enumerating of the days lived by Petrus and Victorinianus shows how much parents cherished moments spent with them. The poignant phrase "*duo innocentes*" encapsulates the immense anguish of this loss.

Some scholars may interpret endearments on inscriptions merely as standardised expressions, rather than authentic indicators of familial sentiments.⁶²⁰ To bolster this view, adjectives denoting affection and commendation for the departed's virtues and character are recurring formulas on both pagan and Christian inscriptions. Nevertheless, this observation may also suggest a shared set of values between the two social communities. Despite the potentially formulaic nature of certain epithets (such as those emphasising the child's endearing, gentle, and innocent disposition), it is entirely possible that they were purposefully selected by grieving families as fitting characterisations of their departed loved ones.⁶²¹ Regardless of the variance in scholarly perspectives, it appears incontrovertible that the human experience remains profoundly unaltered by established customs. Even in cases where feelings might not have found expression in more original phrases, we can surmise the anguish experienced by parents tasked with burying a child, let alone two.

This inscription also attests that the two boys received baptism and were part of the Christian community (*fideles*). This detail may be accentuated due to the rarity of baptising children at such a tender age in early Christianity. By assuming they were baptised shortly after birth, we may also infer that their parents, too, likely received this sacrament, signifying their commitment to Christian practices. Furthermore, it suggests that the intolerance towards Christians, which endured in the distant past, diminished, and that Sirmium housed at least one Christian temple, separate from the necropolis.

⁶¹⁹ AE 2016, 1286.

⁶²⁰ Jonathan Edmondson, "Roman Family History," in *The Oxford Handbook of Roman Epigraphy*, ed. Christer Bruun and Jonathan Edmondson (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2014), 571.

⁶²¹ Leonard A. Curchin, "Convention or Originality?: The Attributes of Christian Children in Latin Epigraphy," *Antigüedad y Cristianismo* 39 (2022): 71.

Distinguished soldier

*T(itus) Cominius | T(iti) f(ilius) Volt(inia) Seve|rus Vienna |(centurio) | leg(ionis) II Adiutric(is) | donis donat(us) | ab Imp(eratore) Caesare | Aug(usto) bello Dacico | torquibus armillis | phaleris corona val|lari vixit ann(os) XXXXV | T(itus) Caesernius Macedo | proc(urator) Aug(usti) her(es) ex test(amento) p(osuit).*⁶²²

T. Cominius Severus, son of Titus, hailing from the city of Vienne and affiliated with the Voltinia tribe, served as a centurion in the Second Legion – Adiutrix. During the Dacian war, he was presented with awards by Emperor Caesar Augustus, including torques, armbands, phalerae, and a camp crown. He lived for 45 years. His heir T. Caesernius Macedo, who held the position of procurator Augusti, had this made as stipulated in his will.

Upon a lavishly adorned marble altar-shaped monument, an illustrious career is inscribed. Titus Cominius Severus holds official Roman citizenship with voting privileges and is affiliated with the rural tribe *Voltinia*. This traces his origins back to Narbonese Gaul, and his birthplace, the city of Vienne on the eastern bank of the Rhone, is meticulously specified. From this city, Cominius embarked on a military trajectory that culminated in notable achievements. Attaining the rank of centurion, he exhibited exceptional military skills. His pinnacle exploits unfolded in the Dacian War, where he garnered four military accolades (*torques, armilla, phalerae, corona vallaris*). These commendations bear witness to his proficiency and audacity as he led charges against adversaries—a distinction personally acknowledged by Emperor Domitian.⁶²³

Given that his funerary inscription was raised in Sirmium prior to the end of his military service, it is conceivable that Cominius was stationed in the city, poised to lead a legion in forthcoming campaigns. While the circumstances of his demise elude us, it is evident that Cominius accrued substantial esteem in Sirmium during times of tranquillity. Furthermore, a camaraderie blossomed between him and the procurator Augusti—a high-ranking financial official reporting directly to the emperor—whom he designated as his successor. The inscription attests to Macedo's dutiful execution of his role, and the craftsmanship of the entire monument to Cominius' possession of considerable material assets, which in all likelihood also transitioned to the procurator. This camaraderie might not have developed had Sirmium not been the host to numerous garrisons over the years.

⁶²² CIL III 10224.

⁶²³ However, his name remains unmentioned on the monument. Given the allusion to the conflict with the Dacians and the dating to the first century, it is presumed that the dedicator deliberately excluded Domitian's name as a result of *damnatio memoriae*.

Character studies

The aforementioned inscriptions were deliberately chosen because, despite their relatively sparse texts, they contain significant implications regarding both the religious and socio-administrative milieu, in addition to providing insights into the lives of the deceased. It is worth noting that there are also inscriptions offering brief but illuminating glimpses into the characters and experiences of ordinary individuals. Within this narrative, selected life stories and personalities will be presented in a succinct manner, allowing for further exploration. In the following, the content of individual inscriptions will be presented more concisely, with a focus not on extracting details about socio-political structures, military, and other institutions. This is not due to a lack of such information, but rather because the research aims to set aside the broader aspects of society and instead concentrate on the individual destinies often disregarded by historiographic trends. Whether these inscriptions describe an entire life or just a specific detail, they contain enough interesting data to vividly depict the streets of Sirmium.

Among them, we encounter Maximina, whose final days were spent in Sirmium, alongside her husband who, on the tombstone, eloquently emphasised not only his love for her but also the profound attachment Maximina held for her homeland (Dalmatia).⁶²⁴ In a similar vein, Macedonius expressed profound admiration for his wife by referring to her as “*matrona*,” a testament to how she embodied feminine virtues like chastity, loyalty, and piety. Moreover, he acknowledged her adherence to Christian values and principles, underscoring her esteemed status within the Christian community. Moreover, this same inscription provides invaluable insight into the inauguration of a new basilica in the city, dedicated to the Sirmian martyr Ireneus.⁶²⁵ The modest sarcophagus narrative poignantly illustrates how, amidst profound sorrow, it succeeded in eternally reuniting a mother with her prematurely departed infant in a tender embrace.⁶²⁶

Likewise, we encounter two soldiers of the *clavicularii*, who collaborated in military service and shared the battlefield. Their respective wives, grappling with the profound pain of losing their husbands in battle, resolved not only to collectively bear the weight of grief but also to share the

⁶²⁴ CIL III 6441: *D(is) M(anibus) Maximina annos vixit | XXVII Gorgonius memori | am posuit compari su(a)e | carissim(a)e de provincia | Dalmatia defuncta penus | colonia(m) Sirmi(um) Manibus | posita memoria.*

To the spirits of the dead. Maximina lived for 27 years. Gorgonius erected this monument in loving memory of his dearest wife, originally from the province of Dalmatia, who passed away within the colony of Sirmium. Monument set up for the spirits of the dead.

⁶²⁵ Mirković 2017, no. 223: *In basilica domini n | ostri Erenei(!) (h)a(n)c(?) mem/oriam posuit Maced | onius una cum m | atrona{m} sua{m} M | ammete Zevenati.*

Macedonius, along with his lady wife Mammete Zevenati, erected this monument in the basilica of our master Ireneus.

⁶²⁶ CIL III 10215 = ILCV 3634: *In hanc arcam posita est | Aurelia Macrina quae | vixit annos XXXV et | Aurelius Iustinianus | <f=E>ilius pius qui vixit annum | unum et menses quinque.*

In this coffin lies Aurelia Macrina, who lived for 35 years, and Aurelius Iustinianus, a beloved son who lived for 1 year and 5 months.

financial burden of raising the monument.⁶²⁷ A young man of modest origins harboured a fervent passion for acquiring knowledge, eagerly embracing new insights. His trajectory towards a promising career in civil service was tragically truncated by an untimely demise.⁶²⁸

In the era preceding the widespread adoption of Christianity, citizens of Sirmium dutifully fulfilled vows to the Capitoline triad, Mars, and Neptune. These entreaties sought blessings not only for their loved ones but also for the welfare of the city itself, and, by extension, the reigning emperors. Additionally, evidence exists attesting to the prominence of the cult of the god Mithras, substantiated by a plethora of votive altars dedicated to him. Notably, this deity commanded his own temple within the city, a structure that also underwent extensive renovations.⁶²⁹ The diverse cultural tapestry of the city is further expressed the interment of an exorcist within its precincts.⁶³⁰

Conclusion

The analyses provided underscore the importance of delving deeper into inscriptions, going beyond their role as political and historical records. Exploring the lives of individuals with minimal historical footprints, whose experiences closely resonate with our own, offers a distinctive perspective. These inscriptions connect us with narratives and emotions, reflecting contemporary sentiments. Territories once under the Roman Empire host myriad small corpora, along with isolated inscriptions. The individuals, whether deceased or dedicants, need not remain in anonymity. Within these engraved words, the humanities discover fertile ground for exploration, extending beyond the immediate subject matter.

The vibrant tableau in Sirmium portrays an organised Christian community thriving alongside its pagan counterpart. Prosperous women commemorate themselves through monuments, exuding confidence in their faith, and finding eternal repose within the church. The

⁶²⁷ IJug 271: *D(is) M(anibus) | Ael(io) Ingen{uo} clav|iculario ex officio | pr(a)esid<i=E>s deci(dit) in bel(lo) | Aelia Procella con|iugi karissimo me/moria(m) posuit | Septi(mio) Decorato | claviculario ex officio | pr(a)esid<i=E>s deci(dit) in b<e=l>(l)lo | Aelia Basilissa coniugi | karissimo memoria(m) | posuit.*

To the spirits of the dead. Aelia Procella erected a monument in memory of her dearest husband, Aelius Ingenuus, a key-keeper in the governor's office, who perished in war. Aelia Basilissa erected a monument in memory of her dearest husband Septimius Decoratus, a key-keeper in the governor's office, who perished in war.

⁶²⁸ CIL III 03240: *P(ublio) Ael(io) Respecto eq(uiti) R(omano) | a milit(iis) filio piissimo | et studiis omni praedito | P(ublius) Ael(ius) Trophimianus pater | v(ir) e(gregius) posuit.*

To Publius Aelius Respectus, a beloved son of equestrian rank who pursued a military career and excelled in all his endeavours, this monument is dedicated by his esteemed father, Publius Aelius Trophimianus.

⁶²⁹ AE 2016, 1279: *Deo Soli In|victo Mi|t<hr=RH>ae C(aius) Iul(ius) | Italicus dec(urio) | col(oniae) Sirme(n)s|ium templum | vetustate | conlabent|<em=A> restituit a | solo.*

C. Iulius Italicus, a decurion of the colony Sirmium, restored a temple dedicated to the invincible sun god Mithra, rebuilding it from the very foundation due to age-induced deterioration.

⁶³⁰ AE 1996, 1256: *In hoc l[oco] | iacet Urs[ici]nus exorcist[a] | co<m=N>memorati[one(m)] | fecit Laurentia | [sa]nctimonia[li]s | [3]VC.*

Here lies Ursicinus, the exorcist, commemorated by the pious Laurentia.

heartfelt words memorialising loved ones warrant concerted study, inviting empathy for the profound and overwhelming grief of parents, spouses, and friends. Alongside magistrates, we encounter a promising and educated young clerk. An exorcist emerges in a city that embraces pagan sanctuaries, including the temple of Mithras and several basilicas. This paints a reliable testament to the rich tapestry of personalities in a city bridging East and West.

An in-depth analysis of specific inscriptions, chosen as representative examples, illustrates how even a single sentence can yield a wealth of information and open numerous avenues for exploration. Even from a modest corpus of, at times, uniform and formulaic inscriptions, meaningful insights can be drawn, providing glimpses into the lives of ordinary individuals. Examining small-scale interactions and experiences provides a more intimate understanding of the past. Special attention should be given to institutions with a significant impact on human behaviour and emotions, such as family, law, religion, the military, and the state.

We believe that using inscriptions as sources to analyse how societal norms, religious beliefs, or political events affected the lives and emotional experiences of specific individuals or communities would yield fruitful results in interdisciplinary comparative studies. It's crucial to recognise that, irrespective of historical context and time span, we are dealing with individuals and their lives. Avoiding generalisations sourced from material across the entire empire, we advocate adopting a microhistorical perspective, starting with individuals within the community. By placing and observing communities alongside each other, revisiting existing material, and examining details overshadowed by significant historical moments, we can unveil the genuine pattern and image of all integral parts of the Empire. The potential for crafting detailed chronicles of cities and their citizens awaits through comprehensive and interconnected examination of richer corpora, whether in terms of volume or diversity of inscriptions.

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Condemnations at the University of Paris: Techniques Used for Restoring the Misplaced Borderline Between Orthodox and Heresy in the Thirteenth Century⁶³¹

TINATIN MIRIANASHVILI

MA Student, CEU Vienna

Abstract

*The main focus of this paper is the thirteenth-century condemnations at the University of Paris. These events reflected the conflict between scientific and theological doctrines in the High Middle Ages. The most imposing of all, the condemnation of 1277, is even regarded as "the birth of modern science" by renowned physicist and historian of science Pierre Duhem. The condemnations were the result of spreading newly translated literature including the philosophical and scientific works of Aristotle as well as commentaries and summaries of them by Arabic philosophers. While the philosophical side of the condemnation of 1277 has been deeply explored by numerous scholars, political and procedural aspects are frequently left aside. The paper tries to review the historical background of the cases of 1277 and previous condemnations that occurred at the University of Paris. It distinguishes similarities and differences between them, and underlines scholarly gaps that future research can inquire. For the methodology, I exploited the primary literature established in *Chartularium Universitatis Parisiensis*, where the lists of condemnations, university statutes, and Papal and episcopal letters are collected together as well as secondary literature, that conduced me to review the historical and theological background leading to the thirteenth-century condemnations and to present assumptions and resolutions concerning the condemnation of 1277 in existing scholarship.*

Keywords: Thirteenth-Century Condemnations – University of Paris – Condemnations of 1277

⁶³¹ This article was written nine months before I finished my MA thesis, *The Role of Ecclesiastical and Academic Authorities in the Thirteenth-Century Academic Condemnations* (CEU Vienna, 2024). The thesis is a continuation of the research started in this article and clarifies the ambiguities presented at the end of this work. It also has to be noted, that I used some parts of this article in my thesis.

Introduction

The thirteenth-century condemnations are a significant element of the history of the University of Paris. They not only reflected the views and debates of scholars and students of the period but also broadened and developed the field of philosophical and scientific thinking. In the thirteenth century, the border between theological and philosophical-scientific concepts in scholarly debates became unclear, which provoked ecclesiastical authorities to act against them. The initial part of this essay will discuss what caused the border to become perceived as misplaced. In the second place, six cases of thirteenth-century condemnations will be analysed. Finally, it will provide the historical background of the condemnation of 1277, the debates around the event, and the scholarly gaps that must be examined and clarified.

The Origins of Heretical Ideas

Several historians contend that there was no medieval philosophy in the Christian West until the integration of Aristotelian and Arabic literature in the thirteenth century.⁶³² However, this does not seem true when one observes the thoughts, reasoning, and main interests of tenth, eleventh, and twelfth-century scholars. There were indeed no philosophers or texts dedicated to philosophy as such; however, philosophical discussions and speculations were apparently present. One manifestation of this is the hostile, or rather suspicious, attitude of “anti-dialecticians”⁶³³ toward discussing theological issues with the help of logical reasoning. For example, Lanfranc (1005–1089) criticised Berengar of Tours (999–1088) for questioning the belief of the “reality” of the presence of blood and body of Christ in the Eucharist. Lanfranc accused him of using logical reasoning inappropriately. Furthermore, Peter Damian (1007–1072), after attempting to discuss theological issues such as Divine omnipotence and the compatibility of divine prescience and human free will with the help of “human logic,” considered it unsuitable to discuss “the sacraments of the church” with “the purely verbal art.”⁶³⁴ The attempts to explain and research theological issues deeply with the help of logic can be considered evidence of the presence of philosophy in the Middle Ages. So, the spread and discussion of the texts of Aristotle and Arabic commentaries were not a beginning but a continuation of Medieval philosophical and theological debates. Newly translated literature opened new ideas and fields of discourse, but it did not provoke philosophical and theological debates *ex nihilo*.

⁶³² John Marenbon, *Early Medieval Philosophy (480-1150)* (Oxfordshire: Taylor & Francis, 2002), 95.

⁶³³ Marenbon, *Early Medieval Philosophy*, 90.

⁶³⁴ Marenbon, *Early Medieval Philosophy*, 93.

“The permanent problem” of reconciling Christianity with ancient philosophy took various approaches during the eleventh century. Scholars such as Peter Damian, Otloh of St. Emmeram (1010–1072), and Gerard of Czanad (980–1046), for example, believed it was not worthwhile to spend time on secular literature.⁶³⁵ However, discussions and attempts to find reason and explanations within theological doctrines remained very important. Anselm (1033–1109), for instance, asserted that “by the use of reason, the Christian can give an understanding of what he already believes.”⁶³⁶ He believed that theologians should attempt to think and find reasons for how divine mysteries can be explained. The accelerated interest in logic during the eleventh and twelfth centuries led to the discovery of Boethius' translations: the *Prior Analytics*, *Topics*, and *Sophistici elenchi*.⁶³⁷ Moreover, Throughout the twelfth and thirteenth centuries, newly translated philosophical and scientific works of Aristotle, such as the texts on natural philosophy and metaphysics, as well as Arabic commentaries by Al-Kindi (801–873), Al-Farabi (870–950), Avicenna (980–1037), and Averroes (1126–1198), became available to the Christian West in Latin. Italian cleric James of Venice (...-1147) completed the translation of the logical corpus with the *Posterior Analytics* from Greek. Subsequently, he translated the *Physics*, *De anima*, *Metaphysics*, five of the *Parva Naturalia* treatises, and an anonymous introduction.⁶³⁸ Some books were translated from Greek, and others from Arabic. For example, Books I-III of *Meteorologica* were translated from Arabic by Gerard of Cremona (1114–1187), and Book IV from Greek by Henricus Aristippus (1105–1162). Gerard of Cremona also translated *Physics*, *De caelo*, *De generatione et corruptione*, *Posterior Analytics*, and Themistius' paraphrase of *Posterior Analytics*, all from Arabic.⁶³⁹

The majority of Aristotle's works were translated in the twelfth century, however, evidence from manuscripts and other sources, such as references to Aristotle's texts, indicates that they were not widely circulated until the thirteenth century.⁶⁴⁰ It is also probable that the establishment of the first European universities facilitated the spreading of the newly translated texts among students and scholars. Given that a significant portion of the thirteenth-century debates occurred within the university environment, that was

⁶³⁵ Marenbon, *Early Medieval Philosophy*, 87

⁶³⁶ Marenbon, *Early Medieval Philosophy*, 95.

⁶³⁷ Bernard G. Dod, “Aristoteles Latinus,” in *The Cambridge History of Later Medieval Philosophy from the Rediscovery of Aristotle to the Disintegration of Scholasticism 1100-1600*, eds. Norman Kretzmann, Anthony Kenny and Jan Pinborg (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2008), 46.

⁶³⁸ Dod, “Aristoteles Latinus,” 46.

⁶³⁹ Dod, “Aristoteles Latinus,” 47.

⁶⁴⁰ Dod, “Aristoteles Latinus,” 46.

reflected in the thirteenth-century academic condemnations at the University of Paris (the cases of 1241, 1270, and 1277).⁶⁴¹

Aristotelian ideas about the eternity of the world, the unicity of human intellect, free will, ordained power of God, etc., contradicted Christian doctrines and were considered heretical by the Church. As a result, ecclesiastical authorities started to act against the great quantity of non-Christian literature and began dealing with them by pronouncing condemnations.

Thirteen-Century Condemnations

One of the clear manifestations that Aristotle's books were already widely spread at the beginning of the thirteenth century is the condemnation of 1210.⁶⁴² Petrus de Corbolio (died in 1222), the archbishop of Sens, convened a local council in Sens with the participation of the bishop of Paris, Peter of Nemours, and other bishops to burn the *Quaternuli* of David of Dinant (1160–1217), one of the Amalricians,⁶⁴³ and forbid reading the books of Aristotle and their commentaries publicly or privately. Furthermore, they made a warning that the *Credo in Deum* and *Pater Noster* and several theological books translated into French,⁶⁴⁴ aside from the life of saints, which had already undergone purification, should have been delivered to the bishop of Paris. Anyone found with these religious texts, *Quaternuli*, or Aristotle's works would be considered a heretic.⁶⁴⁵ In 1210, fourteen individuals were condemned. Ten of them were degraded and sent to secular court, where they were burnt at the stake, while the remaining four were imprisoned perpetually.⁶⁴⁶ Here, one can see the influence of the recently introduced inquisitorial procedure for the prosecution of heretics.⁶⁴⁷ Usually, clerics,

⁶⁴¹ The condemnation of 1241 in Heinrich Denifle and Aemilio Chatelain, *Chartularium Universitatis Parisiensis*, vol. 1 (Paris: ex Typis Fratrum Delalain, 1889), 170, no. 128. Further references to the first volume of *Chartularium Universitatis Parisiensis* will be abbreviated CUP; The condemnation of 1270 in CUP, 486, no. 432; The condemnation of 1277 in CUP, 543, no. 473.

⁶⁴² CUP, 70, no. 11.

⁶⁴³ A sect emerged in the twelfth century, associated with the teachings of Amalric of Bena (1150-1207), a master in the faculty of theology in Paris. He himself was condemned in 1206, shortly before his death. As Hans Thijssen writes in his book *Censure and Heresy at the University of Paris 1200-1400* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 1998), "In brief, the heresies attributed to the Amalricians can be grouped around three themes: pantheism, the attainment of spiritual perfection here on earth, and the antinomian and antisacramental implications of the Amalricians' views on the preceding two topics."

⁶⁴⁴ Lynn Thorndike, *University Records and Life in the Middle Ages* (New York: Columbia University Press, 1944), 26-27, no. 14.

⁶⁴⁵ CUP, 70, no. 11.

⁶⁴⁶ Hans Thijssen, "Master Amalric and the Amalricians: Inquisitorial Procedure and the Suppression of Heresy at the University of Paris," *Speculum* 71, no. 1 (Januray 1996), 61.

⁶⁴⁷ Thijssen, "The Amalricians," 61.

and therefore, the members of the University, enjoyed the *Privilegium Fori*. According to the privilege, they were exempt from secular courts, even in criminal cases. However, this was changed after issuing the decretal *Vergentis in Senium* by Innocent III (1161–1216) and the reform of 1205–1206 by King Philip Augustus (1165–1223), that the degraded cleric would be handed not directly to a secular court but would be taken to an external place to punish him without committing sacrilege.⁶⁴⁸ A similar thing happened in 1210. Clerics were degraded at the Saint-Honore church and were taken to Champeaux, outside the walls of Paris to burn them at the stake.⁶⁴⁹

Subsequently, the papal legate Robert of Courçon renewed the condemnation in 1215.⁶⁵⁰ More exactly, he was charged with reorganising studies and improving the condition of scholars in Paris to keep the peace among them (*scolarum tranquillitati*). He re-established the condemnation of the teachings of David of Dinant and Amalric of Bene. Besides, he permitted reading all of logic and ethics but forbade lecturing on the texts of Aristotle on metaphysics and natural philosophy as well as commentaries or summaries of them.⁶⁵¹ Apparently, the papal legate banned these texts since they were the main sources of philosophical and scientific thinking and discussions at the university. Reading these texts raised questions among students and scholars that were considered hazardous for Christian doctrines.

In 1225 Pope Honorius III established the condemnation of the *Periphyseon* by John Scottus Eriugena (815–877), referring to it as having been “justly condemned”⁶⁵² by the archbishop of Sens. This means that most probably it was also condemned in 1210. The important point is that the work of Eriugena was connected to Amalric’s heresy, condemned in 1210 as well as at the fourth Lateran Council. Archbishop of Odo of Tuscany, who also participated in the condemnation of 1210 in Paris mentioned that “the impious dogma of Amalric is collected in the book of Master John the Scot.”⁶⁵³ Therefore, one can conclude that

⁶⁴⁸ John W. Baldwin, “Le Contexte Politique et Institutionnel,” in *Les Débuts de L’enseignement Universitaire à Paris (1200 - 1245 Environ)*, eds., Jacques Verger and Olga Weijers (Tournhour : Brepols Publishers, 2013), 23.

⁶⁴⁹ Baldwin, “Le Contexte Politique,” 23.

⁶⁵⁰ CUP, 78, no. 20.

⁶⁵¹ CUP, 78, no. 20.

⁶⁵² CUP, 106, no. 50.

⁶⁵³ This citation of Odo is made by Henry Suso and it is quoted by Stephen Lahey, “Eriugena’s Condemnation and His Idealism,” in *A Companion to John Scottus Eriugena*, ed., Adrian Guiu (Leiden: Brill, 2020), 449.

the condemnation of 1225 was connected to the earlier condemnations of Amalric since the source of his heretical teachings has been associated with the *Periphyseon*.

Furthermore, Pope Gregory IX issued warning letters in 1228 and 1231. In 1228, he advised regent masters in theology not to adulterate God's word by the figments of Philosophers,⁶⁵⁴ and in 1231, he stated that Master of Arts faculty should not use *libros illos naturales*, which had been forbidden in *Concilium provinciali* until they were examined and purged of all suspicion errors. Besides that, he advised Masters and scholars of theology not to declare themselves philosophers but to strive to be *theodocti*.⁶⁵⁵

As Charles H. Lohr writes, the changes in the learning of the faculty of arts are noticeable in a thirteenth-century manuscript in Barcelona in the Archives of the Crown of Aragon, which contains a manual or guidebook for the benefit of students who had to prepare for examinations in the Arts Faculty in Paris.⁶⁵⁶ This text, composed about 1230–40 by an unknown master of the faculty contains the newly translated works and so, reveals the direction which the development of the faculty took in the period. He establishes the works of Aristotle on metaphysics and natural philosophy condemned in 1210 and 1215 as part of *trivium* and *quadrivium*. Therefore, as one can notice, the condemnation did not have an influence in 1230–1240 anymore. As the author conveys, the arts faculty changed its guidance from teaching simply the seven liberal arts of the *trivium* and *quadrivium* to rather all the philosophical and scientific disciplines newly recovered at his time.⁶⁵⁷

Subsequently, there was the condemnation of 1241, which is the first condemnation listing not certain individuals or texts but only erroneous ideas.⁶⁵⁸ The list contains ten banned propositions. The document says that the condemnation was established by the bishop of Paris, William of Auvergne (1190–1249), the chancellor, Odo of Chateauroux (1190–1273), and all masters of the faculty of theology. The involvement of the chancellor and masters of the faculty of theology in the process demonstrates the increase of their role and importance in doctrinal issues of the university if one compares it to the previous cases when only the Pope or bishops participated in the decision.⁶⁵⁹ As Courtenay writes, depending on the

⁶⁵⁴ CUP, 114, no. 59.

⁶⁵⁵ CUP, 136, no. 79.

⁶⁵⁶ Charles H. Lohr, "The Medieval Interpretation," in *Later Medieval Philosophy*, eds. Kretzmann, Kenny and Pinborg, 84.

⁶⁵⁷ MS Ripoll 109 f. 134^r – 158^v, as quoted in Lohr, "The Medieval Interpretation," 86.

⁶⁵⁸ CUP, 170, no. 128.

⁶⁵⁹ Deborah Grice, *Church, Society and University* (New York: Taylor & Francis group, 2020), 22–31.

information contained in the numerous versions of the opening line of the condemnation decree, it started on the episcopal level since the initiator of the condemnation was the bishop of Paris, William of Auvergne.⁶⁶⁰ Besides that, it is important to underline that the condemnation of 1241 can be considered the first academic condemnation at the University of Paris. As Hans Thijssen singled out there were two important features of academic condemnations: 1. "Cases of academic censure were initiated in the institutional context of the university,"⁶⁶¹ and 2. "The judicial proceedings against an allegedly erring academic focused on suspect statements and views, and not on the holder of those views."⁶⁶² Guided by this definition, the case of 1241 satisfies both aspects.

Despite these prohibitions and warnings, it is known that already in 1245, Roger Bacon made comments on Aristotle's *libri naturales* and metaphysics in Paris.⁶⁶³ In 1255 the statutes of the Arts Faculty were renewed and incorporated practically the whole corpus of Aristotle: Ethics, Physics, Metaphysics, *De animalibus*, *De caelo*, *Meteorologica* (Books I and IV), etc.⁶⁶⁴ Thus, after that, the Faculty of Arts developed a teaching philosophy independent of the Faculty of Theology.⁶⁶⁵ Such a development aroused violent reactions and rivalry between the two faculties.⁶⁶⁶ The incompatibility of theological and philosophical-scientific ideas and the conflicts between scholars at the faculty of arts and theology among a number of topics were revealed in the condemnation of 1270 and 1277 by the Bishop of Paris, Etienne Tempier (...-1279).⁶⁶⁷ He condemned thirteen theses, deemed heretical, in the first case and two hundred and nineteen in the second. It can be said that this so-called technique of publishing condemnations became the tool to defend Christianity from heretical teachings and prevent "corrupting the minds" of scholars and students from philosophical and scientific ideas. Apparently, the goal of these condemnations was not only to prohibit talking and lecturing about the ideas but also *tranquillitas scholarum*, as it was indicated in the condemnation of 1210, to cease debates and controversies between scholars and disclose the border between Christian doctrine and heretical views.

⁶⁶⁰ William J. Courtenay, "Dominicans and Suspect Opinion in the Thirteenth Century: The Cases of Stephen of Venizy, Peter of Tarentaise, and the Articles of 1270 and 1271," *Vivarium* 32, no. 2 (1994): 189.

⁶⁶¹ Thijssen, "The Amalricians," 49.

⁶⁶² Thijssen, "The Amalricians," 49.

⁶⁶³ Fernand Van Steenberghen, *La philosophie au XIIIe siecle* (Paris: Béatrice-Nauwelaerts, 1966), 143.

⁶⁶⁴ CUP, 277, no. 246.

⁶⁶⁵ Lohr, "The Medieval Interpretation," 87.

⁶⁶⁶ Lohr, "The Medieval Interpretation," 87.

⁶⁶⁷ The Condemnation of 1270 in CUP, 486; The Condemnation of 1277 in CUP, 543, no. 473.

The Condemnation of 1277

While the previous condemnations were instigated by ecclesiastical authorities, the initiators of the cases of 1270 and 1277 are still ambiguous. It is known that sixteen theology masters assisted Tempier in constructing the list of propositions in the case of 1277, but the initiator of the action is still controversial, which will be discussed later in the paper. Similar to the condemnation of 1241, Tempier condemned not certain scholars or theologians but ideas themselves.

The new and distinctive features of Tempier's condemnation raise questions about the jurisdiction and how the procedures and rights of ecclesiastical authorities over the university were stipulated in canon law. The significance of the condemnation seems so influential that Pierre Duhem regarded it as “the birth of modern science.”⁶⁶⁸ While this might be an exaggeration, the influence of the condemnation of 1277 on Scholasticism and medieval thought is evident. The banned propositions reflected the thoughts from the critical works of Thomas Aquinas (1225–1274), Siger of Brabant (1240–1280), and Boethius of Dacia (1240–1284) concerning Aristotelian ideas about free will, the unicity of the human intellect, divine knowledge, the nature of eternity, individuation, virtue, wisdom, as well as every-day-life issues, such as carnal acts, confession, Christian morality, etc.⁶⁶⁹ Besides these two hundred and nineteen theses, Tempier condemned some books, precisely, *De Amore* of Andreas Capellanus (1150–1220), the book of Geomancy, and texts, scrolls, and quatrains on necromancy, sorcery, or invocation of demons. However, they are mentioned only in the introductory letter of Etienne Tempier, prefacing the list of propositions, not explicitly among these two hundred and nineteen propositions.⁶⁷⁰ However, a textual analysis of the document suggests that an organisational structure can be found there. While reading the list of propositions, it is evident that there is a certain logic beyond the propositions, especially when one pays attention to the vocabulary used. Ostensibly, there are certain groups concerning one problematic topic or idea. Nevertheless, frequently unrelated articles are interjected. It

⁶⁶⁸ Pierre Duhem, *Etudes sur Leonard de Vinci*, vol. 1 (Paris : Hermann, 1906-1913), 412.

⁶⁶⁹ About free will in Article 102, CUP, 543, no. 473; the unicity of the human intellect in Article 117, CUP, 543, no. 473; divine knowledge in Article 13, CUP, 543, no. 473; the nature of eternity in Article 86, CUP, 543, no. 473; individuation in Article 116, CUP, 543, no. 473; virtue in Article 116, CUP, 543, no. 473; wisdom in Article 154, CUP, 543, no. 473; carnal acts in Article 172, CUP, 543, no. 473; confession in Article 179, CUP, 543, no. 473; Christian morality in Article 183, CUP, 543, no. 473.

⁶⁷⁰ Steenberghen, *La philosophie*, 483. Pierre Mandonnet, *Siger De Brabant et L'Averroisme Latin au XIIIe Siècle* (Fribourg, 1899), 229.

is possible that the articles had a series of headings during a preparatory phase of the censorship, as is presented in *Collectio Errorum in Anglia et Parisius Condemnatorum*.⁶⁷¹ Some proposals could have been misplaced or moved later, accidentally or deliberately, when preparing the final version of the decree. However, there is not yet a specific answer in today's scholarship.⁶⁷²

While the philosophical side of the condemnation of 1277 has been researched by various scholars, political and procedural aspects are frequently left aside. However, there still are several authors who were concerned with that side of condemnation: Gregory Moule, Hans Thijssen, William Courtenay, Andrew Larsen, and Sylvain Piron.⁶⁷³

Concerning the question of who had the authority to establish academic condemnations at the university, Courtenay wrote that in the thirteenth century, the corporation of regent masters took over the task of policing academic orthodoxy, but it is not stated who or what granted this power to them, whether they regularly existed in the thirteenth century or it was formed by ecclesiastical authorities only in certain cases.⁶⁷⁴ For example, as John of Pouilly writes, a commission of sixteen theology masters assisted bishop Etienne Tempier in composing condemned propositions in 1277, but it is not discussed what necessitated this action of the bishop - canon law, common practice, or simply his will to discuss the ideas with scholars.⁶⁷⁵ Clarifying these issues will explain not only Tempier's action of forming the commission but also the function of the corporation of theology masters. Gregory Moule is the only one who examined academic heresy and corporate jurisdiction, concentrating on the rules and procedures set down in canon law. However, his discussion is more general and does not reflect concrete cases of academic heresy in the thirteenth century.⁶⁷⁶

⁶⁷¹ C. du Plessis d'Argentré, ed., *Collectio errorum in anglia et parisius condemnatorum*, in *Collectio juridiciorum de novis erroribus*, vol. 1 (Paris, 1728), 188–200.

⁶⁷² On this issue, please refer to Sylvain Piron, "Le Plan de L'évêque pour une critique interne de la condamnation du 7 Mars 1277," *Recherches de théologie et philosophie médiévales* 78, no. 2 (2011): 383–415. He argues quite convincingly about the architecture and arrangement of Tempier's condemnations and makes several substantiated assumptions.

⁶⁷³ Gregory Moule, *Corporate Jurisdiction, Academic Heresy, and Fraternal Correction at the University of Paris, 1200-1400*, vol. 51 of *Education and Society in the Middle Ages and Renaissance* (Leiden: Brill, 2016); Thijssen, *Censure and Heresy*; Courtenay, "Inquiry and Inquisition: Academic Freedom in Medieval Universities," *Church History* 58, no. 2 (June 1989); Andrew Larsen, *The School of Heretics, Academic Condemnation at the University of Oxford, 1277-1409* (Leiden: Brill, 2011); Piron, "Le Plan de L'évêque."

⁶⁷⁴ Courtenay, "Inquiry and Inquisition," 173.

⁶⁷⁵ John of Pouilly, *Quodlibet* II, 11, quoted in Robert Wielockx, ed., *Aegidii Romani Opera Omnia* III.1 (Florence, 1985), 98.

⁶⁷⁶ Moule, "Corporate Jurisdiction." He discusses several cases of condemnations but from the from the fourteenth century.

The historical background of the condemnations also includes several circumstances that are worth mentioning. On January 18, 1277, Pope John XXI (1215–1277) sent a letter to Etienne Tempier. The Pope stated that he had heard rumours of heresy and charged him with examining where and by whom these errors had been proclaimed at the University of Paris (*facias inspici vel inquiri, a quibus personis et in quibus locis errores hujusmodi dicti sunt sive scripti*).⁶⁷⁷ John XXI did not oblige or authorise him to publish condemnations. He only asked the bishop to investigate and inform back about the outcomes. Tempier instead formed a Commission of sixteen theology masters and published the list of two hundred and nineteen propositions on 7 March 1277, without replying to the Pope.

There is no evidence that the Pope knew of Tempier's condemnation beforehand. Presumably, the bishop made the decision on his own. The arbitrariness of the decision is also supported by the papal letter *Flumen aquae vivae* of April 28.⁶⁷⁸ Here, he already stated the sources of the heretical ideas: “some scholars in the faculties of arts and theology at Paris” (*nonnulli tam in artibus quam in theologica facultate studentes Parisius*)⁶⁷⁹ and mandated Tempier once again to notify him about the results of the investigation. Nevertheless, the action of the bishop remained without any reproach from the papal authorities. It is also important to underline that while the Pope mentioned both scholars in the faculties of arts and theology, Tempier, in his introductory letter prefacing the list of propositions, only referred to scholars in the arts faculty.

Furthermore, there are several theories about what may have provoked Tempier's action to publish condemnation. One of them is that his action was encouraged by Pope John XXI, who, as mentioned above, sent two letters to Tempier.⁶⁸⁰ Another theory proposed by Hans Thijssen is that the bishop was triggered by an inquisitorial investigation by inquisitor Simon du Val. He cited Siger of Brabant, Bernier of Nivelles, and Goswin of Chapelle to appear before his court on November 23, 1276.⁶⁸¹ As Thijssen confers, after that, Tempier could not condemn Siger's ideas *nominatim* according to the juridical principle: *ne bis in idem crimen judicetur*.⁶⁸² Therefore, for Thijssen, this fact seems to be the reason for the anonymity of the

⁶⁷⁷ CUP, 541, no. 471.

⁶⁷⁸ *Archivum Franciscanum Historicum*, vol. 18 (Florence: Quaracchi presso Firenze, 1925), 459–460.

⁶⁷⁹ *Archivum Franciscanum Historicum*, 459.

⁶⁸⁰ Steenberghen, *La Philosophie*, 34.

⁶⁸¹ Thijssen, *Censure and Heresy*, 46.

⁶⁸² Gratian's *Decretum*, C.2 q.1 C.14 par.1, cited in Thijssen, *Censure and Heresy*, 48.

condemnations of 1277.⁶⁸³ The argument seems quite convincing, but the fact that the case of 1270 was also anonymous casts serious doubts on the assumption.

Besides that, Sylvain Piron, depending on Tempier's previous arbitrary actions at the university,⁶⁸⁴ claims that he himself promulgated the censorship of the two hundred and nineteen theses.⁶⁸⁵ It is a more common opinion that the condemnations started at the episcopal level.⁶⁸⁶ However, according to his introductory letter: "Repeated accounts of great and serious persons have intimated that a number of students in the arts at Paris are overstepping the boundaries of their own faculty."⁶⁸⁷ So, it is also possible that the bishop was prompted by the "reports" of university scholars.

⁶⁸³ Thijssen, *Censure and Heresy*, 38–48.

⁶⁸⁴ He had an argument with university scholars concerning the teaching license. See Moule, "Corporate Jurisdiction," 53–56.

⁶⁸⁵ Piron, "Le Plan de L'évêque."

⁶⁸⁶ Thijssen, *Censure and Heresy at the University of Paris 1200-1400* (Philadelphia: University of Pennsylvania Press, 1998), 43.

⁶⁸⁷ CUP, 543, no. 473.

Conclusion

One can safely conclude that the publishing of academic condemnations began in the middle of the thirteenth century, taking the case of 1241 as a starting point. It was the first instance where university members, specifically the chancellor and the masters of the faculty of theology, were involved. Previous condemnations, except the case of 1215, were not explicitly connected to the university. However, since in 1210, Master William of Poitiers is said to have been condemned,⁶⁸⁸ and in 1225, schoolmen are mentioned as readers of *Periphyseon*, one can say that they still touched the university environment.⁶⁸⁹ In the end, the distinctive features of the condemnation of 1277 have to be emphasised. Firstly, it is the largest condemnation of the thirteenth century, with two hundred and nineteen banned propositions established. Other distinguishing characteristics include the summoning of a commission of sixteen Theology Masters, the role of the Pope's letter, reference to only the Faculty of Arts, anonymity and the ambiguity concerning the initiator of the action. These features need further research to reveal important methodological aspects and the extent of involvement of ecclesiastical authorities in university issues. Elaborating on Canon Law is crucial for distinguishing the procedures of condemning heresy and identifying the authorities who were obliged, whether doctrinally or institutionally, to take action against erroneous ideas.

⁶⁸⁸ Denifle and Chatelain, *Chartularium Universitatis Parisiensis*, 70:11.

⁶⁸⁹ Denifle and Chatelain, *Chartularium Universitatis Parisiensis*, 106:50, *Quia igitur idem liber, sicut accepimus, in nonnullis monasteriis et aliis locis habetur, et nonnulli claustrales et viri scolastici novitatum forte plus quam expediat amatores, se studiosius occupant dicti libri.*

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***Husinska buna – proizvodnja revolucionarnog subjekta* by
Damir Arsenijević. Tuzla: Rosa-Luxemburg-Stiftung SEE
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OMER MERZIĆ

MA in History, University of London

Review

Towards the end of 2020, the 100th anniversary of the Husino rebellion was commemorated. While this anniversary was relatively covered in the media and social networks, the same cannot be said for academic and cultural circles. Several works related to the labour movement in the interwar period have been written by authors such as Denis Bećirović, current member of the Presidency of Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Salkan Užičanin, both historians. Additionally, an artistic performance was organised by the JU Museum of Eastern Bosnia Tuzla and by the author Branko Šimić. Apart from these few sporadic works, the greatest contribution has been made in the form of a shorter collection of papers titled *Husino rebellion – Production of the Revolutionary Subject*, edited by Damir Arsenijević and published by Rosa-Luxemburg-Stiftung SEE – Office in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

This shorter collection of papers contains eight works that address various topics. The main focus is placed on the historical aspect of the rebellion and its position in the chronology of the labour movement's development in Bosnia and Herzegovina and beyond. Furthermore, significant emphasis is placed on the manifestation and remembrance of Husino rebellion in later periods. The collection also includes works that are more oriented towards the question and exploration of “production of the revolutionary subject.” A particular place is dedicated to the comparison between the protests in Bosnia and Herzegovina in 2014 and the events of Husino rebellion. The book concludes with a bibliographic appendix on Husino rebellion, providing a brief historical overview of the emergence of different works and sections, thus presenting the evolution and development of this topic in historiography.

The book begins with a brief introduction by Krunoslav Stojaković, Director of the Belgrade Office of Rosa-Luxemburg-Stiftung, and the first paper is authored by Damir Arsenijević

⁶⁹⁰ The book is available as an open-source book on the website of the Rosa Luxemburg Stiftung <https://rosalux.rs/rosa-publications/husinska-buna/>.

titled *Husinska buna – proizvodnja revolucionarnog subjekta* (Husino rebellion – Production of the Revolutionary Subject). In his work, Arsenijević attempts to connect the events in Husino near Tuzla with the broader context of workers' emancipation and the events that marked the workers' struggle in that period. Furthermore, he frequently links the Husino rebellion with the events in Bosnia and Herzegovina after the aggression and the situation in which the population and the economy found themselves. Arsenijević's work is primarily based on the recollections of the main participants, Jure Kerošević and Božo Petrović. The author provides limited critical analysis of their writings and often directly quotes them.

The next three papers are very similar to one another, and their approaches are generally based on the same principles, examining the causal-events before and during the Husino rebellion as well as the significance of those events. The first paper, titled *Značaj elementa solidarnosti u husinskoj buni* (The Significance of Solidarity in Husino Rebellion) is written by Dino Šakanović. His main thesis is that the central reason for Husino rebellion is based on the solidarity of local miners from the Krka mine with the evicted individuals from state-owned apartments. According to Šakanović, these actions and solidarity are at the core of the socialist movement, and it is not surprising that miners, who were among the main initiators of the socialist movement, exhibited such behaviour. He primarily focuses on contextualising Husino rebellion within the broader labour and socialist movement, linking the commitment of workers to the following two decades until the beginning of World War II. The second paper, authored by Enes S. Omerović and titled *Mjesto husinske bune u hronologiji fenomena političkog nasilja* (The Place of Husino Rebellion in the Chronology of Political Violence Phenomena) dedicates most of its attention to the events preceding the rebellion and all the events within the workers' rights movement that led to the outbreak of the rebellion, as well as the reactions of both central and local authorities to these strikes and obstructions. In a way, Omerović's initial thesis contradicts Šakanović, as he argues that the participants in this movement belonged to a heterogeneous group whose main connection was their oppositional stance towards the state. The next article is titled *Odjeci husinske bune na ljevicu u bosni i hercegovini - uzroci povodi i posljedice* (Echoes of Husino Rebellion on the Left in Bosnia and Herzegovina – Causes, Triggers, and Consequences) and is authored by Dino Dupanović. His work focuses on the consequences of Husino rebellion on the left in Bosnia and Herzegovina and the result of conflicts among different political actors within the leftist movements. He primarily examines the conflict between the reformist-social democratic or centrist and revolutionary communist factions within the labour movement. Due to radical actions, the Communist Party soon faced a ban, and the centrists took the initiative on the left and within the labour movement. However, according to the author, there

would still be “intraparty pluralism among Bosnian Herzegovinian leftists” (p. 63.) despite the ban on communist activities and their retreat into illegality or “neutrality.”

Jasmina Husanović's work, similar to Damir Arsenijević's, primarily focuses on comparing the events related to the Husino rebellion with the current situation faced by Bosnian Herzegovinian miners. In the paper *Rudari u štrajku: stoljetna iskustva društveno-političkog rada i klasne borbe* (Miners on Strike: Centuries of Experience in Social and Political Work and Class Struggle), the emphasis is placed on the workers' struggle for their rights and their confrontation with centres of power in an attempt to improve their situation. Husanović divides her work into two parts. The first part primarily discusses the Husino rebellion and contains similar elements to Arsenijević's work, which turn these papers more into political speeches. Both authors enrich their texts with various citations from memoirs, and in both cases, the authors relatively uncritically refer to the writings of the participants of the Husino rebellion and the labour movement between the two world wars. The second part of the work is dedicated to the period after World War II, with a special focus on the events between 2014 and 2020. Husanović concludes the paper by analysing and briefly reflecting on Henry Giroux's writings regarding neoliberalism and its impact on the world.

The next two papers are culturally oriented towards the topic of the Husino rebellion. The author of the first paper is Nebojša Jovanović, and his work *Husinska buna na filmu* (Husino rebellion on Film) specifically deals with the cinematographic adaptations of the Husino rebellion during the period of Yugoslavia. Initially, the author discusses the trends within Yugoslav cinematography and the avoidance of pre-war topics by Yugoslav directors. Additionally, Jovanović analyses the film *Konjuh planinaj* (1966), which subtly evokes the Husino rebellion, although the plot takes place during World War II. The end of the paper is primarily devoted to the film *Husino Rebellion* produced by Sarajevo Television in 1980. Alongside the analysis of the *Husino Rebellion*, the author also examines other historical films produced during this period. Jovanović recognizes that earlier films could only subtly evoke certain events from Yugoslav history since the population had direct knowledge of these events from firsthand or second-hand sources. However, this was not the case with later films, as these events had already become history, and a new audience had emerged.

The next paper is titled *O klasnoj borbi i nasilju: krleža o husinskoj buni* (On Class Struggle and Violence: Krleža on the Husino rebellion) by Šejla Šehabović. In her work, the author analyses different texts written by Miroslav Krleža regarding the Husino rebellion. Similar to the works of Damir Arsenijević and Jasmina Husanović, this paper primarily deals with events in Bosnia and Herzegovina in the twenty-first century after a few pages. Šehabović compares the bloody

descriptions of violence given by Krleža, especially concerning the disembowelment of one of the leaders of the Husino rebellion, and the partial burning of the National Archive of Bosnia and Herzegovina during the protests of 2014. While Šehabović covers the comparison of other events of contemporary Bosnia to the Husino rebellion writings of Krleža, such as the burning of the Sarajevo City Hall and its restoration, the author also compares the gradual destruction of national institutions brought up by government neglect and the struggle between profit and work, which was represented in the text written by Krleža. (pp. 100–102) Nevertheless, most attention is given to the protests in 2014 and their course, as well as the results of the protests.

This collection of papers concludes with the work of Ana Vujković Šakanović titled *Istoriografija o husinskoj buni: prilog bibliografiji* (Historiography on the Husino rebellion: Contribution to the Bibliography). The author primarily analyses and presents the historical development of academic writings on the Husino rebellion. She also provides a brief overview of authors, journals, and institutions that have excelled in the study of the Husino rebellion. At the end of the paper, Vujković Šakanović presents an alphabetically arranged bibliography of sources, literature, and online resources.

Overall, this collection of papers represents an important revival of interest in a topic that has been neglected in recent times within Bosnian-Herzegovinian historiography. Additionally, this collection is significant as one of the few ways in which the centenary of the Husino rebellion has been commemorated. Although the papers within this collection do not present new historical discoveries that would shake the existing conclusions regarding the Husino rebellion, they offer a fresh perspective on this historical event. Some papers, such as the papers by Dupanović and Jovanović, have more concise themes, ideas, and conclusions presented within them. Their linear historical approach and focus on the Husino rebellion rather than on the contemporary events give them a noticeable advantage compared to other papers. That being said, other papers have a rather confusing approach to the topic, and when reading them, one gets the feeling of not reading papers about the Husino rebellion but rather about other topics.